

PERSISTENT PLACES AND EMERGENT LANDSCAPES:
A RELATIONAL HISTORY OF TUNIIT (PALEO-INUIT) OCCUPATION IN AMITTUQ, NUNAVUT

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MARCH 2024

A THESIS SUBMITTED TO MCGILL UNIVERSITY IN PARTIAL FULFILLMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENTS OF THE DEGREE OF DOCTOR OF PHILOSOPHY

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For my brother, Shawn — I will always look up to you.

Land Acknowledgment

I respectfully acknowledge that my doctoral degree at McGill University was completed on the ancestral homelands of Indigenous peoples. The island called Montreal, on which McGill University is situated, is known as Tiohtiá:ke in the language of the Kanien'kehá:ka, and has long been a place of residence, meeting and exchange among Iroquoian peoples. Historically, this land has also been a meeting place for other Indigenous peoples, including Algonquian and Inuit peoples. As a descendant of Settlers, I have been a beneficiary of the dispossession of Indigenous lands; I recognize and respect these peoples and their nations as the traditional stewards of the lands and waters in Tiohtiá:ke.

Abstract

This dissertation presents a place-based approach to the study of Tuniit (Paleo-Inuit) social worlds in the Amittuq region of northern Foxe Basin, Nunavut. The central problem is the identification and explanation of how socially diverse communities emerged through placemaking activities of different durations, scales, and intensities. In Amittuq, persistent settlement places were integral to these processes. These are places that were repeatedly occupied by Tuniit peoples (c. 4500 – 600 BP) and that endure as sites of living history among contemporary Amitturmiut Inuit. To investigate what these places might embody about the structure, scale, and character of Tuniit communities, the study employs multiple lines of evidence. These include 1) oral testimonies of Inuit Knowledge Holders to develop new expectations about Tuniit placemaking practice; 2) predictive GIS models to interpret postglacial change in landforms and nearshore environments; and 3) the analysis of Tuniit artifacts and architecture from three persistent settlement places — Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq — documented by multimethod survey, excavation, and radiocarbon sequencing. Rather than static backgrounds to predefined archaeological cultures (i.e., Pre-Dorset and Dorset), the research suggests how persistent places, through dynamic relations with people, historically articulated Tuniit communities at the scales of the household and camp. As product and process of millennia of community practices, these places were also affective fields where knowledge, memory, and perceptions of history connected people from different times and contexts, contributing to a broader sense of belonging. The result is a narrative in which people and places were co-constitutive of a historically contingent and emergent occupational landscape — one whose material remains continue to acquire meaning as valued components of Inuit cultural heritage.

Résumé

Cette dissertation présente une approche basée sur le lieu pour l'étude des mondes sociaux des Tuniit (paléo-inuits) à Amittuq (le nord du bassin de Foxe), NU. Le problème central est l'identification et l'explication de la manière dont des communautés relationnelles, socialement diversifiées, ont été créées et redéfinies de manière répétée à travers des activités de création de lieu de différentes durées, échelles et intensités. À Amittuq, des lieux d'établissement persistants étaient intégraux à ces processus. Ce sont des lieux qui ont été occupés de manière répétée par les peuples Tuniit (env. 4500 – 600 BP) et qui perdurent comme sites d'histoire vivante parmi les Inuits d'Amittuq contemporains. Pour enquêter sur ce que ces lieux pourraient incarner au sujet de la structure, de l'échelle et du caractère des communautés Tuniit, l'étude emploie plusieurs lignes de preuves. Celles-ci incluent 1) des témoignages oraux des gardiens du savoir inuit pour développer de nouvelles attentes concernant la pratique de création de lieu par les Tuniit ; 2) des modèles prédictifs SIG pour interpréter le changement postglaciaire dans les formes de relief et les environnements proches du rivage ; et 3) des artefacts et architectures Tuniit de trois lieux d'établissement persistants — Kapuivik, Qalirusiq et Alarniq — documentés par des enquêtes multiméthodes, des fouilles et des séquençages au radiocarbone. Plutôt que des arrière-plans statiques pour des cultures archéologiques prédéfinies (c.-à-d., Prédorsétien et Dorsétien), la recherche suggère comment les relations dynamiques entre les personnes et les lieux ont historiquement articulé les communautés Tuniit aux échelles du ménage et du camp. En tant que produit et processus de millénaires de relations communautaires locales, ces lieux étaient également des champs affectifs où la connaissance, la mémoire et les perceptions de l'histoire connectaient les personnes de différents temps et contextes, contribuant à un sens plus large d'appartenance. Le résultat est un récit dans lequel les personnes et les lieux étaient co-

constitutifs d'un paysage d'occupation historiquement contingent et émergent — un dont les restes matériels continuent d'acquérir du sens comme composants valorisés du patrimoine culturel inuit.

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List of Abbreviations

IE: Interview code for transcribed oral testimonies collected by the Igloolik Oral History Project (OHP), standing for “Inuit Elder” (e.g., IE001; IE006). Keeping with Nunavut Research Institute and McGill Research Ethics Board approval agreements, interviews are kept confidential.

IQ: Inuit Qaujimajatuqangit, a holistic term referring to Inuit epistemology and knowledge, including cosmology, lived experience, traditions, and history.

KH: Interview code used by author for oral testimonies collected as part of dissertation research, standing for “Knowledge Holder”, to distinguish interviews from those in the Igloolik Oral History Project database (e.g., KH001; KH004). Keeping with Nunavut Research Institute and McGill Research Ethics Board approval agreements, interviews are kept confidential.

OHP: Igloolik Oral History Project

QIA: Qikiqtani Inuit Association

QTC: Qikiqtani Truth Commission

RCAN: Natural Resources Canada’s data sources

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Acknowledgments

This dissertation was made possible through the support and encouragement of many people and institutions. Foremost, I would like to express my utmost gratitude to my supervisor, Peter Johansen, for encouraging me to take on an ambitious project and whose expertise, patience, and guidance have made this dissertation possible. Thank you, Peter, for making me a better writer and a more critical scholar, and for supporting me throughout this program, both personally and professionally.

I extend my deep gratitude to my committee. I would like to express my appreciation to Lisa Overholtzer for her mentorship both in and outside of the classroom. In addition to providing me with critical feedback on this dissertation, I am grateful for her insights into community-oriented research and for providing me with a novel and contrasting research experience in Tlaxcala, Mexico. A special thank you to James Savelle, for introducing me to Arctic archaeology and supporting my fieldwork and new experiments. I have appreciated the many inspiring Arctic tales, and what turned out to be very sound advice about encountering polar bears! James Conolly's guidance and feedback have been central to this project. Thank you, James, for the critical and supportive mentorship you have provided me since my MA, and for helping me develop a specialized GIS skillset without which this project would not have been possible. To Nicole Couture, thank you for many thought-provoking chats about theory and pedagogy, and for serving as my internal examiner on this dissertation. I extend my sincerest thanks to my external examiner Christopher Wolff and external member George Wenzel.

I would also like to thank the faculty and staff of the Department of Anthropology at McGill, especially Connie Di Giuseppe, Cynthia Romanyk, Franca Cianci, Joanne Terrasi, Michael Bisson, Olga Harmazy, Setrag Manoukian, Erin Hensen, Shameem Mooradun, and Heidi Cheung for showing me so much kindness and support over the course of my program. I am grateful to my fellow graduate students past and present, with special thanks to Kariuki, Naim, Jonathon, Camilo, Rine, Vanessa, Meaghan, and Callan. My success in this program would not be possible without the humour and friendship you have all provided. To Katie, fellow sketti enthusiast and arctic comrade — our friendship can survive any climate.

Many contributed to the success of the 2018 and 2019 field seasons. I am deeply indebted to Rachel Qitsualik-Tinsley for educating me on Inuit epistemology, helping to facilitate interviews, and for arranging access to the oral history archives in Igloolik. Thank you as well to Sylvie LeBlanc, for guiding me through best practices and supporting my project development. The project would not have been possible without the aid of Salomon Mikki and his family, including the Mikki's, Irngaut's and Kadlutsiak's, for their friendship, logistic support, and participation in field research. I would also like to thank Janet Airut for serving as an interview interpreter. My sincerest thanks to the co-investigators, collaborators, and field crews of the 2018 and 2019 field seasons, especially to Arthur Dyke, James Savelle, Francois P. Levasseur, Katie Kotar, and Kyle Forsythe, whose problem-solving and respective specialisms were integral to the success of my PhD project. I extend my gratitude to Pierre Desrosiers and Lesley Howse for including me on their prior field projects in Foxe Basin, and to Sean Desjardins for facilitating community connections in Igloolik and always offering great advice in and out of the field.

I must thank several institutions for financially and logistically supporting this project. Many organizations in Nunavut facilitated this research, including the Hamlet of Igloolik, Igloolik Hunters and Trappers Association, Qikiqtani Inuit Association, and Inuit Heritage Trust. I extend my appreciation to the Canadian Museum of Nature and the Canadian Conservation Institute for collections, conservation, and archival support. Thank you, as well, to John Southon at the Keck AMS facility for processing and analyzing the radiocarbon samples. Financial support for my program and research was received from Canadian Northern Studies Trust, DigitalGlobe (Maxar), The Explorers Club, Fjällräven, Fonds de Recherche du Québec, Hexagon Spatial, McGill University, National Geographic Society, Polar Continental Shelf Program, Polar Knowledge Canada, the Social Sciences and Humanities Research Council of Canada, and the Weston Foundation. My gratitude extends to the Government of Nunavut Department of Culture and Heritage, Elders and Youth Division, for providing funding for field school participants and the archaeology youth camp program.

A special thanks to Arthur Stefanski, for reading my many drafts and for his friendship and support at each step of our academic careers since undergrad. I'll think of you often and miss you always. My sincere appreciation to Phil Cook for reading and providing much needed feedback on this dissertation, you're the best! Thank you, as well, to my stepmom Alison for her feedback and support throughout the writing process. I also owe a debt of gratitude to Catherine Macdonald, my high school teacher who first introduced me to archaeology. Your enthusiasm for the field sparked my initial interest and has continued to inspire me as an archaeologist and a teacher. My sincere appreciation, as well, to Susan Pfeiffer for her mentorship during my undergraduate degree, including invaluable research opportunities and professional advice that holds true to this day.

I am grateful to my mom, Doris, for always encouraging me to press forward, even when it meant we would be apart. Your unwavering support and our many talks on the hard days have been a big part of my success. To my dad, Michael, who always encouraged me to pursue to my dreams and taught me the importance of perseverance, thank you for shaping who I am today. I am so grateful to have shared my love of archaeology with you, and your passion for learning will forever remain with me. To my brother, Shawn: thank you for always encouraging me to think outside the box, to take risks, and to “live a little”. You taught me the importance of community and caring for others, and I wouldn’t be who I am today without you. Your memory will always guide me. Finally, to Kyle, thank you for supporting me when I was at my worst and for helping me be my best — you will always be my greatest find.

Chapter One

Introduction

1.1 Introduction to the Research Problem

In Amittuq¹, Nunavut, pioneering peoples called the Tuniit — the Amitturmiut Inuit term for the non-ancestral Paleo-Inuit² peoples (c. 4500 – 600 BP) that preceded the ancestral Inuit (c. 800 – 500 BP) — repeatedly inhabited coastal places for millennia. Today, these places are marked with the material remains of ancient camps and settlements, the majority of which are arranged along residual terraced coastlines formed from postglacial uplift³. This unique archaeological landscape has long been thought to represent a continuous series of stable, shoreward-shifting occupations that were organized around dependable nearshore hunting areas (Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1954;1962). The cultural logics underlying this perspective have permeated explanatory narratives of Tuniit archaeological landscapes throughout the Canadian Arctic, with Amittuq described as a “core area” (sensu McGhee 1972) of occupational continuity and cultural development that stands in stark contrast to the regions of irregular occupation that surround its margins (Appelt et al. 2016:788; Darwent et al. 2018:532; Desjardins 2020:165; Friesen 2007:200; Hardenberg 2013:46; Mary-Rousselière 2002:5).

Within archaeological narratives of the core area, coastal places of recurrent settlement

¹ Amittuq (ᐱᓄᓄᓄᓄ) is the name of the territorial electoral district that covers the northern Foxe Basin region, and the homeland of the Amitturmiut people who reside in Sanirajak and Igloodik (Bennett and Rowley 2004).

² Previously termed Paleoeskimo, Paleo-Inuit is now a commonly accepted term for the first Canadian Arctic peoples (see Friesen 2015). Recent work has used “Tuniit” to describe the latter half of the Paleo-Inuit period (see Desjardins et al. 2023; Friesen 2022; Siebrecht et al. 2023), but I use the term to refer to the entire period (see Walker 2020).

³ Postglacial uplift refers to the rising of land masses relative to sea level in areas that were once weighed down by ice sheets. The process causes land surfaces in Amittuq to slowly rise out of the sea, resulting in a horizontal stratigraphy of residual beach formations.

are typically approached as “stairways of history” (Howse 2019:533; Odgaard 2015), in which each previously occupied beach terrace is framed as a material expression of the Pre-Dorset (c. 4500 – 2500 BP) or Dorset (c. 2500 – 1000 BP) archaeological cultures⁴ that have traditionally defined and divided Tuniit peoples (Fitzhugh 1976; Maxwell et al. 1976; Maxwell 1985; McGhee 1972, 1976; Meldgaard 1954a;1960a;1962;; Murray 1999; Ryan 2010). This framing presents Tuniit peoples as monolithic cultural entities structured by large-scale external forces such as cultural diffusion or environmental adaptation, and their settlement places as static backgrounds to these processes. As a result, the potential of recurrent placemaking practices to define and reshape past communities has largely remained outside the scope of archaeological inquiry. However, recent archaeological investigations suggest that Tuniit occupational activities may have varied substantively within and between repeatedly occupied sites, with evidence of episodic abandonments, localized architecture, and the intergenerational reuse of dwellings increasingly characterizing the archaeological record (Dyke et al. 2019; Howse et al. 2019; Howse et al. 2021; Ryan 2009; Savelle and Dyke 2014; Walker 2020a). This diversity in placemaking practices may point to the emergence of social differences at local scales, as well as broader traditions of land use outside of the expected shoreward-shifting settlement model.

My goal in this dissertation is to expand on recent findings to demonstrate how persistent settlement places are both product and process of complex occupational histories involving dynamic social relations between land and people. I argue that these relations were constitutive of emergent, relational communities during the Tuniit Period, and continue to connect people from different times and contexts, entangling Tuniit places with the histories and identities of contemporary Inuit communities. I explore these propositions through a landscape study that

⁴ I use the terms Early Tuniit and Late Tuniit to describe the chronological periods previously associated with the Pre-Dorset and Dorset archaeological cultures.

employs multiple lines of historic evidence. The investigation centres on the analysis of Tuniit artifacts and architecture from three persistent settlement places — Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq — documented by pedestrian surveys, remotely piloted aircraft (RPA) surveys, targeted excavations, and the analysis of 147 radiocarbon dates (including 51 newly acquired dates). I combine these data with the assessment of semi-structured interviews conducted with Inuit Knowledge Holders and archival research of transcribed oral testimonies from the Igloodik Oral History Project to develop new expectations about Tuniit placemaking. The examination of oral historical data also contributes to a richer understanding of local environments and new spatial criteria for purposive archaeological survey. Lastly, the study employs predictive GIS models produced from geological records, radiocarbon dates, RPA data, and satellite imagery to interpret postglacial changes in landforms and nearshore environments during the Tuniit Period. The combined approach elicits productively agonistic dialogues of local people-place relations that challenge and expand previous conceptions of Tuniit settlement strategies, organizational structures, and social memberships.

The result of this study is an alternative narrative of Amittuq’s occupational history that offers new perspectives on the emergence and differentiation of local communities, as well as a broader sense of place and social belonging (i.e., homeland), during the Tuniit Period. Additionally, the research illustrates how Tuniit sites continue to acquire meaning as valued components of Inuit heritage, and highlights the importance of collaborative knowledge exchanges with Inuit communities to produce more inclusive archaeological narratives. In doing so, the research addresses broader issues of continuity and change, temporality and historicity, scale, agency, and intellectual authority within Arctic archaeology.

1.1.1 From “Core Area” Narratives to Relational Narratives of Place

Archaeological models centered on the conception of Amittuq as a “core area” remain valuable for describing some of the large-scale patterning observed in Tuniit tool and architectural technologies (Houmard 2018; Ryan 2016), and human population dynamics (Dyke and Savelle 2009; Howse et al. 2021; Savelle and Dyke 2014). However, I argue that a relational approach is more productive for investigating placemaking practices of different durations, scales, and intensities, and for interpreting what these activities might suggest about the scale and character of Tuniit communities.

Core area narratives often focus on the refinement of a culture history in which material traits are grouped into broad spatial and chronological phases, and change (in culture and society) is explained through macro-scale forces, like pan-Arctic migrations and regional resource stress. These frameworks overlook processes of change that do not fit neatly into established cultural-historical taxa, such as Pre-Dorset and Dorset archaeological cultures (see Birch et al. 2022; Feinman and Neitzel 2020; Johansen 2003; Johansen and Bauer 2024; Pluckhahn et al. 2023). Additionally, these framings do not recognize agents and processes that blur the boundaries of the nature/culture and subject/object divides that underlie the Western Cartesian rubrics they tend to work from (Cipolla 2021:511; Harris 2018:88; Harris and Robb 2012:668). Linear and binary frames of thinking do not fully capture how dynamic people-place relations contributed to the emergence of social differences beyond the established periodization that characterizes Arctic archaeology.

In this dissertation, I use the terms Early Tuniit (c. 4500 – 2500 BP) and Late Tuniit (c. 2500 – 4500 BP) to situate previously recognized temporal shifts in large-scale material

patterning, while drawing a connection to Inuit history and challenging implicit assumptions of culture history (e.g., that culture is an entity, rather than a relational process). As feminist anthropologist Vicki Kirby (2017:15) writes, “our need to identify materiality oppositionally involves us in an agonistic wrangle over right or wrong adjudications that necessarily censors mystery, contradiction and surprise.” By presuming to know *a priori* what an archaeological place represents (e.g., an infinitesimal temporal slice, a monolithic culture) we inadvertently limit the possibilities of the kinds of historic differences that places and their material constituents might have made (and continue to make) to human social worlds (Gero 2015:7-10; Harris 2021:6).

To construct archaeological narratives that better account for the dynamic and generative connections between past people and places, I propose that Tuniit occupational landscapes should be investigated through the consultation of diverse and potentially contrasting lines of evidence (e.g., local oral history). Recognizing the possible onto-epistemological differences between our own worlds and those of the past peoples we study are important ethical considerations for any archaeological project (Alberti 2016). However, they are even more critical in Indigenous research contexts such as Amittuq where archaeological sites are also places of living history. Like many Indigenous peoples, Inuit are deeply connected to places; their communities are created from the land and are socially located through the land (Heyes and Dowsley 2018; Kushwaha 2013; Nuttal 1992; Price 2008; Qitsualik 2008). And yet, “since different Indigenous philosophies and practices vary amongst territory, it must also be true that the stuff of place is thoughtful” (Watts 2016:21, see also Wub-e-ke-niew 1995). By addressing how people and places collectively participate in the making of relational and multiscalar communities, I argue that Arctic archaeologists can begin to move past frameworks that treat the

landscapes we study as static representations of a singular (linear) past, and instead make moves towards plural narratives that more fully explore what it means to be human in an emergent, more-than-human world.

To better understand the social worlds of Tuniit, I argue that archaeologists must learn to think with places differently by 1) prioritizing responsible collaborative engagement with the contemporary stewards of the lands we study (Inuit communities) and by 2) attending to how multiple and, at times, conflicting place-histories are enmeshed and continuously reshaped through the stories we perform and create through archaeological research (Haraway 2019:565; Lyons et al 2010; Tuhiwai Smith 2012:34). I make a critical move towards these efforts by aligning my research design with the Inuit principle of *Saimaqtigiingniq*⁵ (*reconciliation/balance between equals*). *Saimaqtigiingniq* promotes collaborative research engagement between Inuit and non-Inuit through the employment of a relational knowledge framework that embraces differences in epistemology and worldview (QIA 2010, see Section 1.2).

These ideas are further developed in my study by engaging with posthuman feminist methodologies of difference, which are process-oriented and affirmative (Barad 2003, 2007; Haraway 1992;1997; Lefebvre 2004:16-17). This frames the archaeological narrative that emerges through my work as more-than-representational: an activity that makes a difference to how knowledge of the past and present are co-created through engagement with places of living history (Barad 2003:802; Bennett 2012:232, 2020:118; Deleuze and Guattari 1987:77-78;

⁵ As a decolonizing practice, Inuktitut terms in this dissertation are not placed in italics, with the logic that how Indigenous names and concepts are made visible within Western writing is instrumental to their empowerment (Agboka 2014; Jones 2016; Sageer 2020). This is especially important when translating Inuit Qaujimajatuqangit principles, like *Saimaqtigiingniq*, that are formally incorporated into Canadian governance policies, and Inuit toponyms that are also official Canadian place names (e.g. Kapuivik).

Garrouette & Westcott 2013; Haraway 2016:39-40; Rosiek and Snyder 2020). The study emphasizes the value of Inuit Qaujimagatuqangit (*epistemology and knowledge*) for interpreting Tuniit occupational landscapes (Kristensen and Davis 2015; Laluk 2017). In doing so, it provides a conceptual and analytical framework through which future collaborative archaeological projects might continue to critically engage with the inseparability of past and present places in Inuit Nunangat (*homeland*).

1.1.2 Orientation of Case Study

The following study presents a relational narrative of Amittuq's archaeological landscape that is centered on the entangled occupational histories of three persistent places (*sensu* Schlanger 1992) that have long served as type-sites for defining Arctic archaeological cultures: Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq (Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1952, 1962). First occupied by Tuniit communities (c. 4000 – 600 BP), these locales were also homes to Early (ancestral) Inuit communities (c. 800 – 500 BP), and today endure as meaningful places through their everyday relations with the Amitturmiut Inuit communities of Igloodik and Sanirajak. Amitturmiut Inuit have a rich oral tradition of their ancestors' relations with these places, which includes stories of Early Inuit encounters with Tuniit peoples. To better understand what archaeological sites might embody about the structure, scale, and social character of Tuniit communities, I explore what they were capable of doing as performative places within both ancient and historic community contexts in which they were created and transformed. This involves the analyses of small-scale differences in Tuniit architecture and artifacts, traces of placemaking embodied in Amitturmiut oral testimonies of Tuniit–Early Inuit encounters, and a treatment of the land as a relational

force, through the analysis of predictive models of Amittuq's paleotopography that visualize changing landmass connectivity and nearshore marine environments during the Tuniit Period.

I propose that local occupational histories in Amittuq entail far more than unilateral human-environment interactions. Persistent settlement places are not exclusively cultural expressions inscribed on the land as cultural-historical frameworks suggest, nor are they products of human adaptation that were structured by regional environments, as socio-evolutionary frameworks might posit. This is because people and their cultures are not ontologically separate from the environments they experience and affect⁶ (Ahenakew 2017:81; Barad 2003:814, 2007:214; Deloria 2003:151; Kirby 2017:ix; Watts 2016:3; Whatmore 2006:602-604). Rather, settlement places are product and process of the worlds in which they participate. They materialize through dynamic associations between humans and nonhumans, who emerge and cross paths through the continued production of landscapes that are at once biophysical and sociocultural in nature (Barad 2003:822, 2007:66; Bender 2006:2; Braidotti 2010:415; Brittain 2016:265; Creese 2011:3; Haraway 2003; Johansen 2010; Jones and Hoskins 2016:78; Smith 2003; Sundberg 2014:35).

Through a multi-method investigation of the present archaeological landscape, I consider how the Tuniit occupational landscape continually shaped, and in turn was shaped by, acts of placemaking – often in unexpected ways that challenge dominant narratives about Tuniit social structures and practices. This includes evidence for the negotiation of Tuniit communities through everyday practices such as the construction of dwellings and exploitation of caches, as well as through broader traditions such as the intergenerational maintenance of campsites. I argue that persistent settlement places in Amittuq are best understood as affective fields (Harris

⁶ Affects are “[w]ays of moving, behaving, and perceiving the world” (Harris 2021:23).

2021a:160) that historically articulated how matter, and by extension space and time, could be experienced and reconfigured by past actors (Barad 2003:815; Cipolla 2019:1090; Deleuze 1992:159; Foucault 1980:194; Merleau-Ponty 1968:143, see Nuttal 1992; Whitridge 2004). They are loci where humans, animals, architecture, and topographic elements repeatedly encountered one another, continually redefining the material boundaries that shaped individual relations, informed perceptions of community and history, and ultimately configured a wider social world.

The analysis of Tuniit artifacts and architecture permits the exploration of how humans and nonhumans routinely acquired shared forms and meanings through their topological connections “*in place*” (TallBear 2015:186 *emphasis original*, cf. Basso 1996:44-45; Casey 1996:35), coalescing as relational communities (Harris 2014; Larsen and Johnson 2017). Non-humans, such as animals and materials, participate in meaning-making because meaning is created through emergent and generative relationships, rather than interactions between fixed bodies (Barad 2007). Meaning is not a static property owned by humans; it arises through dynamic interplays of co-belonging⁷ as part of a more-than-human world that transcends language, discourse, and representation.

Acts of co-belonging are acts of placemaking, as they mobilize some elements (e.g., people, architecture, memories) at the expense of others, altering what can be seen, felt, and known with and as part of the landscape (Deloria 2001a:16; Fredengren 2021:5; Haraway 2017:26; Harris 2014:87; Harvey 1996:69-76; Lefebvre 1991:64; Massumi 2015; vi-ix; Pries 2018:5; Shorter 2016:20; Watts 2013:22). Following these logics, I argue that Tuniit communities cannot be conceived of as bounded cultures that were imposed on, or determined

⁷ I consider co-belonging not just as resting together, but as “movement and encounter” (Hägerstrand 1976: 332 in Alfred 2021:31), as “intensive, affective, associations of repeated collectivity (Harris 2021a:173).

by, their regional environments. Instead, they were relational and vibrant collectives that were co-created *with* materially locatable places at multiple, intersecting scales (Barad 2001:93; Basso 1996:6; Brittain 2016: 258; Casey 2016:49; Deloria 2001:23, 150; Harris 2014:89; Pries 2018:7; Watts 2016:3; Wildcat 2001:76).

This investigation is guided by the aforementioned principle of Saimaqatigiingniq. Saimaqatigiingniq in this context provides a neutral conceptual space where Inuit and non-Inuit thoughts, methods, and experiences can together generate productive frictions that result in new knowledge about people, land and history (Qikiqtani Inuit Association 2010:50). Approaching my work through Saimaqatigiingniq enables me to bring different forms and scales of historic evidence (e.g., archaeological, geophysical, oral-historical, ethnographic) into constructive and open-ended dialogues that move past ideal types that tend to present Western knowledge as truth and Indigenous knowledge as perception⁸ (Atalay 2020; Nassaney 2021; Wub-e-ke-niew 1995). This approach reframes differences between Inuit and archaeological epistemologies not as oppositional or contradictory phenomena, but rather as productively agonistic processes through which new possibilities about past actors and the production of landscapes can emerge (Barad 2007; Crellin 2020; Harris 2021a; Jervis 2018; Joyce 2021).

Within this research, I foster Saimaqatigiingniq through research collaborations with the Amitturmiut Inuit community of Igloolik, NU. This includes a series of semi-structured interviews conducted with Inuit Knowledge Holders and the archival analysis of Inuit oral testimonies transcribed by the Igloolik Oral History Project. These sources provide insight into

⁸ Here I refer to the logics and divisions of hierarchical epistemologies in which objects and people embodied in the archaeological record differ from idealized Western standards, including fixed archaeological types, and predefined ideas about what has agency and meaning. These categories conceptually limit the identity of both materials and people, and therefore what we might imagine they could do as part of past relations.

what Amitturmiut ancestors have passed down about Late Tuniit people, as well as Inuit land-based ways of knowing that challenge, support, and otherwise contextualize archaeological inferences of people-place relations in earlier periods.

The work also involved regular consultations with local authorities such as the Igloodik Hunters and Trappers Association, the inclusion of Igloodik high school students and adult community members in archaeological fieldwork, the delivery of translated non-technical reports to the community, and the running of a youth archaeology camp and public lecture events in Igloodik. By prioritizing more inclusive archaeological practices, the initiatives helped to ensure that the research remained aligned with community interests and concerns, including emphasis on capacity building and advocacy for local stewardship and intellectual authority within broader disciplinary circles (Atalay 2016, 2019; Friesen 2022; Kelvin and Hodgetts 2020; Lyons et al 2010; Lyons et al. 2023; Nassaney 2021; Stuhl 2017; Tuhiwai Smith 2012). The research presented in this dissertation focuses on the interview and archival research outputs — collaborative initiatives will be discussed in future publications.

Exploring Inuit Qaujimagatuqangit in conversation with archaeological and paleogeographical data enables the development of historically situated expectations for how Tuniit communities were co-constituted with the places repeatedly inhabited, which guide the project design. Importantly, my interrogations are not limited to what different elements and forces *did do* or, at least, *appear to have done* as part of past landscapes (the actual) but also their historically contingent potentials: what situated actors *could* do towards their own becoming and the becoming of others, through their affective relations (the virtual). My framing of the virtual is informed by Karen Barad's theory of virtuality, also known as intra-action, in which the

capacities of human and non-human bodies to act is not fixed, but rather is specific to the historic context of their emergence and relations with others (Barad 2007, 2015, 2017). I argue that the affective capacities of locally situated actors are themselves real and performative phenomena: the virtual contextualizes possibilities for what could have taken place and therefore offers deeper meaning to community relations inferred through the archaeological record (Barad 2007, 2015; Braidotti 2017; Conneller 2012; Deleuze and Guattari 2004; Jervis 2022).

By attending to the materiality, performativity, and virtuality of places in my analyses, I identify instances of Tuniit placemaking embodied through the archaeological record of camp contexts, caching places, and relict topographical elements. This allows me to assess how Tuniit community practices and structures may have emerged through local material relations without constraining interpretations to what certain archaeological types represent about norms or identities within dominant cultural-historical models (see Feinman and Neitzel 2020, Johansen 2003; Johansen and Bauer 2024; Tsing 2015:23). Throughout these exercises, I integrate Western-scientific analyses often misrepresented as objective with qualitative analyses misrepresented as subjective. The former includes remote-sensing and pedestrian land surveys, excavations, radiocarbon analyses, and digital modelling. The latter includes my interview and archival research components, and previously published toponymic maps and ethnographic studies (Aporta 2003, IT Kanatami 2007; Pauktuutit 2006; QIA 2010; Tester and Irniq 2008). By combining these data through a variety of mapping technologies (*ArcGIS Pro 3.2, NVivo 14, Pix4d 4.8*), I explore the formation, maintenance, and differentiation of communities at the social and spatial scales of the household, camp, and broader homeland, and offer new perspectives on how people and places contributed to these historic processes.

1.2 Theoretical and Methodological Orientation:

1.2.1 *Thinking Relationally about Community, Place, and History*

Central to the lines of thinking employed in my study, which originate in Indigenous metaphysics and are mobilized through Indigenist and feminist posthumanist scholarship, is the idea that Tuniit places *matter* in both senses of the verb (Akiwenzie-Damm et al. 2019; Cipolla et al 2021; Colwell-Chanthaphonh and Ferguson 2007; Crellin and Harris 2020; Deloria 1992, 2001b; Harris 2021a; TallBear 2015; Tester and Irniq 2008; Watts 2013, see Barad 2003:817 on *mattering*). Places are “more-than-human materializing forces” (Fredengren 2021:5), made of lively intercutting elements ranging from humans, animals, and landforms to artworks, buildings, and maps, all of which are constantly emerging and changing through material encounters (Bradley 2000:35; Eastman 2020 [1911]:9; Karen Barad in Dolphijn and Van de Tuin 2012:16; Harris 2021a:3; Harris and Crellin 2020:471-472; Joyce 2015, 2020; Kirby 2013:100). But they are also sites of embodied knowledge that engender emotion, memory, desire, and other affects that stick to divergent elements and connect them with different times and contexts (Ahmed 2005:104; Deleuze and Guattari 1987:263; Haraway 1988:578; Tilley 2016:26; Watts 2020:124-125; Wub-e-ke-niew 1995).

These relational modes of mattering are effectively brought together through Anishnaabe – Kanien’kehá:ka scholar Vanessa Watt’s (2016:34) theorization of Place as “the non-distinctive space where place and thought were never separated because they never could or can be separated.” This concept is particularly relevant in the context of Inuit Nunangat, where Nuna (*the land*) is recognized for its agency in shaping human knowledge, perception, experience, and spiritual connection (IE290; IE498; Nuttall 1992:77-80, Price 2008; Qitusalik 2008). Place, or

Place-Thought (sensu Watts 2013), elucidates how persistent places are, despite their enduring presence, always in a process of mattering with others, with emergent capacities to not only condition human experiences and practices, but to move, remember, and create as active participants of the landscape (Deloria 2001:2; Watts 2013:22, 2016:21; see also Coulthard 2014 and Simpson 2017 on grounded normativity). It suggests that people's understandings of the world and their position within it are shaped, in part, by the material ability of places to impart and inherit knowledge (Tallbear 2015; Qitsualik 2013; Watts 2016). By emphasizing the agency of places and the relational nature of knowledge, Place-Thought invites me to attend to the more-than-human and performative character of archaeological landscapes, and to consider how my own senses, experiences, and understandings are affected by material encounters *in place* (sensu Tallbear 2015).

As a non-Indigenous scholar seeking to access the vitalism of places from an archaeological perspective, I combine Indigenous epistemologies of Place with posthumanist approaches that parallel some (although not all) of these themes and concepts. While posthumanism has been rightfully critiqued by Indigenous scholars (see Todd 2016, Watts 2016), several Indigenous and allied scholars have demonstrated how posthumanist feminisms can productively engage with Indigenous scholarship when the intellectual origins of relational thinking are recognized, the historic positionality of the researcher is explicitly addressed, and mutually beneficial research objectives are prioritized (Alberti et al. 2011; Barad 2017:61; Cipolla 2021; Hokowhitu 2016, 2021; Kolopenuk 2020; Legg 2016; Marshall 2021; Marshall and Alberti 2014; Rosiek et al. 2020, Sikka et al. 2023; Tallbear 2017). Vanessa Watts (2016:7) adds that the difference between Western and Indigenous onto-epistemologies “lies in the inheritable and material transmission of agency and spirit between places and beings, as opposed

to these worlds of beings influencing one another causally, referentially or imaginatively.” She argues that responsible collaborative research hinges on Indigenous stories being approached by Western scholars not simply as representations or metaphors, but as materially locatable entities tied to real, palpable places – as realities rather than worldviews.

I argue that Karen Barad’s metaontology of agential realism helps to facilitate the collaborative intellectual project advocated by Watts, as well as the principle of Saimaqatigiingniq. This is because it provides an understanding of reality as relational and plural, enabling multiple intellectual worlds to co-exist and affect one another through difference-oriented research practices (Crellin and Harris 2021:470, see Marshall and Alberti 2014 for an application of agential realism). Archaeological contexts in this framework are no longer conceived of as isolated events that “happen” in space and time, because space and time are relational (Bergson 1939:113, 162; Johansen 2010, 2018; Knapp and Ashmore 1999; Morrison 2016; Smith 2003; Qitsualik 2013; Wub-e-ke-niew 1995). Places are at once the outcomes of our discursive facilities and emergent properties of the material configurations in which we, as thinking subjects, are continually remade through historically specific movements, practices, and connections (Aldred 2020; Barad 2014:169; Bourdieu 1977, 1990, Butler 2010; Morrison 2016:621).

When combined with Place-Thought, agential realism serves as a powerful forum for the expansion of what can be observed and explained through archaeological research, as it allows for a particular artifact or feature to signify and be capable of doing many potential things at once (see Marshall and Alberti 2014: 28-34 on chevron amulets). For example, it allows the remains of a Tuniit sod house to exist as a single entity – an ancient human shelter – but also as a

series of different material components (e.g., stone, earth, sod) that are connected to other elements which are no longer visible but that matter nonetheless (e.g., animal bodies that became bone tools, tools that cut sod, human hands that moved sod bricks). Moreover, these relations involve numerous moments, actions, and processes beyond dwelling construction and maintenance, such as moments of knowledge-sharing, movement, food processing, and other everyday practices (Binford 1982; Hendon 2004; LeMoine 2003; Lightfoot 1993; Overholtzer 2012; Whitridge 1999, 2004). The expected affordances of these material relations to shape the actions and perceptions of people vary between archaeological and Inuit epistemologies, permitting a greater range of possibilities for how the practices and identities of Tuniit communities can be interpreted through material remains.

The sod house materials can also participate in processes beyond the household. For instance, their relations with glacial ice and permafrost may (through isostatic rebound) transform their surroundings from coastlines to inland areas (Harris 2021a; Joyce 2021), while rock-encrusting lichens that take centuries to grow may increasingly cover *in situ* architectural boulders. These relations engender new latent potentials for the once coastal sod house, such as its ability to serve as an affective field for the memories and histories of later people (Bauer and Johansen 2023; Morrison 2016; Schlanger 1992). Because these relations can alter how spaces and temporalities are perceived and experienced, they have the potential to affirm or alter senses of belonging and identity through acts of placemaking (Harris 2021a; Tringham 1991; Trouillot 1995).

In each of these examples, historically specific sociomaterial relations open up possibilities for what the sod house elements could do towards their own becoming and the becoming of

others. Whether or not these materials exist as an archaeological feature, directional aid, or mnemonic device depends on the moment in which they are enacted with others. This is an important contribution that agential realism offers to archaeological studies that engage with oral history and ethnography: it draws our concentration to specific material circumstances rather than abstractive homologies or analogies (Barad 2007:88; Joyce 2021: 96). It allows us to understand the virtual and actual as interdependent forces of history that structure how humans and non-humans emerge and affect one another *in place* (Deloria 2001; Haraway 2016; Harris 2014; Jervis 2022; Robinson 2021; Qitsualik 2013; Supernant 2022).

By making space for alternative onto-epistemologies of who and what counts as an agent of knowledge, Place-Thought and agential realism provide a way to take the historic realities of Inuit communities seriously in archaeological research (Cipolla 2021:511; Harris 2021a:18; Marshall 2021:516) while staying “with the trouble” (Haraway 2016:3) that our own encounters *in place* create (Tallbear 2015). In the research context of Amittuq, this draws attention to the epistemological value of Amitturmiut oral stories and landscape knowledge, which have emerged through repeated relations with many of the same places Tuniit occupied (Price 2008; Qitsualik 2013). Collaborations with Knowledge Holders promote a historically specific research design that engages with difference and alterity, permitting archaeological interpretations of place and community beyond Western ways of thinking and being.

1.2.2 Constructing Landscapes of Difference

As persistent places emerge and change through layered and dynamic sociomaterial

processes, investigating their changing affective capacities requires careful attention to a wide range of historic relations, and to the different contexts and scales at which these relations continue to unfold (Deleuze & Guattari 1987:555). This requires a methodology for evaluating the “complexity and multilayered-ness” of the archaeological present by evaluating the “encounters and relay points, generative connections, and productive zig-zagging” of elements and forces that constitute the archaeological past, including those we tend to label as cultural or natural, material or discursive, real or imagined (Braidotti 2017:8). Towards these objectives, my project maps together traces of Tuniit placemaking through a posthuman feminist approach that combines archaeological, palaeogeographical, and oral historical analyses, and that treats conflicting knowledge sources as opportunities to examine and interpret archaeological evidence in different (multiple) ways.

This approach is centered on the conception of difference as an analytical process, which provides an accessible tool for mapping together diverse landscape relations. For posthumanist archaeology, especially that which integrates Deleuzian assemblage theory (Deleuze and Guattari 1987) with posthumanist feminisms (Barad 2007; Bennett 2010; Braidotti 2017), the world is comprised of heterogeneous elements that are always in a process of becoming (Cipolla 2019, 2021; Crellin 2020; Harris 2021a; Harris and Crellin 2021; Jones 2020). Here, assemblage refers to the temporary territorializations that elements find themselves a part of, the dynamic entanglements of vibrant matter that make up all existence (Bennett 2010:23; Crellin 2017:3). Assemblages are relational and multiscalar, and so are always composed of other assemblages (Delanda 2016 in Harris 2018:6). People, for example, are assemblages of flesh, cultural norms, traditions, memories, and many other elements, but they are also important constituents of other assemblages like communities and landscapes that are constantly changing through their diverse

connections (Harris 2018:6). I argue that mapping an archaeological landscape that is product and process of vibrant assemblages becomes a more-than-representational practice: one that orients and delineates the archaeological past, but that also creates and diversifies the relations that make our observations and inferences in the present possible (Crellin 2017:15).

Assemblage mapping is amenable to Indigenous epistemologies of Place because it prioritizes the relations between emergent actors rather than the identification of discrete phenomena, attending to the multiple scales and directions through which various elements emerge, break apart, and come together differently (Harris 2021a:10). Like performative and practice-based approaches, rather than beginning with stratified social and spatial scales (e.g., such as the equivocation of an archaeological site with a monolithic archaeological culture), it attends to small-scale material relations and considers their potential for generating social structures that serve as both the medium and outcome of human practices (Bourdieu 1977). However, rather than a dialectical relationship between practice and structure, agency is attributed to relations themselves. This means that social norms and ideals are internal, mutable components of people-place relations, rather than external phenomena mediated through practice. Archaeological phenomena therefore exist only within specific (but dynamic) sets of relations (Barad 2003:815, 2007:66; Crellin 2020:157; Deleuze and Guattari 1987:239), and the social (or cultural) structures they may embody do not pre-exist discourse, practice, or material relations. This reframes Western mapping as a spatial apparatus that differs from others, such as the sharing of *unikkaaqtuangit* (Inuit traditional stories), the carving of Ammassalik (wooden coastline sculptures), or the construction and use of *ikahimaluk* or *niungvaliruluit inuksugait* (navigational monuments) not in its value, importance, or authenticity, but in its historical articulations with archaeologists and tendencies to present representation in a singular or fixed

way (Whitridge 2004, see also Hallendy 1985:32).

Understanding things and places as part of historically contingent and emergent assemblages helps to overcome the essentialism of culture history and associated issues of representation by accounting for the agency of individuals and small-scale collectives, connecting these momentary experiences with a dynamic and plural framing of history (Pauketat 2013a:40). Like Place-Thought and agential realism, assemblage mapping approaches the world from a relational framing of space (Lefebvre 1991) and time (Deleuze 1991), in which the two function not as static dimensions of a singular reality, but as fluid properties of the vibrant matter that bring divergent worlds into existence. History, in this relational perspective, is not inherently shaped by its distance from the present; it *can* be linear, but linear history is not universal (Harris 2021b). The world as we know it is instead the product of multiple, coexisting moments that are shaped by the intensity of their relations and encounters *with* the present (Bergson 1939:113), processes that we as researchers have some control over through the methods, tools, and data we consciously engage with (Barad 2003:815; Gero 2015:341). When the assemblage concept is combined with Barad's (2007) recognition of multiple realities, alternative narratives of the past emerge as productive opportunities to explore the materiality, sociality, and agency of Place within a broader range of historical contexts and agential worlds.

By structuring archaeological research around a relational spatial itinerary and non-linear temporality, I approach each line of historic evidence in my study both as a record of what past communities were ceasing to be in a given moment (the actual) – and as a catalyst of what these communities were capable of becoming (the virtual) (Braidotti 2017:10; Deleuze and Guattari 2004:283). For example, a lake that serves as a spawning ground for Arctic char has the potential

to bring people and others together through the catching, storing, and sharing of fish (Robinson 2017; Whitridge 2001). However, whether fishing practices are actualized is dependent on knowledge of how to fish and the proper equipment, as well as other-than-human and social forces, like climatic processes and cultural taboos that affect when and how the lake is accessible to fish and people (IE263). The landscape is variably affected by these relations, most notably the construction of weirs (IE249), caches (IE433), and middens (IE086), but also through stories and traditions that preserve knowledge and memory of people-place relations within this context. These elements, in turn, maintain and differentiate social relationships, informing how people participate in the ongoing production of this particular place (Harris 2016; Johansen 2008; Smith 2003; Swenson 2012).

I extend archaeological interpretations of the virtual through Karen Barad's concept of intra-action (2007), which is sometimes also referred to as virtuality in the agential realism literature (Barad 2017:78-80). Intra-action emphasises how the virtual does not simply describe the latent capacities of humans and nonhumans that are actualized through assemblages – as is the case in Actor-Network Theory (Latour 2005) – but rather describes the conditions of possibility for particular humans and non-humans to exist at all. The conditional possibilities of assemblages are a cornerstone of both social and scientific knowledge production because both are affected by the emergent and historically specific properties of material elements (Barad 2015:395). By approaching the virtuality of archaeological phenomena (e.g., their affective possibilities and potential connections) as equally impactful to their actualized capacities (e.g., their momentary forms, as materialized in archaeological contexts), I expand what is observable through my research and the kinds of historic participants I include in my analyses. This allows me to infer both continuity (repetition) and change in the material and spatial structures of Tuniit

households and camps, permitting new perspectives about local, translocal, and regional communities.

The interdependency of the virtual and the actual restructures how we can map the past because it frames cause and effect as entangled rather than distinct processes (Govier 2019:51). Intra-action emphasizes how the identity and agency of a person, thing, concept, or place emerges from the historic context in which it materializes and acquires meaning with others (Barad and Gandorfer 2021:49). To use the terminology of Donna Haraway (1992,1997) and Karen Barad (2003, 2007), this results in a *diffRACTIVE* rather than a *reflective* methodology that approaches difference as not opposed to sameness (i.e., as a bifurcation or existential state), but instead as a productive process of mattering that makes and remakes the worlds we occupy (Haraway 1997:273). Understanding the subjects and apparatuses of research as interdependent and generative permits the tracing of how constituents of landscape, such as oral stories and architectural remains, shape our observations and interpretive conclusions. In bringing these relational processes into focus, this framework centers my work on mapping-out the times, spaces, bodies, affects, and ideas that “bleed through one another” in unpredictable and performative ways through engagement with landscapes: the specific embedded practices that create and continuously differentiate histories (Barad 2017:68; Massey 2005:9; Watts 2016:2).

Diffraction and other process-oriented conceptions of difference enable archaeologists to rethink how patterns form through shared historical processes, rather than through comparisons with ideal types (Crellin and Harris 2021:8; see also Grosz 2013: 332-342; Deleuze 1994; Derrida 1982; Lefebvre 2004:16-17). Mapping multi-scalar assemblages is an effective way to approach archaeological data diffractively as it requires us to be fully present as emergent and

corporeal subjects that are intertwined with the numerous configurations of materials, times, and places that we study (Haraway 2016:1). It offers important intellectual challenges to the oppositional binaries that characterize dominant archaeological narratives of Arctic landscapes by allowing for experience, observation, and storytelling to shape archaeological knowledge actively rather than relying on cultural-historical taxa or other archaeological types (Cipolla 2021:511; Harris 2021:18). This informs a theoretical levelling of Western and Indigenous forms of knowledge in which relations between bodies, ideas, places, conventions, memories, and other vibrant elements offer new possibilities for meaning and action (Crellin and Harris 2021:472; see also Govier 2019; Jervis 2018). As Donna Haraway (2016:12) puts it, “it matters what stories we tell to tell other stories with; it matters what knots knot knots, what thoughts think thoughts...It matters what stories make worlds, what worlds make stories.”

1.3 Structure of the Dissertation

This introductory chapter has provided a preliminary outline and some important operational definitions for the central problem of this research: the identification and explanation of how Tuniit communities in Amittuq, NU emerged through mutually constitutive relationships between people and places. I have argued that the narratives we begin with impact the kinds of stories we can create about archaeological places, and therefore, how we navigate through the past and produce knowledge in the present (Haraway 2016; Harris 2021b; Joyce 2008; QIA 2010). When archaeologists take up the calls of Indigenous and posthuman feminist scholars to accept that humans are not separate from the rest of the world, we are able to move past understandings of the places we study as reflections of a singular history, and instead make

moves toward Saimaqatigiingniq: towards relational narratives that explore what it means to be a historically situated subject that matters (in both senses).

The primary objectives of my dissertation are not to dismantle the work of previous generations of Arctic archaeologists, but rather 1) to introduce how lesser acknowledged elements and actors contributed to the emergence and differentiation of past landscapes, 2) to identify how new stories about the past emerge when we map these participants into existing archaeological narratives, and 3) to explore how the inclusion of different ways of knowing and being with places can foster archaeological research that is historically situated, scientifically rigorous, and relevant to contemporary communities. These objectives have initiated a conceptual shift in my original research problem, moving it from an inquiry for a distinct explanation about a particular archaeological phenomenon (i.e., how and why Tuniit people repeatedly occupied a small number of coastal sites) to an interrogation of the many open-ended possibilities of what Tuniit places were, are, and can be through material engagements *in place* (Jervis 2018:8).

This dissertation is divided into eight chapters. In Chapter Two, I present a historiographic review of archaeological research in the eastern Canadian Arctic to contextualize how Amittuq's archaeological landscape is currently understood by researchers. This includes an overview of major theoretical paradigms, including cultural-historical, cultural ecological, and structuralist/poststructuralist frameworks. The discussion provides a summary of the dominant culture history of the Canadian Arctic, and how the framing of Amittuq as a "core area" of cultural development has emerged from, and in turn maintained, the popularity of this model. As part of this discussion, I suggest new chronological terms, including the Early and Late Tuniit

Periods (in place of Pre-Dorset and Dorset), to help conceptually separate periodization based on large-scale material patterning from the cultural-historical taxa that my work seeks to move beyond.

In my review, I suggest that while past approaches have been effective for understanding large-scale spatial and temporal patterns in artifacts and demographic change during the Tuniit Period, a place-based approach is better equipped for investigating small-scale social differences and for interpreting these differences within the context of a multiscalar social landscape. An understanding of uniformity and variability in spatial and material practices is necessary, I argue, to build interpretations of Tuniit social life and community membership at a regional scale. I position this critique around a discussion of how studying the human past *through* places, rather than imposing predefined models *onto* places, permits new perspectives on the structure, scale, and extent of Tuniit communities in Amittuq.

In Chapter Three, I further outline the relational and difference-oriented framework that informs my study of place and landscape, as well as the methods of data collection and analyses employed as part the oral historical, archaeological, and paleogeographic research components. This includes a description of the semi-structured interviews conducted with Amitturmiut Inuit Elders and my archival analysis of the Igloolik Oral History Project, as well as my approach to pedestrian and RPA survey, excavation, and radiocarbon dating analyses at Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq. I also explain my methods for producing predictive GIS models that visualize past topographies and nearshore environments, covering 500-year intervals from 5000-500 BP. By bringing these diverse lines of evidence into conversation with one another, the case study offers new perspectives on people-place relations, including how non-humans such as landforms,

animals, and architecture likely participated in the formation and diversification of Tuniit communities. The approach provides an alternative to frameworks focused on large-scale diffusionary and adaptive forces by engaging Amitturmiut Inuit knowledge, memory, and experience with landscape to interpret locally situated social relationships.

The results of my research are reported in Chapters Four, Five, Six, and Seven. Chapter Four presents a study of Amitturmiut oral history, which included qualitative analyses in the analytical platform *Nvivo 14* of both the interviews I conducted with Amitturmiut Knowledge Holders and transcribed oral testimonies from the Igloolik Oral History Project. I also employ exploratory GIS analysis of spatialized oral historical data, in conjunction with secondary ethnographic sources, to visualize and interpret the historic settlement landscape. I discuss how Amitturmiut stories about ancestral Inuit landscape practices, as well as stories about Late Tuniit people, offer new archaeological expectations for people-place relations in earlier periods. A central finding is the prevalence of stories about Tuniit and ancestral Inuit regularly occupying inland areas. This challenges archaeological presumptions of outer seacoast settlement, and offers new spatial criteria that inform my purposive archaeological survey. The results also indicate that nearshore sea ice development may have impacted the perceived proximity and social closeness of Tuniit settlements, and provides new perspectives on the location, function, and seasonal context of storage structures underrepresented in previous site surveys (e.g., equipment caches). The research also highlights the social value of archaeological sites for local Inuit communities, including how the durable record of Tuniit and ancestral Inuit caches, dwellings, and burials serve as inherited expressions of community land use histories. The study suggests that local peoples' engagements with persistent places in earlier periods were informed by a myriad of social decisions, and underlines the importance of approaching human-nonhuman

agency through historically situated perspectives.

Chapters Five through Seven examine and discuss Tuniit artifacts and architecture from Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq, respectively. I explore archaeological data documented through pedestrian surveys, RPA visible light and thermal surveys, excavations, and an expanded radiocarbon sequence that includes 51 newly acquired radiocarbon dates (147 dates total). This permits inferences of persistence and change in the form, structure, materials, location, and scale of Tuniit campsites. I consider this evidence against a series of paleotopographic models that visualize changing material conditions to help contextualize differences in camp and intercamp organizational structures, as well as continuity in local settlement traditions and broader community connections during the Tuniit Period.

Chapter Five centers on the occupational history of Kapuivik. Paleotopographic models and oral history suggest that Kapuivik was a dynamic and environmentally diverse settlement place during the Tuniit Period. Archaeological evidence indicates that camp communities engaged with changing landscape features in various ways, suggesting differences in household and camp-level practices and structures. This includes evidence for synchronic differences in dwelling size and form, the strategic organization of camps around topographic features to establish social distinctions, and changing locational practices that include both coastal and inland camps and caching places. Radiocarbon evidence also suggests continuity in site maintenance practices during the “transitional period” (c. 2800-2500 BP), which has traditionally marked the replacement of the Pre-Dorset by the Dorset archaeological culture. Along with radiocarbon evidence for the repeated use of dwelling structures and caching areas, the results illustrate how a diverse array of recurrent placemaking practices may have facilitated the

production of intergenerational camp communities on a local level. The study at Kapuivik presents challenges to dominant cultural-historical narratives and the temporal logics of relative chronologies developed from beach ridge sequences.

In Chapter Six, I turn my attention to Qalirusiq to examine people-place relations within the context of a remote islet. Paleotopographic modelling indicates that Qalirusiq was subject to pronounced changes in landmass and coastal shallowing during the Tuniit Period, which impacted the accessibility and connectivity of the islet to neighbouring settlements and marine hunting areas. Small-scale variability in Tuniit camp structures suggest that local groups managed changing environmental conditions in various ways, highlighting differences in the scale and interactions of people within a restricted but dynamic spatial setting. This includes evidence in the Early Tuniit Period for the strategic organization of campsites around coastal landscape features, possibly to establish social distinctions between local groups and/or to manage cooperative floe-edge hunting areas. Possible evidence for the reuse of storage structures may indicate that caching traditions may have contributed to the maintenance of local group membership through a tangible history of repeated land use. In the Late Tuniit Period, there is evidence for the organization of smaller, dispersed settlements between Qalirusiq and neighbouring peninsulas and islets, possibly suggesting the increased importance of translocal community structures maintained through shared viewsheds and expedient travel routes, in place of previous large-scale aggregations. The research at Qalirusiq positions local communities as flexible and relational social collectives, and suggests how recurrent and emergent coastal settlement practices may have contributed to the maintenance of large-scale social connections in the landscape.

In Chapter Seven, I present a new occupational history of Alarniq, which has been previously understood as a Late Tuniit wintering site. I present radiocarbon evidence for the possible construction of semi-subterranean dwellings at the end of the Early Tuniit Period (c. 2800-2500 BP) as well as evidence for dwelling reoccupations at the beginning of the Late Tuniit Period (c. 2500-2300 BP). Like Kapuivik, these findings challenge the dominant cultural-historical model that separates Tuniit peoples into bounded archaeological cultures, and suggests local variation in the emergence of architectural practices. Early occupational contexts (c. 2700-2000 BP) feature a diverse range of seasonal architecture and campsite structures, while later periods (c. 2000-600 BP) exhibit more uniform patterning (e.g., linearly arranged sod houses).

Paleotopographic models indicate that this shift may relate to large-scale spatial connections that were facilitated, in part, by Alarniq's transformation from an island to a coastal point fused to the mainland of Melville Peninsula. I also present radiocarbon evidence that extends regional Tuniit occupation by several centuries (c. 700–500 BP), suggesting temporal overlap with Early Inuit (c. 800 – 350 BP) and supporting Amitturmiut oral stories that describe cohabitation at Alarniq. The spatial and temporal complexity of Tuniit occupations illustrates how lasting social connections were sustained through a wide range of historically contingent and emergent settlement practices, and offers new perspectives on community movement and interaction within the broader landscape.

Chapter Eight centers on a comparative examination of the occupational patterning of Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq. I discuss how the oral historical, archaeological, and palaeogeographical research components articulate with one another to facilitate new interpretations of placemaking and community-building during the Tuniit Period. This includes

variability in household and intra-camp spatial structures that are suggestive of community differences, such as locally specific dwelling types, extramural feature layouts (e.g. the arrangement of hearths), and locational strategies (e.g., inland fishing and caching sites). Chronological changes in organizational strategies that may indicate social affiliation and difference are also discussed, most notably the demarcation of Early Tuniit camps by using landscape elements as visual barriers, and the construction of Late Tuniit winter settlements in elevated areas to establish viewsheds between non-local groups.

The analyses also demonstrate complex temporalities in the construction, differential use, and abandonment of settlement places that suggest intergenerational community identities and the active negotiation of social memberships through daily practices. This includes the maintenance of residential camps across the Early and Late Tuniit periods, as well as evidence for the recurrent use of warm weather dwellings and caches often inferred as ephemeral in previous regional research. These interpretations suggest how Tuniit communities were formed and differentiated at multiple social, spatial, and chronological scales through daily practices, land use strategies, and broader assemblages of movement, memory, and history that were articulated through repeated encounters with settlement places.

In Chapter Nine, I return to the objectives outlined in this introductory chapter and reflect on what has emerged differently in my research through the employment of a relational and place-based framework. The result of this research, I argue, is a narrative that presents Tuniit communities as relational and multiscalar collectives that were created and maintained, at least in part, through recurrent and emergent relations with persistent places. I then discuss the broader implications of this conclusion, including the importance of examining low-density occupation

areas located inland from outer seacoasts, and the efficiency of combining local landscape knowledge, RPA technologies, and pedestrian survey to identify and study these areas. I also problematize the region's beach ridge chronology and present a challenge to the long-held cultural division between Pre-Dorset and Dorset. In place, I demonstrate the efficacy of extensive radiocarbon dating to develop chronologies that account for local variability in community practices and structures, and a posthuman feminist and Indigenous framework that permits the interpretation of these differences as both records and seeds of past social worlds. Finally, I argue for the value and importance of including Inuit Qaujimajatuqangit in the study of non-descendant peoples like the Tuniit, to help make archaeology truly collaborative and to facilitate more historically contingent interpretations of settlement places in the Canadian Arctic.

I then outline the problems and limitations encountered through my study and suggest productive research directions for future archaeological projects in Amittuq and elsewhere in Inuit Nunangat. My discussion addresses the need for future projects to expand archaeological surveys to include a wide range of spatial settings while using more intensive and systematic survey techniques, and the importance of collaborating with local communities when building sampling frameworks and field designs. I conclude this chapter and dissertation by considering the potential of systematic test pitting to better understand low density site types, the benefits of further expanding local radiocarbon sequences, the restricted but still valuable utility of beach ridge chronological modelling for providing early temporal limits, and the need to prioritize further collaborations with Amitturmiut Knowledge Holders to locate and examine Tuniit archaeological sites described in oral history within deep interior locations.

Chapter Two

Assembling Archaeological Narratives in the Eastern Canadian Arctic

This chapter traces the development of current understandings of Tuniit occupational history in the eastern Canadian Arctic as informed through culture-historical, cultural ecological, and – to a lesser extent – structuralist and poststructuralist interpretive frameworks. Through this historiography, I outline some of the interpretive difficulties that cultural-historical taxa (e.g., archaeological cultures) and models of cultural systems (e.g., the core area) present for interpreting the structure, character, and scale of relational communities. I argue that while existing cultural models have been important for building spatial-temporal frameworks that map large-scale material change, they should not be treated as prerequisites for new studies of Tuniit settlement and social life (Birch et al. 2022; Feinman and Neitzel 2020; Johansen 2003; Harris 2014; Johansen and Bauer 2024; Pluckhahn et al. 2023; Watts 2016). Instead, I suggest the need for Arctic archaeologists to develop relational narratives of Tuniit communities through the places we study, which are often also places of living history that continue to affect the knowledge, perceptions, and identities of local people.

Theorizations of place (e.g., Basso 1996; Brittain 2016; Casey 1996; Harvey 1996; Price 2008, TallBear 2015; Watts 2016; Whitridge 2004) have not factored significantly into archaeological discourses on Tuniit peoples⁹. Instead, bounded spatial groupings such as typesites and cultural regions (e.g., Amittuq as the “core area”) continue to be the primary analytical units through which spatial variation in Tuniit material culture is described and explained. These

⁹ Although there are some relevant studies in the context of historic Inuit and Yup’ik archaeology (see Butler 2011; Hill 2013; Whitridge 2004, 2016).

categories work from an absolute conception of space and time in which material remains are relegated to an objective reality while the capacities and meanings they hold are confined to the human mind (e.g., cultural history and structuralism) or biological condition (e.g., cultural ecology) (Crellin 2021; Hillerhal and Siapkas 2015; Trigger 1998). These approaches risk reducing the landscape to an inert backdrop upon which material remains are measured and compared to produce knowledge about bounded cultural groups or developmental stage types. In contrast, an approach informed by Indigenous and posthuman feminist understandings of place treats archaeological materials and sites as both records and catalysts of past communities, which presents culture and sociality as historically contingent and relational processes. This makes space for the investigation of local variability in material remains, everyday practices, and spatial structures that shaped, and were shaped by, Tuniit social worlds.

Mobilizing *Saimaqatigiingniq* (*reconciliation/balance between equals*) with an affirmative conception of difference (see Barad 2003, 2007) encourages a relational ethic and the integration of multiple modes of analysis to keep this research open to multivocality. It also helps elide implicit assumptions about human and nonhuman agency that are often embedded in cultural-historical and socioevolutionary frameworks. As part of this approach, the study engages with the histories and knowledge of contemporary Amitturmiut Inuit to develop more historically contingent expectations about the affective capacities of people-place relationships in earlier periods. At the same time, the affordances and constraints of past environments on possibilities for community movement and practice are explored through the construction and analysis of paleotopographic models. This permits new explanations for what diversity and uniformity in archaeological remains might suggest about the changing structures and scale of communities during the Tuniit Period. Through the combination of different lines of historical evidence and

attention to difference and relational agency, this research permits richer interpretive conclusions about the formation and differentiation of Tuniit communities and the emergent, more-than-human worlds they helped create.

The first main section of this chapter explains how cultural-historical taxa were first developed and continue to inform the trajectory of Tuniit archaeological research. This includes descriptions and critiques of the Pre-Dorset (c.4500 – 2500 BP) and Dorset (c. 2500 – 1000 BP) archaeological cultures, the division of Arctic peoples into coastal and interior groups associated with different levels of cultural complexity, issues of scale resulting from a reliance on type-sites, and restricted engagement with Inuit ethnographies and oral histories. I demonstrate how implicit ideals from the development of cultural-historical frameworks continue to shape the methods and approaches employed in Tuniit archaeology (e.g., beach ridge chronology), largely because culture history continues to serve as a prerequisite for Arctic archaeological studies. I use this discussion to situate the relational, place-based approach I employ to examine small-scale variability in archaeological remains — the study of which is necessary for moving past the dominant cultural-historical framework (Feinman and Neitzel 2020; Johansen 2003).

A central (but lesser discussed) ethical problem of cultural-historical frameworks is the ways in which a reliance on archaeological cultures distances past peoples from contemporary local communities. As Birch et al. (2022:2) argue, culture history is not actually history: it is the bundling of artifacts into broad geographic and/or chronological groups that reflect narrow dimensions of past social worlds. In Amittuq, this process involves chronological typologies in which harpoon heads, lithic end blades, and architecture located on relic beach terraces are treated as material expressions of regional cultural groups that changed abruptly through

diffusionary forces, or — in later socioevolutionary models — adaptations to major climatic events (Maxwell 1985). While culture histories may remain useful starting points for some archaeological studies, they are not compatible with the conception of culture as a process, which limits their utility in studies of relational communities and social landscapes (Johansen 2003).

The concept of assemblage introduced in Chapter One (Section 1.2.2) helps elide the essentialism of cultural-historical taxa by reframing archaeological types as traces of *some* of the historical processes that unfolded at broad social and spatial scales (Fowler 2017). In other words, the periodization that has emerged from beach ridge typologies is reframed as a flexible framework that presents a partial perspective on the diverse relations and historical processes involving people and materials, rather than predefined, bounded cultures. To reinforce this conceptual difference in my work, I refer to the past peoples associated with the categories of Pre-Dorset and Dorset as the Early Tuniit and Late Tuniit, respectively —terms that represent a diversity of communities that occupied Amittuq prior to the ancestral Inuit, but that are connected through the historically situated places they repeatedly occupied (Walker 2020a:3).

In the second section of this chapter, I trace how cultural ecological approaches have reimagined Arctic archaeological cultures as adaptative cultural systems, resulting in the conception of Amittuq as a “core area” of resource prosperity and cultural development (Maxwell 1985; McGhee 1972; Savelle and Dyke 2014). This characterization is juxtaposed with the portrayal of neighbouring regions as home to less “complex” variants of archaeological cultures whose development was hindered by sparse or unpredictable resources (Darwent et al. 2018:532; Friesen et al. 2020:152; Hardenberg 2013:46; Mary-Rousselière 2002; Nagy 1996). This core-periphery binary presents a unidirectional relationship between people and their

biophysical environments in which the latter is the primary catalyst of sociocultural change. Moreover, it portrays Tuniit peoples as reactive entities that behaved in predictable and rationalist ways (e.g., always occupying the active shoreline). The core area model also brings issues of scale by presuming uniformity in regional environments and people's economic practices, and as such does not account for the dynamism of Arctic lands that is central to Inuit epistemology, social geography, and history (cf. Qitsualik 2013; Hudson et al. 2022).

By reframing social and biophysical processes as synchronous, co-productive forces of history, my work helps to challenge the normative systematics of the core area model and offers new perspectives on multiscale people-place relations. To further address issues of representation and scale, I investigate spatial contexts outside of shoreward-shifting coastal sequences (i.e., relic shorelines) to account for a greater variety of site types (e.g., coastal, lacustrine, paludal). I bring these data into conversation with paleoenvironmental data to reconstruct dynamic material places, and with Inuit epistemology of place to interpret the relational and historically specific agencies of human-nonhuman relationships embodied through archaeological remains.

The third section of this chapter expands on how the core area framework has enforced metaphysical divisions (e.g., nature/culture, subject/object, data/interpretation) that separate humans from their worlds. These binaries make up the intellectual structure of more recent structuralist approaches in Canadian Arctic archaeology that seek to identify the underlying cultural norms that structured Tuniit communities. While these approaches are valuable for considering how humans actively contributed to shaping broad social structures, I argue there is also need of approaches that are more attuned to small-scale relations and the fluidity of social

structures to better understand the emergence and differentiation of past communities.

Moving towards relational approaches requires an unbinding of the oppositional devices that continue to structure practice and interpretation in Tuniit archaeology. These include the ontological divisions mentioned above, but also conceptual oppositions such as simple/complex, prehistory/history, inland/coastal, continuity/discontinuity, and style/function which have been central to the formulation of the Pre-Dorset and Dorset archaeological cultures and the core/periphery generalization of their regional variants. I move past these dichotomies in my research by approaching “difference” as a historical and agentic process in which the boundaries between subject and object are fluid and mutable. This involves consulting a greater range of historical evidence (e.g., palaeogeographical data and oral histories), and the treatment of archaeological remains as traces of dynamic relationships in which individuals, places, and communities were ceasing to be one thing and becoming another (the virtual) (Barad 2007; Braidotti 2017; Harris 2014).

By attending to difference as affirmative and productive, I present Amittuq’s archaeological places as the congealment of Tuniit, Inuit, and Western histories rather than dormant records of a singular, linear past (Joyce 2021, Qitsualik 2008; Watts 2016). Framing Amittuq’s persistent places as participants in the continuous remaking of history opens new avenues for Saimaqatigiingniq by attending to the epistemological value of Inuit experiences and oral traditions for building new interpretations of Tuniit landscapes. In providing a clearer picture of the historic processes that connected humans and nonhumans through a shared occupational landscape, the place-based framework applied in this dissertation helps to reconcile issues of scale and representation, and offers new interpretive potentials from which to construct

a relational and plural narrative of Amittuq's human past.

2.1. A Note on the New Chronological Terminology Employed in this Dissertation

A major focus of this chapter is the explanation of how the Pre-Dorset and Dorset archaeological cultures, and their derived socioevolutionary stage types, continue to serve as precursors to new research. As argued in Chapter One (Section 1.2.2), this creates agential cuts that inform the kind and scale of material variability recognized by archaeologists, as well as what this variability is thought to represent (e.g. bounded cultures). In this dissertation, I instead employ the terms Early Tuniit and Late Tuniit as heuristic devices that encapsulate some of the broad chronological differences in material patterning previously recognized by archaeologists, such as the emergence of sod houses at the onset of the Late Tuniit (Dorset) Period (Table 2.1). These terms represent time periods rather than bounded representations of cultural (or biological) groups, or ethnic identity: sod houses affected communities as much as they were a product of them, as elements of emergent, multiscalar assemblages involving humans, non-humans, practices, and knowledge. I recognize that the terms Pre-Dorset and Dorset may also be used heuristically, and likely have been by many researchers in recent decades (e.g., Houmard 2018; Kotar 2022). However, the replacement of these terms helps to further distance my study from the implicit assumptions of culture history (e.g., culture as a bounded entity), and makes explicit how the prevalent archaeological chronology is mobilized. This choice attributes more intellectual authority to Inuit histories and perspectives that are integral to this research, and which should be more visible within academic research circles (Igloliorte et al 2017: 198).

Table 2.1: Overview of Arctic Culture History. Shaded areas refer to Amittuq’s regional history.

Proposed Terminology <i>*old terms</i>	Proposed Chronology of Major Material Shifts	Traditional Archaeological Cultures	Date Ranges by Region (Before Present)	Sources	
Inuit	Historic Inuit	Historic Inuit	500 – present	<i>Igloolik OHP; Maxwell 1985</i>	
<i>*Neo-Inuit</i> <i>*Neoeskimo</i>	Early (Ancestral) Inuit	Thule	1100 – 1500 <i>Eastern Arctic</i>	<i>Mathiassen 1925; Appelt 2003; McGhee 2000; Gullov 1997</i>	
Tuniit <i>*Paleo-Inuit</i> <i>*Paleoeskimo</i>	Late Tuniit	Dorset/Thule Transition	1000 – 600 <i>Nunavut/Nunavik</i>	<i>Igloolik OHP; Maxwell 1985; McGhee 1996; 2000; Morrison 1999; Pinard and Grendon 2009; Plumet 1994</i>	
		Terminal →	Late Dorset	1500 – 1000/600 <i>High Arctic, Nunavut, Nunavik</i>	<i>Friesen 2007; Maxwell 1985; McGhee 1996; Plumet 1994</i>
		Middle →	Middle Dorset	2000 – 1500 <i>Nunavut, Nunavik, Labrador</i>	<i>Desrosiers, et al. 2006; Maxwell 1985</i>
		Initial →	Early Dorset	2500 – 2000 <i>Nunavut</i> 2800 – 2000 <i>Labrador</i>	<i>Arundale 1981; Maxwell 1989; Tuck and Ramsden 1990; Savelle and Dyke 2014</i>
			Greenlandic Dorset/ Independence II	2800 – 2400 <i>Greenland</i>	<i>Damkjar 2003; Gronnow and Sorensen; Fitzhugh 1984; Knuth 1966, 1967, 1981, McGhee 1976, 1979, Schledermann 1990; Sutherland 1996</i>
	Early Tuniit		Groswater Dorset	2800 – 1900 <i>Eastern Nunavut, Newfoundland and Labrador</i>	<i>Auger 1984, 1986, Kennet 1990; LeBlanc 1996; Grendon 1990; Fitzhugh 1972; 1976, Renouf 1994</i>
		Terminal →	Late Pre–Dorset	3300–2500 <i>Nunavut/ Eastern Arctic Canada</i>	<i>Arundale 1981; Grendon 1990; Maxwell 1985; McGhee 1976; Plumet 1994; Savelle and Dyke 2002</i>
		Middle →	Middle Pre–Dorset	3700–3300 <i>Nunavut/ Eastern Arctic Canada</i>	
		Initial →	Early Pre–Dorset	4500–3700 <i>Nunavut/ Eastern Arctic Canada</i>	
			Saqqaq	4500–2400 <i>South–Western/Low Arctic Greenland</i>	<i>Larsen 1956; Larsen and Meldgaard 1958; Meldgaard 1952; 1958; Maxwell 1985</i>
		Independence I	4000– 3700 <i>Central Arctic/Nunavut</i> 4500–4000 <i>North–Eastern Greenland</i>	<i>Anderson 2011; Fitzhugh 1984; Gronnow and Jensen 2003; Knuth 1952, 1954, 1958, 1977, 1978, 1981, 1983; McGhee 1976, 1979</i>	
		Denbigh Flint Complex	5500–4000 <i>North Alaska</i>	<i>Giddings 1949, 1951, 1964; Harrit 1998:63–69; Hopkins 1952; Slaughter 2005</i>	
Siberian Neolithic			6000–3000 BP	<i>Raghavan et al. 2014</i>	

While archaeologists often describe the term “Tuniit” as referring to the people that ancestral Inuit encountered during the terminal Dorset period, contemporary Amitturmiut Inuit use this term to also identify much earlier archaeological sites constructed by Tuniit ancestors. Oral histories are not the only line of evidence for continuity between Early Tuniit (Pre-Dorset) and Late Tuniit (Dorset) communities. Radiocarbon dates presented within this dissertation suggest site maintenance practices and local community traditions that transcend these periods, supporting the broader use of the term Tuniit, at least within the region of Amittuq. Where relevant, when discussing prior archaeological research, I use the ordinal adjectives “initial”, “middle”, and “terminal” along with the terms Early Tuniit (Pre-Dorset) and Late Tuniit (Dorset) to discuss temporal changes previously framed as progressive stages of cultural development. For example, I describe the sub-period known as “Late Dorset” as terminal Late Tuniit. This reframing helps me reference previously documented patterns of large-scale material change, such as the emergence of new harpoon head technologies at the start of the Late Tuniit period, commonly referred to as “Early Dorset” (c. 2500-2000 BP), without implying that these differences represent discrete cultural groups (Crellin and Harris 2021:8; Haraway 1997:273; Kirby 2017:151). With this as my starting point, I take a relational approach to past communities that attends to small-scale variation in the form and arrangement of Tuniit campsites, and reinterpret these contexts as embodying social differences and affiliations beyond the geographic and chronological phases that govern the culture-historical model.

2.2 The Logic and Practices of Arctic Culture History

Until the mid-1970s, most archaeological projects in the Canadian Arctic were centered

on the construction of culture history. This involved the identification of broadly defined ethnological traits or material types that were first used to define culture circles, and later construct archaeological cultures (e.g. Pre-Dorset and Dorset), that represented uniform and bounded cultural groups that corresponded with biological groups (Hood 1998; Maxwell 1985). These classifications presented past people as static cultural entities and focused studies on a relatively narrow dimension of the archaeological record — that is, broad patterns of technological and architectural change (Birch et al. 2022; Feinmen and Neitzal 2020; Johansen 2003; Matthew et al. 2002).

Below I trace the logic and practice of cultural-historical frameworks in Arctic research, and suggest how archaeologists might begin to move past their implicit use. I discuss the limitations that cultural-historical taxa present, both for investigating small-scale diversity in community practices and addressing the complexities of human and nonhuman agency in specific historical contexts. Because cultural-historical frameworks present society and culture as spatially uniform entities, their use also corresponds with a continued reliance on “type-sites” that project interpretations of local assemblages onto massive regions. In Amittuq, type-sites are also associated with the construction and use of beach ridge chronologies that further generalize the temporality of communities and present cultural change as abrupt and progressive. I suggest how reframing Tuniit communities as dynamic assemblages, and “type-sites” as persistent places that actively participated in these assemblages, help me move past bounded cultures to interpret multiscalar and dynamic social landscapes during the Tuniit period. I also present extensive radiocarbon dating and engagement with oral histories as important interventions for addressing the complex temporalities of Tuniit settlement sites and historically situating archaeological research designs.

2.2.1 Ethnology, Anthro-geography, and Early Scandinavian Influences

Arctic archaeology emerged from an early curiosity in Inuit ethnology and its relationship with physical geography (Birket-Smith 1929; Steensby 1916; Mathiassen 1924; Rasmussen et al. 1925, cf. Dekin 1978:8). This involved the projection of cultural variability observed in the ethnographic present onto the past to interpret the diffusion of past cultures. Underlying these comparisons was a belief that Inuit societies did not develop like Western societies, and were instead relatively static collectives defined by regional subsistence economies (Trigger 1981).

Early anthropologists took inspiration from Hinrich Rink's research in Greenland (1887), who argued for an easterly Inuit migration from Alaska by way of the Yukon River, adapting to new environmental conditions as they moved coastward (Figure 2.1). Boas (1888) kept with Rink's logic by mapping the reciprocal connections of Inuit groups through their language and folklore, but concluded that the source of most Inuit myths centered around Foxe Basin (Amittuq) in the Qikiqtaaluk region¹⁰, where year-round maritime activities and seasonal aggregations between groups took place (Boas 1888:461- 462, see also Rink and Boas 1889). This work was of great interest to Danish ethnologist Hans Peder Steensby, who suggested that the ancestral Inuit were not the first Canadian Arctic peoples, coining the term "Palæeskimo" for the original settlers (Steensby 1916:171). Steensby argued that the Palæeskimo developed along Arctic coastlines, as only these areas could have provided the necessary environmental conditions for their development (Steensby 1916:205). While Rink, Boas, and Steensby were critical to the initial development of culture history, their reliance on the ethnographic present prehistory perpetuated an essentialist notion of history that was defined by progression and

¹⁰ The official name of the region, previously referred to by Western (southern) researchers as the Baffin region, which includes waters and islands surrounding Baffin Island.

development, resulting in ahistorical narratives about Indigenous pasts (Trigger 1981:5). This treatment of the ethnographic record would continue to underlie Arctic archaeological projects in the following decades.

Figure 2.1 Map of Inuit Nunangat (*homeland*) showing places discussed in Chapter Two. The orange line defines the Qikiqtaaluk region, and Amittuq is highlighted in red. A grey dashed line shows the maximum extent of the Foxe Basin “core area”. Projected in WGS84 NSIDC to reduce distortion of polar land mass.

2.2.2 *Kulturkreislehre* and the Development of Culture Circles

It was not until the Fifth Thule Expedition (1921-1924) that the first substantial set of archaeological excavations took place in the eastern Canadian Arctic, led by Danish archaeologist Therkel Mathiassen (Mathiassen 1924; Rasmussen et al. 1925). Mathiassen argued that modern Inuit were relatively recent arrivals to the Eastern Arctic and that a separate cultural group, later to be named the Thule culture¹¹, had preceded them (Mathiassen 1925:212, 1927:89, see Table 2.1).

Mathiassen was influenced by the theory of culture circles (*Kulturkreislehre*), a German cultural-historical movement that had begun to dominate interpretations of prehistoric archaeology in continental Europe (Harp 1984:20). The term *kulturkreis* was used to describe an archaeologically or ethnographically observed complex of cultural traits, as well as the inferred “circle” or area¹² of its distribution. While this movement sought to refute the idea of a universal human nature, the persisting influence of Scandinavian ethnology meant that cultural evolutionism and culture history were treated as complementary concepts (Harris 2001:174; Rebay-Salisbury 2011:42; Trigger 2006:123; Wissler 1920:125). As such, geographic comparisons in cultural trait diffusion, as seen for instance in Mathiassen’s (1930:596) and colleague Birket-Smith’s (1929:11) analysis of morphological differences in qulliqs (*soapstone lamps*), served to define culture circles. At the same time, the emergence of the qulliq as an archaeological type, which Mathiassen (1930:596) believed originated in Central Asia, was explained through the technological progression of past societies through evolutionary stages

¹¹ Thule is a Western academic term for Inuit culture prior to the historical period. I refer to Thule-period communities in later chapters of this dissertation as Early Inuit communities. Early Inuit is the preferred term as expressed by the Igloolik Hunters and Trappers Association (Igloolik HTA pre-field meeting, 2018).

¹² The term “culture area” was more common elsewhere in North America during the 1920s and 1930s but adhered to a similar theoretic (cf. Kroeber 1939; Wissler 1922).

(Harp 1984:20; Morgan 1964 [1877]). This perpetuated binaries of “simple” versus “complex” Arctic societies based on their respective associations with inland and coastal environments, while prioritizing conceptions of intragroup uniformity through broad geographic and chronological patterns in material culture.

2.2.2.1 Beach Ridge Chronology and Early Culture History. The most influential component of Mathiassen’s study involved chronology building centered on coastal arctic sites, using beach ridge sequencing. *Kulturkreislehre* reduced culture to the spatial dimension of the ethnological present, and Mathiassen turned to geological methods employed by earlier evolutionists to interpret the temporal depth of trait distribution and diffusion. Conventional stratigraphic analyses presented complications due to the very thin lenses of tundra soils, and so Mathiassen employed a “horizontal” stratigraphic method in which he estimated the antiquity of sites located on relic shorelines based on their elevation above sea level. Although post-glacial rebound rates for the Canadian Arctic were not well understood in the early 20th century (Birket-Smith 1930:610), their value for reconstructing culture history was supported by an archaeological study in northeast Greenland (Wissler 1918:113), as well as previous studies on the coasts of northern Europe conducted by Scandinavian antiquarians and geologists (De Geer 1890; Knowles 1879:209; Lamplugh 1913; Prestwich 1892; Smith 1893:360; Trigger 2006:315).

Mathiassen (1925:206) premised his beach ridge chronology on Steensby’s (1916) presupposition that, given the marine-based economies of modern Inuit, prehistoric cultural groups would have continuously occupied outer seacoasts. Through beach ridge sequencing he deduced that a Paleoeskimo culture – should it be found – would be located about 20 metres above sea level (MASL), inland from the residual coastal terraces occupied by Thule people

(Mathiassen 1930:596). As clear beach ridge sequences were only present in some coastal areas, Mathiassen's diachronic inferences were applied to certain archaeological contexts. This further enforced the regionalization of archaeological cultures, and presented material change as linear, progressive, and centered on coastal environmental contexts.

2.2.3 *The Legacy of "Paleoeskimo" (Paleo-Inuit, Tuniiit) Archaeological Cultures*

Canadian-led Arctic research began with the work of Diamond Jenness (1925). A large collection of archaeological materials originally collected by Inuit near Kinngait (Figure 2.1), formerly known as Cape Dorset, was brought to the National Museum of Canada (Taylor 1959). Comparing the materials of this collection with Mathiassen's reports, Jenness noted that some of the Kinngait artifacts lacked the evidence of drilling that characterized Mathiassen's Thule assemblages (1925:435-436). Based on these observations, Jenness identified what would come to be called the Dorset culture (Table 2.1). Jenness' hypothesis was not immediately accepted (Mathiassen 1927:2), but by the 1940s several archaeological discoveries had constructed the Dorset culture, as well as a series of potential progenitor cultures (e.g., Pre-Dorset, Independence I), in occupational sequences as far west as Alaska and as far east as Greenland.

The 1940s and 1950s saw a significant increase in the number of North American archaeologists working in the Canadian Arctic, and with them a movement away from *Kulturkreislehre* toward American cultural-historical frameworks. American archaeologists were more overtly opposed to unilinear schemes that viewed analogous cultural traits as sharing a singular casual path, and instead saw culture as developing through historically particular

mechanisms (Trigger 2006:219). This was accompanied by a conceptual shift from the ethnological problem of Inuit origins to inquiries about how various Pre-Inuit archaeological cultures, especially Pre-Dorset and Dorset, fit into existing schemes of Arctic culture history (Hood 1998:14; Harp 1984:21; Taylor 1959:39).

American cultural-historical frameworks focused more on the temporal dimension of cultural development and described the past through a chronological sequence of archaeological cultures that represented discrete ethnic groups. These archaeological cultures were constructed by comparing sites whose assemblages shared distinct material characteristics, by means of synchronisms, stratigraphy, and seriation (Maxwell 1985, see Trigger 2006:244). Typological differences in lithic and osseous toolkits, especially chert endblade and harpoon heads were conceived of as reflections of cultural, and often biological, differences resulting from ethnic replacement or diffusionary processes (Ford 1938; Maxwell 1985; Phillips and Willey 1953:617; Trigger 2006:279).

Graham Rowley's 1939 excavation of Avvajja (Abverjar) in Amittuq was one of the first excavations to contain an extensive Dorset lithic assemblage "uncontaminated" by Thule artifacts, helping to define the Dorset and Thule archaeological cultures (Dekin 1978:19; Rowley 1940). The same year, Jenness (1940:9) suggested that the Dorset lithic toolkit was too developed to represent the first culture in the Canadian Arctic, and likely shared a cultural ancestor from Alaska. A progenitor for the Dorset culture was soon after proposed by Louis Giddings based on flint microliths identified in Denbigh, Alaska (Figure 2.1), which he named the Denbigh Flint Complex (1949; 1951, see *Table 2.1*). Similar lithic toolkits were excavated elsewhere during the 1940s, leading to the identification of the Independence I culture in

northeastern Greenland (Knuth 1952, 1954) and the Saqqaq culture in western Greenland and the Canadian Arctic¹³ (Holtved 1944; Meldgaard 1952; Larsen 1961). In 1951, Henry Collins (1951:428) proposed that these lithic assemblages represented variations of a macroscale cultural entity that preceded the Dorset migration from Alaska to Greenland, which he named the Arctic Small Tool Tradition (ASTt)¹⁴.

Scholarly identification of the “Pre-Dorset” culture emerged in the early 1950s (Collins 1954:299) and was soon understood by many as the ASTt variant that covered most of the Canadian Arctic and Subarctic coasts from 4000 BP until at least 2800 BP (Taylor 1968:88, see Table 2.1). Pre-Dorset sites were identified in Nunavut (Cox 1978; McGhee 1996), Ungava/Nunavik (Grendon and Pinard 2000; LeBlanc 1996; Plumet 1994), Manitoba (Anderson and Hodgetts 2007; Nash 1969), Nunatsiavut/Labrador (Fitzhugh 1972; 1980; Cox 1978), and some areas in Western Greenland (Grønnow and Sørensen 2006:70). The discovery of Pre-Dorset in so many regions suggested that the ASTt had undertaken a rapid territorial expansion eastward shortly after it emerged in Alaska. New archaeological finds would increasingly point to the Bering Strait for ASTt and Dorset origins (Collins 1953), a hypothesis that gained acceptance as archaeological studies demonstrated increasing time-depth in the western Arctic through the relatively rare but growing number of stratified sites (Dekin 1978:20-22).

Overall, most archaeologists today agree concerning the broad chronological sequence that the archaeological record represents (Table 2.1). In the context of Amittuq, this sequence describes the arrival of the “Pre-Dorset” (Early Tuniiit) from Alaska shortly after the region’s

¹³ The term Saqqaq (*Sarqaq*) was originally applied by Meldgaard (1952) to sites in Amittuq, which are now referred to as “Pre-Dorset” (Maxwell 1985).

¹⁴ Cultures included in the ASTt include Denbigh, Independence I, Saqqaq (sometimes spelled Sarqaq), and Pre-Dorset.

deglaciation (4500 – 3700 BP) (Arundale 1981; Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1965; Savelle and Dyke 2014; Ryan 2016). This was followed by the emergence of the “Dorset” (Late Tuniiit) around 2500 – 2000 BP, either by way of an incoming migration or through *in situ* development in the Foxe Basin region. Ancestral Inuit populations then migrated to Amittuq around 1000 BP, and shortly after the Dorset disappear from the archaeological record.

Although this general scheme is accepted by many, there remains considerable debate regarding the specific timing of, and meanings behind, the observed shifts in material culture (e.g., chert endblades, ivory harpoon heads, sod house architecture) underpinning these chronological phases. These include conflicting models of the emergence and spread of tool technologies and the nature of the Pre-Dorset to Dorset cultural transition (Friesen and Mason 2016; Hood 1998; Maxwell 1985; Houmard 2018; Ryan 2016; Savelle and Dyke 2014). While explanations vary, the viability of cultural-historical taxa for explaining the social lives of past peoples are rarely questioned (Kotar 2022). However, a reliance on cultural-historical taxa presents interpretive problems for socially oriented research, as they restrict analysis to broad spatial and social scales (e.g., type-sites, culture areas), and presume cultural uniformity within these classifications. While the recognition of major spatiotemporal differences in artifact types provided a critical foundation for building refined models of technological change, the continued presumption of large-scale cultural uniformity has meant that culture is rarely explicitly recognized as a process (see Johansen 2003; Johansen and Bauer 2024; Feinman and Neitzel 2020), and small-scale differences in material remains remain overlooked as valuable dimensions of these processes. Attention to multiple scales of analysis remain a priority for moving past archaeological cultures in Arctic research, and this is something that reframing culture as a historical process, and communities as assemblages, can help facilitate. More specific

interpretive problems of Arctic culture history, and their proposed interventions, are further explained in the following section.

2.2.4 The Effects of Cultural Replacement Theories

In Canadian Arctic research, explanations of cultural change centered on the replacement of local peoples by incoming groups. Migration and acculturation frameworks focused on the results of culture contact rather than processes of cultural interaction (Friesen 2013:6). This presented typological changes as sudden and radical, leaving little room to examine social differences beyond the confines of bounded cultures. For example, the replacement of the Pre-Dorset by the Dorset culture in eastern Canadian Arctic has largely been founded on the decline of spalled burins and the emergence of slate tools and semisubterranean sod dwellings, conclusions that tend to overlook the continued production of open-socket harpoon heads, lances, and boulder tent rings identified in the earlier Pre-Dorset period, that may speak to social continuity in local contexts (Collins 1954; Cox 1978; Maxwell 1985; Ryan 2003; Taylor 1968:85).

Acculturation theories facilitated a progressive, linear model of history in which “superior” cultures, as defined by a bounded, tangible set of artifacts, were replaced “inferior” ones through continuous contact between distinct ethnic groups (Friesen 2013:5-6). This lent itself to the notion of cultural extinction as a natural consequence of societal progress (Atalay 2006; Lawrence 2004; Schindler et al. 1985; Stuhl 2017). Acculturation presented a tautology in which archaeological data were organized into broad temporal classifications and interpreted as

discrete cultural episodes that ultimately served to affirm preconceived understandings of pan-Arctic migration events and the spread of archaeological cultures (Taylor 1968:80). This had two lasting problematic effects in Canadian Arctic archaeology: it restricted how the Inuit ethnographic record and local community knowledge were attended to by archaeologists (see Hood 2002; Riche 1990), and enforced a reductive view of cultural development that constrained how data could be mobilized to understand social continuity and change at local and regional scales.

2.2.4.1 Impacts on the Mobilization of Inuit Ethnography and Local Knowledge. Cultural replacement theories presented contemporary Inuit societies as too contaminated by Westerners to be relied on as a source of historic information or analogy (Valle 1962; Hughes 1965; 1984; Balikci 1989). This restricted Inuit involvement in discussions over the history of their land, and limited archaeological engagements with local knowledge about the deep past (Balikci 1989:105; IE181; IE355). Up until the 1970s, archaeologists working in the eastern Canadian Arctic relied almost exclusively on the ethnological studies of Boas (1888), Steensby (1916), and the Fifth Thule Expedition (Birket-Smith 1930; Rasmussen 1925) to support their archaeological inferences, since these works preceded significant colonial contact (Campbell 1986:1; Mary-Rousselière 1984:431; Riche 1990:72; Schindler et al. 1985:481; Wobst 1978:304). The consequence of this was two-fold. First, it dogmatized early ethnographic texts, presenting them as objective records of historic Inuit lifeways, which resulted in the acceptance of ethnocentric assumptions as fact (Balikci 1989:104; Schindler 1985:481). Second, it relegated the concerns, beliefs, and knowledge of Inuit to the work of salvage ethnographers (Brody 1976:186; Innuksuk and Cowan 1976:15). This meant that homologous resonances between the diversity and fluidity of modern Inuit communities and material variability of the archaeological record were not

considered, which left archaeological cultures to be assessed solely through the reductive classification systems and idealist assumptions from which they originated (Stahl 1993).

2.2.4.2 Impacts on Type-Sites and Linear Histories. Acculturation approaches overlooked nuances in material variation, and often neglected the cultural importance of archaeological evidence for repeated occupation and continuity in occupational practices at multiperiod sites. The 1953 excavations of the Sermermiut “type-site” in Greenland are illustrative of these interpretive restrictions (Figure 2.1). After discovering a rich Thule midden, Meldgaard and Larsen (1958) dug through the sterile stratum beneath to reveal successive Dorset and Saqqaq deposits (Meldgaard 1954a:5). This clear succession was a rare find that allowed Meldgaard and Larsen to test and refine Saqqaq, Dorset, and Thule artifact typologies, which allowed archaeologists to better identify the cultural affiliations of more ephemeral sites in the Eastern Arctic. From the small set of local data retrieved from Sermermiut, Meldgaard and Larsen (1958 65-66) stabilized the assumption that Eastern Arctic culture history involved a clear succession of discrete ethnic entities that migrated from the west. To many, this demonstrated the credibility of focusing on a small number of stratified sites scattered throughout the Eastern Arctic to assess the timing and spread of human migrations, and for constructing occupational histories (Maxwell 1985:210).

That Sermermiut was repeatedly occupied for over two millennia was overlooked as a phenomenon of potential cultural significance¹⁵. Archaeological cultures represented as discrete biological entities that replaced one another, and evidence of relations that might have connected people from different times through places like Sermermiut, such as the intergenerational

¹⁵ It is now known that Sermermiut was occupied even longer, as the initial Saqqaq layer dated to 810 BCE has since been redated with radiocarbon assays of 1410 ± 120 and 1560 ± 120 BCE from plant matter (Maxwell 1985: 103).

maintenance of dwellings or the living memory of Inuit, were not considered. Sermermiut was limited to its characterization as a type-site: an inert, spatially bounded stage upon which discrete ethnic groups expressed their identities in a chronological fashion through material culture. This left little room to consider Sermermiut as a participant in the diverse historical processes that shaped Tuniit social groups and their material culture. The treatment of multi-period sites as linear records of successive, archaeological cultures has remained a major structuring force of Arctic culture history. This is something my project works to overcome by reframing Arctic “type-sites” as relational, messy, and emergent persistent places.

2.2.5 Culture History in Amittuq

In the late 1950s, type-sites became the primary apparatus for developing regional typological systems and refining culture history (Fitzhugh et al. 2002; Houmard 2018; Howse 2019; Ryan 2009). Coastal type-sites characterized by sequences of relic shorelines were particularly important, as they served as the primary epistemological measure for geological chronologies that were equated with the emergence and development of archaeological cultures (Meldgaard 1962; Savelle and Dyke 2014). This perpetuated earlier evolutionary assumptions about Arctic societies while enforcing the idea that the “Pre-Dorset” and “Dorset” archaeological cultures represented homogenous, widespread ethnic groups. This section describes the development of coastal type-sites in Amittuq (Meldgaard 1962) and elsewhere in Foxe Basin (Taylor 1968), and outlines their continued role in structuring the temporalizing logics of Arctic culture history.

2.2.5.1 Increased Importance of Beach Ridge Archaeology. In 1954, Jørgen Meldgaard

continued developing artifact typologies of Arctic archaeological cultures through a series of excavations in the Amittuq region (Figure 2.2, see Meldgaard 1954a). Meldgaard had studied Dorset artifacts from the region housed at the National Museum of Copenhagen and noticed striking similarities to assemblages in Western Greenland. However, it was the environmental setting described by Mathiassen that compelled him to excavate in Amittuq, as the region's "eroded limestone country showed a well-developed system of raised beaches" (1954a:7) from which he hoped to construct a comprehensive chronology of archaeological cultures.

While Sermermiut provided a stratified sequence for building a relative chronology, type-sites in Amittuq offered horizontal sequences of beach terraces that Meldgaard (1965) perceived as offering a higher temporal resolution. He denoted beach terraces in metres above sea level (MASL) and used a small set of radiocarbon assays obtained from *in situ* contexts to establish calendar year associations for terrace intervals (Meldgaard and Wallace 1960). By comparing how the form and frequency of archaeological types changed within local beach ridge sequences, Meldgaard established what remains one of the most referenced typological systems in Eastern Arctic archaeology (Maxwell 1985; Røe 2021). A reliance on geological chronologies resulted in the construction of what were essentially chronotypes — that is, bounded categories of space and time that perpetuate a static view of culture, painting the past with a broad brush and presenting narrow interpretations of human social lives (Roddick 2018; Joyce 2002; Stahl 1993).

2.2.5.2 Meldgaard's Type-Sites. Meldgaard saw the Pre-Dorset culture as the result of migrations from Alaska, and Dorset as a migration of separate people from the Canadian Subarctic that subsequently adapted to the Arctic coasts (Meldgaard 1954a;1962). This explained how new cultural traits emerged in the Early Dorset period, but also how tool types resembling

Pre-Dorset re-emerged as the Dorset adapted to the same environment. He explained how material culture became more “Eskimo-like” at the end of the Dorset period through the assimilation of people by incoming Inuit seafaring groups (Meldgaard 1960a:594).

Meldgaard’s interpretations were premised on a small number of type-sites, including Qalirusiq (Parry Hill), Kapuivik, and Alarniq (Alarnerk) (Figure 2.2). Qalirusiq was distinguished by a continuous occupational sequence between 37 to 51 MASL that spanned from 4000 to 2800 BP (Figure 2.3, see Meldgaard 1962b:93; 1965:2). Qalirusiq served as a type-site for the Pre-Dorset archaeological culture. Meldgaard (1962:93) noted that spalled burins and chert blades decreased in size over time at Qalirusiq, and that ivory sewing needles, while remaining relatively small, tended to increase in size. As artifact styles changed subtly but no “new” types emerged, Meldgaard inferred Pre-Dorset as a stable cultural entity¹⁶. Based on the identification of several cache features with evidence of walrus remains, Melgaard (1965:5-7) interpreted Qalirusiq as wintering site and – echoing Mathiassen – attributed its occupational continuity to the adaptation of Pre-Dorset people to a coastal environment.

¹⁶ Meldgaard’s field notes were never submitted to a Canadian repository and only short technical reports are available for reference. It has been an objective of the Foxe Basin Archaeological Project to reconstruct Meldgaard’s field activities by mapping his excavation units and examining his back dirt piles at these type-sites.

Figure 2.2: Meldgaard's primary type-sites are marked in red: 1) Parry Hill/ Qalirusiq; 2) Kapuivik; 3) Alarnerk/ Alarniq.
Digitally modified from Meldgaard (1954a: Map No.1).

Figure 2.3 Meldgaard's map of the main Pre-Dorset sequence at Qalirusiq. Digitally modified from Rowley (1991).

Kapuvik, located on Kapuiviit Island (formerly Jens Munk Island, see *Nunavut [2009]*), was the only site continuously occupied for both the Pre-Dorset and Dorset periods, which allowed Meldgaard to identify typological differences between the archaeological cultures (1962:1-2). Based on his sketches of the site (Figures 2.4a and 2.4b), Meldgaard identified approximately 165 Tuniit features located on beach terraces between 8 and 51 MASL, associated with geological ages of 4500 to 1000 BP. He described the shift in material culture between Pre-Dorset and Dorset as a rapid change, evidenced by the last traces of Pre-Dorset spalled burins around 23 MASL and the emergence of Dorset burin-like tools, slate knives, and rectangular dwellings at 22 MASL (Meldgaard 1962:13). Between his technological reports and conference papers (Taylor 1968:101), Meldgaard offered two hypotheses: 1) that the Kapuvik transition

represented the cultural replacement of Pre-Dorset by Dorset (i.e., acculturation), or 2) that Dorset migrated to Amittuq within a few centuries after a Pre-Dorset extinction event – a time range that reflects his estimated isostatic uplift rate for a metre gain (i.e., 22 to 23 MASL) in coastal elevation (Meldgaard 1954a, 1962; Meldgaard and Wallace 1960). This latter explanation of a Pre-Dorset decline and extinction was supported by Meldgaard’s (1960b:75) observation of the “degenerate and inferior workmanship” of Pre-Dorset tools along the 23 MASL terrace. These interpretations were applied to Amittuq as a whole despite lacking archaeological evidence for a rapid transition at other sites in the region (Nagy 1994: 2-3).

Figure 2.4a Distribution of features at Kapuvik showing elevation intervals associated with the Pre-Dorset to Dorset transition. *Digitally modified from Meldgaard (1962:92)*

Figure 2.4b Close up of Kapuivik, Highlighting the Late Dorset occupational area identified by Meldgaard. *Digitally modified from Melgaard (1954a: Map No. 3).*

Alarniq, the third type-site located on Melville Peninsula, contained over one hundred Dorset features that were distributed in a continuous sequence from 8 to 22 MASL (Figure 2.5). Meldgaard believed that Alarniq represented the temporal extent of the Dorset culture and divided his local typology into five periods (1965:67-69), the earliest of which was attributed to a radiocarbon date of 1952 BP \pm 129 (Rainey and Ralph 1959). These periods are often now simplified into the “Early”, “Middle”, and “Late” Dorset periods (Table 2.1). Meldgaard excavated several Dorset burial features at Alarniq¹⁷ from which he recovered a great deal of art made from walrus ivory. The increasing frequency and “sophistication” of ivory art throughout the Dorset sequence supported his argument for the progressive development of Dorset into a marine-adapted culture (Meldgaard 1962:3; see Lynnerup et al. 2003).

¹⁷ Tuniit human remains are exceptionally rare, with only 20 individuals having been identified in published reports, contributing to the exceptionality of Alarniq as a “type-site” at this time (McGhee 1996:147).

Figure 2.5 Distribution of Archaeological Features at Alarniq showing elevation intervals associated with Dorset Sub-Periods. *Digitally Modified from Melgaard (1954a: Map No.2).*

2.2.5.3 *Taylor's Type-Sites and the In Situ Hypothesis.* In 1958, William Taylor undertook a series of investigations just south of Amittuq that provided an alternative hypothesis for the development of the Dorset culture. While Meldgaard viewed Pre-Dorset and Dorset as biologically distinct groups of people, Taylor (1968: viii) argued that there was sufficient similarity in their archaeological assemblages to demonstrate continuity between the two cultures. His work was centered on two type-sites, Arnapiik and Tayara (Figure 2.1), that were initially identified through elevation comparisons with Meldgaard's coastal sequences (Figure 2.6). Arnapiik was located between 28 and 42 MASL and so was attributed to the Pre-Dorset culture, while Tayara was a semi-stratified site located on coastal plateau around 16.5 MASL, and as such was attributed to Dorset (Periods II and III).

Taylor (1968:80-81) argued that stressing material difference when constructing typologies would inevitably lead to the inference of discrete ethnic groups, even if cultural continuity had occurred. He inferred the continuous development of Pre-Dorset ground burins to Early Dorset burin-like tools, and from Pre-Dorset semi-lunate to Dorset ovate side blades (1968:82-84). Based on their coastal location, the identification of toggling harpoon heads, and faunal assemblages dominated by flipped sea mammals, he argued that Dorset emerged from the adaptation of Pre-Dorset to a coastal setting (Taylor 1968:87). Meldgaard later revised his hypothesis in favour of Taylor's *in situ* hypothesis (Meldgaard 1965:1), but debates over the cultural and biological affiliations of Pre-Dorset and Dorset have persisted (Flegontov et al. 2019; Houmard 2018; Raghavan et al. 2014; Ryan 2016; Savelle and Dyke 2014). A contributing factor to these debates is the tendency of beach ridge archaeology to portray material change as abrupt large-scale events, even though terraces may represent palimpsests of cultural activity.

Figure 2.6 Distribution of excavated areas along coastal terraces at (A) Arnapiik (*JIGu-9*) and (B) Tyara. Digitally Modified from Taylor (1968: 13, 45).

2.2.6 The Coastal Type-Site Problem

Beach ridge elevation is generally accepted within Arctic archaeological research as an epistemological measure of chronology that serves as the basis for both cultural-historical and social evolutionary explanations of material change (Friesen 2016:675; Giddings 1986; Mason 1993; Savelle et al. 2014; Howse et al. 2019). The primary issue related to the employment of Meldgaard and Taylor's typologies in this context is data-stretching: the erection of typological systems spanning large regions and durations of time from small local datasets, for the purpose of demonstrating broad cultural patterns (Gero 2007:321). For example, the "T1" occupation of Native Point on Shugliaq (Figure 2.1) was identified as Dorset Period II (c. 2500 BP) from the presence of three harpoon head types found at Kapuivik and Alarniq (Rainey and Ralph 1959), and sites at Port Refuge (Figure 2.1) were identified as "earliest Pre-Dorset" from a self-bladed harpoon head type found at Qalirusiq (McGhee 1976:20). A major problem with data-stretching is that it can become so entrenched in scholarship that it is difficult to account for its effects on archaeological interpretations (Boozer 2014:97). In the eastern Canadian Arctic, this has led to significant analytical and interpretive limitations for constructing Arctic culture history.

2.2.6.1 Poor Temporal Control. Meldgaard and Taylor's typologies are also complicated by chronological problems related to radiocarbon dates and coastal uplift rates. Many of the radiocarbon dates retrieved from coastal sites during the 1950s and 1960s were sourced from marine mammals, and as such were impacted by a marine reservoir effect¹⁸ that was poorly understood at this time (Arundale 1981; Becker and Kromer 1993; see Dyke et al. 2019). The fact that marine mammal dates appear older than contemporary terrestrial mammal dates likely

¹⁸ Marine reservoirs cause ¹⁴C dates from marine sources to appear notably older due to variability in oceanic carbon cycles. This effect varies between locales, and within locales, between species (for exception see Dyke et al. 2018).

attributed to Meldgaard and Taylor's inferences that the earliest Dorset occupations occurred along Foxe Basin's coasts (Maxwell 1985:70). Charcoal samples sourced from old driftwood for radiocarbon dating also artificially increased the antiquity of coastal contexts, while the precision of ^{14}C dates associated with the Late Pre-Dorset/Early Dorset periods were obscured by the Hallstatt plateau, which causes these dates to calibrate to 2750 – 2350 BP regardless of measurement precision (Bielawski 1988; Grønnow 2017; McGhee and Tuck 1976; Tuck and McGhee 1983). Given the limited number of published reports, most ^{14}C dates from this time are also subject to unknown lab errors, further complicating their reliability (Dyke et al. 2019:72).

New ^{14}C assays are revealing the problematic effects that early radiocarbon dates have had on interpretations of type-site beach sequences. A set of new dates on charcoal at Tyara, for example, has identified a previously unrecognized Pre-Dorset horizon and redated Taylor's Early Dorset component as Middle Dorset (Desrosiers et al. 2008:760). These refinements have significant interpretive consequences. For instance, Taylor's "Tyara sliced" harpoon head, long considered a diagnostic type of Early Dorset, is now known to have been produced well into the Middle Dorset period (Table 2.1). This necessitates a re-evaluation of ephemeral sites throughout the Eastern Arctic that were interpreted based on the presence of the Tyara sliced type (Desrosiers and Sørensen 2012). Likewise, the new radiocarbon sequence from Alarniq (Howse et al. 2019) has established several dates for features ranging between 14.5 and 21.5 MASL that are all generally the same age (i.e., 1800-1600 BP). This calls Meldgaard's Dorset sequence into question and has unknown interpretive consequences for several other sites that were classified through this typology (Maxwell 1985; Savelle and Dyke 2014; Houmard 2018; Ryan 2016).

Elevation differences present another caveat for the reliability of beach ridge

chronologies. Meldgaard and Taylor assumed that isostatic uplift rates throughout Foxe Basin were isochronic and isomorphic: that is, they were consistent over time and between locales. However, uplift energy has decreased exponentially since land around Foxe Basin first surfaced c. 6000 BP (Savelle and Dyke 2014). Rates also differ geographically based on directional variables such as glacial retreat, ice load, and permafrost thickness (Dyke and Peltier 2000). Due to anisomorphism, even sites in proximity to one another such as Qalirusiq, Kapuivik, and Alarniq have slightly different rebound rates, so that the geological age of elevated terraces at one site do not necessarily correspond to the others ((Savelle and Dyke 2014:253, see Figure 2.7). These elevation differences further compromise Meldgaard’s regional typological system, especially in the context of using his beach ridge chronology to establish the cultural affiliations of coastal sites in nearby regions (e.g., Taylor 1968).

Table 2.2 Summary of relic shoreline elevations (MASL) in the Amittuq region. J M (Jens Munk) Island refers to Kapuivitt. *Reproduced from Savelle and Dyke (2014:455)*

Age	Igloolik	J M Island	C Thalbitzer-Koch Island	Rowley Island.	Rowley River
1 ka	5–8	7	7	6–8	6
1.5 ka	10	10	10	10–15	9
2 ka	15	15	13	10–18	12
2.5 ka	19	22	18	10–25	16
3 ka	30	30	25	17–30	21
3.5 ka	40	43	34	35	27
4 ka	50–60	58	45	45–50	34
4.5 ka	68		57		48
5 ka	81		72		71

2.2.6.2 Economic Rationalist Assumptions. In addition to the problems associated with chronology-building, the temporal conflation of beach ridges and coastal type-sites is problematic because it is premised on untested expectations about Tuniit settlement behaviour.

People from the Qikiqtaaluk region had long been inferred as coast-adapted societies (see Section 1.2). Based on their expectations of how coastal cultural evolution took place, Meldgaard and Taylor both assumed that Pre-Dorset and Dorset groups in Foxe Basin maintained their proximity to marine resources by continuously occupying the active shoreline (Meldgaard 1962; Steensby 1916; Taylor 1968). However, this perspective ignored the dynamics of human social life and the reciprocal and largely unpredictable sociohistorical relationships that place-community encounters often facilitate, such as those known to have connected ancestral Inuit with places like Kapuivik and Alarniq (IE010; IE246, see Akiwenzie-Damm et al. 2019; Cipolla et al 2021; Deloria 1992, 2001b; Price 2008; TallBear 2015; Watts 2013).

As the presupposition of a shoreward-shifting settlement pattern was so well accepted (e.g., Mathiassen 1925), Meldgaard, Taylor, and others working in and around Amittuq (e.g., Collins 1950; Mary-Rousselière 1979) did not survey above “Pre-Dorset” terraces or in non-coastal parts of the region (cf. Bielawski 1988). This has resulted in significant biases for the kinds of archaeological data collected in maritime regions, as archaeological investigations have continued to focus on coastal terraces that formed during the Tuniiit Period (c. 3700-1000 BP), namely those now located between 8-52 MASL (Savelle and Dyke 2014). It remains unknown if coastal type-sites represent only a portion of Tuniiit occupational activities and therefore if typologies developed from these sites are representative of broader regional archaeological landscapes.

The projection of local data from coastal type-sites onto regional and inter-regional scales has remained a normative practice in eastern Canadian Arctic archaeology. Many see the regional typological systems that developed from these contexts as being salvageable through the

reinvestigation of type-sites to clarify the cultural associations of artifact types and to refine their chronological sequences with absolute dating (Desrosiers et al. 2008; Howse et al. 2019; Ryan 2016; Savelle and Dyke 2014). Such reinvestigations will surely inform a clearer understanding of the utility and limitations of dominant typologies. However, the prevalence of the type-site concept remains problematic. It perpetuates the notion that Arctic archaeological cultures are viable categories that represent homogenous and predictable groups of people, and the implicit assumptions underlying these classifications in which culture is presented as an entity shaped by external forces, and that can be adequately defined by presumed regional and chronological differences in artifact assemblages and architecture. This diminishes the agency of people and overlooks diversity in material culture through which traces of complex and emergent social relations may otherwise be inferred. Additionally, it fails to account for the dynamic and overlapping temporalities of site use and spatial practice that contributed to how past communities were historically articulated. As discussed in the chapter introduction, reimagining coastal type-sites as performative and historically persistent places provides an avenue in my research to break away from this linear frame of cultural development, as well as the homogenizing spatial frames of migration and trait diffusion that remained tied to type-sites. Understanding coastal places as elements of emergent, relational landscapes also facilitates explorations of different site types and organizational structures during the Tuniiit Period.

2.3 Cultural Ecology and the Core-Periphery Framework

Although refining culture history remained a primary objective of Arctic archaeology (Odess 2002:16), the 1970s brought a new focus to ecological relationships and processes as

explanations for cultural change (Bielawki 1982; 1988; Helmer 1981; Maxwell 1985; Odess 1998). This focus presented culture as an adaptive mechanism that allowed past people to maintain an ecological balance with extreme, fluctuating polar environments (Maxwell 1985:3, Trigger 2006:314). Archaeologists sought to understand the adaptative mechanisms of culture by reconstructing the technologies and economic structures used to acquire subsistence resources within their narrow empirical understandings of archaeological cultures (Fitzhugh 1972:167; Maxwell 1976; McGhee 1972; Fitzhugh 1974; Trigger 2006:279). These initiatives continued to stretch local site data onto large geographic regions and presented the Pre-Dorset and Dorset as bounded cultural systems structured by uniform environments. As a result, applications of cultural ecology to Tuniit contexts tend to produce big picture models in which cultural change is explained through large-scale biophysical processes (Bhiry et al. 2021; Savelle and Dyke 2014).

This section traces the development of the most influential framework for reconstructing Tuniit cultural systems in the eastern Canadian Arctic: the core-periphery framework. I outline how the reinterpretation of coastal type-sites through cultural ecological principles led to conceptions of Foxe Basin as a “core area” of cultural adaptation, and how comparisons between this core area and neighbouring regions led to understandings of “core” and “peripheral” variants of archaeological cultures. I outline the interpretive problems this framework presents for understanding Tuniit peoples, many of which are derived of earlier classificatory schemes (e.g., archaeological cultures, type-sites), and present an alternative understanding of human-environment interactions employed in my research.

To overcome the environmental determinism underlying this analytical scheme, I turn to theorizations of Place that account for the fluid, emergent, and historically contingent nature of

place-community relationships (Basso 1996; Casey 2016; Deloria 2001, 2003; Deleuze 1992; Foucault 1980; Harris 2014; TallBear 2015; Watts 2016; Whitridge 2004; Wildcat 2001). This allows me to document and analyze Tuniit social relations outside of the spatial parameters of coastal type-sites, including low density/non-residential occupational activities and residential practices at the scales of the household and the camp. I challenge the notion that Amittuq's occupational past was structured by a uniform regional environment by modelling dynamic and variable landscape elements during the Tuniit Period (see Conolly 2020; Cipolla 2019, 2018; Larmon 2019; Supernant 2017) and by evaluating material patterns of difference that emerge between these elements and archaeological evidence. By reframing culture and environment as entangled historical processes, my research challenges the normative systematics of cultural ecological frameworks and attends to the production of sociomaterial differences at multiple social and spatial scales in the landscape.

2.3.1 The "Core Area" as a Structuring Force of Arctic Culture History

2.3.1.1 Culture Circles and Cultural Cores. Cultural ecological frameworks facilitated a multilinear evolutionary narrative that attended to cultural differences between environmentally variable Arctic regions (Hood 1998:20; Steward 1955:18). However, the remote nature of fieldwork meant that regional variants of archaeological cultures were still largely inferred from a small number of type-sites (McGhee 1982:68). Many archaeologists predicted Tuniit settlement and subsistence practices through ethnographic analogies and the functional analysis of artifacts (Hood 1998:28; Schwarz 1990:46, see Clarke 1978; Binford 1980, Willey 1953; Trigger 1998:12). Technological similarities between artifact assemblages in different locations

and time periods were explained as adaptations to shared environmental conditions, while major disparities were attributed to climatic differences (Fitzhugh 1972; Maxwell 1985).

This inferential procedure developed through continued research engagement with Arctic culture circles¹⁹ as well as Steward's (1955:37) reworking of the concept through his proposition of the "cultural core" (Steward 1955:37, 84). In the 1980s, increasing recognition of stylistic variability across sites in the eastern Canadian Arctic presented new challenges for the application of legacy typologies such as Meldgaard's to Tuniit contexts (Bielawski 1988:54). Steward's (1955:84) model explained how these sorts of typological problems arose from drawing cultural boundaries from a small number of stylistic regularities, such as those originally used to define the Pre-Dorset and Dorset archaeological cultures (see Section 1.3, this chapter). By identifying the "primary" economic traits through which cultures evolved, typological irregularities between neighbouring regions could be more appropriately classified as "secondary" stylistic traits – as nonadaptive social, political, and religious differences that were less fundamental to a culture's systematic structure, at least in the context of small-scale subsistence societies (Steward 1955:87, see Trigger 2006: 396).

Steward's "cultural core" was intended to serve as a heuristic device rather than a universal model of culture (Steward 1955:89). However, in the context of the eastern Canadian Arctic, historized understandings of coastal evolution led to the projection of previous cultural-historical frameworks onto a discourse of eco-functionalism (Hood 1998:20). This discourse presented culture as an adaptation that functioned to keep humans and their environments in a sustainable balance. From this line of thinking, broadly defined tool types — the most prevalent

¹⁹ Which Steward refers to as "culture areas" in his seminal work *Theory of culture change: The methodology of multilineal evolution* (Steward 1955).

of which were harpoon heads — were viewed as the primary traits of the Pre-Dorset and Dorset cultures because of their economic associations (Maxwell 1985:198; Odess 2002:119).

Alternatively, nuanced differences in these types and more idiosyncratic items such as ivory art were treated as “stylistic” variants because of their connection with “secondary” social practices, and continued to be explained primarily through processes of diffusion (Bielawski 1988:57; Tacon 1983; Thomson 1982; Friesen 2016:675). This approach restricted the interpretive significance of small-scale material differences and downplayed the importance of social, political, and religious aspects of Tuniit life (Harp 1976:119; Lemoine 2003).

2.3.1.2 Legacy Typologies and the Core Area Concept. Meldgaard’s (1962) and Taylor’s (1968) typological systems contained most of the primary artifact types recognized throughout the eastern Canadian Arctic (Odess 2005:89). In contrast, many of the arctic and subarctic regions surrounding Foxe Basin, including the Arctic Archipelago, Nunavik, the Barren Grounds, Labrador, and Newfoundland (Figure 2.1), were characterized by sparse archaeological assemblages that contained significant stylistic variation in – or a total absence of – functional archaeological types such as notched points and dwelling midpassages (Cox 1978:427; Maxwell 1985:82; McGhee 1982:68; Odess 2002). The perceived homogeneity of Tuniit technologies within Foxe Basin led to its (re)interpretation as the “cultural core” for Pre-Dorset and Dorset peoples (McGhee 1982:69). This was positioned against the “peripheral” variants of archaeological cultures observed in surrounding regions (Maxwell 1985: 82,102; Steward 1955:82). The identification of a cultural core served to reconcile typological irregularities throughout the eastern Canadian Arctic while preserving extant narratives of Arctic culture history (Harp 1976:119, Plummet 1985).

Aside from the interpretive issues associated with the Foxe Basin type-sites, eco-

functionalist comparisons of material culture patterning were problematic because they did not account for sampling differences and worked from universalizing ideas about cultural change (Taylor 1968:88; Todisco and Monchot 2008). Archaeologists compared small datasets from sparsely investigated regions with much larger datasets supplied by type-sites with long histories of archaeological and ethnographic research in Foxe Basin (Birket-Smith 1929; Boas 1888; Mathiassen 1930; Rowley 1940; Meldgaard 1962; Taylor 1968). These were not equivalent comparisons: “peripheral” sites were smaller, their absolute chronologies less clear, and their ecological settings many and varied. As such, they were bound to contain artifact assemblages that differed from the Foxe Basin type-sites (cf. Bielawski 1988, McCartney and Helmer 1989). As the documentation of archaeological assemblages have grown in peripheral regions, many have questioned these early interpretations (Fitzhugh 1997; Helmer 1991; Schledernann 1990). Tuck’s (1976) work, for example, demonstrated gradual development in Pre-Dorset and Dorset endblade technologies along the coasts of Northern Labrador, findings that are supported by more recent research in Labrador and Newfoundland (Cox 1978; Fitzhugh 1980; Maxwell 50-51; Renouf 2011). This research suggested historical cultural development on a similar scale to the “core area”. However, Meldgaard and Taylor’s legacy typologies have continued to play a key role in defining the geographical and temporal boundaries of archaeological cultures, perpetuating reductive conceptions of cultural identity and change during the Tuniit Period (Milne and Park 2016:699, 707; Odess 2005:81-82; Ryan 2016:774-775, Stenton et al. 2000).

2.3.2 Settlement in the Core-Periphery Framework

Researchers in the 1970s and 1980s became increasingly interested with identifying the ecological factors unique to Foxe Basin that could explain the size and density of archaeological sites in the region (Fitzhugh 1974; McGhee 1972; Maxwell 1985). Archaeologists borrowed from ecological studies that described how katabatic winds and ocean currents maintained recurring polynyas where seals and walrus could bask and breed and promoted the phytoplankton that maintained their food sources (Bursa 1961; Grainger 1962; Jeffray 1969; Stirling 1980). Contemporary Inuit ethnographies contextualized how these coastal conditions supported a stable year-round sea mammal hunting economy on which Amitturmiut Inuit had continued to thrive (Beaubier 1971; Crowe 1969; Damas 1963; 1969). Based on the presupposition that Tuniit in Foxe Basin, at least during the Dorset period (cf. Maxwell 1976a), would have had access to similar subsistence resources, Amittuq's type-sites were now understood as products of continuous human populations that were maintained by a stable marine ecosystem (Maxwell 1985:51, 183). In contrast, "peripheral" sites were interpreted as the product of unstable occupational episodes shaped by the scarcity and/or unpredictability of subsistence resources (Collins 1950; Harp 1960; Knuth 1965; Maxwell 1973b; McGhee 1970, 1976, 1977, 1979; Taylor 1975).

This model had three important interpretive consequences for Tuniit occupational history. First, it reimagined Foxe Basin as an increasingly uniform socioeconomic system that became fully realized during the Dorset period (see McGhee 1972; Maxwell 1976b:5, 1985:183). This overlooked local variability in Tuniit occupational practices and impeded the recognition of multiscale social relationships that individuals, households, and camps shared with and through

their landscape (Johansen 2010:438, see also Ahenakew 2017:81; Deloria 2003:151; Whatmore 2006:602-604c; Watts 2016:3). Second, an intensive research focus on Dorset settlement and subsistence strategies left those of Pre-Dorset to be inferred retroactively based on the absence of distinctive Dorset elements, such as storage features, sod houses, and closed-socket harpoon heads (Bielawski 1988:54). This reduced Pre-Dorset peoples to a less economically specialized precursor to Dorset, and as a corollary, a homogenous, simple cultural system (Milne and Park 2016:707, Steward 1955). Third, the core-periphery framework facilitated research engagement with ecologically focused Inuit ethnographies, but largely ignored ethnographic works that attended to the role of social, political, and religious structures in shaping Inuit culture (Balicki 1989:105, see Binford 1978). The ethnographic analogies drawn from these studies largely produced environmentally deterministic interpretations and overlooked archaeological evidence for social relations that less-directly connected to economic needs and risk-reducing behaviour (Friesen 2000:209; Whitridge 2012:46).

2.3.2.1 Models of Stasis and Change. Explanations for how archaeological cultures in the core area functioned as adaptative systems can be simplified into one of two camps: the “Maxwell hypothesis” and the “Meldgaard hypothesis” (sensu McGhee 1982: 69). Proponents of the Maxwell hypothesis borrowed from the Binfords’ (1968) systems theory approach and interpreted the Dorset culture as having developed within a closed natural system in which little cumulative change in artifact technologies or socioeconomic structures took place (Maxwell 1976:69; Nash 1976:150). Alternatively, the more commonly accepted Meldgaard hypothesis built on the *in situ* premise proposed by Taylor (1968). These proponents saw Dorset as adapting to Amittuq’s environment gradually, with increasing sedentism, food surpluses, and higher populations resulting in cumulative stylistic and techno-economic change within the region

(Friesen 2007; Houmard 2018; McGhee 1982; Ryan 2016). In other words, environmental stability provided the necessary conditions for the Dorset culture to progress along its expected trajectory, while environmental instability outside of Foxe Basin altered that trajectory (Steensby 1916; Mathiassen 1925; Meldgaard 1962).

Cultural variation observed beyond Foxe Basin is also explained primarily through the external forces of diffusion and environmental adaptation remaining paramount. Many see Tuniit technologies as having spread through brief, irregular episodes of migration from Foxe Basin during times of resource affluence, and to Foxe Basin during periods of resource stress (Cox 1978; Mary-Rousselière 1976:56; Maxwell 1985:50; McGhee 1976:39, McGhee and Tuck 1976; Fitzhugh 1976:145-147). Regionalism is also discussed, with mosaics of small regional populations resulting in the irregular diffusion of material technologies (Sutherland 1996). Others have suggested that subsequent historic development of Tuniit groups in coastal parts of the periphery resulted in “sub-core” cultural systems similar to Foxe Basin, explaining the observed continuity in Dorset material culture along the coasts of Labrador and Newfoundland (Fitzhugh 1997; Helmer 1991; Schledermann 1990:322-323) and around the Pikiyasorsuaq polynya at the Northern Qikiqtaaluk/Greenlandic border (Jeppesen et al. 2018; Ribeiro et al. 2021).

Common to these hypotheses is their portrayal of past peoples as responding to uniform regional environments in predictable, rationalist fashion. This is problematic, in part, because the Canadian Arctic makes up some of the most heterogenous and dynamic environments in the world, and ethnographic and oral historical data highlight how people in earlier periods engaged with these environments in diverse and historically contingent ways (Bennett and Rowley 2004;

Nuttal 1992; Qitsualik 2013). For example, the distribution of animals, ice bridges, land routes, and fresh water sources in Amittuq change drastically between seasons, years, and localities, requiring in-depth knowledge of sea ice and alternate travel routes (IE40; IE101). New research has begun to demonstrate how settlement analyses can facilitate new interpretations of Tuniit occupational history that attend to local environmental variability. Surveys conducted through the Foxe Basin Archaeology (FBA) Project by James Savelle and Arthur Dyke (Savelle et al. 2009; Savelle and Dyke 2014:258) have identified a considerable number of new Tuniit sites in Amittuq, including several outside of the expected 50-8 MASL coastal range – such as the six sites at 95-60 MASL located on Kapuiviit Island²⁰. The authors' evaluations of site size and frequency within local beach ridge sequences questions the basic premise of the core area model by demonstrating that human populations likely fluctuated considerably in Amittuq during the Tuniit Period (Savelle at Dyke 2009:249). However, unlike demographic trends identified in other regions (Dyke et al. 2011; Savelle and Dyke 2002; Savelle et al. 2012) evidence for these population fluctuations does not adhere to a recognizable chronological pattern; that is, population peaks and crashes occurred at different times in various parts of the region (Savelle and Dyke 2014: 264-265). This suggests that region-wide climatic changes were not the primary force behind shifts in Tuniit occupational practices.

While Savelle and Dyke's (2014) inferences may be complicated by the analytical issues associated with beach ridge chronology (see Section 1.5, this chapter), their findings are significant for challenging narratives of continuity and homogeneity in Amittuq. Their conclusions are supported by recent research, such as zooarchaeological and isotopic studies that

²⁰ These sites were not radiocarbon dated due to the absence of organic surface finds, but were inferred as likely representing sporadic early Pre-Dorset occupations unrelated to the continuous occupational patterning present 10km to the south at the Kapuivik site (Savelle and Dyke 2014: 259).

indicate substantial variability in ancient sea mammal populations in Foxe Basin, opposing the presumed ecological stability on which the Maxwell and Meldgaard hypotheses were founded (Desjardin 2017; Szpak 2017; Szpak et al. 2019). This is corroborated by zooarchaeological studies that suggest how Dorset hunting economies changed seasonally and generationally (Kotar 2022; Howse 2017).

These recent studies are valuable because they question the viability of core-periphery frameworks for describing and explaining Tuniit occupational histories, and offer more detailed understandings of human-environment interactions. What is needed now is for archaeologists to undertake finer-grained analyses of Tuniit occupational practices by expanding site investigations beyond outer seacoasts, and by considering the impacts that placemaking practice in different material settings may have had on community practices and relations. This is something that the core area model is ill-equipped to navigate but that a place-oriented framework necessitates (see Chapter One, Section 1.2.1). In my study, I interrogate the shifting relationships between Amittuq's biophysical environment and Tuniit people on more local scales through the careful analysis of local palaeogeographical data (e.g., geological records, zooarchaeological assemblages) as well as the high resolution documentation and comparative analysis of settlement sites (Binford 1982; Deleuze and Guattari 2004; Gero 2015; Johansen 2018; Lightfoot 1993; Pauketat 2013, *for relevant studies around Qikiqtaaluk see Adams and Finklestein 2010; Coltrain et al. 2004; Desjardins et al. 2020; Szpak et al. 2019*). This permits a richer understanding of the specific material affordances of persistent places at different points in time, helping to contextualize the various ways local groups managed their connections with places and other people in the landscape.

2.3.2.2 *Interpreting Pre-Dorset and Dorset Spatial Structures in Amittuq.* Until recently, Pre-Dorset studies have been largely focused on the earliest and latest occupational episodes, the former to understand initial migrations to the eastern Canadian Arctic and the latter to contextualize the Pre-Dorset to Dorset cultural transition, with little work attending to continuity and change in social structures and practices over the *longue durée* (Anderson and Hodgetts 2007; Milne 2003, Milne et al. 2016:699, Milne and Park 2016 Savelle et al. 2012; see also Mary-Rousseliere 1976, Houmard 2018; Ryan 2011). This pattern is evident in research pertaining to Amittuq, where an extensive focus on Dorset technologies and socioeconomic structures has led Pre-Dorset practices to be understood comparatively as a less developed culture (Bielawski 1988:70; Friesen 2000; McCartney and Helmer 1989; Murray 1996). These comparisons are problematic in part because Pre-Dorset assemblages have been primarily approached through stochastic typologies in which some diagnostic attributes are deemed functional and others stylistic (Steward 1955:89), often without researchers explaining how function and style relate to material variability recognized at different scales of analyses (Bielawski 1988:57). Pre-Dorset attributes are difficult to compare with Dorset ones, as the latter have been rigorously reorganized through eco-functionalist models. Additionally, comparisons between Pre-Dorset and Dorset are constrained by the poor preservation of Pre-Dorset organic remains (Milne and Park 2016:705).

Explanations for inferred differences between Pre-Dorset and Dorset socioeconomic organization have centered on adaptations to distinct regional environments (Maxwell 1985:107; Murray 1999:468). Warmer weather during the Pre-Dorset period is presumed to have resulted in broad-spectrum hunting strategies that involved coastal hunting in the winter and the inland exploitation of terrestrial game in the summer (Milne and Park 2016:694; Nagy 1994 cf.

Meldgaard 1960b:66; 1965:5, Boas 1888 461- 462). This model is supported by the inferred frequency of “ephemeral” single-family dwellings (three to six people) and small transient camps (one to five families) (Ryan 2003; Ryan 2010), as well as ovate endblades (Meldgaard 1960b:75,1965:5) and open socket harpoon heads (Houmard 2018:26-27, cf. McCartney and Helmer 1989). However, the ephemerality associated with Pre-Dorset dwellings may be a product of taphonomic differences between earlier and later occupations, and requires more extensive radiocarbon dating in local contexts to verify (Bielawski 1988:57;). Failure to consider post-abandonment processes, such as the appropriation of structural materials by later groups, is another unexplored problem that might affect the interpretation of Pre-Dorset sites when compared with Dorset sites (Binford 1989; Bielawski 1988:57; Milne and Park 2016:705). This is especially an issue in Amittuq where a focus on occupations along coastal terraces may hinder the identification of maintenance and differential reuse practices (see Morrison 2016).

Alternatively, the onset of colder weather during the Dorset period is thought to have initiated a year-round coastal hunting economy centered on both seal and walrus (Maxwell 1985; Friesen 2007). This change is thought to have freed up time and energy for Dorset peoples that enabled the development of a more “complex” social system, as evidenced by multi-family households (ten or more people), new technologies (e.g., closed socket harpoons), and the growing frequency and elaboration of ivory art (Maxwell 1985:154; McGhee 1996:131, Murray 1999:468, cf. Binford 1980). However, it is important to note that small, single-family dwellings during Dorset are in fact quite common in Foxe Basin (Savelle et al. 2009:226), and that multi-family dwellings, as well as large camps with over 30 individuals, have been inferred in some Pre-Dorset contexts in Qikiqtaaluk (Maxwell 1985:98; Savelle et al. 2009:228; Schledermann 1980:298; Walker 2020b). The dualism of Pre-Dorset and Dorset is therefore not supported by

available settlement data.

Interpretations of Pre-Dorset demography and settlement in Amittuq are also restricted by the continued focus on outer seacoasts (Howse et al. 2019; Murray 1996; Savelle et al 2009; Savelle and Dyke 2014). Consequently, the hypothesis that Pre-Dorset groups in the "core area" regularly traveled inland has not been thoroughly investigated, despite some exceptions noted in the southern Qikiqtaaluk region (MacAvoy 2014; Milne 2003; Milne and Donnelly). Additionally, zooarchaeological studies of Pre-Dorset sites in the eastern Canadian Arctic have been relatively rare, with most focusing on Late Pre-Dorset contexts, limiting available evidence for the seasonal diversification of Pre-Dorset subsistence practices (Kotar 2022; Maxwell 1985:95; Milne and Park 2016; Murray 1999, see Table 2.1). As Bielawski (1981; 1982;1984;1988) has long argued, the lack of appropriate data for understanding seasonality, mobility, and social organization during the Pre-Dorset period has significantly restricted interpretations of who these peoples were: their community relationships and identities, their seasonal practices and movements, and their affiliations with communities from other times and places (Basso 1996; Harris 2014; Morrison 2016; Watts 2016). Expanding survey locations and investigating small-scale temporal changes in settlement practices will contribute to a greater understanding of Early Tuniit (Pre-Dorset) community structures, mobility, and social continuity within the region, and are a priority of the current project.

2.3.2.3 Ethnography and Social Archaeology. Arctic studies inspired by cultural ecology have relied on both classic Inuit ethnographies (e.g., Boas 1888) and more recent eco-functional ethnographies that focus on how Inuit group formation and social structures are shaped by environmental variables (Hood 1998:26, McGhee 1976:36, see Balikci 1964, Binford

1978, Damas 1969). These uses of ethnography draw on subject-side analogies, in which Tuniit and Inuit are believed to have faced some universally applicable constraints on their behaviour due to the similar environments they shared (Maxwell 1985:51, cf. McGhee 1996). This has led to a restricted analytical frame in which classic ethnographies set expectations for archaeologists, such as how material traits should be organized and what they may reflect about ethnicity, while eco-functionalist ethnographies serve as a means to test or verify cultural ecological interpretations of material culture change (Balikci 1998:107-108; Hood 1998:26, Schlinder 1985:481, cf. Wobst 1978:303). This procedure runs the risk of reproducing socio-evolutionary ideas from earlier archaeological studies by overlooking the social agency of past people and historic examples for sociopolitical practices in Inuit contexts (Damas 1998:171, Fitzhugh and Loring 2002:4, see also Steensby 1916; Maxwell 1985; McGhee 1972; Meldgaard 1962).

While Inuit ethnographies informed by cultural ecology have remained a popular source of analogy (Anderson et al.2019; Holly et al. 2018; Murray 1996), lesser referenced are structuralist ethnographies from the 1980s and 1990s that explore Inuit social relationships, language, symbolism, and beliefs (Bielawski 1995; d'Anglure 1986; Guemple 1979; Maxwell 1986; Trott 1982; Hood 1998:25). This has been influenced by two factors. First, the techno-environmental determinism of the core area-periphery framework leaves little room to conceive of Tuniit cultural processes outside of their conditioning by external forces (Hood 2002:244; Odess 2002:117, Meldgaard and Gulløv 2002:92; Ryan 2016:766; Stahl 1993). Second, the positioning of Tuniit archaeological cultures in opposition to ancestral Inuit (Thule) has left a general impression among many that, outside of certain technological similarities and economic strategies (e.g., floe-edge hunting, harpoon heads, the use of qulliqs), Inuit societies are far too different to provide an adequate reference model for Tuniit social life (Friesen 2000:209; Hood

1998:27; McGhee 1996:54; Stahl 1993:237). This idea has been enforced through a reliance on the direct historical approach (Steward 1942) in Inuit archaeology, which was popularized in the 1960s and 1970s along with Julian Steward's other work (Hood 1998:25). In the instances where structuralist ethnographies are employed in Tuniit archaeology, they are usually limited to Late Dorset contexts, perhaps due to perceived cultural similarities explained through models of interactions and acculturation (see Section 1.4.1). This positions Inuit societies as a null hypothesis from which to measure and compare cultural differences, rather than considering what the fluid and flexible character of Inuit communities may suggest about human-environment conditions in Arctic contexts (d'Anglure 1988; Hood 1998:26; McGhee 1996; Searles 2008; Stern and Stevenson 2006; Whitridge 1999).

By framing difference as an affirmative process (Barad 2007; Haraway 1997), I approach ethnography as an opportunity to consider human and nonhuman agency in historically contingent ways and develop archaeological expectations for Tuniit social practices. For example, Historic Inuit groups are known to have undertaken long-distance movements motivated by social connections such as desire to die in one's birthplace and inter-family feuds (Rowley 1985). Rather than approaching Tuniit groups through cultural ecological models that presume short migrations motivated primarily by climatic fluctuation and resource stress (Fitzhugh 1974; Maxwell 1985:101), I consider possibilities for broader social connections in the landscape and explore evidence for accessibility and connectivity between settlements and residential mobility on both local and regional scales. I take the position that whether or not Tuniit and Inuit groups shared similar social structures, it is important to open up archaeological expectations to a wider range of possibilities for how Tuniit communities might have emerged and changed throughout engagements *in place* (TallBear 2015:186). This is something that

consulting oral history and local community knowledge can help facilitate (Ahenakew 2017:88; Cipolla 2021a; Howey 2020; Irniq 2008; Price 2008; Thomas 2003). In Amittuq, local oral history offers a unique lens into these possibilities by detailing how historic and contemporary Amitturmiut Inuit have engaged with the same places Tuniit occupied, as well as how community identities and practices have been regularly influenced by the inherited stories, memories, and emotion that these places hold (see Watts 2016).

2.4 Re-Thinking the Core Area: Structuralism and Relational Frameworks

Since the early 2000s, Arctic archaeologists have begun to ask new questions concerning Tuniit social, political, and spiritual life by engaging with structuralist interpretive frameworks. These studies reimagine Tuniit material culture as symbolic codes that represent learned sets of ideas and norms that are only intelligible in relation to the wider cultural systems that structured them (Assiter 1984; Descola 2013; Geertz 1973; Levi-Strauss 1973; Leroi-Gourhan 1988). Given this emphasis on symbolism, many applications of structuralism have focused on Late Tuniit (Dorset) art. This has involved the identification of broadly utilized motifs that are interpreted as evidence for widespread artistic traditions that reflect a shared cosmology or cultural identity (Carpenter 2002:76; Gulløv and Appelt 2001; Hardenberg 2013; Lyons 1982; Macrae 2013; McGhee 1984:3; Odgaard 2011; Sutherland 2001; Tacon 1983; Taylor and Swinton 1967; Thomson 1982, Zságer 2010). However, some studies have also examined more quotidian aspects of Tuniit social life, such as domestic organization and hunting practices, which are of interest for reconstructing Tuniit occupational histories (Betts et al. 2015; Friesen 2007; Le Moine 2003; Hardenberg 2013; Hood 2002; Macrae 2013; Rast and Wolff 2016; Røe 2021:34;

Ryan 2010).

Structuralist studies of Tuniit social life are important because they attend to the social identities of Tuniit peoples and demonstrate how cultural change is not reliant on external environmental forces (Hood 2002). However, they perpetuate some of the issues of scale and representation present in cultural-historical and cultural ecological approaches. This includes a continued reliance on polarizing categories and essentializing classifications (culture/nature, style/function, Pre-Dorset/Dorset), and a tendency to prioritize symmetries and synchronies across large regions and periods of time at the expense of small-scale differences. Alternatively, employing a posthuman feminist framework in which difference is treated a generative process rather than an oppositional force may help to move interpretations of Tuniit social practices and structures beyond binary categories. By employing this framework, my study aims to address material patterning in the archaeological record at the smaller scales of the household and the camp, and opens new avenues for engaging with Inuit knowledge and history beyond comparative differences between the ethnographic and archaeological records (Wylie 1985).

2.4.1 Domestic Organization and Architecture. One of the most influential structuralist studies in Tuniit archaeology is LeMoine's (2003) exploration of the role of women in Late Dorset households. Based on the diffusionist logic that Tuniit and Inuit cultures were structured around a circumpolar shamanic tradition that originated in Siberia, LeMoine (2003:132) draws analogies from Inuit cosmology to infer the underlying norms that structured Late Dorset society. Her work centers around a dichotomy outlined in classic Inuit ethnographies (Boas 1888; Mathiassen 1928) in which men are associated with hunting on the land (i.e., *outside*) while women are associated with domestic labour (i.e., *inside*). This gendered distinction is supported by structuralist ethnographies that describe how the shape of Inuit sod houses served as a

metaphor for a woman's womb (LeMoine 2003:131, see also Oosten 1986; Saladin D'Anglur 1988).

The emphasis on binary oppositions, such as man/woman and inside/outside, is a key element of structuralism. Structuralists explore the "hidden rules" that material elements represent through binary orderings that they believe structure human cognition (Hood 1998:30,39, see also Levi-Strauss 1973:22). Although oppositional pairs may vary between contexts, some, like man/woman, are seen as common among most cultures (Derrida 1993:205). LeMoine uses this binary to contrast the similarities and differences between Early Inuit (Thule) and terminal Late Tuniit (Late Dorset) societies, as reflected through the archaeological remains of vernacular architecture. She argues that, although Dorset and Inuit women shared similar domestic roles, the higher frequency of hearths and axial features in Late Dorset houses suggests that domestic labour was distributed between dual-family rather than single-family households. Inferring these internal structures as symbols of a shared womb, she suggests they served as intentional metaphors that reinforced inter-family social bonds (LeMoine 2003:135).

While LeMoine's study is insightful, there are two caveats regarding her comparisons between Inuit and Late Tuniit worth discussing. First, binary oppositions such as man/woman only *appear* universal because of our repeated material encounters with these categories through our personal experiences and our projection of Western norms onto our research subjects (Barad 2003; Butler 1993; 2004; Minh-Ha 1997). Inuit gender does not adhere to a binary structure, and there are several exceptions to the gendered division of domestic labour described by LeMoine (2003), such as the third gender concept of sipiniq (*the split person*) (Walley 2019). In Amittuq, this is apparent in the tradition of naming a child after a deceased relative, which bestows the namesake with a likeness of the individual that includes a gendered essence (KH04). Binary

oppositions like man/woman exclude these individuals from our expectations about the past, which may deflate the specific historical contexts in which past social identities were articulated (Marshall and Alberti 2014; Meskell 2002; Wylie 2007).

Second, the application of structuralist binaries is complicated by a tendency for these dichotomies to borrow from earlier research (Table 2.3). Legacy models may bring with them the reductive idealist and rationalist logics that underlined the studies they were constructed from (Betts et al. 2015:92). This can be seen in the persistent use of core/periphery and coast/inland distinctions in socially engaged research. In her structuralist study of Late Dorset architecture, Ryan (2009) identifies technological differences in the regional patterning of dwellings as a means to trace the diffusion of Dorset social knowledge. Building on the work of LeMoine (2003) she argues that multi-family Late Dorset dwellings were symbols of social cohesion, adding that they helped to maintain the large-scale cooperation needed for intensive seasonal hunting practices (see also Friesen 2007). She argues that dwelling structures serve as signifiers of regional knowledge systems, and that reading the degree of homogeneity within architectural assemblages can reveal how regional cultural variants responded to stable vs. unstable environments (2009:461). While discussions of norms and traditions in architectural practice contribute to understandings of Tuniit social life, the conceptual ordering of inferences within coastal/inland and stability/instability binaries results in a continued emphasis on large scale environmental factors. This hinders inferences of local community practices and interactions may have contributed to how knowledge of the landscape was cultivated and shared.

Table 2.3 Legacy Binaries Common to Arctic Archaeological Research

Simple	Complex	Rink 1887; Steensby 1916; Mathiassen 1925; Meldgaard 1962
Prehistory	History	Appelt 2003; Boas 1888; Damas 1998; McGhee 1996; Hardenberg 2013
Interior	Coastal	Appelt 2003; Mathiassen 1930; Fitzhugh 1972; McGhee 1977; Steensby 1916
Subarctic	Arctic	Birket-Smith 1930; Rink 1887; Meldgaard 1962
Paleoeskimo	Neoeskimo	Birket-Smith 1930; Cox 1978; Mathiassen 1925; Maxwell 1985; Steensby 1916
Pre-Dorset	Dorset	Collins 1956; Jenness 1940; Maxwell 1985
Diffusion	Migration	Birket-Smith 1925; Rowley 1940; Meldgaard and Larsen 1961; Giddings 1951; Nielson 2001
Function	Style	Bielawski 1988; Colins 1954; Helmer 1980; Nagy 1994; Odess 1998; Park 2000; Ryan 2003
Discontinuity	Continuity	Birket-Smith 1930; Taylor 1968
↔		
Mobile	Sedentary	Maxwell 1976; Meldgaard 1962; Murray 1996; Nagy 2000
Tent	House	Fitzhugh 1976; Gronnow 2003; Meldgaard 1960a; 190b; 1962; Ryan 2003
Breadth	Specialization	Bielawski 1982; Friesen 2000; McCartney and Helmer 1989 ; Nagy 1994
Homogeneity	Heterogeneity	Giddings 1951; Fitzhugh 1976; McGhee 1972; Maxwell 1976; Prentiss and Lenert 2009
Dearth	Prosperity	Fitzhugh 1976; 1997; Maxwell 1985
Highly Mobile	Semi-Sedentary	Nagy 1996; 2000; Murray and Ramsden 1997; Friesn 2007
Fission	Fusion	Balikci 1989; Boas 1888; Maus 1906; Maxwell 1958; Nagy 1996
Core	Periphery	Fitzhugh 1974; Friesen 2007; McGhee 1972; Maxwell 1976; Savelle and Dyke 2014

2.4.2 *Dorset Traditions and Relational Practices*. In their investigation of Dorset bear effigy carvings, Betts et al. (2015:92) move beyond binary pairs like human/nonhuman and instead take a relational approach inspired by the neostructuralism of Descola (2013a, 2013b) to explore the representational ecologies embodied by this artifact type. Descola (2013a) argues that each society drafts its own cosmology, which may or may not adhere to the binaries of Euro-American thinking. While acknowledging the historic specificity of social structures, Descola (2013a:123-129) proposes a limited typological schema to organize societies into four

anthropological dispositions – animism, naturalism, totemism, and analogism – a system that he ultimately concedes is still rooted in Western thought (2013a:303).

Betts et al. (2015:92) classify most circumpolar Indigenous peoples under animism and argue that the worldview of Dorset peoples was ultimately dictated by biology, behaviour, and habitat, so that their ontological connections with polar bears were the result of human-animal encounters within coastal environments of the Eastern Arctic (see also Betts et al. 2012:625). They argue that Dorset people and polar bears were united by the practice of floe-edge seal hunting, an inference they support through a comparative analysis of zooarchaeological legacy data, functional interpretations of Dorset harpoon technologies (cf. Maxwell 1976), and ecologically focused Inuit ethnographies (Betts et al. 2015:95, cf. Balicki 1970; Nelson 1969). They conclude that Dorset bear effigies embodied a broad worldview wherein seal hunters maintained a shared cultural identity through an affinity to polar bears. From this foundation, the authors argue that the increasing frequency of polar bear effigies in the Late Dorset period likely represents a collective effort to assert a cultural identity as floe-edge hunters at a time when the ice was melting due to a warmer climate (Betts et al. 2015:109).

This study is insightful and rich with interpretive potential, especially in its approach to human-environment relations, and offers new perspectives on Dorset social identity. However, there are two caveats worth discussing. First, Betts et al.'s (2015) study comprises 141 effigy artifacts collected from 42 sites, all of which are coastal (*see* Betts et al. 2015: supplementary data). While the relations between bear effigies and floe-edge hunters are significant, it remains unknown how this connection relates to wider sets of sociomaterial practices, especially at a time when Dorset peoples are presumed to have been more reliant on terrestrial subsistence resources.

Tuniit occupational activities included practices such as fishing and bird hunting at inland lakes, caribou hunting at lake crossings and mossy lowlands, and tool stone procurement along glacial tills and outcrops – activities which, according to Amitturmiut Knowledge Holders, were common in coastal regions like Amittuq (IE001; IE010, see Friesen 2022). Archaeologists have inferred many such activities in Dorset contexts elsewhere in the Qikiqtaaluk region, including the identification of fish bones and barbed fishing points in lacustrine and riparian settings (Collins 1950; Friesen 2022; Maxwell 1976; 1985; Mary- Rousselière 1976; Peregrine 2001), interior tool stone quarries (Milne et al. 2011; Milne et al 2012), and caribou hunting implements and structural aids at lake and river crossings (Hilts 2021; McGhee 1996; Milne 2007). Further research on local variation in people-place relations within and outside of coastal contexts is important to better understand how the production and use of bear effigies relates to the cultivation of community identities at multiple scales and in different material and historical contexts.

Second, while polar bear carvings are divided into several distinct variants (e.g., swimming, sitting), the application of Descola’s (2013a) framework leans more towards the interpretation of a shared cultural identity across large regions, which in this case is a diverse geographic range of over 25 million km². This may inadvertently perpetuate an understanding of social identity and practice as something relatively inert rather than plural and cultivated through everyday relations (Marshall and Alberti 2014:32; see Barad 2003; 2007). Considering locally situated differences in Tuniit economic practices, community structures, and material surroundings may help in further understanding how broader traditions like the production of bear effigies contributed to identity and membership at multiple social and spatial scales (see Kotar 2022).

Building on Bett's productive study, it is important for future relational approaches to consider Tuniit identity beyond the terminal Late Tuniit (Late Dorset) period. Late Dorset people have often been approached as an exception to generalized interpretations of Tuniit "culture", based on their presumed social complexity and likeness to Inuit (LeMoine 2003:122; Meldgaard 1960a:594, see also Friesen 2002:340-342). It may be argued that underlying a history of Late Dorset exceptionalism in Arctic archaeology are earlier understandings of acculturation in which "complex" incoming groups have a unidirectional influence on "less complex" groups — in this case, ancestral Inuit influencing Late Tuniit peoples, resulting in rapid and widespread changes in material culture. Late Dorset exceptionalism may serve as an example of how Tuniit archaeological narratives continue to be constructed through an intellectual tradition centered on legacy data. The implicit recycling of legacy data, often through the citing of grey literature, is a black box effect in which hard facts are produced from soft data that then serve as an empirical foundation for new studies (Hillerdal 2015:145; Taylor 1968:24; cf. Wolgar and Latour 1986:107). I argue that expanding the use of Inuit ethnography and oral history within Tuniit research contexts may help to address these issues, by enabling the development of research programs that consider questions, scales of analysis, and interpretations that are not represented in the cultural models that have emerged from legacy studies.

2.5 Conclusion: Towards a Relational and Posthumanist Archaeology of Place

Despite the challenges that archaeological, ethnographic, and oral historical data present for dominant conceptions of Arctic culture history and evolution, the core-periphery framework has continued to provide the primary organizational scheme through which archaeological sites are

integrated and systematically understood to produce narratives of Tuniit occupational history (Appelt et al. 2016:788; Darwent et al. 2018:532; Dyke et al. 2019; Fitzhugh and Loring 2002:16; Friesen 2007:200; Friesen et al. 2020:152; Hardenberg 2013:46; Howse et al. 2021; Mary-Rousselière 2002; Odess 2002; Ryan 2009; Savelle and Dyke 2014). I argue in this chapter that the core-periphery framework – along with its underlying foundation of cultural-historical taxa and socioevolutionary explanations of change – is insufficient for examining the intimate social relations and broader historic processes that shaped placemaking practices and community membership during the Tuniit Period. What is needed is for archaeologists to go beyond cultural-historical and socio-evolutionary models by developing new research agendas that collaborate with local communities and engage with different epistemologies of Place (Price 2008; TallBear 2015; Watts 2016).

As discussed here and in Chapter One, persistent places are not cultural expressions inscribed *on* the land as culture-historical frameworks might suggest, nor are they products of rational human behaviour that are structured *by* particular environments, as cultural ecological frameworks might posit. Their elements cannot be reduced to symbols or metaphors of timeless traditions or large-scale social systems (i.e., structuralism), and while human thought and action are important constituents of past places, they are far from the only agents responsible for their production (i.e., poststructuralism). Persistent places are more than type-sites or reflections of regional cultural systems: they are product and process of an emergent, more-than-human occupational history (Harris 2014; Watts 2016; Whatmore 2006; Whitridge 2016).

This conception of Place breaks away from universalizing rules about what society and culture are and how they work, and instead approaches humanity as a process of community-

making: of *becoming with* a material world (Haraway 2016; Watts 2016). A place-based approach makes room for the identification of camp communities rather than type-sites, and homelands rather than cultural cores or systems. In other words, it makes room for the inference of multiscalar and fluid social relationships involving both humans and nonhumans, rather than static or bounded cultural entities. I further cultivate this argument in the following chapter by mapping out how a place-based approach grounded in a difference-oriented methodology can be mobilized to address these issues and identify archaeological patterning in the landscape. The presented methodology involves a reinvestigation of Tuniit occupational history that engages with Amitturmiut Knowledge Holders and places of living history, and that considers human-environment relationships and the production of social identities, norms, and knowledge on a local level.

Chapter Three

A Place-Based Approach to Community and History in Amittuq, NU

Knowledge exists within the rhythms and realities of the land - Jackie Price (2008:130)

In Chapter Two, I explained how core area narratives reduce persistent places in Amittuq to inert representations of archaeological cultures and socio-evolutionary stage-types. This framework limits our understanding of Tuniit peoples to monolithic cultural entities and overlooks the contribution of people–place relationships to the production of human social worlds (Birch et al. 2022; Harris 2014; Watts 2016). In this chapter, I present the methods of data collection and analysis that I employ to produce a locally and historically situated narrative of the Tuniit archaeological landscape. This involves the examination of small-scale variability in Tuniit placemaking practice through the analysis of artifacts and architecture from three extensively researched “type-sites”— Qalirusiq, Kapuivik, and Alarniq — which I reframe as vibrant places of living history. I approach patterns of material difference recognized in these contexts as product and process of past social relations, and explore how these relations may have contributed to the materialization of Tuniit communities at the scales of the household, camp, and broader homeland.

As placemaking is a multifaceted and more-than-human process, my investigation incorporates multiple modes of analyses including oral historical, archaeological, and palaeogeographical components. I first discuss how these components work together toward my research problem: the explanation of how Tuniit communities in Amittuq, NU were shaped through reciprocal relationships between people and places. I then discuss my fieldwork and data for each component. This entails a description of my archival analysis of Amitturmiut oral testimonies and the interviews I conducted with local Knowledge Holders, followed by the design and execution of

my archaeological surveys, excavations, radiocarbon analyses, and digital modelling of Amittuq's paleoenvironment. I follow each description with a discussion of how the resulting datasets were incorporated into a GIS (*ArcGIS Pro 3.2*) for further modelling and exploratory analyses.

Examining these diverse lines of historic evidence in a GIS environment facilitated the observation of material patterning at multiple spatial and social scales, permitting new interpretations of the scale, extent, structure, and mobility of Tuniit communities.

3.1 Preliminary Fieldwork and Methodology

Preparation for my fieldwork began in 2016 through discussions with Rachel Qitsualik-Tinsley, Inuit cosmologist and manager of the Igloolik Oral History Project (OHP), as well as with community leaders at the Igloolik Hunters and Trappers Association (HTA). The reciprocal sharing of research ideas and interests with community members enabled me to gather early insights into the breadth of local knowledge related to persistent places and the concerns that Amitturmiut share about archaeological research. It is through this preliminary work I came to understand my engagement with *qanuqturniq* (*knowledge acquisition*) as ethnohistorical, since even the acts of reading and referencing oral testimonies result in situated knowledge that cannot be separated from my subject position as a non-Inuit academic (see Strong 2015). In other words, by conducting research that involves Amitturmiut oral testimonies, my work produces specific, subjective knowledges of the landscape: valuable, but partial, insights and perspectives about the past located within my personal history as much as local history (Haraway 1997:138).

In establishing this intellectual foundation, my background research initiated the

development of a difference-oriented approach. The rationale for this approach is that every time we interact with data — whether it be in the form of legacy data, artifacts, sites, or oral stories — we impose a specific point of view upon the elements under our observation, or what Barad refers to as “agential cuts” (2007:185). Agential cuts affect what we can see, feel, think, discuss, and imagine, and as such, critically inform how we act and react as part of our research practices. In other words, agential cuts are the primary apparatus of both social and scientific knowledge production because they enact what matters as well as what is excluded from mattering in our analyses and interpretations (Barad 2007:148, cf. Deleuze 1992:159). A difference-oriented (or “diffractive”) methodology attends to these agential cuts by exploring the patterns of interference that emerge between researcher and researched: the productive friction that arises between being *in place* and studying places (Price 2008:129, see Chapter One Section 1.2.3). Understanding difference as a generative process challenges the cultural-historical boundaries present in Tuniit archaeology that have restricted engagement with Inuit ethnography and oral history (see Chapter Two, Section 1.1.4.1), as it allows me to approach the memories, memorates²¹, and myths of local communities as active components of the places I investigate, and as apparatuses capable of shifting the nature of archaeological inquiry and observation.

In practice, this difference-oriented approach involved reading the insights of “subjective” oral historical and ethnohistorical data (e.g., archival records, personal testimonies) and data considered “objective” (e.g., site maps, radiocarbon dates, geological records) through one another to reveal new and unexpected patterning in the landscape (Barad 2011:452). As discussed in Chapter One, this is more than an act of comparison: a diffractive reading does not foreground any one line of evidence as foundational, and more importantly it attends to the vibrant entanglements

²¹ An oral narrative recounting a personal experience, intended for intergenerational cultural transmission.

between researcher and subject-matter that unfold through the process of research and that contribute to the narratives we build (Barad 2003; Haraway 1997). This approach aligns my research design with the principle of Saimaqatigiingniq as it attends to both collaborative and conflictual elements of Inuit and non-Inuit knowledge, which kept subject positions visible and open to critical intervention. This moves my research design from the statement “this is what the archaeological landscape is and how it came to be” towards the question “what can the archaeological landscape become if we include Amitturmiut stories, philosophies, and practices as part of archaeological practice?” This way of thinking about history, place, and landscape enabled the exploration of a wider range of possibilities for what persistent places could do through their relations with communities, and provided a richer understanding of the affective potentials that different sets of historic relations facilitated in terms of affirming and differentiating community membership during the Tuniit Period.

3.1.1 Applied Structure of the Difference-Oriented Approach

Reconstructing the Tuniit occupational landscape through materially locatable, performative places required approaching archaeological sites not as inert reflections of cultural-historical taxa (e.g., archaeological cultures) or homogenous adaptive systems (e.g., the core area), but as multiscale assemblages that embody dynamic and co-productive community relations (see Chapter 1, Section 1.2.2). A research design incorporating oral historical, archaeological, and paleogeographical analyses met the data requirements of this study by providing rich and contrasting inferences of the landscape at the spatial and social scales of the dwelling/household, campsite/camp community, and inter-site/homeland. The productive frictions offered through this

diverse mapwork provided insight into how persistent places emerged and changed in Amittuq, and their affective roles in shaping the connections, actions, and identities of local communities, past and present.

The oral historical research component involved interviews with Knowledge Holders in Igloolik and the analysis of transcribed oral testimonies from the Igloolik Oral History Archives to construct a cohesive historical mapwork of the Amitturmiut landscape. The primary objective of these efforts was to gain a better understanding of Inuit Qaujimajatuqangit (IQ), or “*things long known to Inuit*”. This included the examination of what Amitturmiut remember about who the Tuniit were and the places they lived (*qaujimajangit*), and Inuit ways of knowing and becoming with places in the landscape (*qaujimaningit*). Exploring Amitturmiut placemaking and history helped me develop a more comprehensive set of archaeological expectations for how Tuniit communities interacted with their landscape. This informed my sampling strategy for my archaeological surveys as well as the interpretive conclusions I drew about the structure and patterning of Tuniit campsites in later GIS analyses.

The archaeological research component centered on the examination of Tuniit architecture and artifacts from Qalirusiq, Kapuivik, and Alarniq to assess differences in the form and arrangement of Tuniit campsites. This involved pedestrian and remotely piloted aircraft (RPA) survey and site-mapping, the excavation of dwellings and extramural areas, and radiocarbon sequencing. The pedestrian surveys documented artifact and feature level distributions of Tuniit occupational remains at each study site, focusing on previously unsurveyed areas. This permitted the identification of a greater diversity in site location choices, including lower-density artifact distributions that had been overlooked due to the sampling biases of previous fieldwork (Bielawski

1988:57). The RPA surveys captured high resolution RGB imagery for the pedestrian survey units and areas between them, enhancing the identification of features and the production of site maps. A second set of RPA surveys using a thermal camera offered subsurface prospection of a sample of the pedestrian survey units. When the thermal data was combined with the RGB data, it was possible to evaluate the extent to which available pedestrian survey data were representative of Tuniit sites in the region (Meldgaard 1960a; Savelle and Dyke 2014). Specific practices related to the construction, maintenance, use, and abandonment of Tuniit campsites were inferred from the excavation of dwellings and extramural settlement areas. This offered insight into how domestic and communal spaces were configured, and in turn how humans and nonhumans likely encountered one another through daily practices. The recovery of organic materials through the excavations were essential for expanding each site's radiocarbon sequence, and provided an absolute chronology of Tuniit occupation independent of the essentializing cultural-historical categories that typically structure archaeological narratives (Birch et al. 2022).

The paleogeographic research component centered on modelling environmental information derived from elevation data and orthoimagery from the RPA surveys. These models were combined with geological records acquired from the Canadian Geological Survey (Art Dyke, personal communication 2020) and satellite-derived imagery from various online databases and from the Digital Globe Foundation. The data were interpolated in the GIS to produce predictive regression models of Amittuq's topography for 500-year intervals (5000 to 500 BP). The resulting models were overlaid with spatialized ethnohistoric data to analyze historic differences in ecological settings, such as freshwater systems. These models allowed me to draw inferences about how Tuniit communities moved between and encountered persistent places in the context of a heterogenous environment that was subject to extreme seasonal and generational changes.

The oral historical, archaeological, and paleogeographic research components were brought together through multiscalar exploratory GIS analyses to construct a cohesive mapwork of the Tuniit occupational landscape. By organizing the archaeological data into temporal intervals and comparing them with other spatial data components within the GIS environment, I identify new occupational patterning indicative of both persistence and change in community relations during the Tuniit Period. This includes patterns of residential mobility, temporal trends in land use, and visual connections between distant camps that serve proxies for ancient navigation routes (Alfred 2020). Following the assemblage-based mapping approach described in Chapter One (Section 2.2), I interpret these GIS models as more-than-representations of what Tuniit occupational landscapes “were” by examining them as virtual sets of potentials for what communities were capable of becoming through their momentary encounters *in place* (Barad 2003; TallBear 2015; Harris 2014; Watts 2013). Mapping place-community relations as multiscalar and performative assemblages produced a rich historical narrative accountable to how past people, animals, materials, and topographies — as well as living people, memories, and traditions — have repeatedly participated in the production of Amittuq’s occupational history.

3.2 Oral Historical Research Component

In this section I discuss the research strategies employed as part of my research and analysis of Amitturmiut oral histories and living knowledge. I first detail my procedures of data collection, which took place in Igloolik, Nunavut through mixed methods approach that included archival research on transcribed interviews from the Igloolik Oral History Project (OHP) and interpreter-aided interviews with Knowledge Holders from the Igloolik community. I then outline the methods

of analyses that I employed to build a working interpretive narrative of the historic Amitturmiut landscape, which included a qualitative analysis of transcribed oral testimonies and a spatial analysis of oral historical and ethnographic data in a GIS. Ultimately, these analyses elucidated how persistent places in Amittuq were historically differentiated through community practices, and vice versa. They also informed my archaeological fieldwork design and the refinement of my predictive environmental models as part of the palaeogeographical research component.

3.2.1 Archival Data Collection

Archival research for my study was undertaken at the OHP archives in Igloolik, Nunavut. The OHP is a collaborative local project run by Iglulingmiut Elders since 1986, who work in cooperation with staff at Nunavut Arctic College. The OHP offers extensive oral history testimonies recorded on tape in Inuktitut, most of which have been transcribed and translated into English. The testimonies belong to Amitturmiut (including Iglulingmiut) Knowledge Holders and were collected either as interview sessions led by Igloolik community members or as self-recorded monologues. The collection is currently comprised of over 700 interviews, with Inuktitut and English transcriptions available on a local computer system at the IQ and Oral History Office. Archival research of the OHP collections provided a more comprehensive picture of Tuniit occupational practices (as observed by Inuit), of how Tuniit places persist through storytelling, and the ways in which local communities have continued to engage with historic places in the landscape.

I conducted a preliminary evaluation of the OHP computer database in 2018 and compiled a list of foundational codes to guide further research. A code is “most often a word or short phrase

that symbolically assigns a summative, salient, essence-capturing, and/or evocative attribute for a portion of language-based or visual data” (Saldaña 2014:4). The drafted code list included words, concepts, and themes associated with any mention of Tuniit or the study sites, as well as stories about travelling, camping, and community organization prior to forced relocation²². Reflecting on this preliminary work under the mentorship of Rachel Qitsualik-Tinsley helped me to better understand the variability in terms used to refer to Tuniit and important places, as well as nuances of Inuit storytelling that are often lost in Qallunaatit (English) translations.

During my return visit in 2019, I formally evaluated the archives using a refined code list. The code list included variations on terms related to Tuniit, including spelling variations such as Tunnit or Tuniq (sing.) and associated terms such as Tunijjuat (*big Tuniit*) and Inugarulligaarjuit (*dwarves*), the latter referring to shapeshifters that are usually described as separate creatures, but who are sometimes presented as the builders of Tuniit boulder dwellings and caches (Rachel Qitsualik-Tinsley personal communication, 2018). Other codes included seasonal land dynamics (e.g., ice patterns, weather changes), seasonal distributions of resources (e.g., flint, caribou, the right snow for igloos), wayfinding practices, sentiments towards the importance of history and being with the land, and cultural taboos and shamanic practices related to land use. The refined code list isolated 150 interviews of immediate relevance to my research. In accordance with my special access agreement and Nunavut Research Institute license, a confidential digital copy of the selected interviews was supplied to me for post-field analyses²³.

²² In the 1950s the Canadian government initiated programs to forcibly assimilate Inuit into large settlements, leading to the creation of the Igloolik hamlet (QIA 2010).

²³ In accordance with this agreement, the names of interviewed participants are kept confidential and only the interview codes provided by the OHP are used in my work, which begin with IE (*Inullariit Elders*) (e.g., IE001).

3.2.2 Interview Procedures

I conducted a small set of interviews with local knowledge holders during the 2019 visit to Igloolik. The purpose of these interviews was to collect in-depth personal accounts about and reflections on Tuniit lifeways and Inuit-Tuniit relations. This helped me build richer interpretive conclusions from the OHP testimonies, which often mentioned Tuniit and the deep past but were rarely centered on these themes. The interviews were also used as an opportunity to refine my field design based on the research questions that Knowledge Holders felt were the most important for me to pursue. All members of the Igloolik community were invited to participate in the interview process through a local radio announcement made in Inuktitut and English, and through a printed notice disseminated through the HTA. Ultimately, four individuals participated in interview sessions. The small number of participants may have to do with the fact that Tuniit stories are part of specialized knowledge that has been distanced from Inuit history through archaeological practice. It is also, of course, because establishing the kind of trust needed for long, intimate interview sessions is a complex and multiyear process, one made more complicated by a complex local history with anthropologists (IE703). The participants were Elders with experience living on the land and who serve as community stewards of important stories, including stories about Tuniit.

Interviews were conducted through a locally recognized Inuktitut interpreter using a semi-structured interview technique involving open-ended questions. While a participatory conversation-based interview structure may have provided richer and more elaborate responses (cf. Klassen 2013:92) use of this method was made complicated by the language barrier. The added benefit of the semi-structured approach is that it allowed participants to expand on themes and stories they felt comfortable sharing while avoiding sensitive topics at their discretion. Interviews were conducted at

a preferred location selected by the participants, in most cases their own homes. Consent was sought from all participants for the use of the testimonies in my research and the preferred length for sessions was discussed, ranging from one to two hours. Interviews were recorded using a mobile phone application, and interview notes were taken for additional context (e.g., material surroundings, body language). The recordings were manually transcribed post-field for analysis²⁴.

3.2.3 Ethnohistoric Mapping

Oral testimonies collected through archival research and interviews were processed and analyzed through a combination of qualitative and spatial analysis. The qualitative analysis involved the processing and organization of the oral testimonies through thematic categories and generative data displays (e.g., word clouds) to identify patterning in names, sentiments, and ideas associated with particular places, times, and practices that are (or were) common to Amitturmiut daily life. Identifying overarching patterns in the texts facilitated the construction of a cohesive narrative of Amitturmiut land use and place histories. The spatialization of these data in *ArcGIS Pro* 3.2 visualized these patterns and allowed me to compare and contrast them with spatial patterns identified through the archaeological and palaeogeographical research components. This offered a wider diversity of candidate site locations outside of the coastal beach ridge setting that previous fieldwork projects have focused on.

The qualitative and spatial data were critical in the development of my survey strategy for the archaeological research component, which ultimately included the sampling of riparian,

²⁴ Much like the OHP archives, my interview participants are kept confidential and referred to by the code KH (knowledge holder) followed by a numerical identifier. (e.g., KH01).

lacustrine, glacial till, and elevated geological formation zones in addition to the littoral gravel ridges where Tuniit sites are traditionally expected to be found. They also provided insight into seasonally specific variables, such as common locations where good snow for building winter dwellings tends to form, or the breeding and feeding grounds of prey species such as caribou and ringed seal. These analyses also contextualized the continued importance of Tuniit places to Amitturmiut as active campsites, historic landmarks, navigational aids, and mnemonic devices. This informed my collaborations with local cultural authorities and expanded the kinds of observations I was able to make as part of my archaeological analyses: the kinds of participants I recognized as intrinsic to a sense of community in Amittuq and the sorts of material practices that — as they did with Inuit communities — may have entangled Tuniit communities with particular places in the landscape.

3.2.3.1 Qualitative Analyses. Thematic and inductive content analyses of the OHP archival documents were conducted using the NVivo 14 qualitative analysis software package. Thematic coding in NVivo allowed me to organize the transcribed testimonies into descriptive themes of analytical significance (referred to nodes in the NVivo platform). Frequent and significant nodes were sorted and nested into case classifications (e.g., places, seasons, key concepts) for streamlined inductive analyses of broad themes. For example, mentions of specific actions such as collecting worms and placenames referring to fish (e.g., Kapuivik “*where we spear the fish*”) were organized under the broader theme of fishing. This permitted information about place-community relations to be cross-referenced to ensure that themes were supported by multiple testimonies and as such could be understood as part of a cohesive historic narrative (Stake 1995:33). I chose not to include the interviews I conducted in 2019 in this analysis because my interview methods varied from those used by the OHP. However, annotations referring to my interviews were incorporated into NVivo

nodes where relevant, to further support themes and sentiments.

My inductive analysis involved the implementation of NVivo's auto-coding procedure to create word frequency lists and data displays to isolate relationships between established nodes. This allowed me to extract analytical insights between separate themes and to examine patterning in the descriptions of daily practices in different social contexts (e.g., offering seal meat in times of dearth or at the grave of a loved one). Data displays were filtered through a stop word list to remove insignificant words such as conjunctions and prepositions, as well as confidential names and terms. The word cloud produced from this effort visualized the degree of connection between disparate terms frequently mentioned in Amitturmiut stories about Tuniit.

3.2.3.2 Spatial Analyses. OHP and interview data associated with materially locatable places were exported into *ArcGIS Pro 3.2* and integrated with spatialized oral history information from the Nunavut Map Series (IHT 2016) and toponymic work of Claudio Aporta (2003). As Amitturmiut places have fluid boundaries, I chose to represent most locations by point data. NVivo codes and annotations were translated into attribute data for geographic points and visualized using symbology categories. Mapping these data allowed me to visually interrogate spatial connections between places, historic events, and sentiments embodied through placenames and stories. When layered with the paleogeographic models and archaeological distributional data, the ethnohistoric maps visualized spatial patterning and temporal trends in land use, including seasonal resource exploitation and travel routes (Figure 3.1). The mapping of the ethnohistoric data also facilitated the reconstruction of historic landscape elements such as shifting waterways and coastlines that had a significant role in shaping community relations during the Early Inuit period (Finkelstein et al. 2009). This enhanced my reconstructions of past environments as part of my paleogeographic

research component, and provided insight into the movements and visual relationships that likely connected campsites and resource exploitation areas during the Tuniit Period.

Figure 3.1 An example of the spatialized coded data, near Kapuivik.

3.3 Archaeological Research Component

In this section, I describe my study area and site selection strategy for the archaeological research component, followed by the design and execution of my fieldwork. This research took place in 2018 and 2019 and consisted of pedestrian survey, RPA survey and site mapping, surface collections, and excavations. I also analyzed a GPS dataset of regional sites collected by Savelle and Dyke (2009, 2014). The purpose of these combined efforts was to document variability in the

structure and arrangement of domestic and communal spaces as evidenced by the remains of Tuniit architecture (e.g., tents, sod houses, caches) and unwallled activity spaces (e.g., middens, tool and food processing areas). These contexts were intimate, affective fields where humans and nonhumans encountered one another on a daily basis and acquired shared social meanings (Ahmed 2005:104; Basso 1996:44-45; Casey 1996:35; TallBear 2015:186). Variability in their material relations provides insight into how communities were articulated at the scales of the household and camp. The section ends with a description of the radiocarbon analyses related to this fieldwork. Radiocarbon analyses were critical for determining temporal trends in survey and excavation data beyond the confines of the cultural-historical taxa inherent to beach ridge archaeology (see Chapter 2, Section 2.1.6). These analyses enabled the identification of contemporaneous campsites and intergenerational site maintenance practices deflated archaeological contexts. This work permitted inferences of small-scale continuity and change in daily occupational practices and richer insight into the shifting intensities of interhousehold and intercamp relations.

3.3.1 Study Region and Site Selection

My selected study region is the result of extensive ATV surveys conducted between 2002 and 2008 by the Foxe Basin Archaeology (FBA) project, covering the northern islands and coastlines of Amittuq (Figure 3.2). There are at least 441 previously identified archaeological sites²⁵ with a Tuniit occupational component in this region, 407 of which are residential campsites, and the remaining of which are mostly cairns and findspots (GNCH 2019; Savelle personal communication 2018). 47 of these sites can be classified as multiperiod settlement sequences. Qalirusiq, Kapuivik, and Alarniq are three of the largest of these sequences, and are unique in that they served as Meldgaard's type-sites for defining Tuniit archaeological cultures (1962; 1965). I focused my

²⁵ As represented by Borden designations, the Canadian numbering system used to classify archaeological sites.

investigation on these sites not only because of their important role in developing the dominant cultural-historical model, but because they remain important places of history for Amitturmiut. This makes them ideal case studies for examining long-term historical processes related to placemaking and community-building in the eastern Canadian Arctic.

Figure 3.2 Tuniit sites in Amittuq. *“Qalirusiq” refers to both Parry Hill and Lyon Hill, I use the spelling “Kaluserk” when referencing Lyon Hill.

3.2 Pedestrian Survey

This section describes the pedestrian surveys conducted at Kapuvik during the 2018 field season and at Qalirusiq and Alarniq during the 2019 field seasons. These surveys permitted ground-level identification and measurement of structural features (e.g., dwellings, caches). They also

served as a means for testing the distribution of surface artifacts and identifying low-density occupational areas such as lithic and faunal scatters. I first present an overview of my field strategy for the pedestrian surveys, which were designed to adequately sample the full range of candidate site locations in each study area, including those outside of the expected coastal setting of littoral gravel beach ridges. I then provide a description of each site's local environment and the design and execution of my surveys at Kapuivik, Alarniq, and Qalirusiq, respectively.

3.3.2.1 Survey Design and Sampling Criteria. While my survey design varied between the study sites, each centred around a judgemental sampling strategy aimed at documenting the diversity present in Tuniit site structure and location. While most identified sites in Amittuq have been coastal, these survey data are subject to a significant confirmation bias because most land outside of the expected coastal setting remains uninvestigated. It is probable that the large coastal sites documented in Amittuq represent only a portion of Tuniit occupational practices, most likely spring and winter settlements (Bielawski 1988:57, cf. Park 1994:30). As estimates on the abundance, clustering, and obtrusiveness of sites in the region are unavailable, it was important for my sample to target underrepresented sites outside of the expected coastal setting (Banning 2021; Schiffer et al 1978). As such, a purposive strategy centered on maximizing the probability of identifying the full range of Tuniit site types was selected for my research.

My surveys examined a variety of geomorphological and ecological settings that have established associations with ancestral and modern Inuit occupational practices — for example fishing and bird hunting at inland lakes, winter travelling camps near natural windbreaks, and caching activities near glacial till areas (e.g., IE001:3; IE010:11). My survey frame included the full range of relevant physiographic contexts walkable from the basecamp of each study site, as

identified through regional geological records (Figure 3.3) and local reconnaissance surveys as part of my participation on previous field projects (Desrosiers 2018; Howse 2018). A break-down of the physiographic variables associated with the sampling universe and their connections with Inuit occupational practices is outlined in Table 3.1 and visualized in Figure 3.4.

Figure 3.3 Regional surficial geology of Amittuq (see Table 3.1 for legend descriptions). *Data from Fulton 1995, CAVM 2003. Base map from HRDEM, Natural Resources Canada (RCAN).*

As biophysical diversity in Amittuq tends to increase as one walks inland from the coast, the pedestrian surveys generally focused on the higher elevated terraces of each site and inland areas beyond known site extents. A survey boundary closer to the shoreline was set at 6 MASL as a conservative elevation limit for the end of the Tuniit Period, as land beneath this point only surfaced

above sea level after 600 BP, well after the latest hypothesized Late Tuniit occupations in the Eastern Arctic ²⁶ (Table 2.1). It is important to note that the pedestrian surveys were conducted during collaborative field seasons that accommodated data collection for multiple FBA-related research projects, most of which were centered on excavation. As such, fieldwalking often took place on non-consecutive days around the schedule of the prioritized excavations. Usually this involved part of the team breaking off to survey units that were on-route to site in the mornings and evenings or when soil was too wet post-rain to excavate. As such, the proximity of survey contexts to our base camp and daily travel routes played a role in determining exactly which physiographic contexts were sampled (e.g., which till areas or wind shelters were included in the surveys).

Figure 3.4 Examples of physiographic variation (see Table 3.1 for descriptions): A) Dry-moist tundra with residual lag; B) Ice wedge polygons; C) Mudflow; D) Coastal wetlands and ponds; E) Muskeg wetland; F) Precambrian metamorphic buttes/escarpments; G) Kettle hole lake with marshland H) Till veneer I) Continuous till deposit (shingle and boulder clasts). *Images captured in 2018 at Kapuivik (F, G, H), 2019 at Qalirusiq (A, B, I) and 2019 at Alarniq (D, E, C).*

Table 3.1 Descriptions of physiographic variables associated with Inuit occupational history.

²⁶ The latest Tuniit features in Amittuq have been found at 8 MASL (~1000 BP) (Savelle and Dyke 2014), but ¹⁴C assays from western Nunavut suggest occupations may have occurred until cal. 600 BP (Friesen 2019).

Data from Bird 1967; Dyke et al. 2002; Gould et al. 2002; OHP 2019; Trettin 1975

Variable	Definition	Affordances for Occupational Practices
Beach Terrace	A relict shore ridge or berm parallel with the coastline and other adjacent terraces	Sea access. Runnels provide wind break and natural contours for dwelling construction.
	Shingle Surface clast 64–256 mm.	Often frost-shattered limestone. Building materials (flagstones for paving, house borders/tent weights).
	Coarse Grained Surface clast 2–4mm.	Building materials (gravel house borders/tent weights).
	Pebble Surface clast 4–64 mm.	Building materials (pebble house borders/tent weights).
Lag	Residual lag from marine submergence including gravel, sand, and washed till.	Building materials (house borders, tent weights), caches for walrus meat.
Butte	Rocky flat-topped hills.	Vantage point, landmark, and wind shelter. The side with more cassiope or heather is used to find one's bearings.
Plain	Flat tundra consistent with the Foxe Plain, Arctic Lowlands.	Caribou grazing supported by patches of dryas and low shrub in dry areas and sedge and moss in wet zones. Quartz crystals and flints are more commonly found in these lowland areas, especially near rivers. Level plains without surface obstructions used as traditional dog sled and modern ATV routes.
Headland	A point of elevated land that juts out into the sea.	Vantage point, landmark, and navigational marker (can be used to look back at to keep boat direction when travelling to a lowland place).
Tundra Pond	Inland water bodies within the photic zone.	Animal habitat, especially waterfowl. Source of drinking water attracting caribou and other roaming animals.
Lake	Seasonal and perennial water bodies with depths outside the photic zone.	Habitat for freshwater and anadromous fish and waterfowl. Caribou crossings. Distinguished landmark/navigational marker. Deeper lakes that do not freeze entirely in winter are important drinking water sources for Inuit hunting parties.
River/ Stream	Seasonal and perennial water drainage features.	Caribou crossings. Can be followed for navigation across land routes in summer or for tracking caribou migration routes in autumn. Seasonal fishing during the spawn.
Glacial Till	Boulders (>256mm) and unsorted granular materials.	Source of tool stone. Good materials to build caches, especially fish caches if located near lake. Source of boulders used as tent weights and dwelling foundations.
	Till Veneer: Thin, discontinuous till interspersed with bedrock.	
	Till Blanket: Thick, continuous till.	
Bedrock	Undivided rock (Paleozoic carbonates) and exposed basement (Precambrian metamorphic)	Vantage point, wind shelter. Inuit children use to draw with augiujaq (powdery stone) on the bedrock. Not good for camping — divides residential spaces.
Ice Wedge Polygon Field	Deep elongated cracks in land formed by ground ice.	Distinct landscape features that help a hunter find their bearings. Affects water drainage and therefore flooding of nearby campsites in the spring.
Ice Flow	General direction of ice movement based on drumlins and fluting.	Ice movements impact the formation of polynyas and ice leads where animals breed and bask, and determine when travel across ice floes is possible.
Antislope Scarp	An up-hill facing steep slope found at the margin of a flat or gently sloping area, usually against the dip of rocks.	Accumulation of vegetation for grazing animals, windbreak, natural contours for dwelling construction. Good snow for houses accumulates here in spring.
Esker	Winding ridges comprised of sediments deposited by glacial meltwater.	Parallel formations serve as inland travel routes for humans and caribou. Vantage point, wind shelter.

To keep my observations consistent between the three study sites and account for time and

labour constraints, I employed a walker spacing of 10-meter intervals. This spacing permitted the sampling of artifact-level remains within one meter on either side of each transect (i.e., 20% artifact-level sample per unit) and the detection of most superficially visible architectural features within each unit — observations that were supported though the RPA surveys (see Section 3.3). This walker spacing was extensive enough to allow for adequate survey coverage of different physiographic settings, including the examination of more inland areas. The geographic locations of units, features, and findspots were recorded in-field using two handheld GPS units equipped with high-resolution satellite imagery (*Worldview-4*) and digitally sketched onto a Samsung tablet using Android-compatible GIS applications (*Mapit GIS* and *Locus GIS*). GPS tracks and waypoints were plotted on the field laptop as an additional measure of spatial control, to map survey units and confirm if plotted features had been previously identified in the Nunavut archaeological repository.

Survey unit sizes were largely determined by the natural demarcation of landscape elements (e.g., lakes, outcrops) and changes in unconsolidated surface materials (e.g., boulder till, vegetation coverage). The decision to define and separate survey units by modern land cover was premised on the understanding that artifacts often behave as sediments, and their preservation and movement are strongly influenced by the same post-depositional processes that define land cover (Schiffer 1978, Bauer 2010). Defining survey units by these variables allowed me to evaluate the effects that different surface properties have on site detection — especially the identification of low density, non-structural archaeological contexts (Balek 2002; Holdaway 2004; Schiffer 1976; Shahack-Gross 2017). These differences generally coincided with the borders of landscape elements that were anticipated to have informed Tuniit occupational practices, such as escarpments, terraces, and lakes (Table 3.1). Natural demarcations also served as visual markers for field walkers and facilitated the georeferencing of survey units and findspots that would have otherwise been difficult to precisely

map due to the challenges presented by compass declination, GPS accuracy, limited optical measuring equipment, and the dependence of RPA techniques on appropriate weather. Ultimately, the pedestrian surveys resulted in the placement of 73 judgemental units: 21 at Kapuivik (totalling 1.4 km² survey coverage), 22 at Alarniq (totalling 5.5 km²), and 30 at Qalirusiq (totalling 1.1km²). These units are described in the following subsections.

3.3.2.2 Kapuivik Pedestrian Survey. Kapuivik is a large coastal site located on Kapuivitt Nuvua — the southwestern cape of Kapuivitt Island. Originally surveyed and excavated by Meldgaard in the 1950s, Kapuivik was resurveyed by Savelle and Dyke in 2002 and 2003 and excavated by Desrosiers in 2016 as part of the FBA project (Savelle and Dyke 2014; Desrosiers 2019). Prior to the 2018 fieldwork there were 282 Tuniit and 79 Early Inuit features identified at the site. The Tuniit features are predominantly surface dwellings inferred as tents or snow houses, but there are also 18 small semi-subterranean sod dwellings affiliated with the “Dorset” archaeological culture on the lower terraces of the site (8-23 MASL). Kapuivik was designated by Meldgaard as a single Borden (NjHa-1), but Savelle and Dyke reorganized the site into a series of “site areas” based on feature clusters, which for all intents and purposes serve as discrete sites (Figure 3.5).

With residual shorelines reaching 100 MASL, Kapuivik Nuvua was one of the first inhabitable places²⁷ in Amittuq (ca. 6000 BP), although the earliest known Tuniit dwelling found at 52 MASL dates to cal. 3445-3778 BP (Savelle et al. 2009), presumably because this was when the initial peopling of Foxe Basin first occurred (Maxwell 1985; Savelle and Dyke 2014). The peninsula is comprised of a Precambrian metamorphic basement (predominately granite) that is exposed in several areas (Figure 3.3). Due to its granite bedrock and glacial history, Kapuivik is

²⁷ Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Kaleruserk were the first areas in Amittuq to rise above sea level (Savelle and Dyke 2014).

characterized by a diverse set of geological formations (e.g., escarpments, valleys) that divert ground water to form kettle hole lakes, ponds, streams, marshlands, and thickly vegetated areas. Glacial processes have also formed several pockets of till veneer and numerous deep ice wedge polygons that affect water drainage and the distribution of unconsolidated quaternary material. It is important to note that even the highest portions of the cape have visible beach ridges, although the further inland one moves from the coast, the wider and more contorted they become. Kapuivik is topographically diverse, and most of the physiographic elements described in Table 3.1 are present.

As Tuniit occupants of Amittuq are thought to have built their camps along active shorelines (Meldgaard 1954b; Maxwell 1976b:4-5), it is accordingly expected by the proponents of this research that most Tuniit features at Kapuivik should be located along coastal terraces that formed during the Tuniit Period of occupation (c. 3700-1000 BP), namely those now located between 8-52 MASL (Meldgaard 1954a, 1954b, 1960a, 1962; Savelle et al. 2009; Savelle and Dyke 2014). While all previously identified features are located within the 8-52 MASL sequence, the identification of six (undated) ephemeral Tuniit sites 10 km north of Kapuivik (70-90 MASL) by Savelle and Dyke (2014:259) lend credence to the possibility that settlement areas outside of the expected coastal setting are underrepresented at Kapuivik. As such, I laid out three survey units (19, 20, 21) approximately 1 km northeast of the site's boundary at 60-70 MASL (Figure 3.5). The northeastern boundary had not been previously surveyed due to the presence of heavy glacial till and escarpments that prevented access by ATV during Savelle and Dyke's surveys (Savelle personal communication 2018). Units 19 and 20 are surrounded by exposed bedrock that provide shelter from onshore winds, while unit 21 is adjacent to a large kettle lake and covered in boulder till that

Figure 3.5 Kapuivik site areas showing extent of pedestrian, visible light RPA, and thermal RPA surveys.

could have provided adequate building material for tents and caches.

Another limitation of previous surveys was their focus on an intra-site sampling strategy in which areas with obvious architectural structures were purposively surveyed, with artifact-level prospection only occurring in the direct vicinity of these features. By prioritizing the identification of architecture, this strategy has invariably excluded the examination of areas with lower density archaeological remains, such as those that result from ephemeral snow houses, butchering activities, or the procurement and processing of tool stone (Savelle 1984:511; Savelle et al. 2012:173-174). As a result, the material assemblages represented by previous survey data are heavily skewed towards large residential coastal sites (see Savelle and Dyke 2014 for exception). This is problematic because artifact typologies developed from these activity-specific (and possibly multitemporal) contexts have been used to construct large-scale occupational histories, and have likely contributed to the chronological issues associated with the application of these typologies to new sites (Desrosiers and Sørensen 2012 on Taylor 1968). Because it also impacts the resolution at which coastal residential contexts are surveyed, sparse or discontinuous distributions of archaeological materials between dwellings have also likely been overlooked, restricting inferences of extramural occupational practices and interhousehold social relations at Kapuivik (Dunnell and Dancey 1983:271; Ebert 1992:32). It was therefore important for existing site areas to be resurveyed.

My sample included the placement of survey units in and around existing site areas, namely 204, 205, 210, 212, 215, 219, 222, and 223, to examine artifact distributions and document extramural occupational areas (Figure 3.5). These units were placed to include clusters of visible architecture as well as the borders of nearby landscape elements such as lakes, outcrops, and marshes. These are areas where structural features had not been previously identified, but where

open-air occupational activities such as fish caching or tool-making may have taken place (Table 3.1). Units were walked systematically using the 10m transect spacing, which provided an artifact-level comparison of both Tuniit architectural contexts and lower-density extramural contexts throughout the site (Caraher et al. 2006, Cherry 2003; Given 2013; Wandsnider and Ebert 1986). This helped me better distinguish between overlapping sets of past activities embodied through the distribution of non-structural archaeological materials (Binford 1992:44; Thomas 1983:26). All identified features were measured and mapped, and all surface artifacts were collected during the Kapuivik survey.

3.3.2.3 Alarniq Pedestrian Survey. Alarniq is located along a coastal point that includes the Alarniq, Quaqsaraarjuk, and Kangiq beach areas on the eastern coast of Melville Peninsula. The site reaches 25 MASL at its highest point, and was likely below sea level until shortly before 2000 BP, the time period associated with “Early Dorset” in the traditional culture history (Savelle and Dyke 2014, see Table 2.1). Alarniq is comprised of Paleozoic carbonate bedrock (predominantly limestone), although glacial erratic granite and gneiss boulders can be found along the higher terraces of the site. The effects of isostasy in this area have been more variable than at Kapuivik. This has led to the formation of coastal terraces with irregular rebound rates, the most notable irregularity being a two-metre decrease in elevation beyond the 24-25 MASL terraces, resulting in a wide flat plain (21-22 MASL) inland from the site (Figure 3.6). Coastal terraces at Alarniq are characterized by thin mineral-based soils (predominantly sandy gravel) that form undulating ridges and softer berms interspersed with deposits of vegetation. Seasonal coastal wetlands and ponds form within the runnels, which increase in size as one moves inland and the space between the coastal terraces expands (Image D, Figure 3.4).

Figure 3.6 Alarniq sites showing extent of pedestrian, visible light RPA, and thermal RPA surveys.

Alarniq was first observed by Mathiassen (1925) in 1922, and then surveyed and excavated by Meldgaard (1962) and Father Mary-Rousselière (1984) in the 1950s. The site was resurveyed by Savelle and Dyke in 2008 and excavated by Lesley Howse in 2015 and 2017 as part of the FBA project. First designated by Meldgaard as NhHd-1, today Alarniq is divided into 38 Borden designations (Figure 3.6). Meldgaard identified 208 Tuniit dwellings at the site, but more recent investigations have identified 191 (Howse et al. 2019) as well as 48 Early Inuit dwellings and numerous Inuit caches, middens, and graves (Savelle and Dyke 2014). Whereas surface dwelling types dominate Kapuivik's Tuniit assemblage, the majority of features at Alarniq are semi-subterranean sod dwellings. There are, however, seven boulder surface dwellings of unknown age located at the southern periphery of site (NhHd-16, Figure 3.6). There are also numerous potential cairn features at the southwest periphery of the site (NhHd-11 and NhHd-19, Figure 3.6) that have been interpreted as either Tuniit graves (Lynnerup 2003) or meat caches (Howse et al. 2019) – however it is important to note that these prospective features are located within dense pockets of glacial erratic.

Similar to Kapuivik, I sampled the full range of physiographic contexts walkable from our base camp, which ultimately led to the placement of eleven survey units inland from the site (Figure 3.6). Alarniq is connected by two day's travel on foot (~100 km) to caribou calving grounds (Nagy 2012:44), caribou sea-ice crossings (QWB 2018), and several fishing lakes (IE263) through two east-west river routes²⁸ known as Majuqtuliliariaq and Tisuqqikululiariaq (IE481). As such, I anticipated that areas east of the site might contain the remains of ephemeral Tuniit dwellings and storage caches related to inter-seasonal travel between coastal and interior camps (Bielawski 1988). Since Early Inuit features at Alarniq are arranged around ponds and wetlands, I also expected that

²⁸ Under the logic that even without boats or dog teams, river routes provide clear and easy-to-navigate footpaths, a guaranteed drinking water source, and attract prey animals that would have appealed to Tuniit travellers.

Tuniit camps may be located slightly inland from the coastal site sequence around similar water features. Most of these areas had not been surveyed by Savelle and Dyke in 2008 since the marshes and ponds prevented ATV access. My sampling of these inland areas included the placement of six survey units (11, 13, 15–19) along the borders of prominent water features and wetlands, and the placement of five units (4, 10, 11, 12, 14) surrounding deposits of glacial till that may have provided convenient building materials for caches and ephemeral camps.

Previous fieldwork at Alarniq was, much like Kapuivik, subject to an intra-site sampling strategy that prioritized the examination of visible architectural structures without systematic survey of the areas between these features. Following the same protocol as at Kapuivik, an additional eleven units were placed in and around previously identified sites to determine the extent of individual Tuniit camps and to examine extramural practices inferred through the distribution of artifacts and ecofacts (3, 5–8, 21, 22). The examination of previously identified sites also included the placement of four units (1, 2, 4, 9) at NhHd-11 and NhHd-19 to gain a clearer understanding of the density and arrangement of cultural features located in these cache/grave areas. All features identified through the Alarniq survey were measured and mapped, and all surface artifacts were recorded and collected.

3.3.2.4 Qalirusiq Pedestrian Survey. Qalirusiq is one of two limestone buttes near Igloolik hamlet, the other being Kaleruserk²⁹, with both reaching a height of 52 MASL. The bedrock of Igloolik Island is predominantly made up of dolomite overlain with a saprolitic crust of frost-shattered limestone, and it is the saprolitic crust that characterizes Qalirusiq's caprock and scree (Figure 3.7). Granite and gneiss glacial erratic are found in low densities across the summit and in

²⁹ Kaleruserk was also surveyed in 2019, however most of the site had been destroyed by the construction of the Igloolik airport and as such is not included in my study. These survey results are described in Walker (2020b).

higher densities along the windward (southwest) slope. Several pond and wetland features are interspersed with pockets of sparsely vegetated tundra atop a sandy gravel substrate on the higher terraces, with thicker mosses covering the lower plateaus. Qalirusiq also contains high densities of modern anthropogenic debris due to its location near the Igloolik hamlet, especially along the 17-20 MASL terraces downhill from the modern garbage dump (Figure 3.7). Along with Kapuivik and Kaleruserk, Qalirusiq is one of the earliest known Tuniit sites in Amittuq, with the oldest Tuniit dwelling found at 52 MASL dated to cal. 3677-4398 BP (Meldgaard 1960b).

Qalirusiq was first surveyed by Meldgaard in the 1950s (1962;1965) and designated as NiHf-1. Meldgaard identified 115 archaeological features, including nine semisubterranean sod dwellings located between 17-20 MASL, and 85 boulder dwellings and 21 hearth features located between 37-51 MASL. Susan Rowley undertook surveys and excavations at NiHf-1 between 1990-1993 (1991a; 1991b; 1992; 2003). She divided the site into two Bordens, with NiHf-1 designating the Pre-Dorset (Early Tuniit) component and NiHf-47 the Dorset (Late Tuniit) component. Rowley identified 102 intact structural features at NiHf-1, and 21 at NiHf-47, but the known distribution of features is not formally reported (see Figure 2.3 of this dissertation and Figure 4.6 in Murray 1996, GNCH 2019).

Igloolik community members expressed concern during our conversations about the preservation of the site due to the expansion of the garbage dump and residential zones that border the lower features, as well as weathering, erosion, vehicle disturbance, and the expansion of the modern cemetery along the upper terraces. Several at-risk dwelling features were mentioned in

Figure 3.7 Qalirusiq study area showing extent of pedestrian and visible light RPA surveys.

Rowley's site report (1993), but local government officials were unable to determine where these features were located and whether they were still intact. As such, the primary goal of the 2019 fieldwork shifted to a comprehensive survey and heritage conservation assessment of the site on behalf of the community. Although this reduced our survey coverage, we were still able to sample a wide range of physiographic contexts including the borders of marshes and ponds, and wind-sheltered scree slopes (Figure 3.7).

While the distribution of previously identified features is unknown, Rowley's reports contain descriptions of the site boundaries for NiHf-1 and NiHf-47: the former defined as the area between two small lakes located at the summit of Qalirusiq (43-52 MASL), and the latter as a plateau (17-20 MASL) 1km southeast of NiHf-1. We resurveyed the total area within these site boundaries. Fourteen adjoining units were placed across NiHf-1 (units 1–8, 11, 13, and 27–30), and an additional five units were placed at the base of the scree slopes to determine if artifacts had eroded downhill and if intact features had been constructed along natural windbreaks. This included three units along the northern slope (units 14, 31, 32), two along the west slope (units 9 and 12), and one along the southern slope (unit 10). Five adjoining units were placed to cover the NiHf-47 plateau (units 15–19). We expanded our survey to include the placement of three units south of NiHf-47 along the 15-7 MASL terraces (units 20–22) to examine if lower density occupational remains could be identified amid the cover of historical and modern debris. Two additional units (24 and 26) were placed east of the modern garbage dump (20-12 MASL) for the same purposes.

As Qalirusiq is also the location of the historic and modern Igloolik cemeteries, the community was hesitant about the collection of artifacts and the possibility of excavation. We agreed to only collect informal artifacts (worked bone and lithic debitage) as well as faunal remains

for radiocarbon dating, during the 2019 field season. Formal artifacts were plotted and photographed, but left *in situ*. Exposed graves were not touched, plotted, or photographed. Consultation with the HTA and government officials post-field season led to an agreement for a follow-up field season centered on salvage excavations, but due to the COVID-19 pandemic this research was cancelled. As such, the pedestrian surveys were the exclusive means through which radiocarbon samples were collected from Qalirusiq, resulting in less chronological control than sites at Kapuivik and Alarniq.

3.3.3 Remotely Piloted Aircraft Survey

This section describes the RPA surveys conducted during the 2018 field season at Kapuivik and 2019 field seasons at Qalirusiq and Alarniq. I first describe the field methods for the RBG photogrammetry surveys, which were designed to capture high resolution imagery of pedestrian survey units and map the topography of the three study areas (Figures 3.5, 3.6, and 3.7). The RBG photogrammetry permitted the precise mapping of findspots and features, and the prospection of areas that could not be surveyed on foot, such as ponds and lakes. I then describe the thermal surveys undertaken at Kapuivik and Alarniq, which permitted the subsurface prospection of a sample of the pedestrian survey units, and which enhanced the documentation of unexcavated architectural elements. The evaluation facilitated an assessment of surface-subsurface feature visibility in the region, and the creation of detailed site maps.

3.3.1 Remotely Piloted Aircraft Prospection and Site Mapping. RBG imagery was captured using a Phantom 4 Pro (P4P) rotary wing quadcopter. The P4P was selected as it is lightweight and

easy to transport, is equipped with GPS and GLONASS, and comes outfitted with a 20 megapixel RGB camera that provides exceptional orthometric precision. The P4P was flown at 30m AGL with a GSD of 0.82cm/pixel for these captures, using a mix of manual techniques and automated flights facilitated by a mobile application (*Pix4Dcapture*). Flights were piloted and visualized on a P4P remote control with a 5.5" inch high-definition display.

RGB captures were compiled on the field laptop using Microsoft Image Composite Editor (ICE) and Pix4D (4.3) rapid processing features, to create orthographic mosaics of the land surface. The preliminary models helped identify subtle and uneven archaeological remains across the land that could then be evaluated through *in situ* observation. They were especially useful for identifying low-contrast features in areas with high visual noise, such as the detection of boulder features against a glacial till background comprised of similar boulders (Figure 3.8), and the slight depressions of semi-subterranean sod dwellings in heavily vegetated areas. In areas that could not be traversed on foot, such as marshes, RPA photogrammetry was the sole means of survey. For this reason, unwalkable features were passed over a second time with a manual flight at 10-15 AGL to enhance feature prospection, when weather permitted (Figure 3.9). Although unwalkable areas could not be ground-truthed, the identification of potential features permits the consideration of a wider ranger of site types, and as discussed in Chapter Five, points to a need for the further investigation of inundated spaces.

Post-field, RGB aerial captures were rendered into high resolution 2D orthomosaics and 3D digital elevation models (DEMs) in Drone2Map (2.2), which were then exported into a GIS (*ArcGIS Pro 3.2*) for further analyses. The orthomosaics enabled the georectification of vector datasets associated with findspots, features, and landscape elements (e.g., ponds, till deposits)

originally collected as GPS waypoints, allowing me to measure and map feature distributions with high precision and to identify new features through exploratory GIS analyses. These data provided an important baseline for examining variability in the location and structure of camp remains both within and between sites.

Figure 3.8 Examples of boulder cache (left) and dwelling (right) in a glacial till setting.

Figure 3.9 A) An inland survey area at Alarniq with B) a close-up RPA capture of a water feature.

3.3.2 *Thermal surveys.* A series of infrared (IR) thermographic surveys were performed on a small sample of pedestrian survey units at Kapuivik and Alarniq (Figures 3.5 and 3.6). IR thermography is an imaging science that involves the registration and visualization of electromagnetic wavelengths in the region of 7000 – 14,000 nm (Meola and Carlmagno 2004; Vollmer and Möllmann 2017). IR radiation is emitted, transmitted, and reflected by most substances on earth, and when IR radiation is visualized through a thermal sensor it can distinguish buried objects from surrounding soils. The heat signatures of subsurface objects surveys were used to identify buried and camouflaged archaeological features in the landscape. As the thermal imagery visualized subsurface anomalies, they were also used to examine the spatial extent and internal structure of previously identified structures that we did not have time to excavate.

The window for thermal data collection is narrow in arctic regions compared to the lower latitudes where most RPA thermal surveys have been conducted (Casana et al., 2014; Brooke, 2018; Levin et al., 2018; Poirier et al., 2013; Šedina et al., 2019; Thomas, 2018, see Fenger-Nielsen et al. 2019 for exception). The surveys took place in late July to mid-August when thermal contrasts were most pronounced during civil twilight (Figure 3.10, Comiso 1994; Woo 1986). As civil twilight periods were brief and volatile weather conditions regularly prevented RPA flights (Hanesiak and Wang, 2005; Shabbar and Bonsal, 2003), the surveys were reduced to three sample units: two at Kapuivik and one at Alarniq (Figures 3.5 and 3.6). These contexts represent the general variability in architectural remains and land surface cover among known Tuniit sites in Amittuq (Table 3.2).

Figure 3.10 The diurnal cycle on Igloolik Island, Nunavut, during July–August 2019. Twilight hours account for sunlight refraction, enhancing thermal contrasts (see Walker 2020).

Table 3.2 RPA thermal survey units at Kapuivik and Alarniq (see also Figures 3.5 and 3.6).

Thermal Survey Units	Area (m ²)	Dominant feature types	Surface properties
Unit 1 (Kapuivik)	355,098	Granite/gneiss boulder and sedimentary flagstone surface dwelling features	Moderate sod and peat surface layer (~3.5 cm) sandy loam substrate.
Unit 2 (Kapuivik)	229,965	Small (2-7m ²) semisubterranean dwelling features	Thick sod and peat surface layer (~10 cm), sandy loam substrate.
Unit 3 (Alarniq)	245,672	Large semisubterranean dwelling features (8-20m ²), granite/gneiss caches/meat pits	Pockets of moderate sod surface (~5 cm) on exposed gravel ridges, sandy substrate.

Analyzing the thermal imagery allowed me to evaluate the rate at which Tuniit sites were identifiable through pedestrian and visible light RPA surveys, as well as the land surface properties that impact the detection of archaeological features. This property-based evaluation (see Ebert 1992:37,52; Lewarch and O’Brien 1981: 299-300) enabled the assessment of whether the remains of most architectural features are superficially visible in coastal contexts (see Urban et al. 2016; Landry et al. 2020, Hodgetts et al. 2011 for other subsurface assessments in other regions). Amittuq’s coastlines are subject to windswept soils that prevent feature burial and vegetation

growth, which has likely contributed to the large number of identified coastal sites and the expectation of a shoreward-shifting settlement pattern (White et al. 2004). Alternatively, inland areas are more prone to feature burial due to the increased presence of solifluction lobes, thick arctic mosses, and rock-encrusting lichens (Arnold 1981; Todisco and Bhiry, 2008; Texier et al., 1998). Understanding the effects of visibility biases on pedestrian survey contextualized how representative legacy data are of the distribution of Tuniit sites in the region. The thermal surveys provided an effective means to meet this objective despite the time, labour, and equipment constraints that prevented extensive test pitting during the 2018 and 2019 field seasons.

The P4P was outfitted with a 3D-printed thermal camera platform for thermal surveys, as well as a 5000 mAh lithium battery and 2000 mW 5.8 Ghz long range video transmitter antenna (Figure 3.11). The modified platform allowed for a FLIR Vue Pro thermal camera (640 x 480, 13 mm) to be equipped in addition to the P4P RGB camera, enabling simultaneous RGB and thermal captures. This permitted the orthorectification of thermal images to compare differences in surface-subsurface visibility across survey zones. RGB imagery was visualized on the P4P remote control and IR imagery on a Flysight Black Pearl RC801 video monitor for in-field comparison and ground-truthing. As the addition of the thermal camera exceeded the P4P's maximum payload by 25%, pre-programmed flight paths were not reliable and the P4P was flown manually. For these reasons, the thermography flights were brief and took short-range weather forecasts and ground observations into consideration. Imagery was captured along 10–15 flight lines for each sampled zone, with the FLIR Vue Pro set on auto to image capture every 2 seconds. The image quality of thermal captures was assessed in-field through real-time video monitoring and ICE.

Figure 3.11 Modified RPA thermography system: A) P4P remote control with monitor, B) P4P rotary quadcopter with platform modifications, C) long-range thermal video transmitter antenna, D) thermal camera video monitor, E) FLIR Vue Pro, F) P4P RGB camera, G) Lithium Battery. *Reproduced from Walker 2020.*

The final thermal models were composited post-field using Exiftool (version 11.73) and Agisoft Metashape 1.5.5 (see Walker 2020 for workflow details). These models were then exported into ArcGIS Pro (3.0) and manually georectified with the RGB orthomosaics (*see Walker 2020a:4-5 for detailed workflow*). In addition to identifying several potential archaeological features, thermal imagery enabled preliminary structural analyses of multiple *in situ* contexts. Unfortunately, because effective thermal surveys could only be conducted near the end of both field seasons because of the diurnal cycle (Figure 3.10), we were unable to excavate newly identified features. However, because the surveys were visually monitored in real time, I was often able to ground truth thermal anomalies by carefully examining the ground surface for changes in vegetation and the shallow recesses of sod dwellings, and by feeling through padded mosses for buried boulders. These details were recorded in the field notebooks.

3.3.4 Excavations

My study employs architecture, artifacts, and ecofacts documented during excavations at Kapuivik and Alarniq as part of the FBA project. I discuss excavation objectives and sampling criteria in relation to my research problem, followed by an outline of the excavation procedures. I then provide details on the excavation fieldwork at Kapuivik and Alarniq. My personal objectives for the excavation work were to identify traces of patterned material relationships in the depositional contexts of dwellings and unwalled areas to draw inferences about household and camp level social relations and structures, and to document changing circumstances related to the seasonality, duration, and differential re-use of campsites. This offered new perspectives on persistence and change in community membership through various placemaking practices.

3.3.4.1. Excavation Objectives and Sampling Criteria. The excavations were designed to capture small-scale change in the material remains of dwellings and extramural settlement areas to understand how Tuniit camp communities were materially and socially configured over the course of each site's occupation (Figure 3.12). The excavation of dwellings served to document and analyze variability in house floors, dwelling walls, and internal architectural structures. This facilitated the reconstruction of dwelling extents and entrances, elucidating how people's homes were organized in relation to other dwellings and to extramural camp areas. As these arrangements would have structured daily encounters between households, their variability provides insight into the differentiation of community membership (Jervis 2022; Overholtzer 2012). The documentation of internal structures and features was also critical for identifying discrete occupational events. Tuniit dwellings, especially larger sod dwellings, are likely palimpsests of occupational practices over multiple seasons or generations (Dyke et al. 2019:78; McGhee 1997:210; Morrison 1999:140;

Habu and Savelle 1994). However, it is difficult to distinguish occupational episodes since a few decimetres in depth often represents a millennium or more of geomorphic deposition (Ledger and Forbes 2019:41). As discussed in section 3.4.2, careful attention to a latent stratigraphy in dwelling contexts — especially the superposition of activity features (e.g., meat platforms, lithic scatters) and overlaps in internal structures (e.g., lampstands, walls) — provide important information about the temporality and use of dwellings.

Figure 3.12 Distribution of excavation activities during the 2018 and 2019 field seasons.

The excavation of extramural spaces included areas outside dwelling entrances, external hearths, middens, and caches. The excavation of these features permitted the inference of communal practices evidenced by everyday objects such as hunting implements, faunal remains, butchering

tools, and sewing needles. This helped me draw inferences about the range of occupational activities that took place within and between camps. It also provided insight into how people from different times connected with one another through the maintenance, re-use, and modification of campsites over seasons and generations (Thatcher et al. 2017).

The excavation also permitted the recovery of faunal materials for radiocarbon dating, and for identifying seasonal practices. While arctic sites are often attributed to a single radiocarbon date (Friesen 2004:685), when multiple samples have been dated the results have significantly enhanced inferences of household practices and site reoccupations (Howse et al. 2019; Arundale 1981; McCullough 1989). Alternatively, the analysis of seasonally restricted faunal evidence (e.g., migratory birds, juvenile mammals) from both dwelling and extramural contexts provided insight into shorter term temporal trends (i.e., seasonality of camp use) and contextualized the affects of these practices in relation to a broader regional history of movement and land use.

3.3.4.2. Excavation Procedures. As mentioned, identifying specific occupational practices in Tuniit excavation contexts is made difficult as Tuniit dwellings are often palimpsests of multiple occupational episodes obscured by thin bioturbated contexts. However, recent research in northern Europe has demonstrated that a latent stratigraphy can be developed in bioturbated contexts by identifying the patterned migrations of cultural materials (Crombé et al. 2015; Crombé et al. 2019). In a similar vein, French archaeologists have employed the *décapage* approach to expose anthropic subdivisions within a stratigraphic deposit (Leroi-Gourhan 1984). In its application to the Arctic, the *décapage* approach demonstrates how slowing down excavations and recording the shared provenience of materials within a stratum can help elucidate discrete occupational events (Desrosiers 2018). However, the *décapage* approach involves a time and labour-intensive manual

technique that severely limits what can be excavated in an Arctic field season. As excavating entire dwellings was required to meet my research objectives, I opted instead to document anthropogenic subdivisions using a more extensive horizontal excavation method that employed high-resolution RPA photogrammetry to quickly plot and visualize internal features, while documenting subtle changes in the distribution of soils, rocks, and artifacts throughout the dwelling (see Howse 2017:36 *for proof-of-concept*).

Dwelling features were excavated using a 1m² local grid system that captured dwelling peripheries and extramural areas near dwelling entrances. Each feature grid was dug down in synchronous layers by trowel and screened using 3mm mesh, conserving artifacts, ecofacts, and independent soil subdivisions as much as possible so that they could be measured *in situ* (i.e., easting, northing, and depth below surface). The visual capture of depositional irregularities during my excavations with the P4P permitted the piece-plotting of multiple feature interfaces for post-field analyses, allowing for the interpretive components of the *décapage* methodology to be incorporated into a more labour-efficient excavation strategy. Essentially, the identification of broader *décap* surfaces served to further divide the O, A, and B soil horizons to assess anthropic activity structures based on superimposed cultural materials and subtle patterned differences in the distribution of artifacts and edaphic materials indicative of building and maintenance events (e.g., the patterning of loam pockets and lithic scatters to identify decayed sod walls). Extramural areas were also excavated using a 1m² local grid system, but individual 1x1m² test units were mapped and photographed manually. All artifacts and ecofacts that were collected from the sites have been catalogued and are described in the respective archaeological reports (Kotar 2019 and Walker 2020a and 2020b).

3.4.3 *Kapuivik Excavations*. Tuniit dwellings at Kapuivik range from 2.3 m² to 48 m² (Savelle et al. 2009:227) and include diverse structural elements such as box hearths, lamp stands, entrance lobes, midpassages, and sleeping platforms that convey different sets of possibilities about the nature and organization of domestic practices. My sampling strategy aimed to evaluate the range of occupational practices that this variability embodies by sampling surface dwellings and extramural areas from three site areas: 223, 222, and 205 (Figure 3.13). I focused my excavations on surface dwellings for three reasons. First, semi-subterranean dwellings are only found below 22 MASL while surface dwellings are present throughout the site, allowing me to document variability in the size and structure of camps throughout the entire occupational sequence. Second, although surface dwellings are often inferred as ephemeral warm weather occupations (Maxwell 1985:52; Murray 1999:468; Ryan 2003; Savelle et al. 2009), the variability in their size and structure at Kapuivik suggests that they served a wide range of functions, including snow houses and inter-seasonal camps for extended families (Savelle et al. 2009:228). Comparing architectural and artifactual evidence for specific occupational practices (e.g., sewing, hunting, fishing) from these dwellings therefore provided insight into the differentiation of camping practices and land use. Finally, the 2016 FBA excavations at Kapuivik (Desrosiers 2018) focused on several semi-subterranean dwellings and as such offer important data on this dwelling type for comparison.

To understand how settlements at Kapuivik were initially occupied and subsequently differentiated through community practices, the 2018 excavations targeted dwelling features along the upper terraces of the site. These features provided the best opportunity to document evidence for the recurring occupation and maintenance of ancestral camps since land in this area has been exposed the longest. As such, nine dwellings located in the 223 site area were excavated, including three along the 52-42 MASL terraces where the earliest known Tuniit occupations were previously

Figure 3.13 A comparison of excavation activities at Kapuvik during the 2016 and 2018 FBA field seasons.

identified, and six dwellings located at 38-31 MASL (c. 3300-3000 BP) where dwelling frequencies are at their highest within the main site sequence.

Five dwellings were also excavated along the terraces associated with Meldgaard's (1960b; 1962) "Pre-Dorset to Dorset" cultural transition (Figure 3.12). Examining material variation in these areas provided insight into changing occupational practices at the site and helped me evaluate whether architectural differences classified as "Pre-Dorset" and "Dorset" in Meldgaard's reports were as pronounced as originally hypothesized. These excavations included four dwellings in area 222 (28-26 MASL) where low but relatively stable occupations have been attributed to "terminal Pre-Dorset". It also included a dwelling located in area 205 (24-22 MASL), where a small increase in feature density has been inferred as the arrival of "Early Dorset" peoples (c.2500) in the traditional culture history (Savelle and Dyke 2014). The excavation of the surface dwelling in area 205 was especially significant since other features in this location are semi-subterranean dwellings. Comparing my excavation data with Desrosiers' 2016 excavations of nearby sod features presented an opportunity to assess whether these dwellings were contemporaneous or instead products of multiple, seasonally discrete occupational episodes (Figure 3.13).

While extramural activity contexts are critical data for reconstructing place-community relations, the 2018 excavations focused on dwelling contexts. This was a deliberate decision, as the 2016 FBA fieldwork had already resulted in over 75 m² of arbitrary test pits for the interpretation of extramural contexts in the 222, 205, and 204 site areas (Figure 3.13). To supplement the 2016 test pit data, additional extramural areas were investigated in 2018 through the excavation of a midden, an external hearth, and two boulder cache features along the higher terraces at the site (Figure 3.12, see Desrosiers 2018 for test pit details). As caches provide an enhanced measure of food security

(Desjardins 2017) and are indicative of an intent to return to a particular camp (Friesen 2002; IE004; IE017; IE022; Stewart 2000), their excavation helped to infer longer-term and recurring occupational practices. In addition, our 2018 excavations included the placement of twelve 1x1m² test units in extramural areas where communal activities such as animal butchering and tool-making were expected to have occurred between dwellings (LeMoine 2003; Thatcher et al. 2017). Two test units were also placed at the periphery of a previously excavated large sod dwelling (205-Feature 1) to identify extramural practices (Meldgaard 1954b; 1962). Faunal analyses of the 2018 excavated materials were conducted by Kathryn Kotar, and lithic and organic artifacts were analyzed by Kyle Forsythe.

3.3.4.4 Alarniq Excavations. The excavation design in 2019 similarly targeted a wide array of architectural elements and extramural areas to capture small-scale differences in the structure and organization of campsites, focusing on areas where previously excavation work had not been concentrated (Howse 2015, 2017). This included the excavation of a large semi-subterranean feature at 25-24 MASL, two boulder surface dwellings located at 21-20 MASL, a semi-subterranean sod dwelling at 14.5 MASL, as well as the placement of fourteen non-arbitrary 1x1m² test units to sample extramural camp areas (Figure 3.14).

The dwelling at 25-24 MASL (NhHd-11, Feature 18) was selected because it was an exceptionally large and amorphous sod patch that was significantly different in its structure from other sod features located at the site and elsewhere in the region. As radiocarbon assays obtained from this site area in 2017 had demonstrated the earliest evidence of Tuniit occupation at Alarniq (2705-2349 cal. BP) as well as much a later occupation event (971-925 cal. BP), excavating this unique feature presented an opportunity to examine multiple construction phases and occupational

Figure 3.14 Excavation activities at Alarniq during the 2015, 2017, and 2019 field seasons.

activities. Seven 1x1m² non-arbitrary test units were placed in this camp area in much smaller, irregularly shaped sod patches to document open-air activities capable of altering soil composition and creating sod cover, such as animal butchering and hide tanning.

The two dwellings excavated at 21-20 MASL (NhHd-16, Features 3 and 7) were boulder surface features that were comparable in size and shape to those found in the 222-site area at Kapuivik. While Alarniq has been described primarily as a cold weather settlement due to its semi-subterranean dwelling features, the presence of seven surface dwellings of unknown origin at NhHd-16 suggests that warm season occupational activities may have also taken place at the site (see Section 2.2.4). Excavating these features allowed me to assess whether they were dwelling or storage features, to confirm if their material culture was indicative of Tuniit or Inuit communities, and to examine how campsite structure may have changed as part of shifting seasonal activities at Alarniq.

We selected the dwelling 14.5 MASL for excavation (NhHe-12, Feature 4) as campsites at this elevation were correlated with an inferred “boom” in occupational density that had not been confirmed through radiocarbon dating (Figure 3.14, see Savelle and Dyke 2014). Obtaining radiocarbon samples was especially important as the most recent set of assays obtained in 2017 demonstrated that several features located between 15 and 24 MASL at Alarniq were all generally the same age (Howse et al. 2018:543). Understanding the spatial structure and temporality of this dwelling was important for determining if the reoccupation of campsites in this area had contributed to the temporal overlap recognized by Howse. Three 1x1m² test units were placed nearby to verify dwellings identified through the pedestrian surveys. An additional four test units were placed along the beach sequence near previously excavated features (Meldgaard 1962) to examine extramural

areas and refine the radiocarbon sequence. Test units were not placed near cairns speculated to be graves, although we anticipate that that most are likely caches (e.g., NhHd-11 and NhHd-19)

3.3.5 Radiocarbon Analysis

The recovery of organic materials through survey and excavation was essential for expanding each site's radiocarbon sequence. This was a critical aspect of the project given the interpretive problems associated with beach ridge archaeology (see Chapter Two, Section 2.1.6). My analysis consists of 144 radiocarbon dates³⁰ obtained from terrestrial and marine mammal bone samples, including 17 new dates from Qalirusiq, 17 from Kapuivik, and 25 from Alarniq. I used the INTCAL20 calibration curve (Reimer et al. 2020) for terrestrial herbivore faunal samples. As INTCAL20 includes a sharper cliff at 2600 cal. BP, it was especially useful for reinterpreting ¹⁴C dates traditionally associated with “Early Dorset” (Table 2.1) – a period often inferred as a time of radical change in technology and socioeconomic organization (see Chapter Two, Section 2.2.2).

The MARINE20 curve (Heaton et al. 2020) was used to calibrate walrus samples. Although marine reservoir effects are difficult to account for in individual circumstances, many Arctic sites do not contain terrestrial faunal remains and so dating marine samples is often necessary. However, the FBA project is uniquely positioned for this purpose as project directors James Savelle and Arthur Dyke have developed a more precise local reservoir calibration for non-migrating Atlantic walrus in Amittuq (Dyke et al. 2019). I calibrated walrus ¹⁴C samples using Dyke et al.'s (2019) 160 ± 50 delta offset value as a secondary, supportive method of temporal analysis for my broader interpretive conclusions about each site's occupational history.

³⁰ The majority of which are AMS dates, with radiometric dates specified during analysis.

The new dates facilitated inferences of site contemporaneity and multiple occupational phases in deflated contexts, and helped refine relative sea level curves used to paleotopographic models. The increased temporal resolution offered by the radiocarbon dates allowed me to explore how occupational events and topographic change corresponded during the Tuniit Period. This provided deeper insight into how Tuniit peoples likely moved between places in the landscape and, in turn, the shifting sociospatial connections between camp communities within the region.

3.4 Paleogeographic Research Component

The paleogeographic component involved the modelling and analysis of Amittuq's paleoenvironment. I first outline the data and methods used to produce isostatic regression models spanning from 5000 BP to 500 BP. I then describe how these models were combined with historical ecological data in a GIS to visualize and interpret local environmental dynamics. As changing landforms present different sets of potentials for how humans, animals, and materials encounter one another in the landscape, they are important participants in the formation of more-than-human communities (Barad 2017; Tilley 2016; Watts 2016). I compare paleotopographic models with distributions of archaeological features, with that caveat that these features represent complex temporalities. When analyzed alongside excavation data and radiocarbon dates, the models serve as valuable interpretive aids for exploring how Tuniit communities might have moved between and encountered different places in the landscape. They also provide evidence for local topographic diversity that challenges interpretive assumptions of a uniform coastal environment — one of the conceptual foundations of the “core area” framework.

3.4.1 Paleotopographic Modelling. Topographic change is one of the most informative measures of paleoenvironmental difference, especially in a postglacial arctic setting. Topography informs how freshwater drains and vegetation grows, as well as where people and animals can travel and what they can see as part of the landscape (Brughmans et al. 2018; Dyke 1996; Stewart et al. 2014; Van Dyke 2019). While using beach ridge chronologies to relatively date archaeological contexts may be problematic (see Chapter Two, Section 2.1.6), understanding coastal transformation offers some chronological control by providing the earliest possible age for features (e.g., when land exposure occurred), and provides insights into the spatial setting of Tuniit occupational activities.

Three independent sets of data were required to model the postglacial topographic transformation of Amittuq: a) a digital elevation model (DEM) of the modern land surface; b) postglacial isobase data to measure isostatic change; and c) relative sea level (RSL) curves to adjust the marine limit for each model. The modern DEM was produced using elevation data from the RPA surveys. The RPA elevation data facilitated the refinement of orthometric heights for landscape features across the study sites that were originally established using optical measuring devices (Mathiassen 1933; Soper 1930) and altimeter readings calibrated to local high-tide kelp lines ³¹ (Savelle and Dyke 2014). The local RPA data was interpolated with a regional topobathy DEM derived from RCAN's raster series. As RCAN is based on the Canadian Geodetic Vertical Datum (CGVD2013), this allowed for all elevation values to be calibrated to mean sea level, resulting in a high resolution, uniform DEM that provided a contemporary baseline for calculating isostatic adjustments for different time periods.

³¹ High tide lines are a good correlate for coastal settlement as they reflect the terrace closest to the shoreline that could actually be occupied at a given time. However, as my results demonstrate, relic tide lines are not always obvious and not all Tuniit occupations took place on strandlines.

Postglacial isobase data was provided by the Canadian Geological Survey (CGS). Isobases are map contours that portray the relative morphometry of time-equivalent topographic deformation, in this case deformation resulting from postglacial unloading and gravitational effects (Andrews 1970; Clark 1976). The isobase files were produced by Arthur Dyke, a lead of FBA project, using the exponential equation outlined in Dyke and Peltier (2000). This calculation was applied to elevation plots belonging to radiocarbon dated marine deposits located along strandlines (i.e., geological, not cultural, contexts), using the altimeter method described above (Dyke and Peltier 2000; Savelle and Dyke 2014). The isobase files obtained from the CGS each represent a 500-year interval beginning with 5000 BP and ending with 500 BP. The isobase files were imported into the GIS as vector shapefiles and transformed into raster formats using the inverse distance weighted interpolation method. The resulting models were resampled to the modern DEM resolution (2m^2) using a bilinear resampling method. This produced continuous isobase surfaces that accounted for directional isostatic adjustment throughout the study region. The isobase surfaces were subtracted from the modern DEM using the raster calculator tool in ArcGIS Pro, to produce bare earth isostatic regression models.

The final process involved the adjustment of relative sea levels for each time-slice model. Ancient marine limits were established from RSL curves calculated by Savelle and Dyke (2014). The RSL curves were derived from multiple beach ridge sequences with associated radiometric and AMS dates recovered primarily from geological contexts. The RSL curves were further refined through my radiocarbon analysis and through the calculation of orthometric heights for relevant features and sites, and comparisons with radiocarbon dates from cultural contexts. The analysis of new radiocarbon dates and recalibration of previous assays allowed me to develop more consistent marine limits for beach ridges between the study sites. Part of this refinement involved, where

possible, the removal of dates recovered from semi-subterranean dwellings, which were more often associated with multiple, overlapping occupational phases. My refinement focused on dates recovered from ephemeral surface dwellings associated with winter occupational contexts, as these yielded significantly earlier dates in site areas with mixed architectural feature types, and were often consistent with Savelle and Dyke's (2014) beach ridge sequences (see Chapters Five-Seven). I also removed dates from features where previously calculated elevations differed substantially from the orthorectified DEM. The earliest dates in shared elevation ranges between the sites were compared and averaged, and this value was used as a parameter against existing RSL data to refine marine limits. The bare earth DEMs were "flooded" using the conditional function in the raster calculator tool in ArcGIS Pro by coding presence and absence values for marine submergence based on the new marine limits for each time-slice (e.g., for a marine limit of 15 MASL at 3000 BP, the function was $\text{Con}(\text{DEM}_{3000} < 15, 1, 0)$). This resulted in predictive models that visualized both topography and sea level changes for 500-year intervals.

3.5 Conclusion

This chapter has outlined how a difference-oriented, multimethod approach can enhance how archaeological landscapes are observed and analyzed. As participants in the histories we reconstruct, archaeologists have a responsibility in how the research process differentiates what can be imagined about the past, and in turn, what can be observed in the present (Barad 2007; Jervis 2018). This requires careful attention to the material configurations that emerge through not only how we interpret archaeological remains, but the questions we ask, literatures we draw on, and lines of historic evidence (e.g., legacy data, oral histories) we deem as relevant to archaeological inquiry

(Deleuze and Guattari 1988:372; Haraway 1997:273; Wylie 2002:xiv). By bringing landscape data from disparate sources into conversation with one another, the methodology presented herein opens archaeological research to productively agonistic sets of historical evidence that provide new possibilities about people-place relations during the Tuniiit Period. The analysis of these diverse datasets in the following four results chapters, beginning with an in-depth analysis of Amitturmiut knowledge and history, will further demonstrate how a relational, posthumanist archaeology of place operates towards new mappings of peoples, landscapes, and history.

Chapter Four

Mapping the Tuniit Landscape through Amitturmiut Oral History

To hold alternative histories is to hold alternative knowledges — Linda Tuhiwai Smith (2012:34)

Tuniit peoples are often investigated through the scope of Western values and ideas. In Amittuq, this work has involved approaching persistent settlement places as type-sites — that is, as “stairways of history” (see Howse 2019:533, Odgaard 2015) upon which predefined archaeological cultures and developmental stage types were repeatedly inscribed (see Chapter Two). By presenting persistent places as static archives, archaeological research has tended to neglect their role as sites of living history, as well as the entangled occupational histories of Late Tuniit and ancestral Inuit people that are important features of Amitturmiut memory and identity (Bennett and Rowley 2004; Friesen 2019; Friesen et al. 2022; Martin 2009; Rachel Qitsualik-Tinsley 2015; cf. Basso 1996). The distancing of contemporary Inuit communities from the Tuniit archaeological landscape marginalizes Inuit Qaujimajatuqangit (*epistemology and knowledge*) and restricts opportunities for meaningful collaboration (Saimaqatigiingniq) (see Atalay 2016; Birch 2022; Hodgetts and Kelvin 2020; Schnieder and Heyes 2020; Supernant 2022; Watts 2016 for supportive arguments and solutions). Through the analysis of Amitturmiut oral history and the personal accounts of Knowledge Holders, this chapter proposes that Tuniit communities were not predetermined by unforgiving environments or overarching cultural norms. Instead, the study offers historically situated expectations for how organizational structures, social identities, and knowledge systems were repeatedly articulated through everyday relations at multiple scales.

I follow Watts’ (2016:7) recommendations for collaborative research by approaching

persistent places as sites of material knowledge production, and Inuit stories as locatable, inherited expressions of these places (see also Barad 2007; Haraway 1997). Inuit are deeply bound to Nuna (*the land*) and acknowledge the agency of Nuna in shaping what is knowable, contributing to the importance of place-based learning and identities within Inuit communities (Price 2008; QIA 2010; Qitsualik 2008, 2013; Tagalik et al. 2023). Amitturmiut oral histories have materialized through encounters with Nuna and stand as an important knowledge source for rethinking how places might have shaped, and been shaped by, encounters with people in earlier periods. I place Amitturmiut oral history in dialogue with the Tuniit archaeological record not to create false equivalences (cf. Friesen 2002; Hood 1998; McGhee 1996), but to recognize resonances and differences that assist in identifying lesser-recognized archaeological features (e.g., various cache types), and for building richer interpretive conclusions about how daily placemaking practice contributed to the emergence of social differences at the scales of the household and camp community (Garrouette & Westcott 2013; Kirby 2017; Marshall 2021, Watts 2016; Whitridge 2016).

Central to my analysis is the idea that people and places have both virtual and actual capacities, and that these capacities are equally important to consider when reconstructing past landscapes (Barad 2007; Crellin 2020; Harris 2021a; Jervis 2018). The virtual refers to the historically situated potentials of different entities to emerge and act, while the actual refers to how these potentials were (or were not) exercised in a given moment (e.g., archaeological context) (Barad 2015, 2017; Braidotti 2017). Investigating how the properties and potentials of places were actualized through Amitturmiut occupational practices facilitates the development of locally situated interpretations of Tuniit material culture, such as a clearer understanding of the complex practices necessary to construct sod dwellings. Conversely, exploring the virtual

contextualizes possibilities for how moments of placemaking could inform future community relations, such as how the decay of sod bricks necessitates their annual dismantlement, reframing their intergenerational reuse as a labour-intensive and meaningful tradition (Conneller 2012; Cipolla et al. 2021; Crellin et al. 2021a; Jervis 2022).

Amitturmiut oral history details how Inuit have engaged with many of the same places that Tuniit occupied, including Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq (Robinson 2021). Amitturmiut testimonies demonstrate how persistent places were materially differentiated through everyday practices and how bodily experiences and generational knowledge affected land use and movement (Barad 2003; Haraway 1997; Massey 2005; TallBear 2015). Amitturmiut oral history also offers important information about past environments that are difficult to access through radiocarbon sequencing and geological proxy data, such as how changing sea ice patterns impacted nearshore environments. This offers new perspectives on local material affordances, permitting inferences of the kinds of occupational practices that were possible during particular time spans, contextualizing archaeological evidence for how people strategically and meaningfully managed their landscape.

I explore three components of Amitturmiut oral history that provide actionable information about the material and spatial patterning of the archaeological landscape, and that together permit the development of a cohesive narrative of place-community relations in Amittuq. These include 1) Amitturmiut stories about Late Tuniit social lives and economic practices as observed by ancestral Inuit, 2) stories about ancestral Inuit settlement practices and engagements with the landscape, and 3) the individual experiences of Elders who repeatedly encountered persistent settlement places while growing up on the land prior to forced relocation

programs. My assessment involves the qualitative and spatial analysis of testimonies from the Igloolik Oral History Project (OHP) and my own interviews, as well as from secondary sources produced by or with Inuit cultural authorities (Aporta 2003; Bennett and Rowley 2004; QIA 2010). Through these lines of historical data, I identify occupational practices that challenge prior models of settlement, subsistence, and sociality in Amittuq, and map together less tangible elements of community practices, such as Inuit perceptions of social belonging and history, that are important for building social interpretations of Tuniit placemaking.

This study offers a series of analytical and interpretive interventions for my archaeological investigations presented in Chapters Five, Six, and Seven. First, Amitturmiut stories outline the dynamic and varied nature of Tuniit occupational practices, suggesting that the study areas (Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq) represent a diverse array of occupational activities rather than timeless settlement traditions (e.g., winter occupations along outer seacoasts). In particular, the research highlights the importance of caching practices in facilitating food security and community cooperation, which often took place in elevated areas inland from coastal settlements. Amitturmiut stories about the complex sets of knowledge and practice necessary for successful food caching suggest how the construction and repeated use of Tuniit caches may have served as important mechanisms for community memory and perceptions of history, reinforcing the interconnectedness of individuals, camps, and broader communities. Knowledge Holders also describe caching practices for equipment storage as part of the seasonal settlement round, providing an important archaeological correlate for Tuniit movement and mobility. More generally, the results underline the importance of surveying underrepresented inland contexts, and prioritizing the study of low-density extramural areas to infer small-scale diversity in land use and reoccupation practices.

Second, Amitturmiut stories offer a deeper comprehension of how changing coastal topographies may have affected the movements and interactions of camp communities during the Tuniit Period. Specifically, the results suggest how the perceived spatial (and social) proximity of ancestral and more recent Inuit camps was informed by the patterning and availability of sea ice, which conditioned possibilities for travel between coastal settlements. Oral stories of Tuniit peoples suggest that dispersed winter camps may have frequently come together in communal practices like floe-edge hunting, while warmer weather camps located within closer proximity to one another may have had more limited social interactions, given the absence of boat technologies during the Tuniit Period. Amitturmiut Knowledge Holders also recount people living in shared camps, and the critical role these encounters played in how local community relationships were formed and negotiated, regardless of blood ties. These interhousehold relations point to the importance of everyday relationships in redefining social identities within a dynamic and heterogeneous landscape, and how local organizational structures and broader community identities may have been repeatedly shaped by the specific material and historical contexts of each settlement place.

Third, the personal experiences of Elders and stories of historic practices passed down to younger generations highlight that social connections between the study sites were maintained through wider assemblages of movement, knowledge, and practice during the Early and Historic Inuit periods. This suggests that local occupational sequences in Amittuq are better assessed in relation to one another, rather than as discrete, isolated contexts. While Qalirusiq, Kapuivik, and Alarniq are often framed as type-sites that represent regional cultural entities, the research presents a different picture of their affects and relations. Encounters with each place were shaped by social connections between local and translocal camp communities, and a wide range of

places that could be reached in less than a day's travel. These include the breeding, feeding, and basking grounds of seal and walrus, caribou hunting grounds, egg collecting spots, small game traps, fishing locales, tool stone outcrops, and places of personal attachment such as birth places and graves. The settlement places also served as landmarks and outposts on established travel routes to more distant places, and feature prominently in navigation stories and memories of historic events. Amitturmiut testimonies indicate that diverse, repeated encounters with persistent places not only facilitated economic partnerships between families, but that the co-presence of people on shared land, or *nunaqatigiit*, fostered a sense of co-belonging, so that even those who briefly visited a camp were considered *ila (kin)* and *-miut (of that place)* for the duration of their stay, regardless of blood relation (see Nuttal 1992:83).

These dynamic relations indicate that persistent places were active participants in the ongoing negotiation of Amitturmiut community membership on a local scale, and offer new perspectives on the fluidity and flexibility of ancestral Inuit social structures and the role of historically situated places in shaping these relations. To explore these possibilities in the context of Tuniit communities, I assess the archaeological patterning of Tuniit architecture and artifacts at the scales of the household and camp in combination with radiocarbon sequencing and exploratory GIS analysis, to draw richer interpretive conclusions about local diversity in organizational strategies and the broader accessibility and connectivity of settlement places in different periods (e.g., the Early Tuniit and Late Tuniit periods). This includes the examination of previously undocumented Tuniit sites identified through my interviews and the oral history archives, and the comparison of site location data against broader paleogeographic models that trace the topographic transformation of Amittuq as a whole.

In the first section of this chapter, I examine themes and patterns present in Amitturmiut stories about Tuniit, which I execute through qualitative content analysis in *NVivo 14*. I discuss how Late Tuniit peoples are remembered by Amitturmiut, and present a deeper understanding of what Tuniit material culture embodies about their social lives and daily practices. My analysis is guided by a word cloud that visualizes the 100 most frequent terms referenced in Amitturmiut stories about Tuniit. The word cloud provides insight into recurring ideas and sentiments shared by storytellers. Amitturmiut stories present a common narrative of Tuniit as flexible and resilient peoples who participated in a greater variety of occupational practices than regional archaeological studies have accounted for (cf. Howse et al. 2019; Meldgaard 1962; Savelle et al. 2009). In doing so, these stories offer explanation for lesser-studied archaeological correlates, such as the different kinds of caches constructed by Tuniit and their relevance for inferring economic practices, residential duration, and episodes of reoccupation. They also demonstrate how Tuniit places, and the stories they hold, continue to matter by affirming Amitturmiut identity and land stewardship through a deep history that extends beyond the Early Inuit period. Acknowledging the affective capacities of persistent places as story holders permits an exploration of the virtual capacities that Early Tuniit places possessed to shape how later Tuniit occupants experienced their landscape and, in turn, how they interacted with ancestral places.

In the second section, I provide qualitative and spatial assessments of Amitturmiut occupational practices recalled within the OHP that are relevant to reconstructing the daily lives, movements, and interactions of Tuniit camp communities. I explore how Amitturmiut camp communities were created, maintained, and altered through repeated encounters and enduring relations with particular settlement places and traditional travel routes. The ethnohistoric narrative I develop in this section is supported and expanded through an exploratory analysis of

Amitturmiut places in the GIS (*ArcMap10.8*). I interrogate spatial relationships between settlements and travel routes discussed in the oral testimonies. These data are explored in conjunction with secondary data sources to further contextualize spatial patterns and temporal trends in land use (Aporta 2003; Bennett and Rowley 2004; IT Kanatami 2007; Pauktuutit 2006; QIA 2010). Exploring temporal land use trends facilitated new expectations about how Tuniit occupational practices may have connected people, animals, and materials in enduring community relationships. The chapter ends with a discussion of how the virtuality of the Amitturmiut landscape informs my investigation of Tuniit occupational history through the examination of Tuniit campsite remains at Kapuivik Qalirusiq and Alarniq (the subjects of Chapters Five, Six, and Seven, respectively).

4.1 An Examination of Late Tuniit Peoples in Amitturmiut Oral History

In this section, I examine how Tuniit are remembered by Amitturmiut, and how archaeological places help to locate these stories and affirm local knowledge of the past. Tuniit figure in nineteen oral testimonies from the OHP database, most of which recount events observed by Inuit ancestors. I analyze these testimonies alongside my four interviews with Amitturmiut Elders, guided by a word cloud derived from the testimonies (Figure 4.1). I consider the role of Tuniit places, and the stories they embody, as living histories that continue to matter as part of the Amitturmiut homeland. The anchoring of Amitturmiut stories through Tuniit materialities helps to affirm community memories and strengthen a shared community identity by emphasizing the differences between the two peoples (cf. Martin 2009). In discussing the performative nature of archaeological remains in Amittuq, I suggest how traces of early Tuniit

occupants may have affected the perceptions and experiences of later inhabitants as they, like Inuit, repeatedly encountered persistent places.

Figure 4.1 The top 100 words referenced in Tuniit stories; word size reflects relative frequency.

1) Anngmaaq: “Flint”, Aivilik form (south of Amittuq); 2) Kilu: Back lobe of Inuit tent (absent on Tuniit dwellings); 3) Kukiksait: “Flint”, Mittimatalik form (north of Amittuq); 4) Tunijjuat: Big Tuniit; 5) Tun(n)ijjuaq: Big Tuniq (sing.)

I then present a reconstruction of the everyday practices of Tuniit as embodied through Amitturmiut stories, and examine archaeological correlates for these activities. My assessment reveals important nuances in how Tuniit are characterized by Amitturmiut compared to the

legends summarized by early ethnographers (Boas 1888; Rasmussen 1925) and archaeologists (Mary-Rousselière 1955; Meldgaard 1954a). Most notably, Amitturmiut stories describe a wide range of Tuniit settlement practices, including some not often recognized archaeologically at sites in Amittuq, like fishing practices or the construction of caches and landmarks. These stories mention places where material evidence of these practices can be found, including several places which have not been surveyed by archaeologists. As such, these stories offer an epistemological framework for identifying and interpreting underrepresented Tuniit site types, and contribute to historically contingent interpretations of the broader settlement landscape.

4.1.1 The Place of Tuniit in Amitturmiut History

Inuit are diverse groups of people united by language, customs, and beliefs, as well as by oral traditions that include stories about Tuniit. While some Inuit communities see Tuniit stories as myths about supernatural beings (Inuit Tapiriit Kanatami 2004:7; Kleivan 1996; Vebæk 1965; Rasmussen 1925:19; Sonne 2005), others, such as the Amitturmiut, see the Tuniit as historic people. As one Amitturmiut Elder (KH01) explains, although the Tuniit were real people, once a story becomes *qaujimajatuqangat* (*old knowledge*) it typically also becomes *unikkaaqtuat* (*a myth*). Amitturmiut understand this and try to take *unikkaaqtuat* as truth, to take it as *qaujimajangit* (*what Inuit know*). It is for this reason, the Elder suggests, that the retelling of Tuniit stories in Amittuq are often accompanied by references to archaeological materials. Amitturmiut know that Tuniit once lived in Igloodik in part because of their stories and in part because of the dwelling remains located on relic beach terraces above the dwellings of their own ancestors (KH01, cf. IE710). The name Igloodik (*there is a house there*) is in fact a reference to

the old houses that cover the island, which were once occupied by Tuniit and Early Inuit (QIA 2014:12, cf. IE329; IE708).

While some Amitturmiut stories portray Tuniit as peculiar and unintelligent, most describe them as skilled people that participated in a wide range of social and economic practices, and who had intimate knowledge of their land. In fact, one possible origin for “Tuniit” is the Inuktitut word “tuniguk” (to give), referring to the knowledge the Tuniit bestowed to Inuit (Qitsualik-Tinsley and Qitsualik-Tinsley 2015:2). This is supported by the similarity of “Tunijjuat” (*Big Tuniit*) to “Tunijjuti” (*gift given to a spirit*), a term from the Inuit shamanic language, Tarriummak (Rachel Qitsualik-Tinsley, personal communication, 2020). The portrayal of Tuniit as gift givers is a common sentiment among Amitturmiut; Tuniit discovered important hunting and fishing places, located raw material deposits, and marked safe travel routes with inuksugait (Bennett and Rowley 2004:143; IE194; IE249; Mathiassen 1927:187; KH01; KH04).

In some respects, the Tuniit are presented as similar to Inuit: they hunted many of the same animals, moved between the same places, and convened with some of the same spiritual forces (KH01; IE249). As such, Tuniit stories preserve knowledge of traditional Arctic lifeways:

It is very important that the Tuniit lived here a very long time ago and are not likely to return, it is important to pass on the knowledge of their capabilities and their ways of doing things. It is important that their skills be honoured because these are skills no one has anymore. (KH03)

In other respects, Tuniit were markedly different from Inuit: they had fewer camps and smaller populations, they did not have boats or dogs, they often hunted alone, and, while they had greater physical abilities than Inuit, they were also painfully shy and easily frightened:

They were fast runners and could hunt on their own successfully... what is said of them was that they rather do things on their own always hunting without a company of others. (IE246)

I would think that when they were only with their wife their tents were small because it was difficult to get their tent material...you still can see their old (VOC) QARMAT [sod house] in some areas.... It is said that they scare easily so they were led to flee away which also happened in Quebec...

It is said that they were humble people that did not like to get into conflict with INUIT even when they lived in the same camp...(IE249)

These stories serve as foils that amplify the qualities and abilities that are central to how Amitturmiut see their ancestors: Early Inuit were not as strong, but they were more innovative; they were not as gentle, but they were more courageous and assertive (KH01; KH03). The emphasis on Tuniit as lone hunters appears to be the most significant contrast. Early Inuit organized themselves into large hunting parties and depended on the sharing of resources to ensure food security and the well-being of the community:

Whenever the conditions were right to hunt walrus, the [Inuit]hunters would go on to the moving ice and there would be different groups of hunting parties to ensure that a game will be caught that day. So when the hunters returned there would be those that were successful and there would be those that did not catch anything that day, and there were those that had to stay at the camp that day, but everyone benefited when one of the hunting parties was successful, all would get a piece of meat for their cooking pots this day. (IE189, cr. IE025)

The suggested sentiment underlying these stories appears to be that the extinction of Tuniit and survival of Inuit are tied to differences in their social structure and traditions, rather than simply their technologies as archaeological studies frequently posit (Maxwell 1985; Hood 1998).

The similarities and differences that Amitturmiut share with Tuniit are reaffirmed through material encounters in the landscape: Tuniit places capture material details present in traditional stories and evoke community memories. For example, while Tuniit are often described by Inuit as short and stout (sometimes as “dwarves”) in published sources (Bentley and Rowley 2004; Boas 1888; Hodgetts and Wells 2016; Gadoua 2016; Mary-Rousselière 1955; Meldgaard 1954a; Rasmussen 1927; Sonne 2015), twelve Amitturmiut testimonies use of the

term “Tunijjuat” (translated as “big” or “giant” Tuniit) as a common descriptor (cf. Figure 4.1). There are, however, two testimonies that refer to shapeshifting dwarves called Inugarulligaarjuit as the builders of cairns that others attribute to Tuniit (IE486; IE710). When asked about this connection, one Elder (KH02) offered that Tunijjuat and Inugarulligaarjuit stories may have become crossed due to the juxtaposition of the miniature tools and enormous boulder caches built by Tuniit— Inuit encounter both on the land and, when considered together, they convey that the Tuniit may have been shapeshifters (Figure 4.2). This shows how affective encounters with material remains have both affirmed and shaped local community memories (Ahmed 2004). KH02 clarified that Inugarulligaarjuit rock piles are different from Tuniit cairns. The Tuniit, he insists, were tall with a similar build to polar bears (cf. IE246; IE249).

Figure 4.2 A comparison between a Tuniit miniature harpoon head from Alarniq (left) and a boulder cache from Qalirusiq (right).

Tuniit stories also preserve knowledge of places and can serve as a means to identify distinctive

landmarks and find one's bearings. For instance, local legends about Ualinaaq, where the Tuniit were murdered by a neighbouring Inuit camp before the survivors fled west (IE272; IE384), are embodied through the broken edge of a tall cliff³². This broken cliff continues to serve as an important navigational landmark for Amitturmiut hunters:

Inuit had begun to realize that the Tuniit were formidable and had gotten scared... But because the Tuniit had love for the Inuit, they left of their own accord... before they were displaced [a Tuniq] threw his harpoon, chipping [the cliff] away. This is Ualinaaq...where the Tuniit fled. (KH01)

Another version of the story tells of a Tuniq who banged his harpoon rod against two very large boulders at Ugliit before resigning to leave, leaving a great dent (IE472; IE703; KH04). When asked about the similarities between the Ualinaaq and Ugliit stories, two Elders clarified that Ualinaaq is where the Tuniit were first displaced, while Ugliit is the last place they had lived before leaving Amittuq (KH01; KH04). These stories also provide insight into how Amitturmiut view Tuniit and deep history: the Tuniit loved their land, but they cared for Inuit more. The Amitturmiut both earned and inherited their land, and the disappearance of Tuniit is a narrative that affirms Amitturmiut as the rightful stewards of Amittuq, its resources, and its history. These material encounters demonstrate how Tuniit places are not simply records of the past, but are active participants in the landscape.

The continued significance of Tuniit places presents the possibility that similar affective relations existed in the deep past, and that Tuniit peoples were also shaped by their encounters with ancestral places (sensu Barad 2003:817). The remains of earlier camps, cairns, and

³² Some testimonies do not distinguish if the Ualinaaq legends are about Tuniit, but mention that the people spoke with a child-like lisp (IE358; IE384; IE385; IE390). This suggests that they were Tuniit, as the Tuniit language is commonly described as “Kutak” (*baby talk*) (Boas 1888:164; Sonne 2015; Qitsualik-Tinsley and Qitsualik-Tinsley 2015:3).

monuments would have been visible to later Tuniit occupants just as they are to Inuit, serving as testaments to the generations that preceded them. Tuniit places may have communicated memories about ancestral settlements, seasonal activities, and safe travel routes, as they have continued to do for Amitturmiut (cf. KH02; IE017; IE327). These relations not only drew people from different times together but also differentiated the experience of place and history through their material affects. Encountering an old camp, for example, was likely a meaningful event for Tuniit people, affirming community membership and creating new possibilities for how people and places could come together as part of the landscape. That Tuniit likely had intimate historic connections with ancestral places, which in turn shaped their practices and influenced the creation and modification of built spaces, provides a valuable framework for interpreting Tuniit material culture and reconstructing past landscapes. To assess these potential historic connections, I expand available radiocarbon sequences and address architectural and artifactual evidence for maintenance and reoccupation activities at Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq. In doing so, I explore evidence for longstanding occupational traditions that challenge economic rationalist models centered on a shoreward shifting settlement strategy, and cultivate a new narrative centered on the enduring, affective, and meaningful connections between people and places in Amittuq.

4.1.2 Exploring Local Diversity in Late Tuniit Occupational Practices

Amitturmiut oral stories about Tuniit provide deeper insight into how human-nonhuman relations may have shaped the material conditions of social life during the Tuniit Period. They contain information about the location of Tuniit settlements and resource places (e.g., flint

sources) that have not been documented by archaeologists, and lesser-studied archaeological correlates, such as the different kinds of caches, that are important for inferring socioeconomic contexts of past occupations. These accounts also reveal nuance in occupational practices that are often not visible in Tuniit archaeological contexts, such as shamanic activities related to hunting and butchering. Incorporating Amitturmiut stories into the design of my archaeological fieldwork and analyses has permitted the identification of a wider range of Tuniit land use activities and community relations, including the occupation of lacustrine and sheltered areas located inland from coastal site sequences. These observations present Tuniit place-community relations as locally varied and dynamic phenomena, challenging dominant archaeological narratives of econometric settlement behaviour.

4.1.2.1 Variation in Tuniit Subsistence Practices. Amitturmiut stories offer new perspectives of Tuniit sea mammal hunting that enrich archaeological interpretations (Friesen 2007; Hood 1998; Maxwell 1985), with walrus and seal being the most commonly mentioned prey (Figure 4.1). Archaeologists link the intensification of walrus hunting in the Late Tuniit Period to the emergence of larger, longer-term settlements and a more complex social system (see Chapter Two, Section 2.2.2). This correlation assumes that larger parties were required to hunt walruses, and that the surplus food acquired through these activities freed time for non-economic activities like the production of art (McGhee 1996:131, Murray 1999:468). However, Amitturmiut stories suggest that Tuniit hunting parties remained small, contradicting archaeological assumptions about the necessity of large hunting parties:

It is said that when the conditions were right for one to go on to the moving ice they would go on to hunt walrus. This TUNIJJUAQ would not try to keep company of other hunters, towards night he could be seen returning with a meat in tow. This was when the TIQITUQQAT [young walruses] have landed [at Alarniq] in the early spring. As he got close to the camp he would be towing a whole

young walrus which he did not bother to butcher. (IE246)

Available archaeological evidence from Amittuq may support this understanding of Late Tuniit hunting and social organization. While Late Tuniit houses at Alarniq appear significantly larger and are present in higher frequencies than Early Tuniit dwellings (Howse et al. 2018), some other Late Tuniit sod house settlements, such as those at Kapuivik, are comparable in size to those from the Early Tuniit Period (cf. Maxwell 1985:98; Savelle et al. 2009:228; Schledermann 1980:298). Late Tuniit campsites at Kapuivik and Qalirusiq are also significantly smaller than their Early Inuit counterparts located nearby. When considered alongside oral history, these data suggest the need for further research to understand persistence and change in camp community structures and their relationship to subsistence practices.

While the Tuniit in Amittuq are often understood as sea mammal hunters (Betts et al. 2015; Maxwell 1985; Savelle and Dyke 2014), oral stories describe an array of subsistence activities, including caribou hunting and fishing, that suggest locally and seasonally diverse people-place relationships. For example, Amitturmiut explain the small size of Tuniit tents, which lack a kilu (*back part of an Inuit tent*), as evidence of their need to sleep with their legs lifted on an anchor rock (Figure 4.3, cf. Figure 4.1) to run faster and chase down caribou:

I know and have seen the tent rings at KINGATUAQ [a hill NW of Hall Lake] at the mouth of the stream. The anchor rock at the back of the tent rock is huge, slanting, this was for them place their feet when they lay down...It is said that if they AJJULUAQ [had an inability to do so] too much they would not be able to run fast, so they needed something to elevate their feet (IE246, cf. Bennett and Rowley 2004:144; Boas 1888:166; Mary-Rousselière 1955:15).

The Tuniit erected cairns and monuments where migrating caribou crossed the water and built camps near their calving grounds, which are still visible in eastern Amittuq (Bennett and Rowley 2004:143; Boas 1888:635; IE249). In other parts of the Eastern Arctic the Tuniit are

remembered as having also built drive lanes out of Inuksugait (stone monuments) that also remain erect (Rasmussen 1927:44). These were connected by sinew ropes and draped with furs and hides when in use (Mary-Rousselière 1955:15). There is one such Inuksugait formation in eastern Amittuq, at Ualinaaq, that may have been built by Tuniit (IE272; IE710; KH04). This area remains a hunting ground for caribou due to its marshy environment, but as previously mentioned has yet to be surveyed by archaeologists (IE384). While visiting Ualinaaq was not possible during my fieldwork, the knowledge that Tuniit peoples may have constructed summer and fall caribou hunting camps on the eastern side of the region suggests that, despite the presumed coastal focus of Tuniit settlement strategies, Tuniit peoples in Amittuq constructed seasonal camps in marshy, inland areas and pursued terrestrial game (cf. Bielawski 1988).

Figure 4.3 An example of a superficially visible Tuniit tent ring (Kapuivik, Feature 222-85) with a possible “anchor rock” identified by KH02.

Several Amitturmiut stories detail the importance of fishing, and offer descriptions of material correlates for Tuniit fishing practices that include weirs, caches, and the locations of

undocumented fishing sites. These details are significant as fishing bones do not preserve well in the archaeological record, but barbed harpoon heads inferred as spearheads for fishing have been found at several sites, including Kapuivik and Alarniq (Desrosiers 2018; Howse 2017). Some of the artifacts recovered from Kapuivik were shown to an Elder (KH02), who confirmed their use (Figure 4.4). Their presence may indicate that fishing activities took place at local lakes or suggest broader movements within the landscape. Tuniit are described as having built saputit (*weirs*) on the banks of rivers, especially near the mouths of lakes (IE246; IE249; IE708, cf. Bennett and Rowley 2004:149). Tuniit harpooned the fish caught in their weirs, but sometimes also harpooned fish in naturally formed tidal shallows by the coast (KH02, cf. IE017; IE327).

Like caribou grounds, fishing locales were also often marked with Inuksugait:

In the places where fishing was done by the TUNIJJUAT you can see a lot of INUKSUGAIT...these were the markers that were left by the TUNIJJUAT to determine the location where there were more fish in the lake. You can see a lot of INUKSUGAIT at the mouth of the rivers on the lakes. (IE194)

Tuniit fishing caches were not buried and covered with boulders in the way that sea mammal caches were, but instead the fish were placed in a surface container built of smaller rocks, to form a cairn (IE434; KH02). Today, Tuniit fish cairns can be spotted on the sides of riverbanks and lakes, similar to tents and weirs (IE249; KH04). As I will describe in Chapters Five and Seven, these stories offer explanation for newly documented sites located inland near freshwater features, which include cache structures that resemble descriptions of fish cairns. In addition to presenting archaeological correlates for Tuniit fishing activities, Amitturmiut stories are significant as they suggest that Late Tuniit peoples frequently travelled up rivers and camped along lakes during the warm seasons. This is an important consideration since most surveys in Amittuq have been limited to coastal contexts (see Chapter Three, Section 3.3.2).

Figure 4.4 Example of a fishing spearhead recovered from Kapuivik.

4.1.2.2 Raw Material Procurement and Land Use. Amitturmiut stories describe the procurement of animal hides for clothing and lithic material for constructing tools and weapons. These raw materials varied seasonally and influenced where people travelled and what animals were prioritized for hunting at different times of the year. For example, ringed seal hides were commonly used for making clothes as well as summer tent skins, while walrus hides were used to line the walls in sod houses (KH02; KH03; IE099; IE281). Some stories mention that Tuniit cached bearded seal and walrus skins to make them more pliable for future hide work, suggesting that communities may have retrieve hides from spring camps at the end of autumn to prepare them for winter use, contributing to complex encounters with settlement places (KH03, IE117).

While the etymology of the term “Tuniit” is unclear, an alternative origin to “tuniguk” (*to give*) is “tunirijaq”, a less common word for flint (Qitsualik-Tinsley and Qitsualik-Tinsley 2015:2). The words kukiksait and anngmaat — two other variants of the word flint — are commonly referenced in Amitturmiut stories (Figure 4.1). The Tuniit are remembered to have

started fires by striking flint with quartz, or by hitting together pieces of a special chert called Inngniq³³ (alt. Igniit) (KH03; IE278; IE283; IE284). Lighter coloured cherts are thought to have been collected from small deposits in littoral areas to make expedient tools, as these are common throughout the region (IE280). However, these are softer and more difficult to work with compared to the more brightly coloured cherts found in bedrock deposits, and it is expected that these were prioritized for important uses like hunting large game (KH03).

Amitturmiut stories offer insight into where Tuniit may have travelled seasonally to retrieve tool stone, including seven placenames that refer to chert deposits through the root angmaa-, such as Angmaaraarjuk (*Big Flint Island*) (IE283). Inngniq, alternatively, is known only from a place called Ingnirit/ Inngniqtarvik and from the nearby site of Tikiraq, on the northwestern coast of Qikiqtaaluk (IE277; IE282). These locations suggest that Tuniit peoples travelled long distances from their coastal settlements to obtain certain material resources (Figure 4.5). Some sources were located on islands and as such were only accessible during the winter or spring when travel over the ice was possible, while other sources were located inland far from winter settlements, and as such were likely visited during the warmer months when communities travelled to caribou hunting and fishing grounds. In Section Two, I explore how Amitturmiut moved through the landscape to acquire raw material resources as part of their seasonal round, and how these movements informed, and were informed by, seasonal subsistence strategies. This allows me to develop richer archaeological expectations for when and how Tuniit communities moved between the study sites.

³³ Inngniq chert is distinguished by its reddish black colour and slightly sweet taste when licked (IE282).

Figure 4.5 Locations of known chert sources in Amittuq in relation to study sites.

4.2 Learning from the Amitturmiut Landscape

Models of Tuniit settlement in Amittuq have been largely informed by abstractive analogies derived from Amitturmiut ethnographies (Birket-Smith 1930; Boas 1888; Crowe 1969; Damas 1963) that frame the occupational landscape as the product of predictable, rationalist behaviours centered on the exploitation of nearshore marine resource (Meldgaard 1962; Steensby 1916; Taylor 1968, see Hood 1998; Riche 1990 for reviews). In this section I demonstrate how the Amitturmiut occupational landscape has emerged through diverse and dynamic people-place relations that unfolded at multiple social, spatial, and chronological scales. I present a deeper understanding of these relations through the qualitative and spatial analysis of 131 oral

testimonies from the OHP. These testimonies describe Amitturmiut subsistence and settlement practices prior to the forced relocation of traditional communities into the modern settlements of Igloolik and Sanirajak (formerly Hall Beach). By centering my examination on local knowledge and history rather than legacy ethnographies, I cultivate an alternative narrative of the Amitturmiut occupational landscape and use these insights to develop historically specific expectations for how persistent places materialized during the Tuniit Period.

I examine three themes that contextualize historic and contemporary people-place relations in Amittuq. I first explore the concept of Igagliit Nunagivaktangit (*the land belongs to them*) and the *-miut* social system, which together demonstrate how camp communities and a shared regional identity have been negotiated through local people-place relations. I then consider the affective roles of inter-seasonal settlement places, followed by the examination of traditional navigational routes, which were both integral to the development of long-term traditions of land use. My exploration of these themes is guided by a series of GIS maps that visualize the spatial and temporal relationships discussed in the testimonies. The maps provide information about the proximity, accessibility, and connectivity of settlement sites, and enable the identification of new spatial patterns relevant to my later analyses of the Tuniit archaeological landscape.

4.2.1 Theme One: Making Kin through Places

To problematize and reframe past archaeological understandings of Tuniit place-community relationships, I here demonstrate how Inuit kinship is negotiated through acts of placemaking. For Amitturmiut, situated knowledges related to settlement, subsistence, and

navigation have facilitated repeated encounters between people and places, fostering a deep sense of familiarity and co-belonging (IE215; IE236). This social topology is often expressed by Inuit through the concepts of *ilagiit nunagivaktangit* (*the land belongs to them*) and *-miut* (*people of a particular place*). These concepts together demonstrate how Amitturmiut make kin and negotiated their social worlds on a local level through both daily practices and intergenerational connections with places. By tying people to places, Igagliit Nunagivaktangit and *-miut* also tie people to other people, cultivating a sense of community through copresence, co-belonging, and a shared landscape history (IE260; IE293, cf. Ahmed 2005:27; Yuval-Davis 2004:215).

As the Qikiqtani Truth Commission states, “the rich expression *ilagiit nunagivaktangit* communicates the importance of kinship among people who share a community, and the permanent relationship they have with the land” (QTC 2013:15). *Igagliit Nunagivaktangit* has several meanings and uses, but implicit in all of them is a conception of home and togetherness through the land (Michael Irngaut, personal communication 2018). In its plural form, *Igagliit Nunagivaktangit* refers to the traditional settlement landscape of a regional group, as well as to the traditional lifestyle of hunting and camping prior to the forced relocation of Inuit into modern settlements (QIA 2013:7). In its singular form, *ilagiit nunagivaktangit* describes “a place used regularly or seasonally by Inuit for hunting, harvesting, and/or gathering”, but can also refer to “special places, such as burial sites of loved ones, or sites with abundant game (QTC 2013:14). The term may also refer to a particular community whose identity emerges through the act of camping and cohabitation, as implied from excerpts such as “the leader of an *ilagiit nunagivaktangit*” (Casagrande 2020:52). As such, a camp community could be identified as a particular *ilagiit nunagivaktangit*, but this community could also be said to move seasonally “between *ilagiit nunagivaktangit*” (QTC 2010:38).

Anthropologists working in the eastern Arctic have traditionally viewed kinship as biologically prescribed and as the foundation of Inuit social organisation (Birket-Smith 1930; Boas 1888; Rasmussen 1925). However, the etymology of “ilagiit” offers insight into the flexibility of social organization at the scale of the camp. Ilagiit is usually thought to mean “kindred”, because the root word *ila-* is often translated to *kin* and the suffix *-giit* translates to *those who share* (Balikci 1964). However, Trott (2005:4) notes that *ila-* can also mean *to be with/accompany*, as in “*ilauniaqpunga?*” (*may I join with you [on your outing]*). *Ila-* therefore does not only refer to blood relatives, but can be used between people brought together through shared activities such as camping:

There were others [in the camp], not only their own kinship that made their home there. Some people that were not related to that family chose to stay with them. In those days the Inuit did not stay in one place at all times. They would move around to other places so they never had one particular place to stay at all times. -IE004 (cf. IE256; IE338)

Blood relation was an important structuring force of community connections across long distances and often influenced how people moved and gathered in the landscape. However, daily encounters in shared places were capable of fostering a sense of community without biological affiliation (cf. Nuttal 2000:33). The versatility of kinship explains how historic Amitturmiut identities are tied to the co-presence of people *in place*, and highlights the fluidity of membership in camp communities as people come together and break apart through daily activities. Kinship groups who shared traditional travel routes and hunting grounds were routinely brought together in local communal contexts, which also established wider social relations within the landscape (see Whitridge 2004).

Naming is an important part of Inuit identity, and tying people to a series of places through toponyms serves to form, strengthen, and differentiate community membership (Correll

1976, cf. Basso 1996). Amitturmiut, like Inuit throughout the Canadian Arctic, affirm place-based identities through the postbase -miut (*people of a particular place*). For example, an elder who was born at Kapuivik but now lives in Igloodik may identify simultaneously as Kapuivimiut and Iglulingmiut, but also as Amitturmiut (people of the Amittuq region) and Nunavummiut (people of the territory of Nunavut) (KH02). Historically, the -miut group was described by ethnographers as a territorial unit associated with “winter socialites” in which families gathered in shared settlements, rather than the temporary configurations of “summer socialites” in which these communities broke into smaller, uneven distributions (Mauss 1906:27). However, the OHP testimonies indicate that -miut groups are not limited to the identification of wintering camps and are by nature fluid, variable, and multiscalar:

This is the place where we use to make it our home. And this is another place where we use to have our home. We used to be called MANIITURMIUT only when we made it our home. - IE284

The place where we made our dwelling was our 'NUNAVUT' [home ground]....The rest was our land too but...the only place that we would call 'NUNAVUT' was the place where we made our dwelling. If we moved to another place that we had not occupied the preceding year, we would only refer to our previous home as (VOC) 'NUNAVINIQPUT' [our previous home ground], the place where we had taken up residency becomes our 'NUNAVUT'. -IE261

Kin terms like Igagliit and -miut are signals that people use to recognize one another through their ties to land, which includes both its material elements as well as its spiritual, emotional, and intellectual elements (Nuttall 1992:81-82; Tuck et al 2014:9). As Opaskwayak Cree scholar Shawn Wilson states, “identity for Indigenous peoples is grounded in their relationships with the land, and their ancestors who have returned to the land and with future generations who will come into being on the land. Rather than viewing ourselves as being in relationship with other people or things, we are the relationships that we hold and are part of” (2008:80). Amitturmiut generate a sense of co-belonging through their connections with places,

and these relations condition the social dynamics of extended kin groups brought together through shared travel routes, overlapping hunting territories, and, at times, shared camps (QIA 2010:15):

[I]t was never mentioned by anyone that they owned the land; the whole land was their home...Whenever they went to a land they would call it their home...That was the way it was. No land alienated no one. — (IE254)

The relational production of community identities through the copresence of people *in place* contextualizes how daily practices, movements, and historic traditions in Amittuq conditioned not only subsistence-settlement practices, but how individuals, families, and larger communities socially located themselves through the land. Within this system, the campsite emerges as the embodied social scale of coexistence, the “scale of relation” that “encompasses the infinite within the immediate” (Howitt 2002: 302). Camp communities were in constant flux, and their exchange of membership fostered a deep sense of belonging within and between extended kin groups. This demonstrates how local communities can be temporary and mutable while continuously informing the historic trajectory of people-place relations and cultural belonging (cf. Haraway 2016; Harris 2014).

4.2.2 Theme Two: Local and Seasonal Diversity in Occupational Practices

In their review of Inuit oral history, Bennett and Rowley (2004) provide a summary of historic Amitturmiut settlement practices derived primarily from the OHP archives and the ethnographic work of Rasmussen (1927). My own analysis of the OHP confirms the general settlement pattern described by the authors, but also reveals significant variability in the seasonal

activities of local camp communities. In this section, I examine how camp communities and persistent places were continuously formed and differentiated through the repeated encounters of humans and nonhumans. This includes large-scale cooperative activities such as annual fish runs and feasting celebrations, as well as smaller-scale practices such as brief but meaningful encounters at outpost camps during travel. These examples demonstrate how the virtual capacities of people-place relationships changed seasonally and interannually in the (relatively recent) past, and highlight the importance of assessing small-scale differences in camp structure, topography, and local ecology when drawing inferences about Tuniit community practices. Ultimately, my analysis reframes Qalirusiq, Kapuivik, and Alarniq as dynamic, inter-seasonal places that were occupied by multiple camp communities throughout the year, and suggests that Tuniit occupational sequences may represent a variety of seasonally specific occupations that required the construction and maintenance of different architectures, camp structures, and spatial settings.

4.2.2.1 The Seasonal Round of the Amitturmiut. Bennett and Rowley (2004) describe how the Amitturmiut lived in sod houses on the land and iglus on the sea ice during the winter. They hunted bearded seals and walrus on the land-fast ice, and opportunistically hunted roaming caribou and exploited meat caches that were prepared in previous the autumn (Bennett and Rowley 2004:387, cf. IE029; IE147; IE163). There were six primary winter settlements located in Amittuq, including Alarniq, Igloolik, Iglurjuat, Iqaluit³⁴, Maniqtuuq, Qaiqsut, as well as a seventh settlement further south on Melville Peninsula, called Usuarjuk (Figure 4.6a; Bennett and Rowley 2004:383). A number of smaller campsites were also routinely occupied, as the Amitturmiut followed a taboo in which a settlement could only be occupied for three winters

³⁴ Not be confused with the capital of Nunavut with the same name: Iqaluit means “place of many fish (arctic char)”.

before being left to “cool down” so that animal populations could recover (Bennett and Rowley 2004:383, cf. IE252).

Although winter is framed as a time when people hunted walrus near the coast (Bennett and Rowley 2004:387), campsites located near recurring polynyas were entangled in wide variety of community relations outside of walrus hunting. One of the most important activities was the hunting of ringed seals by “Mauliq”, a technique in which dogs were trained to sniff out snow-covered breathing holes on nights with good moonlight³⁵ (IE012; IE078; IE122; IE143; IE317; IE327). Hunters would travel to other sea ice camps to join in Mauliq, briefly bringing smaller wintering camps together into shared communities comparable to those formed in the springtime:

I remember the time when there was a camp in the winter time so that the hunters could hunt seals by MAULIQ....When we went over to their hunting grounds, we would join in the hunt, after the day's hunt, we would go to their camp to spend the night. (IE166)

Kapuivik and Siruq were common places where Mauliq was practiced, and those who lived near Igloodik and Siuraajaruk concentrated their winter hunting on Mauliq more than those that lived elsewhere in Amittuq (Figure 4.6a; IE086). The importance of Mauliq as a winter practice indicates that, even during the dark period, camp communities were in constant flux as families moved between locales and participated in large-scale subsistence activities.

My analysis also reveals that winter caribou hunting was more than an opportunistic rarity, as some communities actively sought them out by establishing settlements on islands that tundra-wintering Peary caribou were known to frequent (Figure 4.6a). People trained these

³⁵ While Amitturmiut and archaeologists agree that Late Tuniit (Dorset period) peoples had only sporadic access to dogs (cf. Morey and Aaris-Sørensen 2002) there is evidence that, at least in some regions, Early Tuniit had access to dogs in higher numbers (cf. Maxwell 1976; Hilts 2021) and as such it is feasible they could have practiced Mauliq seal hunting.

caribou using a technique called Maliruaq, in which a lone hunter would familiarize a herd to humans, to make hunting them as a group more successful (IE001; IE010; IE058). Kapuivik is a well-known place where Maliruaq was practiced:

In KAPUIVIK they used to train caribou to get used to the appearance of human beings... When they didn't flee inland, then they would keep coming back to the place where they fed... It is said that KAPUIVIK was the best place to train caribou. (IE010, cf. IE057; IE177; IE439)

Fox trapping was also an important winter practice, as it offered another source of meat to supplement sea mammal hunting. Intricate stone fox traps were reused for centuries, requiring only the routine replacement of a uqaliqpaa (*ice door*) and the bait inside the trap (IE180; IE182). The known locations of old fox traps influenced the paths that hunters would take on trips between seal, walrus, and caribou hunting locales, repeatedly drawing people to ancestral trapping grounds and shaping traditional winter travel routes (Figure 4.6a; IE473).

In the early spring, people camped on the sea ice in higher numbers to hunt walrus and ringed seals pups at their dens (Bennet and Rowley 2004:394, cf. IE114). This was a time of heavy snowfall when it was easiest to travel by dogsled, and communities moved between camps and congregated in large iglus called qaggiq. In the late spring, Amitturmiut hunted ringed seals at their breathing holes and basking bearded and ringed seals at the floe edge. The snow was less ideal for travel at this time, but the hot sun also meant that people could safely travel through the night and reach more distant places (Bennet and Rowley 2004:395).

Figure 4.6 The cold weather occupational landscape of the Amitturmiut in winter (A) and spring (B). Spatial data from OHP (2019), Inuit Heritage Trust Nunavut Map Series (2016) and Aporta (2003)

Although many communities camped on the sea ice, my analysis demonstrates that spring was a time of movement between ice camps and land settlements (Figure 4.6b). For example, some chose to build their iglus along the coastlines so that they would have access to flagstones and moss to line their bed platforms and prevent them from melting (IE108; IE157). Pingiqqalik, Alarniq, and Kangiq were common places where Amitturmiut built land camps in the spring (IE056; IE134; IE479). This observation is important for assessing the archaeological record, as it suggests that at least some of the stone rings interpreted as the borders of tents at coastal Tuniit sites could be the remains of snow houses — a possibility that is commonly overlooked due to the extensive identification of such features as tent rings in legacy reports (cf. Meldgaard 1954a; 1962).

Alarniq and Kangiq were also important as they were the closest campsites in the early spring to a large polynya called Sikutuqqijuq (*land of the walrus*) (IE477), and as a result walrus were hunted more aggressively in this area than they were at the spring camps north of Igloolik. An important feature of this polynya is that old pack ice gathers around it and remains relatively stable into the early summer, allowing hunters to pursue basking ringed seal, bearded seal, and walrus when conditions are favourable in warmer months, as well (IE054; IE056; KH02). This is significant as it reframes Alarniq as not only an important winter and spring settlement, but as a potential summer camping ground, during the Early Inuit period.

The OHP testimonies describe how Mauliq seal hunting continued to be practiced in the spring during the period of heavy snow fall, followed by the Nuqingaq technique of using sound and memory to stalk seals at their breathing holes (IE114; Figure 4.7b). It was important to catch ringed seals for their skins; women would save the larger skins to prepare tent covers for the

coming summer and use the smaller skins to make footwear (IE202; IE375). Blubber from these seals would be cached in stone lined holes near summer campgrounds for later use, to prevent spoilage (IE433).

As the rivers began to thaw in late spring, some camps moved inland to partake in Tinujjijut (*spring fish runs*) (Figure 4.7b; IE023; IE169; IE433). Fish caught at this time would be dried (*pissi*) rather than cached (*siriaktaq*) due to the heat of the sun (IE433). *Pissi* was an important food for dog sled trips and for supplementing summer food stuffs (IE413), and dried ringed seal meat prepared at this time may have served similar purposes (Desjardins 2017). The importance of dried foodstuffs in the late spring may help explain the identification of large but seemingly ephemeral dwelling structures with little or no faunal remains at Tuniit sites, as the storage and consumption of dried meat strips would leave few faunal remains (Friesen 2001).

As the snow began to melt in the summer, people moved into land tents constructed of bones and animal skins weighed down by boulders (Bennett and Rowley 2004:396). It was difficult to visit other camps at this time due to the breaking up of the ice (cf. IE154). Snow geese moulted and were unable to fly, and as such were herded into stone pens where they could be killed and cached. Arctic char began to be fished at the weirs (Bennett and Rowley 2004:399), and were also fished with rods at inland lakes and along the coasts (IE441; IE471). Iqalulikuluk lake on Igloolik island was a popular fishing spot, as was the coast of Iglurjuat to the northeast (Figure 4.8a).

Bennet and Rowley (2004: 400-401) also discuss the diversification of occupational practices during “summerless” years when the weather remained cold. Tents were uncomfortable during these times due to the frigid wind, and there was not enough snow to build iglus. As a

result, some families would make ice iglus from frozen ponds and live in these inland areas, while others built qarmats (*huts with stone walls and tent roofs*) and lived closer to the shore. This demonstrates how the availability of building materials could affect the spatial practices of Amitturmiut communities, and suggests that ephemeral dwelling features located slightly inland from coastal sequences at Tuniit sites may have served similar purposes.

During times of scarcity, blubber caches prepared in the spring for lamp fuel were consumed alongside edible plants and roots, which were gathered from inland areas (IE435). Plants such as cassiope (heather) also served as insulation for roofs as well as fuel for hearths and lamps when blubber was depleted (IE157). Avvajja was a common place where cassiope was gathered for insulation in the late summer and autumn (Figure 7a; IE017). Like the construction of ice iglus, these practices demonstrate how the availability of material resources significantly affected the movements and settlement choices of local communities. This challenges anthropological expectations that past peoples always prioritized their proximity to abundant coastal hunting spots when selecting campsite locations (cf. Meldgaard 1965; Taylor 1968).

My OHP research indicates that egg collecting was also an important summer activity (IE491). Seagull eggs were collected from cliffsides around Qaiqsut and from the island of Pikiuliarjuk near Igloodik (IE017; IE203; KH02), and arctic tern, snow geese, brant geese, and eider duck eggs were gathered along coastal shores (Figure 4.8a). Children were able to participate in egg hunting and as such it was a frequent activity for young families (IE092; IE115; IE191; IE338; IE370; IE470). Eggs were both eaten and used to bait birds with corded snares (IE371; IE471).

Figure 4.7 The warm weather occupational landscape of the Amitturmiut in summer (A) and autumn (B).

Spatial data from OHP (2019) and Inuit Heritage Trust Nunavut Map Series (2016)

Bennett and Rowley (2004:398) describe how qajaq (*kayak*) hunting was at its peak in the late summer and early autumn; and communities who remained in coastal areas would hunt sea mammals on the open water. Other communities moved inland to hunt caribou for their skins and to collect sinew to sew clothes and lash hunting weapons for the coming winter (IE298; IE414; KH03). While some communities did stay at coastal camps, my research suggests that, more often, communities would break off into smaller groups to diversify their cached resources for the coming winter; families that stayed littoral would ferry their kin up inland rivers (IE281; IE379; IE427). Some caribou grounds, like the lake crossing at Inuksulik (Figure 4.7b), were used exclusively by Elders due to their ease of access and the helpful presence of inuksugait drive lines and hunting blinds; younger hunters would travel further on foot to more inland hunting grounds (IE65; IE157; IE276). Those who hunted inland would bury some of the caribou meat nearby for their return the following autumn, and dry the remaining meat so that it would not spoil or weigh them down during travel back to their cold weather campsites (IE072; IE095).

Tool materials such as soapstone, quartz, and slate, were also typically collected in the summer and autumn (IE279; IE703). Some of these places, such as Akunniq (IE277), were inland (2003) and could be visited on the way to caribou hunting grounds. Other sources, such as the soapstone found at Qinnua (IE279) or the slate source at Aupajuktuq (IE284), were coastal and could be visited by those who remained littoral (IE304). Some of these sources were large boulder outcrops that could also be located during times of snow cover (IE277; IE703). One such boulder of soapstone is known near Tasiujaq (IE279), and there is one of flint located near Kapuivik (IE278) (Figure 4.7a). Given the frequency of these stone tool materials in Tuniit assemblages and the restricted availability of outcrops throughout the region, it is likely that local Tuniit communities visited many of these same places.

In late autumn, the Historic Amitturmiut moved back into sod houses at their winter settlements. As the sea ice reformed, people would travel to the camps of their friends and relatives who they had not visited since the spring (Bennett and Rowley 2004:401, cf. IE128; IE149). In coastal areas where thin, young ice first formed, bearded seal began to be hunted again at their breathing holes, followed by walrus that had returned to the land fast ice (Figure 4.7b, cf. IE 148). The strait between Igloodik and Avvajja was the first place where this young ice would form and connect with the older pack ice, and people from these islands would gather in the strait at an ice camp named Qikiqtaarjjuk where they would spend the rest of autumn and the early winter (IE148; Figure 4.7b). This was also the time when women — and in a more supportive role, men— would rush to finish sewing their winter clothes, as it was taboo to make clothes during the dark period (Bennett and Rowley 2004:402, cf. IE 184).

4.2.2.2. Reinterpreting Persistent Coastal Places: While anthropologists usually present Amitturmiut as a people whose way of life has been historically centered on hunting walrus and seal at the floe edge (Bennet and Rowley 2004; Damas 1998; Mary-Rousseliere 1984; Meldgaard 1965; Taylor 1968), my analysis demonstrates that their relationships with animals and places were diverse, locally situated, and in constant flux (Figure 4.8). Occupational activities varied among camp communities based on the proximity and accessibility of seasonal hunting grounds from winter and spring settlements (Bennett and Rowley 2004; cf. Binford 1980). However, settlement practices were also structured by the availability of raw materials for constructing dwellings and producing tools (cf. Morgan et al. 2018), the demographics of the camp (e.g., children, elderly folks), the preferences and traditions of families (e.g., returning to ancestral trapping grounds), and the observation of broader customs like feasts and celebrations.

My analysis also demonstrates how Tirinnngnaqtuq (taboos) conditioned settlement practices. Given that the Amitturmiut cosmological system is believed by local Knowledge Holders to have emerged through interactions with Tuniit peoples (cf. section 1.4), it is important to consider that Tuniit occupational practices may have been informed by similar beliefs and customs (cf. Hardenberg 2013; LeMoine 2003; Zságer 2010). One such set of Tirinnngnaqtuq was called Naatiingujaq (*taboos surrounding death*). Naatiingujaq would require a person who had handled the remains of the deceased to refrain from certain practices, such as extracting the marrow of caribou bones, for an entire year (IE176; IE440; IE456). This abstinence would affect the subsistence practices of afflicted persons, who, for example, may bury caribou bones in permafrost caches so that they could be consumed the following year (IE440).

Naatiingujaq also affected residential mobility. When someone died, the camp community would wait a set amount of time determined by a local shaman before moving camp (IE079; IE508). Places where tragedies had occurred, or where important people had been buried, were often no longer used as primary settlements; Salliq was abandoned after a terrible season where the caribou had died out and many people had starved (IE330), and Kangiq and Avvajja were no longer occupied by certain families after community leaders had been buried there (IE001; IE287).

There were taboos other than Naatiingujaq that also impacted residential mobility, such as the previously mentioned taboo of Uunarsiqunagu, in which winter settlements were relocated every three to five years³⁶ to allow the land to “cool down” and regenerate (IE098; IE128; IE287; Bennett and Rowley 2004). The practice of leaving settlements to regenerate is particularly

³⁶ Bennett and Rowley (2004:383) state that relocation occurred every three years, but other testimonies mention five (IE098; IE128; IE466).

important to consider when reinterpreting “gaps” in the occupational sequences of repeatedly occupied sites, as it suggests that abandonments may be the result of deliberate, historically

Figure 4.8 Amitturmiut seasonal settlement round. Calendar adapted from Bennett and Rowley (2004: Figure 11), with additions from OHP testimonies discussed in this section.

situated social practices rather than local extinction events (cf. McGhee 1972; Meldgaard 1954a;

1960b; Savelle and Dyke 2014). The variability present among Amitturmiut occupational practices offers insight into where and how Tuniit might have camped during the summer and autumn. Archaeologists have long assumed that the Tuniit travelled inland during the warmer months, since they did not have access to boats for open-water hunting (Bielawski 1988; Maxwell 1985). However, the oral testimonies indicate it was possible to hunt sea mammals on the pack ice near places like Alarniq when the winds were favourable (Desjardins 2017:32; IE054; IE058; IE056; KH02). There were also coastal summer camps to the southeast of the region that caribou frequented in the summer, such as Ualinaaq and Saatturjuaq (Figure 4.7a). Historically, pack ice remained stable in these areas regardless of the wind direction, and people could travel on this ice to hunt seal and travel to nearby islands (IE073; E382; IE385; IE355; IE389, cf. Figure 4.7a). The diversity of resources in these coastal areas meant that some communities did not need to relocate for winter, and could instead sustain themselves on caches, supplemented by seal hunting, throughout the dark period (IE162). The capacities of coastal areas to support year-round occupation suggests that Tuniit communities may have remained coastal even in the summer, taking short trips to the interior of Qikiqtaaluk and smaller islands to acquire caribou, fish, or small game when ice conditions allowed.

The diversity of food preparation and storage practices in the warm seasons are also worth considering from an archaeological standpoint, as they offer new expectations about faunal assemblages at coastal sites. The overrepresentation of caribou limb bones and ribs, for example, may indicate the exploitation of permafrost caches (IE420), while caribou hunted locally in the winter will result in a more even representation of faunal elements (Faith et al. 2007; Henrikson 2003; Krasinski 2018; Stewart et al. 2000). Alternatively, caribou meat that has been butchered, stripped, dried, and transported prior to caching will result in fewer faunal

remains, especially large limb bones (Friesen 2001; Friesen and Stewart 2013). The preparation of dried fish and seal, as mentioned, may result in a similar underrepresentation of faunal remains.

In addition to the summer camps to the southeast, there are several other places that were continuously occupied and/or repeatedly visited throughout the year, the most notable among them being Kapuivik, Qaiqsut, Alarniq, Igloodik and Avvajja. Interestingly, while Kapuivik has been inferred by archaeologists as a winter and spring settlement focused on the hunting of walrus and seal (cf. Bennett and Rowley 2004; Meldgaard 1954a; Desrosiers 2018), the OHP testimonies indicate that it was also an important locale for winter caribou hunting (IE010) and for coastal and lake fishing in the summer (IE010; IE122). The name Kapuivik, in fact, translates to “the place where we spear the fish” (IE263), and Tuniit fish spears have been found in multiple Tuniit dwellings at the site. Kapuivik is also home to one of the few chert outcrops mentioned in the OHP archives, which may have been a particularly valuable resource for Tuniit occupants (IE278; Kyle Forsythe personal communication 2022). The site is also uniquely accessible to other important places, most notably Qaiqsut, which can be reached in less than a five hours’ walk across a chain of small islands and shallow sea ice (KH02, cf. Figure 4.7a). Qaiqsut was an important locale for hunting walrus and seal in both the Tuniit and Early Inuit periods, and remains one of the best places to collect seagull eggs along cliffsides in the spring (IE017).

Alarniq, also framed as a winter settlement (Bennett and Rowley 2004), was frequently visited throughout the warmer months since the pack ice along the nearby Sikutuqqijuq polynya remained stable for seal and walrus hunting (IE056; IE246); the name of one of its three beaches,

Kaniq, originates from “qainguq” (*ice build up*) because of the importance of this pack ice (KH04). Alarniq’s beaches offered a variety of rocks and vegetation to line the platforms of snow houses that, paired with its proximity Sikutuqqijuq, made it an ideal land camp in the spring. In the summer, Alarniq is also a productive coastal fishing locale for Arctic char.

Although Qalirusiq is not explicitly mentioned as a settlement place in relation to Amitturmiut occupational practices, there were several historic camps nearby on Igloolik Island, and across the narrow strait at Avvajja, that contextualize its virtual capacities as a settlement (Figure 4.8). Igloolik was historically known among Amitturmiut as Pirlimiguuq Pirliqtaqanngittuq (*to have never known starvation*), because even though no particular animal lived there in abundance, food sources were accessible from the island in every season (IE001; IE477; IE486). Ringed seal were especially important and could be hunted year-round (IE329; IE471), and, when the southeast wind prevailed, walrus were hunted on the pack ice (IE148; IE273). Additionally, caribou were known to have once passed through the centre of the island at Iqalulikuluk lake in the early spring (IE378; IE471), and Iqalulikuluk remains an important locale for spring fishing (Figure 4.7b).

At Avvajja, people arrived in the late spring to hunt walrus and gather seagull eggs (IE086). Arctic char were fished along the coast in the summer (IE017), and in the autumn ringed seal and bearded seal were hunted on the nearby young ice (IE004). Avvajja was home to many raw materials, such as red ochre (IE278), sharpening stone material (IE279), and quartz (IE280), making it an ideal location for constructing household items and hunting implements needed for the winter (Figure 4.8). In the late autumn, those camping at Igloolik and Avvajja would gather in the strait on the new ice to hunt along nearby polynyas and ice leads (Figure

4.7a).

These relationships indicate that persistently occupied places were, as one Elder describes, “central habitats” (IE054): places that were in close proximity to seasonally diverse hunting areas and raw materials resources, as well as other settlements. This challenges archaeological understandings of the core area settlement model, as it suggests that repeatedly occupied Tuniit sites may represent a wide range of dynamic and locally situated community practices rather than predictable and regionally uniform settlement behaviours centered on winter floe-edge hunting (cf. Meldgaard 1962; Savelle and Dyke 2014). This argument is supported by archaeological differences in the size, structure, and spatial orientation of Tuniit dwellings along the upper ridges of Kapuivik, which may represent a mix of winter settlements, ephemeral snow camps, and summer dwellings for extended families (Savelle et al. 2009:228). Likewise, boulder dwellings located along the southwestern periphery of Alarniq suggest that warm weather camping activities may have also taken place at the site during the Tuniit Period. These material patterns warrant further examination of evidence for seasonally specific practices (e.g., faunal remains of seasonal species) at the study sites to establish how architecture and camp structure relate to different occupational practices.

My analysis of oral history also challenges archaeological interpretations of large, multi-family dwellings. These dwellings have been previously inferred as a means of increasing social cohesion between households during times of pronounced environmental change and resource stress (cf. Howse et al. 2021; Ryan 2010). However, radiocarbon dates recovered from Alarniq demonstrate that these houses were repeatedly occupied by Late Tuniit peoples during the “Middle Dorset” archaeological period (2000-1550 cal. BP) (Howse et al. 2021:8), a time of

gradual climatic cooling when sea ice was stable and reliable for sea mammal hunting (Briere and Gajewsk 2020; Friesen et al. 2020; Savelle et al. 2014). Additionally, these features were not occupied during the final Tuniit (“Late Dorset”) occupations, when resource stress was presumably at its peak (Howse et al. 2021:11). I argue that large, multifamily houses may instead represent a cultural tradition of gathering and feasting in times of prosperity, similar to Amitturmiut qaggiqs. This suggestion is supported by the diverse resources that were likely accessible from sites like Alarniq and Kapuivik where multifamily Tuniit dwellings and substantial faunal middens are found³⁷. Further examination of occupational seasonality, paired with paleotopographic reconstructions, will help to clarify the socioeconomic contexts associated with multi-family Tuniit dwellings.

4.2.3 Theme Three: Movement and Mobility in the Amitturmiut Landscape

The OHP testimonies indicate that persistent places were repeatedly visited by Amitturmiut not only because of their proximity and accessibility to a wide array of resources, but for their connectivity to more distant places in the landscape. Kapuivik was a popular outpost for those travelling between Iqaluit and Qaiqsut by sled in the winter and spring (Figure 4.6), as well as for those travelling to northern Qikiqtaaluk (Baffin) to hunt caribou in the autumn (Figure 4.10). Alarniq served as an access point between the Sikituqqijjuq polynya and the trail of Angmaluqtuq, an important route that led to caribou hunting grounds and fishing lakes on the western side of Melville Peninsula (IE054, cf. Figure 4.7). Alarniq was also a waycamp for those

³⁷ While the Tuniit sod houses found at Kapuivik are relatively small, there are several surface dwellings inferred as either multi-family tents or snow houses along the site’s northeastern periphery.

travelling south towards Pingiqqalik to fish and hunt walrus in the summer, and to Arviqsiurvik where bowhead whales were pursued in the autumn (Desjardins 2017; IE303, cf. Figure 4.7b). Avvajja — close to Qalirusiq — was important for its proximity to the crossroad of Avammunganiq (*place where one can go many directions*), which served as a gateway between the mainland to the west, Igloolik to the east, and the polynyas and ice camps to the north (IE375).

In this section, I explore how traditional navigational practices have shaped the Amitturmiut occupational landscape, and use these insights to build richer expectations about the movements and interactions of people during the Tuniit Period. My analysis centers on Amitturmiut practices related to travelling on sled routes and foot paths over land and sea ice. Although the Tuniit, at least during the Late Tuniit (“Dorset”) period, did not have regular access to dogs (Maxwell 1985; Morey and Aaris-Sørensen 2002), they are known to have pulled their own sleds (KH02; KH03; Mary-Rousselière 1955), and ivory sled runners are common artifacts at Tuniit sites in Amittuq (Meldgaard 1962; Howse 2017; Desrosiers 2018). I first examine how Amitturmiut perceive and experience spatial relationships, and how the fluidity of these relationships has shaped the social geography of Amittuq. I then discuss how traditional navigational knowledge, especially knowledge related to visual markers, the winds, and snow formations has structured how Amitturmiut locate themselves in the landscape. These sensual experiences produce and affirm social memory and enculturate travellers through a shared landscape history in which places are active participants in communities (see section 2.1, cf. Nuttal 1992). These examples indicate that proximity and location alone are ineffective measures of spatiality in Arctic landscapes, and that communities were forged and differentiated through movement and memory as much as they were through the long-term occupation of specific

places.

4.2.3.1 Inuit Space-Time and Community Relations. Space in the historic Amitturmiut landscape was organized according to the situated movements of local camp communities, who measured the proximity of places through the number of “sleeps” (travelling days) it took to reach them (IE263; IE413; IE455; IE475). This frames space and time as interdependent and locally situated qualities of the landscape (Igloliorte 2017; Irniq 2018; Price 2008; QIA 2010; d’Anglure 1988). For instance, one Elder describes the journey from Akunniq to Ajagutalik in the early autumn as taking five sleeps “if one walked all through the day” (IE200), while another describes the spring dog sled journey from Salliq to Nagjuktuuq on the southwestern coast of Qikiqtaaluk as taking two sleeps (IE417, cf. Figure 4.6b). This conception of space-time was not exclusive to Amitturmiut; Whitridge (2004:225) describes how the scales of historic maps made by Greenlandic Inuit were proportional to time distance, while Rasmussen (1930) outlines the importance of “sleeps” and “moons” in the verbal maps shared among the Kitlinermiut and Inuinnait. The importance of time-distance throughout Inuit Nunangat speaks to the critical role of embodied experience and everyday practices in defining people-place relationships (Whitridge 2004:228).

Amitturmiut space-time was dependant on a number of factors, the most important of which were seasonal weather and the method of travel (e.g., on foot, by sled). Inland travel depended on the melting of snow and ice so that *tulliniit* (*worn foot tracks made by humans and animals*) were visible (Aporta 2003:86; IE385; IE413; IE466). Alternatively, sledding routes required stable sea ice, frozen rivers and padded snow on flat terrain, and the fluctuating accessibility of these features impacted the course and length of travel (cf. Supernant 2017). One

elder, for example, describes his uncle's journey from Uliqqajaaq to Kapuivik by dog sled to retrieve a walrus cache in the autumn. The journey took two full days, which he attributes to the less direct route his uncle was forced to take on the windward side of Qikiktaarjuk (*Baffin*), due to thin sea ice (IE411). Another Elder discusses how shifting temperatures affected the speed and steering of sleds:

In the winter the ground is really hard to drive on, in the early spring the ground becomes fast. In the winter, when the temperatures are cold, it is really slow... This is caused by so much friction on the runners and... the sleds do not gain momentum at all. (IE505)

Time-distance may also vary based on the people travelling and the purpose of their journey:

Grandpa said that between here and Pond Inlet [by dog team] it's only one sleep whereas another person would probably have said it's about 10 sleeps...but then take into consideration that they hauled heavy loads, you know, that 10 sleeps...would be more true.- IE263

Relocating a camp community required heavier hauls than hunting trips (IE351; IE475), and the demographics of travelling parties, such as the presence of children (IE072; IE195) and elderly folks (IE140; IE230; IE413), impacted the length of travel days. When heading inland on foot in the summer, families would cache winter household items to lighten their loads. Many would sleep under the stars with only blankets (IE469), and in place of qulliqs they would use nearby rocks with natural hollows (IE281). Still, having to backpack with one's belongings significantly slowed travel and time-distance was dependent on the physical abilities of each traveller (IE200; IE435).

As time-distance varied, Amitturmiut space was constantly expanding and contracting (IE004; IE263). These spatial relationships produced a fluid geometry of nearness and rifts in the landscape that had significant consequences for how camp communities perceived their

connections with other camps (cf. Barad 2014:169). For example, the accessibility of sled routes across the sea ice on “fast” spring snow meant that even dispersed camps could be reached in less than one sleep, and as such were thought of as neighbours (IE029; IE184; IE475; IE505). Alternatively, in the winter these same routes would take significantly longer due to snow friction (IE001; IE505), and in the late autumn may be entirely inaccessible due to thin ice, limiting the interaction between camps and their perceived closeness (IE128; IE271; IE408). These shifting topographies had pronounced affects on when and how people encountered one another *in place*, and as such how camp communities were formed, dissolved, and reformed through daily practices and movements (IE162).

Amitturmiut space-time offers new interpretations of the spatial patterning of Tuniit sites. Given the absence of dog sleds for Late Tuniit, it is likely that Tuniit navigational routes covered shorter distances. However, the time-distance between places would have still fluctuated between seasons and travel contexts (e.g., relocating a camp, a brief hunting trip), meaning that a similar spatial pattern to that of Amitturmiut settlement practices is expected. Camp communities that visited one another regularly would have likely camped within daily walking distance in the winter, but may have been further dispersed in the spring. Likewise, in the late summer and early autumn camps located on islands would have had little to no contact, with the exception of those located in the southwest of Foxe Basin where pack ice was more stable (IE073; E382; IE385; IE355; IE389). The examination of the spatial clustering of Tuniit sites, paired with evidence for the seasonality of their occupations, will help explain how camp communities may have interacted with one another on a regional scale throughout the Tuniit Period.

4.2.3.2 Navigating the Landscape through Sense and Memory. Amitturmiut have a

complex system of knowledge for navigating the shifting topographies of their landscape, including directional aids, landmarks, and weather patterns (Aporta 2003, 2005; Boas 1888; Crowe 1969; MacDonald 1998; Rasmussen 1976). Amitturmiut use a variety of visual markers including the contours of coastlines, sea ice formations (e.g., ice build-up), rivers, and inuksugait (standing stones and cairns) to identify places and keep their bearings (Aporta 2005; Hallendy 1994; Heyes 2002; IE089; IE167; IE194; Macdonald 1998:184; Plumet 1985). Ice leads and polynyas are also important navigational features and can be discerned through the reflections they make in the sky, called tunguniq (*the sky map*) (IE139; IE187). In the dark period of winter, Amitturmiut also rely on the position of stars to keep their bearings, the most important of which is Nuutuittuq (*Polaris*) (IE263; IE467). In the summer they use the sun, which at midnight points north and at midday south, aiding travellers in a similar fashion (IE478).

Although visual aids are important components of traditional travel routes, there are many times they cannot be relied upon, such as during white-outs and on starless nights. As such, Amitturmiut have also historically relied on sound and touch to navigate their landscape. Among the most important sets of sensory knowledge is that of the winds, in which Uangnaq (*the north wind*) is the predominant wind (IE040, IE263; IE496) (Figure 4.9). This is a frigid, high pressure katabatic wind that maintains stable sea ice patterns — including the formation of ice leads and polynyas — but that is also responsible for dangerous weather conditions, such as blizzards. The winds are not only important directional aids, but are the primary means of calibrating time-distance to shifting factors such as temperature, visibility, snow texture, and sea ice movement (IE314; IE400). For example, if Uangnaq blows strong at night, it is expected that the next day will be cold but clear (IE496). Alternatively, Kanangnaq (*the east wind*) brings milder weather, and sometimes fog (IE273). The shifting strength and direction of the wind

enables hunters to anticipate the movement of ice floes and predict where sea mammals will congregate each day. For example, when Nigiq (the south wind) blows in the early morning during the winter, walrus move to the land fast ice near Igloolik (IE273; IE355). These predictions are critical for successful hunting and for preventing people from being blown out to sea on the moving ice (IE410).

Figure 4.9 Amitturmiut wind compass. *Note that Uangnaq (North) blows from the northwest according to western geographical standards.*

While the winds are a critical component of the Amitturmiut landscape, there are weather conditions, such as blizzards, in which they too cannot be relied on for travel. During these times Amitturmiut depend on snowdrifts, which are felt with the soles of their boots to keep their bearings (IE170). The most important of these formations are called uqaluraq (*tongue*), which are formed by the prevailing Uangnaq wind, and as such always point northwest (IE165, IE496, Figure 4.10). Uqalurait are more stable than other snow formations and are permanent fixtures throughout the winter after they are initially formed (IE165; IE314; IE469). They are also the

easiest to identify:

UQALURAIT are very easily identifiable, more so than other wind directions...As you travel and you may lose your sense of direction then these become very handy...to get your bearings. Other drifts created from other wind directions are difficult to tell if you are not experienced. (IE265).

Uqalurait support travellers in the most dangerous weather conditions when all other navigational aids fail, allowing a person to keep their bearings as long as they travel in a straight line (IE008). It is perhaps because of uqalurait that Historic Inuit winter camps are connected in straight lines while spring routes, which benefit from daylight and less volatile weather, often “zig zag” through stable ice paths and frozen plains (IE138; IE235; IE424; IE506). Because of the important place uqalurait within the Amitturmiut landscape, they were believed to have Inua (*a spirit to which they belonged*), which in this case was the woman who embodied the Uangnaq wind ((IE167; IE265). They were lifelines, and as such were seen as alive, themselves (KH01).

That Tuniit movements may have been structured by a similar system of navigational knowledge is supported by two material correlates. First, at least some of the inuksugait that mark Inuit travel routes are known to have been built by the Tuniit, suggesting that the two peoples travelled on shared inland routes and encountered many of the same topographic features and resource areas (Hallendy 1994:32; IE194; KH04; Rasmussen 1927:44). The second is an ivory carving recovered from a Late Tuniit sod house at Kapuivik (NjHa-1:2209), originally interpreted as a bird flock (Figure 4.11). When NjHa-1:2209 was shown to KH01 during the interview, they remarked on its similarity to uqalurait, as the artifact depicts sharp ridges with curved points. Although the object bears some resemblance to Tuniit carvings of bird flocks and animal teeth (Figure 4.12), NjHa-1:2209 lacks the high base, stylized heads, and elongated tail that characterise these other carvings. The uniformity of the triangular formations on NjHa-

1:2209 resemble depictions of uqalurait drawn by Inuit Elders (Figure 4.10). That this was an intentional carving form rather than a discarded attempt is supported by a perforation on its base and polishing on the edges, which indicate it was likely worn as an amulet and was a valued personal item.

Figure 4.10 Illustration of linear navigation using uqalurait. *Modified from IE008.*

Figure 4.11 Ivory carving possibly depicting uqalurait (NjHa-1:2209). *Note the pendant hole at the base of item.*

Figure 4.12 A) Ivory carvings depicting a flock of loons (NhHd-1:632) and B) a bird flock or animal teeth (NiHa-3:429). *Images reproduced from Hardenberg 2013*

The expectation that uqalurait were an important component of Tuniit navigation is supported by the fact that Tuniit occupied many of the same coastal winter sites as Amitturmiut. Although the topography of Amittuq's coastlines has changed significantly over the past four millennia, the recurring polynyas present within Foxe Basin are primarily maintained by katabatic winds and ocean currents (Prinsenbergs 1986) and have formed annually in the same locations since time immemorial (IE060; IE330). The sea ice topography between places like Kapuivik and Alarniq were likely similar for much of the Tuniit Period, and many of the same formations and travelling conditions could be expected (albeit their timing and frequency may have varied with global climate trends). Given that Tuniit did not have watercraft or dog sleds, those that lived at or near coastal campsites for the majority of the year would have shared intimate relationships with the sea ice, relying on its stability and movements for most of the year (cf. Betts et al. 2015). The lifeline that uqalurait provide for travellers may have played an important role in how Tuniit navigated their landscape, and may have structured the placement of wintering sites and their connectivity with one another in similar ways to historic Amitturmiut settlements (i.e., linear pathways; Figure 4.7).

Regardless of whether NjHa-1:2209 represents uqalurait, acknowledgement of this

possibility demonstrates an overlooked component of situated archaeological knowledges in the eastern Canadian Arctic. Archaeologists typically experience places like Kapuivik during the brief summer months when the ground is thawed enough for excavation, and our interpretations are heavily influenced by the objects and material surroundings that are routinely reported during fieldwork. As such, we do not experience many of the snow and ice formations that characterize the physical landscape for most of the year, and that affect how local people interact with their environments. As NjHa-1:2209 was recovered from a winter sod house (Area 204, Feature 5), snow formations like uqalurait were likely part of the present world of the carver, and yet they are foreign to non-Inuit archaeologists whose experiences are limited to Arctic summers. This highlights the importance of engaging with the historic realities of local peoples at the onset of Arctic archaeological projects to expand and challenge archaeological expectations (cf. Hood 1998).

4.3 Conclusion

This chapter has investigated new perspectives on Tuniit placemaking practice through the analysis of Amitturmiut oral history and environmental knowledge. Amitturmiut testimonies illustrate how traditional Inuit lifeways have not simply been dictated by survival in a harsh and unforgiving environment. Although Inuit lands are nalunaqtuq (*unpredictable*), they are abundant places for those with the abilities and resources to inhabit them, and their dynamic character serves as a catalyst for Inuit knowledge (Qitsualik-Tinsley and Qitsualik-Tinsley 2015:2; Stuhl 2017). Within a fluid and ever-changing landscape, persistent places like Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq have deep meaning and importance. They carry a variety of

material references to community knowledge and history that continue to shape the practices and structures of daily life (Howitt 2002; Price 2008; Qitsualik-Tinsley 2008; Tallbear 2015).

The research suggests that ancient communities in Amittuq were forged primarily through locally situated relationships with the land, within daily movements and activities, memories, stories, and traditions that repeatedly brought people together *in place* (Aldred 2014; Bell and Leary 2020; Binford 1980; Conolly 2018; Heyes and Dowsley 2018; Price 2008; Supernant 2017; Vergunst and Árnason 2012). Central to my discussion have been stories that emphasize the diversity of Tuniit resource practices and settlement structures within coastal settings, and stories that highlight the importance of inland sites that have gone largely undocumented within the region. I have examined analogues for underrepresented storage features and site types, and discussed how, in Inuit contexts, these places impart and inherit memory and community history. The study also presented historically situated expectations for how changing coastal topographies may have impacted the movements of Tuniit camp communities and helped shape the scale and intensity of their broader interactions.

Learning from the Amitturmiut landscape, it appears that Tuniit communities, like ancestral and contemporary Inuit communities, were fluid entities that emerged and changed through diverse placemaking practice. The entanglements of Tuniit and Inuit place histories offer an avenue towards meaningful collaboration and Saimaqatigiingniq (*reconciliation/balance between equals*), by foregrounding the agential connections of people and land in archaeological research, a perspective that takes Inuit knowledge seriously (Goldring 2015; Price 2007; QIA 2010; Rowan 2014; Todd 2016; Tuhiwai Smith 2012;). In the next three chapters, I consider Tuniit archaeological sites outside of the boundaries of culture history and aim to address both

persistence and change in the spatial and material forms I analyze (see Jervis 2018). Building on the interpretive interventions of this chapter, I explore how Tuniit settlement practices were informed not only by access to floe edge hunting spots, but through a diversity of relationships between people, animals, and materials. Attending to local occupational practices and broader landscape relations offers new explanations for how persistent places materialized through the production of camp communities, and in turn how these places may have shaped the social, economic, and political contexts in which these communities were formed and differentiated.

Chapter Five

Reconstructing Tuniit Occupational History at Kapuivik

In Amittuq, the campsite served as the primary scale of relations through which places and communities were mutually formed and differentiated. It is through the construction and use of campsites, as well as nearby extramural spaces like cache places, that humans and nonhumans routinely came together in productive and contentious dialogues through which local communities and a wider homeland were negotiated (see Chapter Four). The remains of Tuniit campsites, including artifacts, architecture, and their spatial configurations, are material manifestations of these dynamic relationships. They are embodiments of specific encounters between people and nonhumans, and expressions of the virtual possibilities for new relations that result through dynamic and historically contingent placemaking practice (Barad 2007; Braidotti 2010; Harris 2014; Watts 2016). In the next three chapters, I assess the material and spatial patterning of campsite remains at Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq to infer elements of Tuniit organizational structures and the production of social differences during the Tuniit Period. By mapping each site's occupational history, I explore how placemaking contributed to the emergence and diversification of Tuniit households and camp communities, and build inferences of inter-camp relations and long-term traditions on local and regional levels.

In this chapter, I examine archaeological and palaeogeographical data from Kapuivik to build inferences about the relationships and activities involved in the production of this important settlement place. I present data on the form, scale, materials, and location of architecture (e.g., tents, sod houses) and unwallled spaces (e.g., middens, external hearths), and

discuss inferences of small-scale variability in intra-camp household structures and inter-camp organizational strategies during the Tuniit Period (Hamilakis 2014; Hrynck and Betts 2017; Ingold 2000:213-233; Johansen 2011; Whitridge 2004: 230-233). I also examine extramural areas, especially those that bear traces of large-scale storage practices, and offer new perspectives on how community structures were produced through ephemeral but repeated engagements in these spaces (Aldred 2020; Binford 1982; Lightfoot 1998; Stewart et al. 2004). I improve the temporal resolution of my analysis by comparing archaeological contexts with an expanded sequence of radiocarbon dates. I pair this analysis with paleotopographic models based on isostasy data from the Canadian Geological Survey, which chronicle the postglacial marine emergence of land and provide earliest age limits for temporally complex settlements in coastal areas. I also assess paleotopographic models to interpret changing local environments. The models are visualized with the distribution of known archaeological features, with that caveat that Tuniit campsites are often the product of multiple construction, maintenance, and reoccupation events. When analyzed alongside excavation data and radiocarbon dates, the models help to interpret how changing material conditions were managed through the decisions, practices, and movements of past inhabitants.

Kapuvik is currently the only site in Amittuq where radiocarbon dates support continuous and relatively large-scale Tuniit occupations during the “transitional period” (c. 2800-2500 BP) — the time range that traditionally marks the replacement of the “Pre-Dorset” by the “Dorset” archaeological culture (cf. Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1962; Savelle and Dyke 2014). I reframe this division as the Early Tuniit (c. 4000 – 2500BP) and Late Tuniit (c.2500 – 1000 BP) periods, and the “transition” as a time in which important technological changes took place, but which is equally marked by continuity in local traditions of site maintenance and land

use. An important finding of this research is radiocarbon evidence for the recurrent occupation of a campsite in Area 222, which suggests that Early and Late Tuniit peoples reoccupied a relatively small residential space where caching and outdoor cooking activities occurred. This evidence challenges the division of Early and Late Tuniit peoples into discrete cultural groups (i.e., Pre-Dorset and Dorset), and suggests instead how intergenerational communities may have been shaped by memories, traditions, and the active negotiation of community histories that extended beyond the “transitional” period (Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1962). Newly acquired radiocarbon dates also indicate the long-term reuse of campsites and caching places located in Areas 223 (Early Tuniit) as well as 205 and 204 (Late Tuniit). This may suggest that recurrent practices contributed to perceptions of temporality and history that connected inhabitants with their ancestors, contributing to the maintenance of intergenerational communities.

The study highlights environmental diversity and dynamic shifts in local topography at Kapuivik during the Tuniit Period, including a rugged terrain comprised of large bedrock outcrops, glacial lakes, and shifting coastlines that formed bays, coves, and land points. People appear to have engaged with changing landscape features and nearshore environments in variable but historically situated ways, suggesting differences in household and camp level norms and traditions between contemporary communities as well as across chronological periods. This includes evidence for the strategic organization of some coastal campsites around elevated landforms during the Early Tuniit Period, possibly to establish or reaffirm social distinctions between local groups living in close proximity. Alternatively, some Late Tuniit camps were strategically located atop elevated landforms (e.g., raised terraces and uplifted plateaus), resulting in shared viewsheds of the floe edge which may have reaffirmed broader group identities and helped to facilitate cooperative hunting and food sharing with neighbouring

communities, such as those that wintered on the nearby island of Qaiqsut.

Another key finding of this research is evidence for the repeated occupation of sheltered areas that were likely located several kilometers inland from the active shoreline at their time of occupation. In most cases, these occupations appear to have centered around meat caching practices, which required an abundance of building materials (e.g., glacial till), shelter from rain and snow (e.g., large outcrops), and elevated, high drainage substrates to function properly. While there were many inland locations at Kapuivik that met these requirements, people appear to have repeatedly engaged with specific areas over several generations (i.e., Area 222). The acts of creating and exploiting a cache can be viewed as instances of memory work and historicity, as each decision about where, when, and how to construct a cache, as well as when to return to it and how to distribute its resources, carries a variety of references and experiences related to community membership, tradition, and knowledge (Bennett and Rowley 2004; IE281; IE379; IE427; IE433; IE440). Despite the ephemeral character of their construction, caches likely contributed to a lasting material record of community practices and as such may have served as important mediums for the negotiation of intergenerational community identities (Bauer and Johansen 2023; Friesen 2001; Lyons et al. 2010; Mills 2008; Morrison 2016; Walls 2019).

The diversity of Tuniit locational strategies, inter-camp organizational structures, and recurrent placemaking activities in both coastal and inland contexts at Kapuivik challenge the temporal logics of using beach ridge sequences as an apparatus to relatively date archaeological sites (cf. Meldgaard 1962, Savelle et al 2009). The findings instead suggest that Tuniit occupational practices were often not structured around the active shoreline, and as such the geological age of beach formations and the cultural age of sites are often not contemporary. While beach ridge sequencing is not a reliable relative dating method on its own, I argue it

remains useful for setting the earliest age limit for coastal occupations and for understanding how radiocarbon dated contexts correspond to pronounced changes in coastal topography, which likely impacted the seasonal accessibility of settlements (e.g., annual sea ice development in nearshore environments) and the availability of local marine resources. As such, they permit the evaluation of the distinct material affordances that these environments offered, contextualizing how Tuniit communities managed their surroundings and maintained connections with emergent places through socially diverse and historically contingent practices.

This chapter begins with an overview of the Kapuivik survey results. I present an updated site map and summarize new features identified through the 2018 pedestrian and RPA surveys. The spatial configuration of Tuniit campsites across Kapuivik is then examined, beginning with a newly identified site (NjHa-45) and feature cluster (near Area 210) followed by revisited areas from the main Kapuivik site (NjHa-1). Next, I provide initial assessment of the character of Tuniit organizational structures and differences in land use. I deepen my inferences of place-community relations by analyzing paleogeographic models that visualize the topographic transformation of Kapuivitt Island. I then expand my narrative through the presentation of a detailed chronological framework of Kapuivik's occupation, informed primarily by the analysis of 56 radiocarbon dates. The chapter ends with a discussion of what the material and spatial patterning of dwellings, campsites, and caching places suggest about the relational nature of Tuniit communities, and offer new perspectives on Tuniit social life at Kapuivik.

5.1 Assessing the Spatial Structure and Setting of Tuniit Campsites at Kapuivik

In this section I examine and discuss 52 new Tuniit features that were identified in 2018

through pedestrian and remotely piloted aircraft (RPA) surveys and compare these data with previously identified site areas. To date, there are 331 known Tuniit features in the Kapuivik area, which include 274 surface dwellings (e.g., tents, snow houses), 18 semi-subterranean sod dwellings, 36 caches, and three burial cairns (Figure 5.1). An additional 17 buried or inundated features were recorded through visible light and thermal RPA captures, and six more probable inundated features were identified through the analysis of Worldview 2 satellite imagery. The survey data suggest synchronic and diachronic differences in locational strategies and organizational structures that were fundamental to the emergence and differentiation of Kapuivik as a settlement place. The data reveals a greater diversity in Tuniit site types, including the preferential selection for sheltered inland areas for caching places, freshwater features rather than coastlines for some seasonal camps, and elevated ridges with vantages of the floe edge for long-term winter settlements in later periods. These findings challenge previous interpretations of Tuniit land use and offer new perspectives on the structure and organization of communities.

I begin with an initial interpretation of two newly documented sites identified through the 2018 surveys, which include NjHa-45 and a new feature cluster near Area 210. Although time and labour constraints in 2018 prevented the testing of these sites, the survey data highlight the importance of inland settlement practices, challenging models of timeless coastal settlement traditions and suggesting that occupations on elevated terraces may represent a wide range of temporalities. I then provide an account of new features identified in the main coastal sequence, specifically the 223 (Early Tuniit), 222 (“Transitional”), and 205 and 204 (Late Tuniit) site areas. I explore what the distribution of feature clusters suggests about land use and community configurations in coastal settings at Kapuivik. Survey data from coastal site areas suggest that elevated landforms, such as outcrops, escarpments, and terraces, were incorporated into Tuniit

Figure 5.1 New site map of Kapuvik showing the distribution of new Tuniit features identified through survey. *Basemap: ArcticDEM*

spatial practices to demarcate campsites and construct specific visual relationships within the landscape. The survey data also indicate that boulder caches (*qinngniit*) are strongly associated with surface dwelling structures (e.g., tents and snow houses) in both inland and coastal contexts, as well as during both the Early and Late Tuniit periods. This suggests that recurring short-term seasonal practices persisted at Kapuivik through both the Early and Late Tuniit periods, and that campsite structure in these contexts differed from long-term cold weather settlements at the site. These differences highlight the flexibility and relationality of community organization in both periods.

5.1.1 New Sites: An Assessment of Inland Settlement Practices

5.1.1.1 NjHa-45. A new site identified 250m northeast of Area 223 suggests that multi-seasonal occupations took place inland from coastal sites during the Tuniit Period (Figure 5.1). NjHa-45 is situated in an area of granite and gneiss till and bordered by a small fluvio-glacial lake and bedrock outcrops. Located at 62-66 meters above sea level (MASL), where marine emergence occurred between 5000 and 4500 BP, the area predates the peopling of the region, which suggests that the coastline receded long before features were constructed. NjHa-45 contains 17 boulder structures made of the surrounding till, including 12 surface dwellings, an isolated midpassage, four boulder caches, and a submerged dwelling near the southern boundary of the lake (Figure 5.2). Although formal artifacts were not identified during survey, chert debitage and *in situ* nodules of oolitic chert were observed near the surfaces of F1 and F2, materials that are typically attributed to Tuniit rather than Inuit assemblages (Maxwell 1985).

Given the preservation of dwellings, it is likely that many features at NjHa-45 were

Figure 5.2 Distribution of Tuniit features and landscape elements at NjHa-45. Feature close ups are RPA captures. *Basemap: Worldview 2, 2021*

constructed after the lake and surrounding bedrock had formed (Ramsden and Murray 1995; Ryan 2003; Taylor 1968). Most of the dwellings are small, heavily disturbed oval structures (2–7m²) without obvious internal features (e.g., hearths), similar to Early Tuniit dwellings identified in Area 223. The F7 isolated midpassage is also characteristic of Early Tuniit axial features (Darwent et al. 2018:526), and heavy coverage of blistered rock tripe on architectural elements support that the site is of Tuniit origin³⁸.

The most notable architectural component of NjHa-45 are the layouts of two dwellings, F4 and F5. These dwellings are each comprised of an oval body connected to three architectural lobes that may have served as separate living or storage areas (Figure 5.3). F4 and F5 are significantly larger than other dwellings at the site, with each measuring 16-17m². F16 may have been similar in structure to F4 and F5, but its architecture has been disturbed by post-depositional processes. Only one other Tuniit dwelling at Kapuivik, F57 in Area 223, appears to share this architectural form (Figure 5.1). Like F4 and F5, F57 is situated in heavy boulder till. A similar dwelling feature was also identified at Kaleruserk (NiHF-2) at 45 MASL³⁹ in an area of frost-shattered limestone (Walker 2019c). These similarities in form may indicate that multilobe dwellings were deliberately constructed in areas where abundant building materials were widely available, suggesting household-level differences in locational strategies and architectural practices during the Early Tuniit Period.

The complex forms of F4 and F5 suggest that they are not the remains of tents.

Additionally, the absence of a berm or depression suggest that they were not sod houses (Ryan

³⁸ Blistered rock tripe has a very slow growth rate in Arctic climates (0.3-0.4mm per year), and as such takes several centuries of undisturbed growth to cover the surface of even small architectural stones (Hansen 2004).

³⁹ Marine emergence of the 45 MASL terrace at NiHF-2 occurred between 4000-3500 BP, suggesting this feature may be contemporaneous with those found along the upper terraces of Area 223.

2016; Savelle and Dyke 2014; Sutherland 2013). Instead, it is possible these structures are the remains of qarmats or snow houses, the latter which are notoriously difficult to identify in the archaeological record (Savelle 1984). While there are no confirmed Tuniit snow houses in Amittuq for comparison, the small circular lobes that characterize F4 and F5 are reminiscent of Early and Historic Inuit snow houses (Figure 5.4). However, the inferred temporality of NjHa-45 and the fact that F4 and F5 lack the sleeping platforms and cold trap entrances characteristic of Inuit dwellings support that they are a Tuniit variant of this architectural technology. The isolated hearth (F7) may also be the remains of a snow dwelling, since small snow houses typically lack peripheral boundary markers (Ramsden and Murray 1995:112-115). Alternatively, larger snow structures, like F4 and F5, required strong stone foundations and circular lobes for structural integrity (IE108; IE157).

Figure 5.3 Comparison of features 4 (left) and 5 (right) at NjHa-45. Note the heavy grey-black coating of blistered rock tripe on the *in situ* boulders of each feature.

Figure 5.4 A) Historic Amitturmiut snow house reconstructed by Mathiassen*(1928:126-127) and B) Close up of Early Inuit multilobe dwelling (Area 209–F21) — note differences in internal architecture, accumulated vegetation, and a lack of rock tripe compared to NjHa-45 F4 and F5.
 * *Reproduced from Dawson (2002:475).*

The possibility that NjHa-45 was a cold weather campsite is supported by the presence of several large cache structures. These structures are slightly raised mounds covered with large slab boulders (as seen in Figure 5.2) that resemble caribou and sea mammal meat caches constructed by ancestral Inuit. It is believed that Tuniiit boulder caches were used for similar storage purposes, as suggested by previous research and local oral history (Bielawski 1988; Mary-Rousselière 1976; IE427; IE433). The identification of sea mammal remains in excavated boulder caches at Kapuivik (e.g., 223-F58⁴⁰ and 222-F82b) and Qalirusiq (Melgaard 1954a; Rowley 2004) further support that these structures were used to store large game.

It is possible that NjHa-45 was selected as a caching place due to its unique physiography. Historically, the Inuit were known to build boulder caches in areas that were

⁴⁰ F58 contained only one faunal element (a walrus maxilla) but cut marks on the specimen confirm human activity.

protected from the dominant winds, which in Amittuq are Uangnnaq (NW) and Nigiq (SE) (cf. Figure 4.13). Building caches in wind-protected areas prevented snow buildup, making them easier to locate at the times they were the most needed (IE438). That the large outcrops surrounding NjHa-45 offer protection from Uangnnaq and Nigiq (Figure 5.2) may indicate that Early Tuniit inhabitants shared similar sets of intergenerational knowledge about caching that informed their practices.

The caches suggests that at least two occupational events took place at NjHa-45: one to construct the caches, and another to exploit them. This may explain variation in the size and form of dwellings at NjHa-45. Small oval boulder dwellings without central hearth features may have been tents constructed in the summer or fall when caches were prepared. Access to the lake at this time would have allowed for meat to be properly cooled and cleaned prior to storage (IE396; IE433). Alternatively, the multilobe dwellings may have been occupied in the winter or early spring when caches were likely exploited. The protection from snow accumulation offered by the outcrops may have ensured that building materials were accessible to construct the stone foundations of these dwellings. In the case of blizzards, which usually blow from Uangnnaq, the northwestern outcrop may have protected snow houses from collapse or burial (IE025; IE172).

Although inferences of NjHa-45 are based on limited survey data, available evidence suggests that some Early Tuniit inhabitants of Kapuivik built their camps inland from the active shoreline, and that these inland occupations were not limited to warm weather seasonal activities as archaeologists have previously anticipated (Maxwell 1985; Bielawski 1988). However, additional fieldwork is necessary to confirm the temporality and seasonality of occupational activities at NjHa-45.

5.1.1.2 Area 210. In Area 210, 19 new Tuniit features (30 total) were identified through pedestrian and RPA surveys (Figure 5.1). Area 210 consists of a flat plain bordered by a large lake and bedrock outcrops. Relative sea level curves indicate that marine emergence of Area 210 occurred shortly after 3300BP (Savelle and Dyke 2014: Figure 3b), providing the earliest possible age of occupations. Features in Area 210 were originally identified as Pre-Dorset (Early Tuniit) by Meldgaard (1962). The identification of partial excavations in F4 and F5 suggest that an open socket harpoon head (M3501-5) recovered from the 35 MASL terrace came from one of these two features (Melgaard 1954b). This harpoon head style remains strongly associated with radiocarbon dated Early Tuniit contexts throughout the Eastern Arctic (Maxwell 1985; Levasseur 2022). Savelle and Dyke (2009) identified 11 circular surface dwellings during their resurvey of Area 210 in 2003. The dwellings range from 4 to 10m², and six of them contain axial features (e.g., hearths or midpassages). The small size of these features indicates that they may have served as temporary dwellings for nuclear families (Savelle and Dyke 2009:228). Savelle and Dyke (2009) noted chert debitage on the surface of several dwellings, which supports that they were constructed and used by Tuniit peoples.

In 2018, our pedestrian surveys identified five new features within the previously defined site boundary of Area 210. These features include four boulder surface dwellings similar in form to those identified by Savelle and Dyke (2009), as well as one boulder cache (Figure 5.5). With the aid of RPA photogrammetry, 14 additional features were identified 50m to the west, in an area of heavy rock tumble separated by an escarpment (Figure 5.5). These western features include five small surface dwellings, two external hearths, and seven cache features. One cache (F24) is a boulder structure similar to those at NjHa-45, while the others are surface cairns without mounds or berms, made of smaller boulders and cobbles (Figures 5.5).

Figure 5.5 Distribution of Tuniit features and landscape elements near Area 210. Feature close ups are RPA captures, and excavations are visualized through RPA-derived elevation modelling. Basemap: Worldview 2, 2021.

Available evidence suggests that the six cairn structures may have been used to cache fish. As described in oral-historical and ethnographic sources, surface containers that permitted good air flow were built by Inuit to cache birds or fish in the fall (IE306; IE427; IE433; Friesen 2002). Amitturmiut oral testimonies describe the Tuniit as having constructed similar structures to store fish, which can still be seen on the sides of rivers and lakes throughout Amittuq (See Chapter Four, Section 4.1.2.1). While fish remains are rarely preserved in faunal assemblages at Kapuivik (Kotar 2022), several barbed fishing harpoon heads recovered from Tuniit dwellings 400m to the south in Areas 204 and 205 support that fishing may have been a component of subsistence practices at Kapuivik, or took place at nearby sites (Desrosiers 2018; Kotar 2019).

Kapuivik, which translates *to the place where we spear the fish*, was an important fishing locale during the Early and Historic Inuit periods (KH02; cf. IE263). The lake in Area 210 is the largest at Kapuivik, and its outflow likely connected to a large estuary that bordered Kapuivitt Qinnua (Skeoch Bay) for much of its history. That the lake may have been used to fish for anadromous char is evidenced by the presence of several Early Inuit houses on the western shore, and a potential inundated feature resembling a small tidal weir at its eastern periphery (Figure 5.6, cf. Stenton 1991). Young char may have swum out to sea from this water body in the spring (IE150), or travelled upriver to spawn in the fall (Figure 5.7, cf. KH02; IE409).

If the cairns structures were used to cache fish, Tuniit dwellings in this area were likely occupied during the fall when arctic char were cached whole (IE433; cf. Chapter four, section 2.2.1). The steep outcrops surrounding the caches would have offered shade to prevent the spoilage in the fall sunlight (IE434). The identification of two external hearth features (F22 and F28) suggest that the site was occupied in warmer weather when outdoor cooking took place (Maxwell 1985; Ryan 2010). It is possible that some dwellings in Area 210 were constructed

Figure 5.6 Drone capture showing the new site area identified near Area 210 as well as a potential submerged dwelling (center) and fishing weir (right) near the outflow of the lake.

Figure 5.7 (Left) A view of the lake output near Area 210 (A), flowing east towards Kapuivitt Qinnngua (B). (Right) a composite image visualizing ground water moisture and drainage, sourced from Worldview 3.

by returning occupants who exploited caches in the winter (IE433; cf. Chapter Four, Section 2.2.1). Like NjHa-45, Area 210 may have been reused as a caching place, in part, because of the shelter the surrounding bedrock provided from snow accumulation (Figure 5.8; IE029; IE147; IE163). The possibility of separate fall and winter occupations may explain why dwellings with external hearths are positioned close to the lakeshore, while dwellings with internal hearths are grouped in the southeastern portion of Area 210m near the boulder caches (Figure 5.5). These differences may suggest seasonally specific organizational strategies and multiple temporalities of site use.

Figure 5.8 A northward facing RPA capture of Area 210 showing the protective outcrops that surround the lake, in relation to the surrounding plateaus. The Area 223 outcrops are depicted as well, further north.

Like NjHa-45, additional fieldwork is required to understand the socioeconomic context of Tuniit occupational episodes in and around Area 210. However, the survey data suggest that Early Tuniit peoples, much like the Amitturmiut, engaged in a diversity of land use practices at

Kapuvik. Occupations at both NjHa-45 and Area 210 appear to have prioritized access to landscape elements that included natural shelters, freshwater features, and building materials (e.g., glacial till), which were presumably favourable for caching activities. These areas are not visible from the coast, so that their repeated use may suggest community memory and intergenerational knowledge of their location and affordances. As campsites at NjHa-45 and Area 210 appear to have been constructed with an intent to return and exploit stored food, further investigation of these areas may provide important information about the larger assemblages of practice, movement, and knowledge that shaped enduring community relations in inland areas.

5.1.2 Reassessing Tuniit Campsites in the Main Coastal Sequence (NjHa-1)

Pedestrian and RPA surveys carried out within the main coastal sequence uncovered 17 new Tuniit features and 17 potential inundated or buried features, located in Areas 223, 222, 205, and 204 (Figure 5.1). These site areas were previously investigated through extensive ATV surveys by Savelle and Dyke in 2003, but were not documented in detail at the time. Through the analysis of survey data and excavated features documented in 2018, I infer elements of Tuniit locational strategies and sociospatial differences between residential areas. I present an overview of Tuniit campsites in each area and offer new interpretations for settlement practices and organizational structures within coastal settings. This overview provides necessary context for chronological comparisons of Tuniit campsite construction and use in Section 2 of this chapter.

The study suggests that Tuniit campsite structures differed within coastal contexts, and that the seasonality, duration, and economic associations of their occupation were varied and complex. This variability is persistent in both Early and Late Tuniit contexts. I propose that some

previously noted differences in the seasonal architecture and social organization of Early and Late Tuniit peoples at Kapuivik (e.g., Meldgaard 1962) may be the product of spatial biases in previous coastal surveys and chronological problems resulting from the relative dating of beach ridges sequences (see Chapter Two, Section 2.1.6). Synchronic differences in architecture and campsite structure in both periods highlight social differences at the household and camp scales, and offer new perspectives on changing inter-camp relations within a local setting.

5.1.2.1 Area 223. Prior to the 2018 fieldwork, Area 223 was believed to have consisted of 71 Early Tuniit structures situated on beach terraces between 28 and 51.5 MASL, which are associated with geological ages of 2800 – 4000 BP (Savelle and Dyke 2009). These structures are primarily comprised of boulder surface dwellings, but also include three boulder caches, two external hearths, two human burial cairns, and an isolated midpassage. Surveys conducted in 2018 using pedestrian and RPA visible light methods revealed three additional boulder caches and a submerged dwelling in a northeastern pond. Two buried dwellings were identified through thermal RPA surveys, and the internal structure of unexcavated dwellings were also documented (Walker 2020a: Figures 7 and 10). An updated map is presented in Figure 5.9a.

There are eight feature clusters in Area 223 which I interpret as separate campsites, as well as several isolated features (Figure 5.9b). While dwellings at NjHa-45 were oriented towards the lake or wind shelters, most in Area 223 appear to face the coast. For example, the entrances of five excavated dwellings (F54, F51, F50, F43, and F38) face south/southwest towards the ancient shoreline (Figure 5.10). However, F20 and 21 in Cluster 7 present an exception to this pattern, as their midpassages (and inferred entrances) face away from the coast and towards a burial cairn located 35m northwest on the same terrace (F37). This may suggest that F20 and F21 are the product of a separate occupational episode related to practices regarding

Figure 5.9 (A) Map of Area 223 showing the distribution of new features in relation to previous features and topography; (B) the distribution of different structural forms and feature clusters in Area 223 in relation to simplified landscape elements.

death and burial (see Chapter Four, Section 4.2.2.2). A similar arrangement may be present in Cluster 1 where four abutting boulder dwellings face either southwest towards the ancient coast or northeast towards a burial cairn, based on the orientation of their axial features (F63).

The spatial organization of features along Area 223's upper terraces illustrates how local topography may have been actively incorporated into organizational practices. For instance, most cache structures are found near the edges of outcrops, similar to those at NjHa-45 and in Area 210 (Figure 5.9). Several campsites were placed near outcrops that limited their visibility and access from one another, which could suggest a conscious effort to establish social distinctions between contemporarily occupied camps (Figure 5.10). For instance, based on the marine emergence of 45 – 40 MASL terraces, Cluster 4 was likely constructed after 3500 BP, with dwellings positioned between multiple outcrops, with their entrances having a clear view of the coastline and floe edge (cf. Figure 5.10b). Given that radiocarbon evidence suggests Cluster 3 was constructed earlier than Cluster 4 (e.g., a date from F51 of cal. 4145-3730 BP [2 σ]), it is likely that Cluster 4 was constructed to be occluded from Cluster 3, and potentially from Clusters 6 and 7, as well. That features along the upper terraces were constructed to produce specific visual relationships, rather than to provide wind shelter, is supported by the fact that the entrances of dwellings in Clusters 3 and 4 were exposed to the open sea. If the intention of was to use bedrock outcrops for a windbreak, it is unlikely that the campsites would have been positioned so that their entrances faced open water.

While the layouts of Clusters 1-4 are well-delineated, those of Clusters 6-8 are less defined and share a similar vantage of the coast and floe edge. The high density of dwellings on these lower terraces may indicate that a greater number of people lived in these camps, as suggested by Savelle and Dyke (2014), or that repeated, brief occupations were carried out by a

Figure 5.10a Topographic evolution of Area 223 at 4000-4500 BP in relation to archaeological features*.

**Quantiles were calculated using the geometrical interval classification method in ArcGIS Pro to enhance the visualization of local topographic variation. As such, class breaks in the elevation data vary between the time-slices.*

Figure 5.10b Topographic evolution of Area 223 at 3000-3500 BP, in relation to archaeological features.

smaller number of people. However, it may also reflect changes in how households identified with a broader community during the later half of the Early Tuniit Period, such as increasing interactions between contemporary occupants or between later occupants and the camp remains of previous occupants. As the gathering of people in shared spaces is an expected catalyst of community formation, the visuospatial patterning of feature clusters in Area 223 may embody changing social affiliations over generations of camp use (cf. Chapter Four, Section 2.1). This interpretation will be further discussed in Section 2 when radiocarbon evidence for campsite contemporaneity and reoccupation are analyzed.

5.1.2.2 Area 222. Area 222 is comprised of coastal terraces covered with a mixture of sparsely vegetated tundra and sandy gravel, located in the center of the main coastal site (NiHf-1). Prior to the 2018 fieldwork, there were 105 documented Tuniit features situated between 26 and 38 MASL, terraces associated with geological ages of 2800–3500 BP and radiocarbon dates that corroborated this time frame of occupation. Features included 98 boulder surface dwellings, five isolated midpassages, an external hearth, and a boulder cache. Pedestrian survey in 2018 of the lower terraces (25–28 MASL) documented 6 surface dwellings, three boulder caches, and two external hearths. A new site map is presented in Figures 5.11a and 5.11b.

Unlike the upper terraces of Area 223, dwellings in Area 222 are not visually separated from one another, and there are fewer distinctive feature clusters. Instead, features on the upper terraces are arranged in dense but even rows with a vantage of the ancient coast (Figure 5.11b and Figure 5.12). Alternatively, dwellings on the lower terraces are fewer in number and irregularly clustered in an area surrounded by glacial erratic. The concentration of caches and external hearths in this lower cluster suggests that the campsite was used primarily as a seasonal

Figure 5.11a Map of Area 222 showing the distribution of new features in relation to previous features and topography.

Figure 5.11b Map of Area 222 showing the distribution of different structural forms and feature groupings in relation to simplified landscape elements.

caching place, and was likely selected because of the building materials available from the surrounding till. However, one remaining cache (F15), is located at 37 MASL in a sheltered area similar to the boulder caches at NjHa-45 and in Area 223. These differences may indicate that occupation of the lower terraces was characterized by brief, seasonal episodes of cache construction and exploitation while dwellings along the upper terraces are the product long-term cold weather settlements, when preventing snow accumulation around caches was necessary.

Some dwellings in the lower cluster, despite their irregular arrangement, are oriented towards the coast. For example, the entrances of F82 and F85, which were excavated in 2018, are oriented south/southwest towards the relic shoreline (Figure 5.12). Alternatively, the entrance to F84 (also excavated in 2018) appears to face southeast, within view of the coast as well as the entrance of F85. A test pit placed between F84 and F85 in 2016 (TP21) yielded a scrapper and several worked flakes, suggesting this was an extramural activity space shared by these households (Figure 5.12). Another test pit placed in a lithic scatter just east of F82 and F83 contained over 130 chert flakes as well as several pieces of worked slate (Desrosiers 2018). This was an interesting find given that slate tools are typically associated with Late Tuniit contexts. As will be further discussed in section 2, radiocarbon dates indicate that F84 and F85 were constructed several centuries prior to F82 and F83, despite their proximity on a shared terrace. The occurrence of multiple occupational episodes at the campsite may explain the irregular arrangement of dwellings within the cluster. Given their spatial and chronological context, the positioning of dwellings suggests that vantage of the floe edge was a prioritized element for some, but not all, occupational episodes along the lower terraces. Archaeological evidence for seasonal differences in caching and camping practices across Kapuivik will be expanded upon in section 2 to draw richer inferences about community organization over the

Figure 5.12a Topographic evolution of Area 222 at 3500 BP, in relation to archaeological features.

Figure 5.12b Topographic evolution of Area 222 at 3000 BP, in relation to archaeological features.

Figure 5.12c Topographic evolution of Area 222 at 2500 BP, in relation to archaeological features.

Temporal period of 2800-2500 BP that has been conventionally associated with the Pre-Dorset to Dorset cultural transition.

5.1.2.3 Areas 204 and 205. The 204 and 205 site areas are situated on opposite sides of a bedrock outcrop, located between 19 and 24 MASL (Figure 5.13a, cf. Meldgaard 1962; Savelle and Dyke 2014). Prior to my fieldwork, Area 205 was comprised of three intact boulder dwellings, two previously excavated dwellings (F1 and F2)

⁵, and a large extramural lithic scatter (TP8), while Area 204 contained 20 Late Tuniit features that included 18 semi-subterranean dwellings, two boulder surface dwellings, and two previously excavated Early Inuit sod houses (F1 and F2). The distribution of new, potential, and previously identified Tuniit features in Areas 204 and 205 are shown in Figure 5.14.

The 2018 surveys identified a boulder cache, external hearth, and unrecorded excavated dwelling. A small circular boulder feature (F6) containing carefully stacked walrus bones and large pieces of antler was also identified during excavation of F5 (cf. Kotar 2022: 241). Oral historical and ethnographic evidence suggest that this structure was possibly an equipment cache used to store raw material resources, such as bone and antler. Due to the frequency of debitage, microblades, and scrapers in F6, and the sewing needles in F5, the cache may have also contained animal skins for cloth work (Figure 5.14, cf. IE281; IE428; IE469). In Area 204, ten potential sod house depressions were also identified through post-field analysis of thermal RPA data. Thermal anomalies were compared with a digital terrain model (DTM) derived from the RPA elevation data to further examine potential dwelling structures (Figure 5.15).

⁴¹ The original form of these dwellings is undocumented (cf. Meldgaard 1962). However, a trench placed at the edge of F1 in 2018 uncovered an *in situ* platform characteristic of Tuniit sod houses (cf. Figure 5.14a). Alternatively, the boulder architecture and shallow excavation of F2 suggests it was surface dwelling.

Figure 5.13 Map of Areas 204 and 205 showing the distribution of new features in relation to previously identified features and topography; (B) the distribution of different structural forms and feature groupings in relation to simplified landscape elements.

Figure 5.14 (*left*) 205-F6, the potential equipment cache abutting 205-F5* compared to (*right*) an Early Inuit equipment cache from Stewart et. al. (2000:265 Figure 8). *Unit Scale=1m.

The layout of dwellings in Area 204 and 205 suggests that the placement of Late Tuniit coastal campsites was — similar to Early Tuniit campsites — strongly influenced by local topography. For instance, features in both site areas appear to have been strategically positioned around the large outcrop, similar to winter campsites located on the upper terraces of Area 223. The strategic positioning around the large outcrop suggests a deliberate practice aimed at establishing specific visual connections within the landscape. This intention is supported by radiocarbon evidence that places the construction of multiple dwellings to several centuries after the marine emergence of the 19-24 MASL terraces (Figure 5.16, see also Section 2). This may have been done to limit the visibility of campsites between the two areas, as feature clusters are positioned so as to not be within view of one another. However, both areas have a clear vantage of the coastline in multiple directions (Figure 5.16). This placement may have offered occupants the ability to monitor potential hunting areas and select the best locations for daily hunting trips based on the movements of sea mammals along the floe edge (IE017; IE062; IKT 1992:96). Area 204 is also within vantage of the nearby island of Qaiqsut, which emerged

Figure 5.15 RPA-derived DTM showing potential sod houses located along the eastern side of Area 204, with thermal imagery close-ups visualizing dwelling extents and internal structures.

Figure 5.16a Topography of Area 204 and 205 at 3000 BP in relation to archaeological features.

Figure 5.16b Topography of Area 204 and 205 at 2500 BP in relation to archaeological features.

Figure 5.16c Topography of Area 204 and 205 at 2000 BP in relation to archaeological features.

Figure 5.16d Topography of Area 204 and 205 at 1500 BP in relation to archaeological features.

around 2000 BP and which was also occupied by Late Tuniit peoples (Figure 5.17; IE017; KH02). As such, its placement may suggest wider community relationships between neighbouring winter or spring camps.

Late Tuniit occupants may have also selected this slightly inland area because of its accessibility to different building materials. The outcrops surrounding Area 204 would have trapped sediments during snowmelt drainage from higher areas, preventing soil erosion and increasing ground moisture. These sedimentation processes would have provided access to the thick organic surfaces required for cutting sod bricks, for the construction of semi-subterranean houses (IE295). Building these dwellings in elevated areas also prevented the flooding of house floors in the event of snow melt (IE426; IE442). That this area was particularly suitable for constructing sod houses is supported by the presence of the two Early Inuit sod houses (204-F1 and 204-F2), as well as by the fact that the only other Tuniit sod houses at Kapuivik are located along the southwest face of the same outcrop, which is also covered in thick caribou moss, in Area 207 (Figure 5.13b).

Two cache structures are found near surface dwellings in Area 205, but caches are absent from Area 204, suggesting they were seasonally specific structures. This could be because semi-subterranean sod houses were mainly occupied from the early winter to early spring, a time of year when people were more likely to exploit caches previously constructed at fall camps rather than preparing new ones. During the winter, meat could be easily stored in the deep freeze, reducing the need for external storage features⁶. This supports the general patterning of boulder caches throughout Kapuivik, which are commonly found in association with inland surface dwellings, suggesting they were constructed during shorter occupational episodes and likely

⁴² This may also explain the lower frequency of caches in Area 223, which were likely long-term winter dwellings.

during the summer or fall.

Figure 5.17 View of the southeastern coast of Kapuivik, towards Qaiqsut.

While most campsites in Areas 223 and 222 are oriented towards the coast, those in area 205 and 204 appear to be oriented towards each other. For example, our excavations confirmed that 205–F5 is oriented southeast towards F1 and F3 (Figure 5.13a). Based on the positioning of the hearth next to F4, it appears that this dwelling also faced towards F1 and F3. This may

suggest that, similar to the lower terraces of Area 222, features in Area 205 were organized around communal extramural spaces. This is supported by the materials recovered from extramural test pits in Area 205, including significant lithic debitage, worked slate, and chert tools like microblades and endblades that are indicative of outdoor workspaces between houses (see TP 6-9 and 13 in Figure 5.13b). Two needles were also found in TP 7 (Desrosiers 2018), suggesting that sewing activities may have taken place between F4 and F5, near the equipment cache. The presence of a large lithic scatter north of 205-F4 also supports that extramural economic activities were commonplace, suggesting that the boulder dwellings in Area 205 were occupied during summer or fall when outdoor flintknapping and hide working activities were more likely to occur.

While it is difficult to discern dwelling entrances in Area 204, features with internal architecture visualized through thermal imagery suggest a similar organizational pattern in the eastern cluster. For example, the orientation of a raised platform (feature A, Figure 5.15) and a hearth (feature B, Figure 5.15) suggest that these dwellings faced north/northeast towards F13 and F15. Extramural test pits in this cluster contained worked ivory and bone, microblades, and chert debitage. However, test pits containing cultural materials were limited to the direct vicinity of particular dwellings rather than the larger extramural spaces between dwellings (cf. TP1-5 in Figure 5.13b). Alternatively, features in the southern portion of Area 204 appear to be oriented in a line and presumably faced either southwest or northeast. As such, it appears that Area 204 contains the remains of multiple campsites, while Area 205 was likely one campsite. The contemporaneity of dwellings in area 204, as well as between Areas 204 and 205, will be further explored through the analysis of radiocarbon dates in the next section.

5.2 Mapping Persistence and Change in Community Relations at Kapuivik

New chronological evidence from Kapuivik offers enriched perspectives on the temporality of Tuniit occupations, including evidence for intergenerational site maintenance practices and small-scale changes in household and camp-scale organizational structures over time. The study includes the analysis of 56 radiocarbon dates, which are compared with paleotopographic models to help determine the earliest age limits for coastal occupations. I assess the degree of occupational continuity present within the Tuniit occupational sequence, and draw inferences about the construction, maintenance, differential reuse, and abandonment of residential areas at Kapuivik. The assessment highlights the complexity of people-place relations during the Tuniit Period, and the agency of these relations in continuously redefining communities at the scales of the household and camp.

I first provide an updated chronological framework to better understand the degree of occupational continuity present within the main site sequence. The paleotopographic models are particularly useful for refining the early limit of marine-modelled radiocarbon dates located in coastal areas, as these dates have greater calibrated temporal ranges compared to terrestrial dates. This new chronology enables the comparison of radiocarbon dates within and between site areas to identify instances of intergenerational campsite maintenance and reoccupation. I explore these data alongside archaeological evidence for seasonality and economic practices (e.g., faunal indicators and architectural forms) to build richer inferences about the social and material relationships that brought people together in enduring ways. I then examine evidence for small scale changes in occupational practices within and between Early and Late Tuniit communities, centering my assessment on the differential patterning of dwelling forms as well the size and organization of campsites. These data suggest a gradual shift from small camps with multi-

family households at the beginning of the Early Tuniit Period to larger camps comprised of nuclear family households by the middle of the Late Tuniit Period. Evidence for continuity in locational strategies and socioeconomic practices suggest persistence in community traditions despite the introduction of new technologies and changes in community organization.

5.2.1 A New Chronological Framework

The expanded radiocarbon sequence from Kapuivik includes 11 new assays as well as the recalibration of 45 previously reported dates (Table 5.1, Figure 5.18 and 5.19). The dates expand the temporal range of Tuniit occupations at Kapuivik by several centuries, providing the first clear evidence for occupation at the beginning of the Early Tuniit Period (Table 5.1). The earliest date, cal. 4145 – 3730 BP (2σ), comes from a walrus sample retrieved from a large surface dwelling, 223-F51, located on the 46 MASL terrace. As the marine emergence of this terrace occurred after 4000 BP, F51 was likely constructed around 3900-3800 BP (Figure 5.11, cf. Figure 5.19). This correlation suggests that at least some Tuniit campsites located along the upper terraces of Area 223 were coastal during their initial construction (see 5.1.2.1). Interestingly, radiocarbon dates recovered from the upper terraces of other site areas, such as 213-F1 (51.6 MASL) and 215-F2 (46.2 MASL), are nearly two centuries later than 223-F51 despite being located at higher elevations. When taken into consideration with the new features located at NjHa-45 and near Area 210, the dates suggest that inland occupations were commonplace near Kapuivik during the first half of the Early Tuniit Period.

Table 5.1 Radiocarbon Assays from Kapuivik. Dates Calibrated in OxCal 4.4 using INTCAL20.

Lab Code*	¹⁴ C Age (bp)	Sample Species**	Calibrated or Marine Modelled Age cal. BP 1σ	Calibrated or Marine Modelled Age cal. BP 2σ	Site, Provenience	Orthometric Height (MASL)	Reference
UCIAMS251137	4215 ± 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	4051 – 3847	4145 – 3730	NjHa-1: 223-51, Level 2	46	Kotar 2022
AA61947	3723 ± 58	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3438 – 3219	3556 – 3099	NjHa-1: 213-F1, Surface	51.6	Savelle et al. 2009
AA61951	3692 ± 58	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3400 – 3182	3510 – 3050	NjHa-1: 216-F1, Surface	45.8	Savelle et al. 2009
AA62365	3114 ± 54	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	3391 – 3245	3449 – 3181	NjHa-1: 216-F1, Surface	45.8	Savelle et al. 2009
UCIAMS251132	3100 ± 15	<i>Lepus arcticus</i>	3361 – 3265	3372 – 3250	NjHa-1: 223-51, Level 2	46	Kotar 2022
AA61950	3582 ± 58	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3286 – 3044	3380 – 2915	NjHa-1: 215-F2, Surface	46.2	Savelle et al. 2009
P210	2898 ± 135	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	3211 – 2870	3361 – 2765	NjHa-1: 216-F1, Unknown	45.8	Meldgaard 1960b, 1962
UCIAMS251131	3535 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3200 – 2999	3305 – 2903	NjHa-1: 223-39, Level 2	34.8	Kotar 2022
AA61952	3503 ± 57	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3185 – 2937	3303 – 2824	NjHa-1: 219-F7, Surface	45.5	Savelle et al. 2009
UCIAMS251129	2960 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	3165 – 3076	3207 – 3066	NjHa-1: 223-39, Level 2	34.8	Kotar 2022
AA61948	3461 ± 57	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3126 – 2883	3229 – 2768	NjHa-1: 214-F3, Surface	48.2	Savelle et al. 2009
AA61954	3459 ± 57	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3119 – 2875	3227 – 2765	NjHa-1: 223-39, Surface	37.8	Savelle et al. 2009
K1042	3410 ± 120	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3110 – 2766	3319 – 2649	NjHa-1: 215-, Unknown	45-46	Meldgaard 1960b, 1962
UCIAMS267466	3440 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3070 – 2870	3163 – 2781	NjHa-1: 223-20, Level 2	39.5	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS251135	2865 ± 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	3056 – 2950	3066 – 2884	NjHa-1: 223-38, Level 1	34.7	Kotar 2022
AA61953	3386 ± 57	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3008 – 2780	3144 – 2712	NjHa-1: 223-12, Surface	40	Savelle et al. 2009
UCIAMS251138	3300 ± 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2883 – 2722	2994 – 2645	NjHa-1: 222-84, Level 2	27	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS251133	3280 ± 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2863 – 2708	2964 – 2611	NjHa-1: 222-85, Level 2	27	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS267467	2750 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2860 – 2787	2874 – 2782	NjHa-1: 223-50, Level 2	29.8	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS185096	3240 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2834 – 2679	2918 – 2556	NjHa-1: 212-Test Pit 65, Level 1	27.8	
Lab Code*	¹⁴ C Age (bp)	Sample Species**	Calibrated or Marine	Calibrated or Marine	Site, Provenience	Orthometric Height	Reference

			Modelled Age cal. BP 1 σ	Modelled Age cal. BP 2 σ		(MASL)	
P211	2354 \pm 135	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2699 – 2163	2745 – 2060	NjHa-1: 205-, Unknown	25–26	Meldgaard 1960b, 1962
UCIAMS251130	3100 \pm 15	<i>Ursus maritimus</i>	2691 – 2440	2751 – 2337	NjHa-1: 222–Cache near F82, Level 2	27.5	
K1043	3040 \pm 120	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2680 – 2351	2824 – 2149	NjHa-1: 205-, Unknown	25–26	Meldgaard 1960b, 1962
UCIAMS185095	3015 \pm 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2568 – 2352	2682 – 2300	NjHa-1: 212–F2, Level 1 (TP59)	30.4	
UCIAMS267469	3005 \pm 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2553 – 2342	2678 – 2287	NjHa-1: 222–83, Level 2	27.7	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS267468	2405 \pm 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2457 – 2358	2489 – 2353	NjHa-1: 222–82, Level 2	27.5	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS189557	2610 \pm 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2057 – 1866	2142 – 1764	NjHa-1: 204–F18, Level 1	23	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS189559	2590 \pm 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2030 – 1837	2119 – 1739	NjHa-1: 204–F18, Level 1	20.2	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS189571	2580 \pm 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2011 – 1824	2107 – 1732	NjHa-1: 204–F13, Level 1	23.3	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS185089	2575 \pm 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2005 – 1819	2100 – 1727	NjHa-1: 204–05, Level 1	23.7	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS189565	2575 \pm 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2005 – 1819	2100 – 1729	NjHa-1: 204–F05, Level 1	23.7	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS267470	2565 \pm 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1996 – 1810	2088 – 1717	NjHa-1: 205–Feature 1 (Test Unit 4), Level 1	26	
UCIAMS185091	2565 \pm 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1995 – 1810	2089 – 1719	NjHa-1: 204–F13, Level 1	23.3	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS189566	2020 \pm 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1991 – 1941	1999 – 1895	NjHa-1: 204–F05, Level 1	23.7	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS189560	2015 \pm 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1991 – 1932	1999 – 1889	NjHa-1: 204–F18, Level 1	23	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS267471	2000 \pm 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1986 – 1898	1992 – 1886	NjHa-1: 205–Feature 1 (Test Unit 5), Level 1	26	
AA62363	1971 \pm 54	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1986 – 1831	2042 – 1740	NjHa-1: 204–5, Surface	23.7	Savelle et al. 2009
UCIAMS185093	2545 \pm 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1976 – 1790	2065 – 1696	NjHa-1: 204–F18, Level 1	23	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS189569	2535 \pm 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1962 – 1775	2054 – 1687	NjHa-1: 204–F13, Level 1	23.3	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS189572	1985 \pm 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1942 – 1886	1989 – 1842	NjHa-1: 204–F13, Level 1	23.3	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS185090	1975 \pm 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1933 – 1877	1984 – 1835	NjHa-1: 204–F05, Level 1	23.7	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS185094	1970 \pm 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1929 – 1874	1978 – 1833	NjHa-1: 204–F18, Level 1	23	Kotar 2022
Lab Code*	¹⁴ C Age (bp)	Sample Species**	Calibrated or Marine	Calibrated or Marine	Site, Provenience	Orthometric Height	Reference

			Modelled Age cal. BP 1 σ	Modelled Age cal. BP 2 σ		(MASL)	
UCIAMS189570	1935 \pm 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1885 – 1827	1929 – 1749	NjHa-1: 204-F13, Level 1	23.3	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS189567	2460 \pm 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1873 – 1691	1959 – 1587	NjHa-1: 204-F05, Level 1	23.7	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS185092	1905 \pm 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1866 – 1748	1871 – 1742	NjHa-1: 204-F13, Level 1	23.3	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS185098	2450 \pm 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1864 – 1683	1941 – 1575	NjHa-1: 205, Trench of TP 8, Level 1	25.8	
UCIAMS189563	2445 \pm 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1861 – 1679	1936 – 1571	NjHa-1: 205, Trench of TP 8, Level 1	25.8	
UCIAMS267472	2445 \pm 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1859 – 1676	1935 – 1570	NjHa-1: 205-F2, Surface	26	
UCIAMS189568	1875 \pm 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1820 – 1743	1827 – 1734	NjHa-1: 204-F05, Level 1	23.7	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS185097	1870 \pm 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1820 – 1739	1825 – 1730	NjHa-1: 205, Trench of TP 8, Level 1	25.8	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS251134	1870 \pm 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1820 – 1739	1827 – 1722	NjHa-1: 205-F5, Level 2	25.4	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS189564	1830 \pm 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1737 – 1712	1817 – 1645	NjHa-1: 205, Trench of TP 8, Level 1	25.8	
UCIAMS251136	1825 \pm 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1735 – 1710	1785 – 1639	NjHa-1: 205-F5, Level 2	25.4	Kotar 2022
UCIAMS189562	1810 \pm 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1735 – 1641	1744 – 1624	NjHa-1: 205, Trench of TP 8, Level 1	25.8	
UCIAMS189561	2345 \pm 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1719 – 1545	1820 – 1459	NjHa-1: 205, Trench of TP 8, Level 1	25.8	
UCIAMS189558	1720 \pm 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1692 – 1570	1696 – 1544	NjHa-1: 204-F18, Level 1	23	Kotar 2022

*“UCAIMS” and “AA” lab numbers refer to AMS dates. “K” and “P” lab numbers refer to radiometric dates.

** *Odobenus rosmarus* $\Delta R = 160 \pm 50$ after Dyke et al. (2019). *Ursus maritimus* modelled on mixed curve (95% marine) based on $\delta^{13}C$ values, $\Delta R = 176 \pm 50$ after McNeely et al. (2006).

Figure 5.18 OxCal multi-plots of calibrated terrestrial mammal dates.

Figure 5.19 OxCal multi-plots of marine modelled walrus dates.
Delta offset of 160 ± 50 after Dyke et al. (2019).

The new sequence also provides the first clear radiocarbon evidence⁷ for occupations at the onset of the Late Tuniit Period, which is known as Early Dorset in the traditional culture history sequence (c.2500). These dates come from site areas with Early Tuniit deposits. This includes Late Tuniit dates ranging from cal. 2678 – 2287 BP (2σ) to cal. 2489 – 2353 BP (2σ) associated with a dwelling (F82), cache (F82b), and external hearth (F83) in Area 222, and from a surface dwelling (F2) in Area 212 (Table 5.1, see also Figure 5.1). The few diagnostic artifacts recovered from these features are characteristic of Early Tuniit rather than Late Tuniit assemblages. For example, 222-F83 contained two spalled burins and a burin spall, while 212-F2 contained the distal end of an A7-8 open socket harpoon head, an artifact dated to the final centuries of the Early Tuniit Period (i.e., Late Pre-Dorset) in Meldgaard's typological system (Levasseur, personal communication 2022, cf. Desrosiers 2018; Kotar 2018). The one exception is the worked slate recovered from TP24. While silicified slate has been found in small quantities at Early Tuniit sites in the eastern Canadian Arctic (such as at Qalirusiq), ground slate artifacts are more commonly associated with Late Tuniit contexts (Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1965).

There are two possible explanations for the presence of Early Tuniit diagnostics in these Late Tuniit features. First, as I proposed in Chapter Two (Section 1.6), such discrepancies may reflect problems with legacy typologies developed from coastal sequences. This is likely given the evidence for Tuniit peoples at Kapuivik constructing camps inland from the coast, which challenges the temporal logics of dating artifacts and features by the beach terraces on which they are located. This possibility has serious implications for understanding sociomaterial change, as it complicates previous inferences of rapid technological shifts at the beginning of the Late Tuniit Period that have served as the basis for cultural replacement theories (see Meldgaard

⁴³ Two of Meldgaard's radiometric dates from Area 205 (P211 and K1043) have high uncertainty ranges and may date anywhere from 2800 to 2000 BP.

1962; Savelle and Dyke 2014). It is also likely that the Early Tuniit features are palimpsests of occupational phases belonging to both Early and Late Tuniit peoples. This possibility is supported by radiocarbon assays from dwellings 222-F84 and F85, which are located 40m southeast on the same terrace as F82 and F83. These dwellings date to the final centuries of the Early Tuniit Period (c. 3000-2600) and contain similar lithic assemblages to F82 and F83. The reoccupation of this small campsite by both Early and Late Tuniit peoples would indicate that they were part of the same enduring camp community, and as such may also present a challenge to conventional chronocultural divisions employed in Tuniit archaeology.

The latest radiocarbon dates from the sequence come from Areas 204 and 205, and date to the middle of the Late Tuniit Period (c. 2000-1500 BP). Several dates obtained from Area 205, such as those from 205-F5 (e.g., cal. 1827 – 1722 BP [2 σ]) and the TP8 lithic scatter (e.g., cal. 1744 – 1624 BP [2 σ]), are over a century later than those obtained from Area 204 (e.g., cal. 1999 – 1889 BP [2 σ] from 204-F18), despite being located along higher terraces (Figures 18 and 19). This, again, demonstrates the complexity of Tuniit spatial practices at the site, and indicates a preference for elevated areas during the Late Tuniit Period. While the latest sample from Area 204 dates to cal. 1696 – 1544 BP (2 σ), the marine emergence of Area 197, where two Tuniit surface dwellings are located, occurred around 1300 BP (Savelle and Dyke 2014:256). Given that Late Tuniit at Kapuivik constructed camps away from the active shoreline, it is possible that even later Tuniit occupations are present elsewhere at Kapuivik, either in unsurveyed inland areas or among undated features within the main coastal sequence. For now, it appears that continuous Tuniit occupation of Kapuivik took place from at least 3800-1300 BP, despite the complex and varied nature of Tuniit residential practices at the site.

5.2.2 Maintenance and Reuse of Campsites

In addition to the reoccupation of Area 222 by both Early and Late Tuniit peoples, the radiocarbon assays provide evidence for the repeated occupation of several other campsites in the Tuniit occupational sequence. Radiocarbon dates of cal. 4145 – 3730 BP (2σ) and cal. 3372 – 3250 BP (2σ) from a large surface boulder dwelling 223-F51 suggests that two occupational phases over three centuries apart took place within the structure. However, as the later date is from a sample of arctic hare and these are burrowing animals, it is possible that this sample is intrusive (Kotar 2022:101). However, there were no observable traces of burrowing or disturbance in the activity later of the unit from which the sample was recovered, and there are no other examples of intrusive Arctic hare in excavation assemblages from Kapuivik (Kotar 2019). The robust faunal and artifact assemblages from F51, compared to dwellings of similar size and age reported on Igloolik Island (Meldgaard 1962; Rowley 2003), support that F51 was likely occupied on multiple occasions or for longer durations of time (cf. Meldgaard 1965). As sod houses at Kapuivik also contain radiocarbon evidence for occupations over multiple centuries, it is within reason that F51, given its large size and robust architecture, could have been repeatedly occupied over several generations.

The radiocarbon assays also provide evidence for the maintenance and reoccupation of dwellings along the lower terraces of Area 223. This part of the site was previously inferred as a series of successive occupations by small Tuniit groups, who built their camps closer to the shore as the coastline advanced from isostatic rebound. However, the radiocarbon sequence suggests a more complex picture of dwelling construction and use along 40-35 MASL terraces (Table 5.1, Figure 5.10). For example, radiocarbon dates recovered from F12 (cal. 3144 – 2712 BP [2σ]) and

F20 (cal. 3163 – 2781 BP [2 σ]) are generally the same age as the sample recovered from F38 (cal. 3066 – 2884 BP [2 σ]), despite the latter being located 6 terraces lower. The two radiocarbon dates recovered from the house floor of F39 (i.e., cal. 3305 – 2903 BP [2 σ] and cal. 3207 – 3066 BP [2 σ]) suggest that an occupational episode occurred here at least several decades prior to the occupation of F38, despite the features being next to each other (Figure 5.18). However, the third radiocarbon date recovered from the surface layer of F39 (cal. 3305 – 2903 BP [2 σ]) was significantly later than the two dates from the dwelling floor, yielding a similar age to the sample from F38. As such, F39 may have been initially constructed as a coastal dwelling and then reoccupied as part of a later occupational phase that involved the construction of F38. That F39 was occupied over multiple generations may explain why its architecture was heavily disturbed and had no clear periphery, while F38 was mostly intact. In either case, the radiocarbon dates suggest that the high number of clustered features along the 40-35 MASL terraces are the product of campsite maintenance activities that included the construction of new dwellings in previously occupied areas, as well as possibly the reoccupation and/or appropriation of ancestral dwellings.

While features in Area 205 are generally younger than those in Area 204, the one sod house in Area 205-F1 shares a similar calibrated age (cal. 1992 – 1886 BP [2 σ]) to dates from 204-F5 (cal. 1999 – 1895 BP [2 σ]) and 204-F18 (cal. 1978 – 1833 BP [2 σ]). As 205-F5 and 205-TP8 were occupied after 205-F1, it appears that Area 205 is the product of multiple occupational episodes, perhaps in different seasonal contexts. The mix of sod houses and surface dwellings in Areas 204 and 205 (Figure 5.13) may relate to sod house construction practices. When constructing a new sod house, Amitturmiut would often prepare the dwelling platform in the late fall and inhabit temporary dwellings nearby while they waited for the winter freeze, which was

required to cut the sod bricks and finish the sod house construction (IE057; IE295). In succeeding years, Amitturmiut could return to a previously occupied sod house after the freeze to reconstruct the dwelling walls. This may explain the varied evidence for reoccupation among semi-subterranean sod house remains within Areas 204 and 205.

Radiocarbon dated sod houses in Area 204 contain the longest occupational ranges at Kapuivik. Tuniit sod houses, like Inuit sod houses, are expected to have been repeatedly occupied for multiple winters, at least until their expanding distance from the advancing shoreline required the construction of a new settlement (cf. Howse et al. 2019; Maxwell 1985; Savelle and Dyke 2014; IE295). In the case of Area 204, dwellings appear to have been constructed well after marine emergence. For example, the earliest of the 19 radiocarbon samples recovered from this area yielded a date of cal. 2142 – 1764 BP (2σ), which is over three centuries after the small peninsula in this location formed (Figure 5.16). As previously mentioned, this may demonstrate a preference for sheltered areas or locations with good building materials, but it may also suggest that cold weather settlement practices during the Late Tuniit Period were more diverse than previously anticipated.

As Kapuivik was one of the main winter caribou hunting locales during the Early Inuit period (IE010; IE057; IE177), it is possible that the campsite in Area 204 was constructed on an elevated plateau to be within vantage of both the coast and nearby grazing grounds. This potential diversity in economic practices may explain the higher quantities of caribou bone recovered here compared to other areas at Kapuivik (Kotar 2022). In addition, an increase in coastal shallows with optimal depths for walrus feeding (15-18m) drastically increased around

Kapuvik shortly before 2000 BP⁹, suggesting that the local availability of walrus was much higher during this time compared to other periods of occupation (Figure 20). As Area 204 has a vantage of the floe edge in multiple directions, it may have served as an ideal wintering site for communal walrus hunting. The intensification of walrus hunting is also supported by the high frequency of walrus in the Area 204 faunal assemblage analyzed by Kotar (2022).

Figure 5.20: Reconstructions of walrus feeding shallows (15-18m) surrounding Kapuvik during the Late Tuniit Period.

5.2.3 Mapping Small-Scale Change in Camp Community Organization

The radiocarbon dates provide deeper insights into the structure and nature of Tuniit camp communities. They challenge prior understandings about architectural changes that were based on Meldgaard's investigation of Kapuvik's coastal sequence and offer new perspectives on the demographic changes inferred by Savelle and Dyke (2014). In his Kapuvik reports, Meldgaard (1960a:591; 1960b:69) noted a shift in architectural technologies from elliptical to

⁴⁴ Walrus feeding depths as established by Murray (1996:98, cf. Fay 1969:113).

rectangular dwellings, which he considered as a key marker of rapid cultural change between the Early and Late Tuniit periods (see also Houmard 2018). However, the 2018 surveys found mostly oval structures with a smaller number of rectangular structures in both Early and Late Tuniit contexts, conflicting with Meldgaard's conclusions. Pedestrian and thermal surveys identified several surface dwellings in Areas 223 and 222 that have a rectangular form, while the surface dwellings in Area 205 are mostly circular (Walker 2020:11-12). The semi-subterranean sod dwellings in Area 204 include a mix of oval and rectangular types, but these dwellings are of similar age and as such do not indicate a temporal shift from one form to the other (Figure 5.15; Table 5.1). While it is possible that Meldgaard's excavations revealed consistent differences in house forms, the platform uncovered from the 2018 trench placed in 205-F1 suggests that this too was an oval dwelling, and that Meldgaard did not always excavate to the boundaries of structures to verify their forms (Figure 5.13a). Overall, the new data indicate that dwelling forms vary on a household scale rather than representing widespread technological change.

The radiocarbon dates provide evidence that the emergence of semi-subterranean sod dwellings at Kapuivik do not date to the onset of the Late Tuniit Period (c. 2500) but rather were constructed after 2100 BP (Table 5.1). Alternatively, the earliest sod houses at Alarniq were potentially constructed prior to 2500 BP⁴¹. This is significant as it suggests that pronounced changes in Tuniit architecture were not confined to a particular time period within the region. Rather, architectural change varied between sites, with many elements of Early Tuniit architecture continuing into the Late Tuniit Period. At Kapuivik, the emergence of semi-subterranean sod houses corresponds with a significant increase in the availability of walrus feeding grounds surrounding the island (Figure 5.20). This is notable, since several scholars have

⁴⁵ Confidence intervals of calibrated radiocarbon dated from NhHd-11 indicate that some features in this area were constructed between 2700-2500 (see. Table 7.1).

proposed a shift to intensive, communal walrus hunting at the start Late Tuniit Period as either a product or catalyst of material culture change (Maxwell 185; Murray 1996; Friesen 2007). In the context of Kapuivik, this may indicate to a significant shift in people-place relations, and that the production of social and material difference during the Tuniit Period varied locally within Amittuq.

While differences in architectural technologies do not exhibit a clear temporal pattern, there are noticeable changes in dwelling size and frequency over time that suggest changes in community organization and population density during the Tuniit Period. The largest dwellings at Kapuivik belong to the first half of the Early Tuniit Period (c.4000-3000 BP) and the middle Late Tuniit Period (c. 2100-1700BP). Areas with very large Early Tuniit dwellings tend to have fewer features, while those with smaller dwellings tend to be in larger clusters (Figure 5.21). For example, the largest dwellings in Area 223 are arranged in small groups of 1-3 features along the upper terraces, while dwellings located in the larger clusters at 40–35 MASL are much smaller in size. Larger Tuniit dwellings, such as 223-F51 and 215-F2, are also some of the oldest features at the site, while the clusters of smaller dwellings tend to date to the later half of the Early Tuniit Period (Table 5.1).

In the Late Tuniit Period, surface dwellings remain small, while semi-subterranean sod dwellings vary from small to large (Figure 5.21); the large sod dwellings in Area 204 are arranged in a bigger cluster of 6 dwellings, while the smaller sod houses in Areas 204 and 207 are arranged in groups of 2-4 dwellings. These changes in architecture and campsite structure are

Figure 5.21: Dwelling size and frequency across Kapuvik. Dwelling size classes calculated using Jenks optimization method.

significant as they reframe previous understandings of social organization and demographic change in Amittuq. They suggest that Early Tuniit camps may have been first organized into multifamily households (ten or more people, see Maxwell 1985:154; McGhee 1996:131 on dwelling size) and shifted to nuclear family households (three to six people, cf. Ryan 2010), as the size of camps increased (cf. Savelle and Dyke 2014:259 on Middle Pre-Dorset population boom). The size of dwellings in relation to dwelling frequencies suggests that while camp size increased throughout the period, the earliest camps may have still housed a considerable number of individuals. Based on the labour investment of their architectural forms, the density of their artifact assemblages, and evidence for reoccupation (e.g., 223-F51), these features may have been established settlements rather than ephemeral, single use camps as is often assumed of Early Tuniit sites (cf. Savelle and Dyke 2014:257).

Household and camp organization appear to have been diverse in the Late Tuniit Period, which may relate to different seasonal occupational contexts and a wider range of occupational activities. For example, surface dwellings like 222-F82 and 205-F5 exhibit evidence of ephemeral warm weather occupations¹⁰. Alternatively, semi-subterranean dwellings were only occupied in cold weather due to the necessity of frozen sod; the small size of camps comprised of both surface and sod dwellings may indicate shorter term occupations, while the cluster of larger sod dwellings appears to be a bigger settlement comprised of several multi-family households who, as evidenced from the radiocarbon sequence, wintered at Kapuivik for generations.

⁴⁶ 222-F82 contained caribou as well polar bear remains, the former which are often hunted in the warmer months on land and the latter on the pack ice (see Chapter Four). Polar bear remains were also recovered from the adjacent cache, linking hunting activities to the preparation of winter caches. 222-F83, the external hearth, is another indicator a summer or fall occupation. Alternatively, 205-F5 contained the remains of migratory birds like snow goose and a larger quantity of caribou, which again are indicators of summer or fall occupation (Kotar 2022:143).

Figure 5.22 Potential inundated features 1.5 north of NjHa-45. Basemap: *Worldview 2*.

The spatiotemporal patterning of Late Tuniit features and reoccupation activities at Kapuivik suggests that gaps in the coastal chronological sequence originally inferred as population crashes, such as those recognized from the 18–16 MASL terraces (Savelle and Dyke 2014:263), are likely the product of people from this time reoccupying ancestral settlements located on higher terraces, such as Area 204. As several Early Tuniit surface dwellings are also located further inland near freshwater features (e.g., 215-F2, 215-F1), it is possible that the establishment of larger settlements at Kapuivik occurred earlier than suggested by current radiocarbon evidence and that Early Tuniit communities were larger than previously anticipated (see Savelle and Dyke 2014). Exploratory analysis of satellite data of areas further inland from NjHa-45 support this possibility, as there appear to be heavy boulder surface structures located near some of the larger inland lakes (Figure 5.21). As such, the 2018 archaeological data demonstrate the importance of surveying different physiographic settings and indicate that inland camping activities were more common in coastal contexts at Kapuivik than current models of Tuniit occupation, like the core area model, allow for.

5.3 Conclusions

In this chapter, I have presented archaeological and palaeogeographical data that challenge dominant archaeological narratives about Tuniit occupational practices and social change at Kapuivik. I discussed and compared Tuniit settlement strategies as exemplified through the location and spatial structure of campsite remains and found evidence for a wide array of community practices that included the recurrent occupation of both coastal and inland areas. Through this assessment, I suggested how Kapuivik's unique topography shaped Tuniit spatial practices, but also how Tuniit peoples modified their environments through constructed

spaces to demarcate camp communities and cooperatively manage access to material and subsistence resource areas. The temporal patterning of campsites indicated that Tuniit peoples may have frequently reoccupied ancestral camps in both the Early and Late Tuniit Periods. This may suggest continuity in camp community affiliations across both periods, despite significant changes in architectural technologies, spatial practices, and community organization at different points in the island's occupational history.

One of the most interesting observations was that several campsites anticipated to be ephemeral because of their architecture, age, or spatial configuration, such as the surface dwellings located on the highest terraces (e.g., 223-F51, 216-F1), and those located in Areas 222 and 205, demonstrated strong evidence for reoccupation over extended periods. As these campsites are associated with the presence of cache features, I infer that the preparation and exploitation of caches was a major component in the establishment of occupational traditions, bringing people together at Kapuivik in different seasons and for varied durations of time. This is significant, as it suggests that the historical processes that brought people together *in place* and that maintained enduring camp communities were not limited to the construction of large permanent settlements. This has important implications for how Tuniit site types are usually interpreted in the eastern Canadian Arctic, as it suggests that seemingly ephemeral structures and extramural contexts were affective fields of social action that contributed to the production of larger landscapes in meaningful and lasting ways (see Chapter Two, Section 2). In the next chapter, I further explore the importance of caching, seasonal variability, and camp organization in the context of Qalirusiq to further assess the nature of camp community maintenance and differentiation in Amittuq during the Tuniit Period.

Chapter Six

Reconstructing Tuniit Occupational History at Qalirusiq

In the preceding chapter, I presented archaeological and palaeogeographical evidence from Kapuivik that challenged dominant narratives about how places and communities emerged and changed on a local scale during the Tuniit Period. In this chapter, I turn my attention to the occupational history of Qalirusiq, which provides a window into emergent and enduring people-place relationships within the context of a remote islet subject to pronounced postglacial geomorphological changes. Through comparisons between archaeological data and paleotopographic models, the study outlines how shifting landmasses and the shallowing of nearshore environments impacted the accessibility and connectivity of the islet to neighbouring settlements and marine hunting areas, and offers interpretations for how local communities responded to these changes in variable yet historically contingent ways. This includes evidence for the strategic organization of campsites around coastal features to define spatial boundaries and social distinctions among local groups, synchronic differences in architecture and land use, and the intergenerational reuse of various cache structures. Small-scale variability in Tuniit organizational strategies and recurrent settlement practices suggest that local peoples were not reactive entities defined by coastal environments and resources. Rather, they actively managed their connections with dynamic settlement places through everyday activities, articulating community membership at the camp level, as well as between camps as part of translocal communities. The research positions Tuniit communities as flexible and multiscalar social collectives that emerged and changed through meaningful placemaking practice.

Qalirusiq contains the largest Early Tuniit site currently identified in Amittuq (NiHf-1),

which is widely recognized as a type-site for explaining material change during the Early Tuniit Period (Houmard 2018; Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1965; Ryan 2010). Meldgaard (1954a; 1962) expected that archaeological remains at the site were contemporary with the geological formation of the relic coastal terraces on which they were located, and inferred a continuous sequence of winter campsites from 40 – 52 MASL, which were formed between 3500 – 4500 BP (Savelle and Dyke 2014). This was followed by a proposed abandonment of the islet and its subsequent reoccupation by smaller groups later in the Dorset (i.e., Late Tuniit) period, along the 17–20 MASL terraces (NiHf-47) which formed between 2000 — 2500 BP. My work centered on remapping the NiHf-1 and NiHf-47 occupational sequences and examining undocumented areas that include a new site found along the western slope (NiHf-117) of the butte (Figure 6.1).

My assessment of Qalirusiq differs from the preceding chapter's analysis of Kapuivik in important ways due to limitations encountered during data collection. First, as my in-field assessment was restricted to survey and surface collections, my analysis focuses on the broader spatial and temporal patterning of camp structures rather than household scale differences. Second, Qalirusiq's proximity to Igloolik hamlet has resulted in damage to archaeological structures and their burial under modern debris. These conditions have disturbed features located on the lower terraces of NiHf-1, as well as most features at NiHf-47. As such, my assessment of campsite temporality is largely limited to Early Tuniit contexts where radiocarbon samples were collected from the surface layers of intact structures. In contrast to other geographic regions, post-depositional processes resulting in feature burial are significantly limited in Arctic environments. Therefore, surface radiocarbon samples located within exposed architectural features are considered fairly reliable (Savelle and Dyke 2014; Howse et al. 2019).

Figure 6.1 New site map of Qalirusiq showing the distribution of Tuniit features identified through survey. *Basemap: ArcticDEM*

As arctic moss takes centuries to grow (Minayeva et al. 2019; Sannel and Kuhry 2009), surface samples embedded in mosses are less likely to have been subject to modern anthropogenic disturbances like looting, vehicle damage, and erosion, and these were prioritized for collection. While surface collections are less than ideal for establishing chronological control, these radiocarbon samples offer improved temporal resolution to an important archaeological place where excavations could not take place of respect for the Igloodik community's wishes, due to the proximity of the historic and modern Inuit cemeteries. The complex temporalities present at Qalirusiq highlight issues with differentiating between Tuniit and Inuit archaeological contexts in shared spaces, but also demonstrate the affective roles of this settlement place in shaping enduring community histories and practices.

I improve the temporal resolution of my analysis by comparing archaeological contexts with paleotopographic models based on isostasy data from the Canadian Geological Survey. These models visualize the postglacial marine emergence of landforms and provide earliest age limits for temporally complex settlements. While the models are visualized with the distribution of known archaeological features, available evidence suggests that documented sites are the product of multiple construction, maintenance, and reoccupation events. However, when analyzed alongside survey data and available radiocarbon dates, the models help to interpret how changing material conditions and the changing accessibility of the islet to other places in the landscape were managed by local occupants through a diverse array of social, economic, and political practices.

The study offers interpretations of Qalirusiq's occupational history that challenge previous models of settlement and subsistence during the Early Tuniit Period, and provide new

perspectives on local community relations and structures. While the data demonstrate similar architectural patterning to Kapuivik in terms of cold weather land use in the Early Tuniit Period, they also suggest specialized coastal settlement practices unique to Qalirusiq. While concentrations of caches at Kapuivik were associated with inland occupations, most at Qalirusiq were arranged along coastal bluffs. The recurrent construction and exploitation of caches may have enabled local communities to remain at Qalirusiq for longer durations of time, allowing them to reoccupy winter camps even if marine resources were unpredictable in the autumn, contributing to large-scale seasonal aggregations at NiHf-1.

In addition to these specialized coastal activities, the research documents a variety of occupied spatial contexts, including wind-sheltered cliff sides, concentrations of scree, and coastal ponds. I examine the material affordances of these contexts alongside traces of architecture, surface faunal assemblages, re-examined legacy data (Murray 1996; Houmard 2018, cf. Meldgaard 1962; Rowley 1991a), and the newly acquired radiocarbon sequence. I argue that Tuniit communities at Qalirusiq participated in specialized sets of late autumn and winter marine mammal hunting and storage practices that appear to have been maintained from at least 4000 to 3500 BP. This pattern is contrasted with Kapuivik, where Early Tuniit campsites exhibit variability in locational settings and seasonal practices. I also find evidence for an increase in the synchronic diversity of architectural types and organizational structures at Qalirusiq after 3500 BP, which may represent multi-seasonal visits, such as the exploitation of meat caches prepared the previous season. Comparisons with paleotopographic models indicate significant changes in walrus feeding shallows between 3500-3000 BP (see also Murray 1996), as well as significant increases in land connectivity that may have facilitated travel between Qalirusiq, nearby islets, and the mainland in warmer weather. The evidence suggests both

persistence and change in land use traditions at Qalirusiq within a dynamic and emergent occupational landscape.

Using insights gained from Kapuivik, I also employ survey data and radiocarbon dates to draw inferences about the reoccupation and differential reuse of residential areas. Specifically, I focus on the upper terraces of NiHf-1, where dense groups of dwellings and boulder caches (buried meat pits marked with boulders) are concentrated. This permits the assessment of whether NiHf-1 was abandoned during the Early Tuniit Period as previously suggested by Meldgaard (1962:93), or if occupational continuity took place through the repeated use of structures and extramural spaces. Through this analysis I present evidence for the intergenerational maintenance of specific residential areas, rather than total site abandonment. Drawing on Amitturmiut oral history (see Chapter Four, Section 4.2.2), I suggest how the frequent reuse and modification of existing cache structures and dwelling areas at NiHf-1, despite the abundance of local building materials (e.g., limestone scree), may have contributed to the maintenance or reimagining of community traditions and histories through recurrent placemaking practice.

Temporal variations in the scale and layout of Tuniit campsites at Qalirusiq indicate that local population dynamics may have been informed by broader spatial relationships and the formation of trans-local communities connected by more accessible travel routes along land and sea ice. The formation of an isthmus between Qalirusiq and Kaleruserk after 3000 BP coincides with an inferred decline in occupations at Qalirusiq and an increase in the settlement of nearby places now located on Igloodik Island, such as Freuchen

⁴⁷ (NiHf-3) and Tikilik (NiHf-4) (Mathiassen 1927; Meldgaard 1965; Rowley 1996).

This shift from larger sites to several smaller site occupations questions the validity of models that solely attribute population changes to large-scale environmental determinants. It suggests instead that variations in local populations may have stemmed from changes organizational and mobility practices that likely involved a range of social, political, and economic factors, rather than from catastrophic declines due to climate change (cf. Appelt et al. 2016; Savelle and Dyke 2014). The transformation of landforms and the faster formation of sea ice in shallow coastal areas likely shortened travel times between communities located on nearby peninsulas and islets. This change may have altered the perceived spatial proximity of neighbouring camps, contributing to a shared sense of belonging that may have involved frequent visits and interaction as part of floe edge hunting and food sharing practices (see Chapter Four, Section 4.2.1).

I begin this chapter with an overview of the survey data collected during the 2019 field season. This includes the presentation of a new site map, a description of new features and resurveyed feature areas, and a discussion of differences in locational strategies and land use present within the occupational sequence. This is followed by an examination of the temporality of Tuniit occupations at Qalirusiq, as informed through the analysis of 6 legacy radiocarbon dates and 13 recently acquired dates, as well as through the analysis of the postglacial marine emergence of feature areas, facilitated by predictive GIS models. I end the chapter with a commentary on the varied nature of Early Tuniit occupational practices in the Igloolik area, and a discussion of the broader community relationships that appear to have both shaped, and been informed by, the materialization of Qalirusiq as a persistent settlement place. Through this discussion, I present a narrative of Tuniit communities as multiscale and relational entities that

⁴⁷ Rowley (2003:71) includes list of surveyed features which indicate that Freuchen contained several cache features in addition to boulder tent rings, similar to NiHf-1.

were forged and differentiated through diverse placemaking practice.

6.1 Assessing Community Structure, Organization, and Seasonal Land Use at Qalirusiq

The 2019 survey data suggest significant diversity in locational preferences, settlement strategies, and land use at Qalirusiq during the Tuniit Period. In this section, I assess archaeological evidence for this diversity, which includes the analysis of a new site (NiHf-117) on the western slope of the butte and 77 newly documented archaeological features across the previously surveyed sites of NiHf-1 and NiHf-47, which are located on the summit and eastern slopes of the butte, respectively (Table 6.1). Newly documented archaeological contexts suggest that a wide array of occupational activities took place, including cold weather occupations, intensive sea mammal storage practices, and warm weather visits potentially centered on the preparation or exploitation of caches. I also describe an additional 69 potential features that include inundated structures and clusters of boulders that may represent disturbed dwellings or exploited caches. I discuss disturbed features to contextualize the complex palimpsests of human activity at Qalirusiq between the Early Tuniit through to the contemporary Inuit periods, such as the possible differential reuse of archaeological structures and spaces. The findings highlight the importance of prioritizing site excavation and radiocarbon analyses in future investigations of this settlement place. A site map showing the distribution of confirmed and potential Tuniit features is presented above in Figure 6.1.

Table 6.1 Summary of Documented Archaeological Features at Qalirusiq

Feature Type	Number of Features
Dwellings	154

Boulder Caches or Cairns	54 (including cairns)
Middens	5
External Hearths	3
Fox Trap	5
Disturbed Boulder Features	29
Lithic Debitage Scatters	5
Ivory Debitage Scatters	2
Potential Features	69

The 2019 survey data permit the inference of spatial practices associated with the production of Qalirusiq as a settlement place, including evidence for increased variability in organizational structures and seasonal practices during the Tuniit Period. This includes higher concentrations of dwelling features along the 39–45 MASL terraces than previously documented, and a new site comprised of 57 Early Tuniit features on the western slope of the butte (NiHf–117). The analysis of the postglacial marine emergence indicates that many dwellings along the butte summit were constructed sometime after 3700 BP, with several being constructed after 3400 BP. This suggests that Tuniit occupations at Qalirusiq may have persisted during the middle Early Tuniit Period (c. 3700–3300 BP), challenging and expanding prior interpretations of site occupation and abandonment (cf. Meldgaard 1962; Rowley 1991a).

The analysis of campsite remains from NiHf–1 and NiHf–117 suggest that Early Tuniit inhabitants favored elevated coastal areas near coves and shallow waters for residential locations, where they organized their dwellings towards the floe edge. Most of these occupations appear to have occurred in cold weather contexts (i.e., late autumn to early spring) as indicated by the inferred durability of dwelling forms and available faunal evidence. However, a cluster of dwellings associated with traces of outdoor cooking and toolmaking on the eastern plateau of NiHf-1 (42–44 MASL) suggest that warm season activities were more common in the later half

of the Early Tuniit Period. Likewise, NiHf-47 exhibits a range of seasonally specific structural elements that suggest both warm and cold weather occupations during the Late Tuniit Period.

Although there are significant differences in the spatial setting and seasonal use of Tuniit campsites, caching practices are present in nearly all feature areas at Qalirusiq. The prevalence of boulder caches throughout Qalirusiq — at NiHf-1, NiHf-117, and NiHf-47 — when compared with available faunal evidence (Murray 1996:64; Walker 2020b), highlights the importance of marine mammal meat storage practices to Tuniit residents. The continuity of cache construction and reuse supports the argument that Early and Late Tuniit communities maintained a specific set of relationships with Qalirusiq that centred on the local exploitation of marine mammals, despite prior evidence for occupational decline during what is commonly referred to as the transitional period (c.2800–2500 BP) (cf. Meldgaard 1962; Rowley 1991a).

In this section, I discuss archaeological evidence for small-scale variability in Tuniit campsite organization and land use at Qalirusiq. The assessment contextualizes the social structure of camp communities and situates the chronological analysis of recurrent and changing community practices in Section Two. I begin with an overview of the new site, NiHf-117, centering on the examination of architectural forms and the structure of individual campsites, which bear similarities to Early Tuniit contexts in Area 223 at Kapuivik. This is followed by a description of archaeological features and reconstructed landscape elements within the NiHf-1 occupational sequence, in which I present evidence for locational preferences, architectural practices, and the seasonal context of land use. Lastly, I consider survey data from NiHf-47, and compare this data with re-examined legacy data (Murray 1996; Houmard 2018, cf. Melgaard 1962; Rowley 1991a) to draw inferences about Late Tuniit occupational history at the site.

Through this assessment, I present evidence for how shifting material conditions and community connections at Qalirusiq contributed to its ongoing production as an important coastal settlement place.

6.1.1. Spatial Analysis of a Newly Documented Settlement Context (NiHf-117)

A new archaeological area at Qalirusiq was identified in 2019 along the northwestern slope of the butte, on terraces ranging from 39 to 46 MASL. NiHf-117 contains 57 Tuniit features constructed from the surrounding limestone scree, including surface dwellings, caches, and a variety of extramural features. An additional 23 potential features were also identified (Table 6.2). These are concentrations of boulders resembling heavily disturbed dwellings or caches, but without the association of artifacts, faunal remains, or evidence of internal structures to help discern if they were human-made or natural in origin⁴⁸ (Walker 2020b). A site plan depicting these features is presented in Figure 6.2.

As radiocarbon dates were not collected from NiHf-117, the temporality of features is unknown. However, given dwelling similarities to Area 223 at Kapuivik, NiHf-117 may have been primarily occupied during the middle Early Tuniit Period. Additionally, the postglacial marine emergence of area suggests that features on the 45–46 MASL terraces could have been constructed as early as 3800 BP. The large macrolichen thalli recorded on structures at the site support their inferred antiquity (see Chapter Five, Section 1.1.1). In contrast, features located at 40 MASL could only have been constructed by 3500 BP and those at 39 MASL by 3400 BP,

⁴⁸ Natural processes such as glacial plucking and rill erosion can gather unconsolidated quaternary material into piles, while frost boils form depressions and berms that can resemble dwelling remains.

based on land exposure rates (Figure 6.3). Given the limited lichen growth on feature stones, structures on the lower terraces may have been constructed much later, representing Late Tuniit or ancestral Inuit practices. However, their appearance could also be the result of weathering and site disturbance given their location on a windward facing slope.

Table 6.2 Summary of Documented Archaeological Features at NiHf-117

Feature Type	Number of Features
Surface Dwellings	27
Boulder Caches	4
Cairns	2
External Hearths	2
Disturbed Features	23
Potential Features	23

The majority of dwellings at NiHf-117 appear to be the remains of winter occupations, particularly those located in rows along the 44 and 45 MASL terraces, as depicted in Groups 3–7 in Figure 6.2b. These structures are characterized by peripheries comprised of multiple dense rows of large boulders. As discussed in Chapter Five (Sections 1.1.1 and 1.2.1), local informants and oral history suggest that multi-row boulder dwellings were cold weather houses, possibly qarmats⁴⁹. Multi-row dwellings at NiHf-117 contain central hearth features, while external hearths and lithic scatters are absent; this patterning supports the inference that this dwelling type

⁴⁹ Multiple rows of large boulders surrounding the dwelling periphery may be the product of collapsed stone walls (qarmats). While Early Inuit qarmats are often inferred by archaeologists as transitional season dwellings, Park (1998:171) notes that such dwellings could be successfully occupied throughout the winter.

Figure 6.2a Map of NiHf-117 highlighting the variation of surveyed features in relation to topography.

Figure 6.2b The distribution of feature groupings and structural forms and in relation to simplified landscape elements at NiHf-117.

Figure 6.3 Topographic evolution of NiHf-117 in relation to archaeological features⁴. was constructed for cold weather conditions. Moreover, as Qalirusiq was a remote islet

⁵⁰ Quantiles were calculated using the geometrical interval classification method in ArcGIS Pro to enhance the visualization of local topographic variation. As such, class breaks in the elevation data vary between the time-slices.

surrounded by deep water in the first half of the Early Tuniit Period, it was likely only accessible by sea ice in the colder seasons, from the late fall to early spring.

The shared spatial setting of campsites on the upper terraces of NiHf-117 and Area 223 at Kapuivik suggest that their construction and maintenance was location-specific. Dwellings in both areas appear to have been oriented northwest towards the ancient coastline, which exposed them to the prevalent Uangnaq (*north*) wind. Given this exposure, it is plausible that robust stone structures were necessary to withstand blizzards, as snow dwellings would have been at risk of collapse without wind shelter. Despite the challenges of Uangnaq, there were likely benefits to constructing camps on the windward side of the islet. For example, Uangnaq would have likely formed pack ice near the coast, resulting in favorable conditions for seal hunting (IE54). A view of the floe edge in this direction may have been advantageous for determining the optimal time and direction to embark on seal hunting trips. Moreover, this orientation may have facilitated winter travel between places, since the camps were aligned with the formation of uqalurait snow drifts (see Chapter Four, Section 4.2.3.2).

The upper terraces of NiHf-117 also exhibit two types of potential storage features that may suggest seasonal differences in caching practices (Figure 6.2a). The first type consists of meat pits covered in large boulders, that were likely used to bury game (e.g., seal, walrus) before the ground froze in late autumn (IE431). The second type consists of cairns constructed from smaller boulders and flagstones, but that are significantly larger than the potential fish cairns found at Kapuivik. While the size of these cairns suggests the possibility of human burials, they lack the central slab component of burial cairns identified at Kapuivik, and no human remains were found nearby. Given the lack of snow sheltered areas on the island, it is also possible that

the cairns were markers for nearby caches rather than storage features in their own right, aiding returning occupants in finding buried caches covered by snow (IE147). However, it is notable that the cairns are only sometimes found in proximity to boulder caches, and similar cairns at NiHf-1 are clustered in a separate area from the boulder caches. Based on the similarity of the cairns to Inuit hunting caches, I propose that they may have served as surface storage containers constructed when the permafrost was too close to the ground surface for the excavation of meat pits (IE234).

Campsites and isolated features located along the lower terraces to the southwest are fewer in number, and exhibit a diversity of structures that suggest varied seasonal contexts. For instance, Groups 1 and 2 include smaller rows of dwellings that consist of sparser peripheries of boulders and flagstones that likely served as tent weights. The presence of two external hearths in Group 2 indicate outdoor cooking activities, which typically took place in warm weather contexts (Figure 6.2b; Ryan 2010; Sutherland 2013). Due to isostatic uplift, the waters surrounding Qalirusiq were shallower around 3500–3000 BP, and the island was located closer to the southern island of Kaleruserk, as well as to Melville Peninsula due to the emergence of the Coxe Islands. As such, NiHf-117 may have been more accessible compared to preceding periods, allowing for occupations in the early autumn

⁷. In contrast, to Groups 1 and 2, F1 is a large sod patch with an internal hearth feature that bears similarity to the remains of Late Tuniit sod houses at Alarniq. However, the examination of RPA-derived elevation models suggest that F1 lacks a semi-subterranean house foundation. As the dwelling also lacks peripheral boundary markers, such as a sod berm, I

⁵¹ Shallow waters are less affected by currents and the hydrothermal effects of upwelling, and as such are typically the first areas where refreeze occurs in Foxe Basin (IE148;KH02; Saucier et al. 2004).

interpret F1 as the remains of a temporary snow house (Ramsden and Murray 1995:112–115). The ephemeral nature of F1 and its isolation from other dwellings may indicate a change in the socioeconomic context and duration of winter occupations at Qalirusiq in later periods.

While further research is necessary to determine the chronology of NiHf-117 and the character of occupational practices that took place at the site, the survey data offer initial interpretations of camp organization and seasonal land use. My findings indicate that the site was primarily used as a winter residence and storage place, and that it was intermittently reoccupied until at least 3400 BP. However, occupational activities appear to have changed over time, as indicated by a transition from large winter settlements to shorter term habitations in varied seasonal contexts. This suggests that people–place relations were dynamic and variable at Qalirusiq during the Early Tuniit Period, despite the restricted space and geography of the islet.

6.1.2 Spatial Analysis of the Main Early Tuniit Sequence (NiHf-1) at Qalirusiq

NiHf-1 is situated on the summit of Qalirusiq on relic terraces ranging from 42–52 MASL, which were formed between 3500 and 4500 BP. The 2019 surveys identified 205 Early Tuniit features at the site, including 109 surface dwellings and a variety of extramural features, such as caches and external hearths, suggestive of seasonally specific community practices (Table 6.3). I classify documented features into 16 groups based on their clustering and orientation, which I interpret as individual campsites. There are also eight potential boulder features within small ponds that may also be the remains of dwellings or caches. These feature groups are depicted in Figure 6.4b. The substantial variation present in feature types suggests

that local camp communities participated in a wide range of site maintenance and organizational practices during the Early Tuniit Period. The findings highlight the complex nature of Tuniit settlement activities within the restricted spatial setting of a small islet, which may indicate that resource availability was influential towards, but far from deterministic of, community structures and relationships.

Table 6.3 Summary of Archaeological Feature Variability at NiHf-1

Feature Type	Description	Inferred Use	Count
Boulder Surface Dwelling	A dwelling enclosed by a boulder perimeter, ranging from a single sparse row to denser borders with multiple boulder rows.	Sparser borders are likely tent remains or snow house platforms. Borders with multiple rows could be the remains of qarmats with walls built from composites of stone and sod, for cold weather use.	70
Flagstone Surface Dwelling	A dwelling enclosed by a sparse perimeter of flat stones.	The remains of tents or snow house platforms.	31
Surface Dwelling (No Boundary)	A dwelling distinguished by a sod patch without a dug foundation, with evidence of internal architectural features such as hearths, storage features, or lamp platforms.	The remains of more temporary snow houses.	7
Isolated Midpassage	A narrow boulder feature, often the length of a dwelling, inferred as an internal storage or hearth feature within dwellings.	Likely the remains of tent dwellings or snow houses.	3
Semi-Subterranean Sod Dwelling	A dwelling distinguished by a semi-subterranean foundation and/or raised sod berm.	Likely the remains of a winter sod house; dug foundations provided insulation, and sod walls were only functional when frozen in the winter.	1
Box Hearth /Fox Trap	A rectangular feature comprised of stone slabs, either with an open top or a balanced stone door.	Either a hearth feature intended to evenly distribute heat within dwellings, or a warm weather fox trap, to be compared with the winter variety that use an ice door.	5
External Hearth	A small circular feature comprised of cobbles and/or boulders, usually with evidence of burning or blubber.	An outdoor hearth intended for cooking and communal activities in warm weather contexts.	1
Cairn	A surface pile of cobbles and/or boulders in a circular or oval formation	A storage feature (fish or meat), navigational marker, or grave.	11
Boulder Cache	A cluster of boulders with a raised mound or accumulated vegetation indicative of a storage pit, sometimes with a centre of flat stones for a secure storage space.	A warm weather meat storage feature.	33
Extramural Lithic	A concentration of chert or slate debitage	A flintknapping station.	6

Scatter	located outside of structure.		
Extramural Ivory Scatter	A concentration of ivory debitage located outside of structure.	An ivory knapping or carving station.	1
Midden	A surface concentration of faunal remains, and possibly lithic or ivory debitage.	A refuse disposal area.	5
Inuit Qarmat	a type of semi-subterranean dwelling construct by ancestral Inuit, characterized by its stone and sod construction.	A cold weather or interseasonal house.	2
Disturbed Feature	inundated structures or clusters of boulders found in association with artifacts or ecofacts.	A possible dwelling, cache, or burial with evidence of later interference or alteration.	31
Potential Features	Boulder clusters not found in association with material culture.	A potentially disturbed dwelling, cache, or burial, otherwise a natural feature (e.g., a disturbed frost boil).	8

While most features at NiHf-117 are arranged in rows along consecutive coastal terraces, campsites at NiHf-1 are spread across the summit, with those situated between 47–52 MASL seemingly organized around various modern landscape elements, such as scree concentrations and ponds. However, the paleotopographic models indicate that the organization of these campsites is better explained by the differential marine emergence of coastal landforms. For instance, Group 4 features are arranged across a small mound that constituted the highest coastal vantage point on Qalirusiq around 4500 BP. Similarly, Group 3 dwellings are arranged along the remains of a thin peninsula that bordered a cove, which both formed around 4000 BP (Figure 6.5). Although the precise age of many features remains uncertain, radiocarbon dates from Groups 3 and 4 corroborate the inferred temporal connection between the formation of these landforms and the construction of Tuniit campsites on the upper terraces (Figure 6.4a). These locational strategies suggest differences in the preferences and possibly the practices of local camp communities, with those in Group Four prioritizing a broad view shed of the floe edge, and those in Group Three prioritizing access to a wind-sheltered bay.

Figure 6.4a Map of NiHf-1 highlighting the variation of surveyed features in relation to topography.

Figure 6.4b The distribution of feature groupings and structural forms and in relation to simplified landscape elements at NiHf-1.

Figure 6.5a Topographic transformation of NiHf-1 in relation to surveyed archaeological features.

Figure 6.5b Topographic evolution of NiHf-1 in relation to surveyed archaeological features.

The examination of potential inundated features offers further insight into Tuniit locational strategies. A comparison between the survey data and Rowley's (1991a) modified sketch of Meldgaard's site map (Figure 2.3) reveals that a submerged structure west of Group 2 was situated more than 20 meters away from a pond's boundary in 1991. This observation indicates that the pond's expansion is recent, suggesting that Early Tuniit peoples may have not constructed their dwellings around freshwater features along the summit, despite the proximity of dwelling remains to modern ponds. These comparisons also help validate the archaeological nature of submerged features identified through the RPA surveys, and underscore the potential impact of paleolimnological processes on interpretations of Tuniit locational strategies and campsite organization in Amittuq.

Rather than high concentrations of multi-row boulder structures, most dwellings located on the 47–52 MASL terraces consist of sparser groupings of boulders or flagstones, which may have functioned as tent weights or platforms for snow houses (IE108; IE157; Ryan 2019; Sutherland 2013, see F77 in Figure 6.2a). There are also numerous dwellings without peripheral boundary markers in these areas, such as isolated midpassages and flat sod patches with central hearths, which I interpret as snow houses (Group 10 in Figure 6.4b, see IE108; IE157; Ramsden and Murray 1995). Areas with greater variability in their architectural forms, such as those in Groups 6–9, are found in association with higher concentrations of boulder caches. Surface faunal remains recorded from these caches include seal, walrus, and polar bear (Walker 2020b). Caribou remains were also discovered in the vicinity of archaeological features, but dated specimens were modern (see Section 6.1). While no neonate faunal elements, which are indicative of spring activities, were recovered from these contexts, several of the seal and walrus bones came from juvenile individuals. As Kotar (2022:146) explains, high frequencies of

sexually immature seal and walrus remains in archaeological assemblages suggest fall and winter hunting activities along shore leads or at the floe edge, rather than open-water hunting in the summer (Kotar 2022:146).

These observations are supported by the analysis of legacy data from excavations on the nearby butte of Kaleruserk (i.e., NiHf-2). Murray's (1996) analysis of the faunal assemblages of two flagstone surface dwellings located at 48–46 MASL revealed high frequencies of migratory bird species that suggest some occupations took place between June to August, as well as high numbers of juvenile seal remains. Alternatively, the faunal assemblage of a larger double-walled boulder dwelling (Feature C) at 45.5 MASL contained migratory bird remains as well as neonate seal remains, which suggests occupations took place in both the autumn and spring (Murray 1996:61–62). The higher concentration of architectural stones in Feature C may indicate it was constructed for cold weather use, while the higher amount of faunal remains and greater depth of the deposit suggest it was occupied for longer durations of time or on multiple occupations (Murray 1996:63). These findings are supported by excavation data from Kapuivik, which indicate that the construction of similar boulder dwellings in Area 223 (F20 and F38) took place between the late autumn and early spring (Kotar 2022).

The higher frequency of more transient architectural forms (e.g., sparser boulder dwellings and those without peripheries) may suggest shorter-term occupations were more common at NiHf-1 compared to those at NiHf-117. Given the frequency of storage structures (Figure 6.4), occupational activities may have focused on preparing and exploiting caches at the beginning and end of the cold seasons. Additionally, excavation data from NiHf-2 suggest that settlements may have also taken place during warmer months (fall and late spring) when hunting

and travelling took place on the pack ice (Murray 1996).

Architectural variability increases along the 42–46 MASL terraces, suggesting changes in the seasonal contexts of occupations later into the Early Tuniit Period. Group 12 contains lithic and ivory debitage scatters and external hearths indicative of warm weather outdoor activities, as well as a variety of dwellings such as isolated midpassages, flagstone dwellings, and boulder dwellings that are likely the products of both cold and warm weather residential contexts (Figure 6.4b). Although modern grading activities have disturbed features in this area, the entrances of dwellings do not appear to be linearly organized but rather are clustered on a flat plain. Similar to Kapuivik (in Area 222), this may suggest the organization of daily household activities within shared extramural spaces, such as those related to cooperative food preparation and storage. Five small slab structures (<1m²), which are likely warm weather fox traps⁵, are also suggestive of shorter yet potentially recurrent occupations in the autumn (Figure 6.6). However, as Amitturmiut Knowledge Holders describe similar stone slab traps set by their ancestors, it is important to recognize that some of these traps may represent later features constructed by Inuit (see IE180; IE182). This said, evidence for black rock tripe between the stones indicate they have not been moved for several centuries, suggesting they are Tuniit or perhaps Early Inuit in origin. This possibility points to the complex, intersecting temporalities of Qalirusiq, and the importance of excavations and more extensive radiocarbon dating in future work to better understand past occupation.

⁵² Amitturmiut Knowledge Holders describe similar stone traps that were set in the autumn (see IE180; IE182).

Figure 6.6 Example of stone slab fox trap at NiHf-1.

Dwellings in Group 12 are interspersed with 18 boulder caches, suggesting that this residential area may have been visited in different seasons for the purpose of cache preparation and exploitation. Several artifacts embedded in the moss within the caches were documented during survey. This includes a large percussion biface similar to one recovered from NhHd-11: F18 at Alarniq, a dwelling which dated to cal. 2704 – 2427 BP (2σ), as well as an open-socket harpoon head that remains chronologically associated with the terminal Early Tuniit Period (3300-2800) within the regional typology (Houmard 2018:33, Walker 2020b). While the current state of artifact typologies in the eastern Canadian Arctic are tenuous (see Chapter Five), the presence of these artifacts may potentially indicate that repeated residential and caching activities in Group 12 included visits at the end of the Early Tuniit Period. Repeated activities may have taken place due to the unique spatial setting of the eastern plateau, as the area would have offered protection from the Uangnaq wind and have been less susceptible to snow accumulation that

could obscure cache locations (Bielawski 1988; IE025; IE172; IE138). As discussed in section 2.3, the repeated use of this area may also be related to its orientation to the floe edge and polynyas to the north and east.

The lower terraces also feature a row of cairns situated on the southern edge of the summit between 42–45 MASL, associated with four double-walled rectangular boulder dwellings containing internal hearths (Group 14, Figure 6.4b). These dwellings potentially indicate winter occupations and storage practices akin to those inferred at NiHf-117, particularly since the cairns at NiHf-117 are positioned on similar terraces between 43–45 MASL. The locational resemblances of the cairn features are significant; while boulder caches are present throughout Qalirusiq, cairns are confined to coastal terraces in areas with concentrated scree (Figure 6.7). Building large cairns in areas with abundant construction materials would have been practical, but their placement might also indicate a desire for visibility from the water or floe edge, or a preference for well-drained areas to preserve their contents (IE433; IE438). If these features correspond temporally to Feature Groups 3–7 at NiHf-117, it could suggest that camp communities at this time demarcated themselves by constructing camps that faced distinct sections of the floe edge and that were not mutually visible, perhaps keeping their hunting activities separate from those who occupied the western and northern sides of the islet.

Figure 6.7 Two cairns (F204 and F205) constructed from the surrounding scree at NiHf-1.

The diversity of cache features and seasonal structures within NiHf-1 suggests that Qalirusiq may have not only been a major settlement for sea mammal hunting on shore leads, but potentially a storage outpost for ice camps located near hunting places such as the Sikutuqqijjuq polynya or the Naggutialuk ice lead, at times when shallower waters and rising seabeds led to increasing distances between land and the floe edge (Figure 4.7). By providing a land base for food caching, NiHf-1 may have served as an important, repeatedly visited residential location for communities. The variation present in the spatial setting and structure of Early Tuniit campsites at NiHf-117 and NiHf-1 highlights the complex nature of Tuniit occupational practices, even in the restricted context of coastal economic activities on a small islet.

6.1.3. Spatial Analysis of the Late Tuniit Sequence (NiHf-47)

NiHf-47 is the only Late Tuniit occupational component at Qalirusiq, and is situated along the southeastern base of the butte, about 300m from the boundary of NiHf-1. Prior to my fieldwork, there were 21 archaeological features at the site located between 20–17 MASL (associated with geological ages of c. 2500- 2000 BP), which included 16 dwellings, two boulder caches, a lithic scatter, and two disturbed structures. The 2019 surveys resulted in the documentation of 40 Tuniit features on terraces ranging from 12–24 MASL (Table 6.4). These features are illustrated in Figure 6.8. The surveys revealed significant architectural variability that may reflect seasonal differences in occupation. While architectural variation during the Early Tuniit Period is associated with local differences in the spatial structure campsites, residential organization at NiHf-47 is fairly consistent, adhering to a linear spatial arrangement. This may indicate changes in intra- and inter-camp relations during the latter half of Qalirusiq’s occupational history, despite significant differences in topography, climate, and regional settlement patterning at this time.

Table 6.4: Summary of Documented Archaeological Features at NiHf-47

Feature Type	Number of Features
Surface Dwelling	17
Semi-Subterranean Dwelling	9
Disturbed Feature	10
Potential Features	4

Figure 6.8a Map of NiHf-47 showing the distribution of identified features in relation to topography.

Figure 6.8b The distribution of feature types in relation to simplified landscape elements at NiHf-47.

The postglacial marine emergence of NiHf-47 indicates that dwellings along the upper terraces could have been constructed as early as 2700 BP, but most are structural forms commonly associated with the Late Tuniit Period (Figure 6.9). For instance, two of the features located between 24–22 MASL are semi-subterranean sod dwellings. Alternatively, marine emergence of the 12–14 MASL terraces where F19, F21, F33, F34 and F38, are located occurred after 2000 BP. As such, the NiHf-47 sequence may represent Tuniit occupations over several centuries, or potentially the construction and repeated use of campsites in slightly inland areas, similar to those found at Kapuivik in areas 204 and 205.

New architectural features identified at NiHf-47 suggest a variety of seasonal and economic occupational contexts. Semi-subterranean sod dwellings imply long-term cold weather occupations because ground freeze is required for their construction and annual repair, and they are unoccupiable in warmer weather due to leaking roofs (IE057; IE295). Conversely, surface dwellings with sparse flagstone peripheries, such as F39, are often interpreted as the remains of temporary snow dwellings or warm weather tents (Meldgaard 1962; Savelle and Dyke 2014, see also Chapter Five, Section 1.1). Murray's (1996:64) faunal analysis of Rowley's (1991a) legacy excavation data from a sod house supports inferences of seasonal variation, revealing migratory summer and autumn species, like goose and duck, and winter prey, such as ptarmigan and Arctic fox within dwelling and midden contexts. Migratory birds may have been retrieved from caches during winter occupations, or hunted locally if sod houses were occupied in late autumn.

The presence of several boulder caches, as well as three extramural lithic scatters identified by Rowley (1992), suggest that summer or autumn activities also took place at NiHf-47. Most of the caches are located in raised areas which may have been ideal locations to bury

Figure 6.9a Topographic evolution of NiHf-47 c. 3000 -2500 BP in relation to surveyed archaeological features.

Figure 6.9b Topographic evolution of NiHf-47 c. 2000 -1500 BP in relation to surveyed archaeological features.

meat due to their high drainage capacity (F6 in Figure 6.8, see also IE426). Given the location of NiHf-47 on the leeward side of the island (Figure 6.9), camps here would have had some protection from the prevalent wind from the northwest, which, similarly to the eastern plateau of NiHF-1, would have offered protection from inclement weather and prevented heavy rain and snow accumulation on the caches. The placement of caches may indicate a shared understanding of the spatial and material requirements for successful meat storage among occupants overtime, pointing to longer-term or widespread norms and knowledge within the broader community.

Although evidence for both warm and cold season occupations is present at NiHf-47, most campsites display a similar linear spatial arrangement, with the few intact dwellings with discernible entrances, such as F19 and F38, oriented towards the ancient coastline (Figure 6.9). In contrast to the dense rows of dwellings at NiHf-117 and NiHf-1, NiHf-47's features are arranged in small clusters of 2–5 dwellings, spaced apart on shared terraces. This suggests that, although the seasonal activities at NiHf-47 were diverse, the Late Tuniit Period saw distinct differences in the size and structure of the camp communities at Qalirusiq⁷. The linear orientation of campsites may suggest that vantages of the floe edge for hunting purposes were prioritized over interhousehold communal orientations, potentially indicating changes in interhousehold relations in later periods, regardless of the seasonal residential context.

6.2 Mapping Persistence and Change in Community Relations at Qalirusiq

⁵³ While the site is disturbed, my findings are corroborated by the survey results described by Meldgaard (1962) and Rowley (1991a), who similarly identified small clusters of features.

New chronological evidence for coastal residential activities at Qalirusiq challenges previous interpretations of occupational decline and abandonment between 3700 – 2500BP (Meldgaard 1962; Rowley 1991a). This includes radiocarbon evidence for initial Early Tuniit habitations that predate those at Kapuivik by several centuries, and paleotopographic evidence that potentially indicates occupations during the terminal Early Tuniit Period. The chronological data also offer explanation for small-scale change in community organization within the Early Tuniit sequence, such as the recurrent use of camps and caching places, and the potential influence of local and regional topographic transformations on the character of community practices at the site. Together, these data offer an enriched narrative of the emergence of community differences at Qalirusiq during the Tuniit Period.

I present an updated chronological framework for Qalirusiq during the Tuniit Period. Employing this new chronology, I examine evidence for campsite contemporaneity, and differences in site maintenance and reoccupation. I build inferences about the organizational structures that enabled local communities to delineate themselves within the restricted space of the islet, and the material practices that may have fostered connections between camps. I also assess evidence for demographic change, as exemplified through temporal trends in the size and frequency of dwellings. My analysis suggests a transition from multi-family to nuclear family households during the Early Tuniit Period that appear to correspond with greater diversity in seasonal contexts and increased land connectivity with the neighbouring sites of Freuchen and Tikilik, located on the southern point of Igloolik Island. The data highlight the diverse nature of local people-place relations during the Tuniit Period, and point to the emergence of flexible, translocal community structures across Igloolik Island during the Late Tuniit Period.

6.2.1 A New Chronological Framework

The expanded radiocarbon sequence from Qalirusiq is comprised of 13 new assays as well as 6 recalibrated dates, all obtained from NiHf-1 (Table 6.2, Figures 6.10 and 6.11). Most radiocarbon samples were recovered from surface contexts within intact archaeological features, primarily dwellings and caches⁸. While surface collections are less than ideal in terms of chronological control, their use is relatively common within Arctic research due to limited feature burial within these settings and the high frequency of exposed architectural remains (Savelle and Dyke 2014, Dyke et al. 2019, Howse et al. 2019). I prioritized collecting samples that were embedded within Arctic mosses, which helped to assure their chronological integrity. This is because arctic moss takes centuries to grow⁹ so that surface samples embedded in mosses have likely not been disturbed by modern anthropogenic disturbances like looting, vehicle damage, and erosion (Figure 6.12). Erosion downslope, however, is still a potential concern within the new radiocarbon sequence, and I approach inferences of campsite temporality with this caveat in mind. Despite their limitations, the new radiocarbon dates offer improved temporal resolution that permits new perspectives on site use and reoccupation.

The new radiocarbon dates provide evidence for earlier occupational activities in Amittuq

⁵⁴ Four radiocarbon samples were also recovered from extramural contexts, but these revealed modern dates and as such are excluded from Table 6.2.

⁵⁵ In dry Arctic climates, it takes approximately ten years for 1cm of peat to form (Minayeva et al. 2019; Sannel and Kuhry 2009).

Table 6.5 Radiocarbon Assays from Qalirusiq. Dates Calibrated in OxCal 4.4 using INTCAL20.

Lab Code*	¹⁴ C age (bp)	Sample Species**	Calibrated or Modelled Age cal. BP 1σ	Calibrated or Modelled Age cal. BP 2σ	Site, Provenience	Orthometric Height (MASL)	References
UCIAMS251123	4310 ± 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	4135 – 3926	4242 – 3831	NiHf-1: F1, Surface	49.8	
K505	3700 ± 300	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	4509 – 3642	4873 – 3272	NiHf-1: Unknown dwelling, Level 2	50–51	Meldgaard 1960b
P208	3560 ± 123	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	4075 – 3649	4231 – 3494	NiHf-1: Unknown dwelling, Level 2	50–51	Meldgaard 1960b
UCIAMS267490	4170 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3951 – 3743	4059 – 3649	NiHf-1: F59, Surface	48.7	
UCIAMS251126	4155 ± 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3919 – 3714	4051 – 3626	NiHf-1: F96, Surface	47.3	
UCIAMS267492	4130 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3891 – 3695	3992 – 3585	NiHf-1: F73, Surface	46.9	
UCIAMS267491	4110 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3875 – 3676	3966 – 3572	NiHf-1: F61, Surface	48	
UCIAMS267494	4090 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3835 – 3639	3946 – 3549	NiHf-1: F101, Surface	46.8	
UCIAMS267489	4085 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3832 – 3636	3942 – 3540	NiHf-1: F31, Surface	51.1	
P207	3958 ± 168	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3819 – 3363	4075 – 3140	NiHf-1: Unknown dwelling, Level 2	50–51	Meldgaard 1960b
UCIAMS267488	4065 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3815 – 3615	3901 – 3504	NiHf-1: F28, Surface	51.6	
UCIAMS267493	4060 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3813 – 3612	3895 – 3499	NiHf-1: F74, Surface	46.9	
UCIAMS251125	4025 ± 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3763 – 3557	3852 – 3461	NiHf-1: F24, Surface	49.5	
UCIAMS267495	3985 ± 15	<i>Ursus maritimus</i>	3743 – 3497	3859 – 3399	NiHf-1: Findspot 1, Surface	49.3	
K1041	3920 ± 130	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3716 – 3349	3922 – 3176	NiHf-1: Extramural context, Level 2	46–47	Meldgaard 1960b
P209	3906 ± 133	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3702 – 3333	3910 – 3147	NiHf-1: Unknown dwelling context, Level 2	48–49	Meldgaard 1960b
UCIAMS251124	4145 ± 20	<i>Ursus maritimus</i>	3690 – 3456	3824 – 3370	NiHf-1: F108, Surface	45.9	
K1040	3880 ± 130	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3686 – 3313	3876 – 3124	NiHf-1: Unknown extramural context, Level 2	44–45	Meldgaard 1960b
UCIAMS251120	3950 ± 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	3666 – 3457	3761 – 3375	NiHf-1: Findspot near F95, Surface	45.7	

“UCAIMS” lab numbers refer to AMS dates, “K” and “P” to radiometric dates.

Odobenus rosmarus ΔR = 160±50 after Dyke et al. (2019). *Ursus maritimus* modelled on mixed curve (95% marine) based on δ13C values, ΔR = 176±50 after McNeely et al. (2006).

Figure 6.10 OxCal multi-plots of calibrated terrestrial mammal dates.

Figure 6.11 OxCal multi-plots of normalized marine modelled walrus dates.

Figure 6.12 Example of *in situ* walrus bone sample from a boulder surface dwelling (F96), embedded in a patch of arctic moss.

than previously documented. The earliest date, cal. 4242 – 3831 BP (2σ), comes from a walrus sample retrieved from a small flagstone dwelling with a central box hearth located at 50 MASL (F1). This feature is located on a ridge that once formed the tip of a small peninsula bordering a cove (Figure 6.5). If contemporary with the ridge, F1 may have been constructed shortly after 4000 BP. A recalibrated legacy sample (K505) from a dwelling at 50–51 MASL may also indicate an early occupation, providing a date of 4873 – 3273 BP (2σ). However, there is no evidence of previously excavated dwellings in areas where marine emergence prior to 4500 BP (Walker 2020b, see also Figure 2.3). Considering the locations of Meldgaard's test units and excavations observed during the 2019 pedestrian survey and through the assessment of RPA-derived elevation models, it is likely that the sample also came from Group 3 where F1 is located¹⁰ (Figure 6.4).

Considering Qalirusiq's topographic transformation during the Tuniit Period, it is

⁵⁶ While the precise locations of Meldgaard's excavated features are unknown, his excavations are easy to distinguish as they were not backfilled.

plausible that dwellings in Group 4 (F38–42) represent even earlier occupations, as they are located on a small ridge at 52 MASL where marine emergence likely took place between 4800–4700 BP (Figure 6.5). The early age of these dwellings is tentatively supported by a "Type C" harpoon head discovered in F38, an artifact type often associated with archaeological contexts dating to the initial Early Tuniit Period (Meldgaard 1960b; Levasseur 2022). However, the radiocarbon sample from F42 resulted in a modern date, leaving it uncertain whether occupations before 4500 BP occurred at the site. Excavations aimed at obtaining suitable radiocarbon dating materials will be necessary to verify the chronology of Group 4.

The latest dates from the radiocarbon sequence come from the 44–45 MASL terraces, and suggest that Early Tuniit peoples occupied Qalirusiq continuously until at least 3500 BP, possibly until 3200 BP (Figure 6.11). This is consistent with the island's postglacial marine emergence, which indicates that some features at NiHf–1 and NiHf–117 could only have been constructed after 3400 BP. These data present a challenge to previous inferences of occupational decline at 3700 BP, and suggest that wintering settlements remained active for at least two more centuries. As features on the 43–38 MASL terraces remain undated, it is unclear if Early Tuniit occupations extend beyond 3400 BP. However, tentative evidence for later residential activities can be found in the surface assemblage of NiHf–1: group 12, which includes artifact types that are routinely attributed to the terminal Early Tuniit Period (i.e., 3300–2500 BP, see Section 6.1.2). Excavation of these features to obtain radiocarbon dating material will be necessary to confirm the temporality of dwellings in Group 12.

While features at NiHf–47 were not investigated through radiocarbon dating, the paleotopographic models indicate that Late Tuniit occupations in this area cover a wider

temporal range than previously anticipated. Initially, the occupational sequence was estimated to date to the beginning of the Late Tuniit Period (e.g., Early Dorset), based on the marine emergence of the 20–17 MASL terraces, which formed between 2500 – 2200 BP, where previous features were located (Meldgaard 1960b; Rowley 1991a, 2003). However, the identification of new features at 24 MASL (e.g., F1 and F2) suggest that occupations could have taken place as early as 2700 BP, while features along the 12–13 MASL terraces (e.g., F33, F34, and F38) were necessarily constructed sometime after 2000 BP (Figure 6.9). As such, the available chronological data demonstrate that Tuniit peoples settled at Qalirusiq by at least 4000 BP and revisited the site until 2000 BP. Future work is necessary to determine if the site was occupied prior to 4000 BP, and to evaluate the timing and nature of occupational decline or abandonment in later periods.

6.2.2 Campsite Contemporaneity and Reoccupation

Comparing the probability distributions of the marine-modeled dates and their respective confidence intervals reveals that several dwellings located on landforms at 47–51 MASL were likely occupied within a similar time frame (Figure 6.11). The most compelling evidence comes from the recovery of relatively early dates from the 50–51 MASL terraces. For example, F28 at 51.6 MASL dates to cal. 3852 – 3461 BP (2σ), while F31 at 51.1 MASL dates to ca. 3942 – 3540 BP (2σ), despite both dwellings being located in areas where postglacial land exposure occurred prior to 4000 BP (Figure 6.4). As erosion is unlikely to move archaeological materials upslope, these dates appear to represent real locational strategies. These findings demonstrate the spatial complexity of Early Tuniit occupational practices, as it implies that the long-term maintenance

and/or differential reuse of ancestral places may have been significant aspects of community relations at the site.

Earlier radiocarbon dates were recovered from surface dwellings situated at lower elevations such as F59 (cal. 4059 – 3649 BP [2σ]) and F96 (cal. 4051 – 3626 BP [2σ]), which are located at 49 and 47 MASL, respectively. While natural processes may have redeposited faunal remains downslope, these samples were imbedded in surface layers and appeared *in situ*. Based on location of the features on terraces that emerged after 4000 BP and the probability distributions of their dates, F59 and F96 were likely constructed around 3900–3800 BP, with F96 having been located much closer to the active coastline than F59. Similar to the occupations identified at 50–51 MASL, these dates demonstrate the complexity of Tuniit spatial practices. The probable contemporaneity of dwellings suggests that Early Tuniit peoples at Qalirusiq sometimes preferentially selected elevated areas with vantages of the floe edge to construct winter camps and other times selected locations closer to the active coastline than dwelling F59. Alternatively, the data may suggest that some campsites were repeatedly occupied centuries after marine emergence, and that the radiocarbon sequence is too small to account for this temporal variability. Additional radiocarbon dates from the upper terraces are required to evaluate the temporal range of dwelling use.

The radiocarbon dates described above also suggest that dwellings from Groups 1, 7 and 8 were constructed and occupied within a similar time frame. Given the inferred similarities of their seasonal contexts (see Section 6.1.2) the use of these campsites may reflect the intentions of local communities to demarcate residential spaces from other camps and restrict access to portions of the coast or floe edge in the process. In this sense, as Groups 7 and 8 were spatially

proximate and include a similar orientation towards the northeast coast, they may represent the convergence of smaller camps into a larger seasonal community. This likely had a pronounced effect on the cooperative relationships that developed between households, and may help explain the similarities in dwelling size, structure, and arrangement between the groups. Alternatively, Group 1 is more spatially isolated, with its intact dwellings are oriented northwest rather than northeast (Figure 6.4). This feature area might represent a distinct camp community that hunted along a separate portion of the floe edge, possibly where prey gathered less frequently. Consequently, the elevated ridge may have offered a necessarily broad vantage point to monitor potential hunting spots on a daily basis (IE006; IE017; Rea et al. 2011). This evidence for vantage points preferences at NiHf-1 may indicate that these campsites were occupied outside of the dark period of winter when visibility was low and animals did not regularly bask on the ice, suggesting occupations within the late fall and or spring.

The samples retrieved from cache features within the sequence are also significant, as they present dates that are significantly younger than those recovered from nearby dwellings. For instance, a sample retrieved from the edge of a boulder cache (F95) yielded a date cal. 3761 – 3375 BP (2σ), despite being located close to a dwelling (F96) that yielded an older date of cal. 4051 – 3626 (2σ). Similarly, a boulder cache in Group 5 (F24) yielded a significantly younger date than nearby dwellings located in Group 6. While additional radiocarbon dates are required to determine if temporal differences within feature areas are commonplace, these examples suggest that caches may have either been constructed as part of later occupations that correspond to undated dwellings, or alternatively that were repeatedly used centuries after nearby dwellings were abandoned.

Inuit oral history offers socially oriented perspectives for how the reuse of caches may have cultivated enduring memories and traditions during the Tuniit Period. Qinnngniit (*boulder caches*) were reused in some instances due to the labor-intensive nature of digging cache pits (Sabo and Stenton 2016: 43), and in others because these places were embedded in social memory and could be easily relocated for generations (Anderson et al., 1993; d'Anglure 2006: 240–242; IE427; Orchard, 1994). At other times, Qinnngniit were repurposed as wayfinding markers or graves; the latter was inferred by Meldgaard (1962) in the context of Tuniit caches at Alarniq (Anderson et al. 1993; d'Anglure 2006: 239; Lynnerup et al. 2003:350; Schweger and Burch 1991:102; Sutherland and McCartney 1991:4). Caches were also constructed where suitable building materials and high drainage substrate were known to be, drawing people back to ancestral places through broader knowledge of the landscape. Excavations will be necessary to further assess the role of caching practices in the maintenance of residential areas at Qalirusiq.

6.2.3 Small-Scale Change in Local Demography and Community Organization

The revised chronological framework allows for the evaluation of temporal differences in campsite size and structure that enrich and challenge previous inferences of demographic shifts and community organization during the Tuniit Period. As described in Chapter Five (Section 2.3), Meldgaard (1954a;1962) inferred a shift in architectural technologies from circular to rectangular dwellings between the Early and Late Tuniit periods, which he considered a marker of rapid cultural change. Similar to Kapuivik, architectural remains at Qalirusiq do not show clear differences in the form or structure of surface dwellings between the two periods. Rectangular boulder dwellings are found within the Early Tuniit sequence, such as those at

NiHf-1: Group 14 (cf. F165 in Figure 6.4), while Late Tuniit dwellings at NiHf-47 include circular structures with flagstone peripheries. Nevertheless, there are some architectural differences, like the presence of cairns and box hearths in Early Tuniit contexts and the restriction of semi-subterranean dwellings to Late Tuniit contexts. These differences suggest that both persistence and change in dwelling technologies occurred in the Late Tuniit Period (Hood 1998; Maxwell 1985, see also Chapter Two Section 2.2.2).

More significant temporal changes are found in the comparison of dwelling size and frequency throughout the occupational sequence (Figure 6.12). The most notable changes are within the Early Tuniit sequence (NiHf-1 and NiHf-117) which exhibits a high frequency of large dwellings (31.9–54.88 m²) prior to 3700 BP. This is followed by a decrease in dwelling size in areas where radiocarbon dates, paleotopographic models, and recovered artifacts suggest later Early Tuniit occupations took place (e.g., NiHf-1: Groups 12–16, NiHf-117: Groups 1–2). This pattern may indicate a shift from multi-family to nuclear family households during the Early Tuniit Period (cf. Savelle et al. 2009:226). This is accompanied by differences in the frequency of dwellings, as campsites dated to 4000–3700 BP are comprised of 5–20 dwellings, while those along the lower terraces range from 2–7 dwellings and are accompanied by a higher incidence of isolated dwellings.

Declining campsite sizes during the Early Tuniit Period may suggest that the number of people living at Qalirusiq decreased throughout the period. Given the inferred increase in local populations at Kapuivik within the same time frame, this reduction is likely not the product of regional population decline brought on climatic changes (cf. Meldgaard 1962; Savelle and Dyke 2014). Instead, available survey data suggest changes in the seasonal context of occupational

activities at Qalirusiq, which appear to have transitioned from longer-term winter settlements to a mixture of short-term warm and cold weather camps (see section 1.1 and 1.2). Available data indicate greater intra-camp variability in Late Tuniit dwelling size, but with a further decline in campsite size compared to NiHf-1 and NiHf-117, with campsites consisting of 2–4 dwellings and an even greater number of isolated features. The similar size but decreased frequency of dwellings suggest that camp communities in the Late Tuniit Period may have consisted of significantly fewer individuals compared to the Early Tuniit Period. While the survey sample is

Figure 6.13 Dwelling size and frequency across Qalirusiq. Dwelling size classes calculated using Jenks optimization method.

complicated by the poor preservation of the site, these inferences are consistent with those of prior work undertaken in the 1950s and 1990s at Qalirusiq (Meldgaard 1962; Rowley 1991a). The patterning of dwelling size and frequency may indicate organizational changes that emphasized family autonomy and smaller communities, at least in the particular socioeconomic contexts represented at the site.

Changes in the size and organization of camp communities may relate to the timing of major topographic shifts and the influence of these shifts on the accessibility and connectivity of places in the landscape. Qalirusiq was a small islet that nearly tripled in size during the Early Tuniit Period. The expanding size of the island, as well as its increasing connectivity with nearby landforms, expanded the possibilities for when and how people could travel between places, as well as where raw material resources and prey were located. Likewise, rising sea depths due to isostatic rebound affected the development and movement of sea ice used for travel, and likely altered the locations where marine mammals were likely to congregate in order to feed and bask.

Qalirusiq was the easternmost island located off the coast of Melville Peninsula until the emergence of Puqtuniq, on what is now Igloodik Island's eastern lobe, shortly after 3500 BP. As such, it was one of the furthest land masses out to sea during the period when occupational continuity is best demonstrated at NiHf-1 (4000–3500 BP). Qalirusiq may have served as an important residential site to hunt on newly formed land fast ice while waiting for the fusion of the multiyear ice that formed recurring polynyas further out to sea, like Naggutialuk (see Figure 4.7). Given its strategic location to the Naggutialuk ice lead, it is possible that Qalirusiq also functioned as an important place of food security where spring kills could be safely cached for later use, such as when inhabitants returned to Qalirusiq the following autumn. This hypothesis is

supported by the temporal range of the radiocarbon dated dwellings, evidence for the potential reuse of boulder caches, and the prevalence of yearling and juvenile walrus and seal remains in the surface assemblages of northern campsites at NiHf-1 (Meldgaard 1962; Murray 1996; Rowley 2003). It is also supported by the bathymetric reconstruction of the seabed surrounding Qalirusiq. By 3500 BP, the seabed had rebounded significantly, and the island was surrounded by shoals and shallow waters. Based on the water current patterns and local sea ice behaviour documented in Amitturmiut oral history (IE21; IE027; IE049), it is probable that Qalirusiq was one of the first places in Amittuq where land fast ice formed in the autumn during the Early Tuniit Period. These shallow waters also likely resulted in the high availability of walrus off-coast of Qalirusiq, as depths between 15–18 MASL are the optimal feeding zone for these animals (Fay 1969:113; Murray 1996:98), and these depths were abundant on the northern and western coasts of the island where large wintering settlements were positioned (Figure 6.14).

The observed decline in Tuniit occupations between 3200–2500 BP may be partially attributed to topographic changes, specifically the emergence of an isthmus between Qalirusiq and Kaleruserk around 3000 BP (Figure 6.15). This isthmus resulted in increased land access between settlements, allowing for seasonal movements in warmer weather. This may be evidenced by the decline in occupations at Qalirusiq, as well as by the emergence of large residential sites like Freuchen (NiHf-3) and Tikilik (NiHf-4) south of Qalirusiq and numerous small sites across the island (Table 6.3, Figure 3.2).

Comparing the paleobathymetry of the island between 3000-2000 BP reveals significant changes in the predicted feeding zones of walrus (i.e., sea depths of 15–18m). At 3000 BP, the southeastern coasts near Freuchen had the highest predicted walrus abundance (Figure 6.14).

Figure 6.14 Paleotopography of the western lobe of Igloolik Island c.4000–3500BP, visualizing optimal walrus feeding zones at bathymetric depths of 15–18 metres below sea level (mbSL).

Figure 6.15 Paleotopography of the western lobe of Igloolik Island, visualizing bathymetric depths of 15–18 metres below sea level (mbSL).

Table 6.6 Legacy radiocarbon dates from other sites on Igloolik Island. Dates Calibrated in OxCal 4.4 using INTCAL20.

*“K” lab numbers refer to radiometric dates.

** *Odobenus rosmarus* $\Delta R = 160 \pm 50$ after Dyke et al. (2019).

Lab Code*	¹⁴ C age (bp)	Sample Species**	Calibrated or Modelled Age cal. BP 1 σ	Calibrated or Modelled Age cal. BP 2 σ	Site	Orthometric Height (MASL)	Reference
K1074	3070 \pm 110	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2613 – 2389	2696 – 2330	Tikilik	22–23	Meldgaard 1960b
K1073	2920 \pm 110	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2399 – 2205	2498 – 2117	Freuchen	20–21	Meldgaard 1960b
K1075	2820 \pm 110	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2293 – 2111	2346 – 1999	Freuchen	24–25	Meldgaard 1960b
K1076	2780 \pm 110	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2247 – 2045	2316 – 1956	Tikilik	21–22	Meldgaard 1960b
K1072	2730 \pm 110	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2164 – 1969	2283 – 1897	Tikilik	18–19	Meldgaard 1960b
K1070	2620 \pm 110	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2026 – 1835	2115 – 1750	Tikilik	18–19	Meldgaard 1960b
K1071	2540 \pm 110	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1920 – 1742	2017 – 1650	Freuchen	18–19	Meldgaard 1960b
K1069	2530 \pm 110	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1909 – 1730	1996 – 1637	Tikilik	17–18	Meldgaard 1960b
K1065	2500 \pm 110	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1872 – 1700	1965 – 1606	Freuchen	18–19	Meldgaard 1960b
K1066	1740 \pm 110	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1695 – 1605	1699 – 1599	Freuchen	18–19	Meldgaard 1960b

However, the rest of the island had moderate, evenly distributed access to these optimal areas. If intensive walrus hunting was indeed a major component of subsistence practices, then many sites on Igloolik Island offered similar access to hunting grounds as Qalirusiq. By 2000 BP, optimal walrus feeding zones had substantially increased, appearing to correspond with a rise in coastal sites on points and peninsulas, including NiHf-47 (Figure 6.14). The increase in ideal feeding depths throughout Amittuq at this time would have resulted in relatively uniform access to ideal floe edge hunting areas not only on Igloolik Island, but on nearby islands and mainland coasts, potentially resulting in the fission of larger communities into smaller camp groups.

While excavations and additional radiocarbon dating are needed to further reconstruct Tuniit residential mobility and community connections on Igloolik Island, these findings have potentially important implications for reinterpreting Tuniit occupational history. While Meldgaard (1962) initially interpreted a population decline in the late Pre-Dorset (terminal Late Tuniit) period and an increase during the Early Dorset (initial Late Tuniit) period, the apparent connections between topographic shifts and demographic change offer new perspectives on how changing land use practices at Qalirusiq related to the production of a wider occupational landscape. Rather than local population declines brought on by climate change and resource scarcity, groups once occupying Qalirusiq appear to have dispersed into smaller groups across the island. As such, smaller camps and increased mobility may have been elements of deliberate community practices related to expanded opportunities for hunting and travel, allowing people to prioritize preferences for building materials, food sources, or residential locations to a greater degree than previous periods. In addition, the increased spatial connectivity resulting from the expansion of land may have meant that small camps remained in close contact despite the modest increases in distance between campsites, perhaps belonging to a wider community defined by their occupation of a shared island.

6.3 Conclusion

This chapter has offered an alternative narrative of Tuniit occupational history that highlights the diversity and fluidity of local camp communities at Qalirusiq. Local Tuniit communities emerged and changed through the production of residential spaces, and these practices emerged from and in turn shaped broader relationships within the landscape. The

results conform in many ways to existing expectations of a coastal economic focus and settlement strategy (Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1962; Rowley 1991a; Savelle and Dyke 2014). However, they also demonstrate synchronic and diachronic variability in campsite structures that include changing seasonal contexts, durations of use, and changing inter-camp organizational strategies. The study suggests that Tuniit occupational practices were relatively continuous until 3500 BP, with Qalirusiq mainly serving as a winter settlement. However, architecture and campsite structures became more variable in later periods, indicating diverse people-place relationships. Qalirusiq appears to have served at different times as a winter settlement, warm weather camp, and ice camp outpost. Throughout all periods, it remained an important caching place, potentially indicating continuity in community memory and the island's historic role within broader community assemblages.

Despite the restricted maritime focus of occupational contexts at Qalirusiq, Tuniit practices materialized complex, persisting relationships among local camp groups. This is demonstrated through the maintenance of caching places, but also through the patterning of campsites along the upper terraces of NiHf-1, which suggest that local camps articulated separate community identities through the spatial demarcation of their camps, likely sharing varying degrees of intercamp social affiliations through time. Qalirusiq's archaeological record also offers insights into how the island's dynamic topography shaped spatial practices, as well as how Tuniit peoples affected changing landscapes through built space. The emergence of land masses and waterways altered how Early Tuniit occupants could move between Qalirusiq and surrounding areas. While Meldgaard (1962) initially interpreted a population decline at Qalirusiq in the late Pre-Dorset period and an increase during the Early Dorset period, the evidence from Qalirusiq offers new explanations for how the differentiation of places related to wider sets of

residential practices during the Tuniit Period.

Similar to Kapuivik, my results indicate that short-term ephemeral occupational contexts, especially caches, were important fields of action for maintaining intergeneration communities. However, while caching practices at Kapuivik demonstrated a wide range of seasonal contexts and locational settings, those at Qalirusiq suggest a more specialized set of hunting and storage practices focused on late autumn and winter coastal activities. Through the construction and exploitation of caches, local communities were able to occupy Qalirusiq for longer durations of time, and could return to wintering camps even if access to sea mammal hunting grounds were unpredictable due to delayed ice development in the autumn. Likewise, the repeated use of traditional caching places brought people back to Qalirusiq even when marine environments surrounding the site had changed substantially.

These findings underscore the fluidity and flexibility of local communities in managing changing environments through strategic organizational practices and historically situated traditions of land use. Inferred people-place relations are suggestive of the persistence of social memory and perceptions of community history at Qalirusiq, and highlight the importance of cooperative spatial practices for maintaining social relationships at different scales. In the next chapter, I further explore the emergence and diversification of Tuniit communities on local and translocal scales by exploring the remains of campsites at Alarniq. This final results chapter will offer explanation for the construction, maintenance, reuse, and abandonment of large settlements, small seasonal camps, and a wide range of hunting and caching places, in a mainland setting during the Late Tuniit Period.

Chapter Seven

Reconstructing Tuniit Occupational History at Alarniq

In the previous chapter, I presented a new history of Tuniit occupation at Qalirusiq that emphasized the diversity and flexibility of local communities within the restricted spatial setting of a remote islet. In this final results chapter, I shift to the occupational history of Alarniq, the largest Late Tuniit site in Amittuq and the only study site located on the mainland of Melville Peninsula. Through the examination of campsite remains, including their form, scale, spatial setting, and temporality, I discuss evidence for enduring communities and the emergence of local social differences during the Tuniit Period. My assessment reveals that a wide range of actors and forces informed local community practices, including shifting topographic elements, the exposure of new landforms, the arrival of new peoples, as well as intergenerational norms, knowledge, and traditions concerning campsite construction, food security activities, seasonal movement, and mortuary practices. The discussion highlights the affective and mutually productive nature people-place relations, and the relational character of local and regional communities, during the Tuniit Period.

Alarniq is currently the only archaeological site in Amittuq where radiocarbon dates confirm extensive occupation throughout the Late Tuniit Period. This includes radiocarbon evidence for the reoccupation of dwellings at the end of the Early Tuniit (c. 2800-2500 BP) and beginning of the Late Tuniit periods (c. 2500-2300 BP), as well as the reoccupation and differential reuse of campsites and caching areas during the middle and end of the Late Tuniit Period (c. 2000-600 BP). Through the examination of architecture and unwallled spaces, I draw inferences about uniformity and difference in occupational practices, and explore how the

production of residential places was informed by, and in turn affected, the maintenance and negotiation of community membership during the Tuniit Period.

New radiocarbon dates also reveal occupations at Alarniq dated to 700–500 BP, extending the Late Tuniit Period in Amittuq by several centuries and providing the first clear archaeological evidence for temporal overlap between Tuniit and Early Inuit communities in the broader Qikiqtaaluk region. This supports oral stories recalled by Amitturmiut Elders that describe cohabitation between Inuit ancestors and the Tuniit, reinforcing oral historical accounts about Tuniit lifeways whose value has remained a subject of contention among archaeologists (see Friesen 2019 for supportive arguments in the Kitikmeot region, NU). By re-examining Amitturmiut stories alongside archaeological evidence for the construction, use, and abandonment of Tuniit sites, I explain how communities were historically articulated through the repeated occupation of this important settlement place in the final centuries of the Tuniit Period. This offers a new understanding of intercommunity (including Tuniit and Inuit) relations in Amittuq, and presents a challenge to epistemological hierarchies that have granted archaeologically derived culture history authority over local histories (Birch et al. 2022).

Similar to my studies of Kapuivik and Qalirusiq, I examine paleotopographic models that document the postglacial land exposure of Alarniq. This permits the exploration of how human-nonhuman relationships, including interactions with shifting landforms, may have influenced how people moved and gathered in the landscape. As a mainland site, Alarniq presented a unique set of spatial connections, such as enabling regular travel between coastal settlements and inland hunting areas in the summer and autumn (IE298; IE414; KH03). However, my analysis reveals that Alarniq was an island during its initial occupation, only fusing with the mainland between

2500-2000 BP. This shift in land connections likely contributed to the varied reuse of residential spaces at Alarniq. Early occupational contexts (c. 2700-2000 BP) feature a diverse range of seasonal architecture and campsite structures, while later periods (c. 2000-600 BP) exhibit more uniform patterning (e.g., linearly arranged sod houses). This transition could indicate that a seasonal round between wintering sites at Alarniq and summer campgrounds on the mainland was shared among multiple communities as spatial connectivity within the landscape increased.

The potential importance of Alarniq as an access route between interior camps and coastal settlements is supported by the spatial associations of caching places. Most caching places at the site are situated along elevated inland terraces known to have historically functioned as *tulliniit* (*foot tracks*) for historic and modern Inuit (IE054; Figure 4.8). The likelihood that the Tuniit engaged in similar landscape practices is supported by the proximity of these caching areas to campsites containing high frequencies of caribou in their faunal assemblages. Radiocarbon dating also indicates that people during the latter part of the Late Tuniit Period were active along the uppermost terraces of the site (21-25 MASL) (Howse et al. 2019). These findings suggest that lasting community connections were sustained not only through the maintenance and reuse of semi-subterranean sod dwellings, but through transient warm weather occupations and broader sociospatial connections with other places in the landscape. A wide range of site types appear to have been actively constructed at Alarniq through community memory, tradition, and broader social practices, as well as how the production and maintenance of settlement places contributed to how communities emerged and changed on multiple scales during the Late Tuniit Period.

I begin this chapter with an analysis of the spatial configuration of Tuniit campsites and

features areas surveyed and excavated in 2019 at Alarniq. I present an updated site map, describe new sites and features, and discuss evidence for small-scale diversity in Tuniit locational strategies, land use, and residential organization. My evaluation focuses on observed differences in the structure and organization of architecture and unwalled features (e.g., middens, caches), as well as seasonal indicators of site occupancy, such as artifacts (e.g., sewing needles, hunting weapons), migratory animal remains, and external hearths (i.e., warm weather outdoor cooking). The spatial context of investigated sites is further examined through the analysis of paleotopographic data and modern landscape elements to assess the potential impact of local environmental changes on people-place relations.

I present a new chronological framework of Tuniit occupation at Alarniq, informed by the analysis of 71 radiocarbon dates (including 27 new dates) and by a time series of paleotopographic models that chronicle the postglacial land exposure of each site within the study area. The paleotopographic models allow me to estimate the earliest landform age limit for human occupations, providing some chronological control for undated sites and enabling the refinement of calibrated radiocarbon dates by excluding predicted age ranges that occurred prior to land exposure. The resulting framework permits an in-depth study of continuity and change in Tuniit occupation, and facilitates new inferences regarding the construction, maintenance, differential reuse, and abandonment of dwellings, camps, and caching places. The chapter ends with a discussion of what the spatiotemporal patterning of archaeological remains suggests about the social scales at which community formation and diversification occurred at Alarniq during the Tuniit Period. This includes a comparison of similarities and differences in the size and organization of campsites occupied within similar timeframes, and inferences of long-term change in land use through the analysis of temporally separated residential contexts. The result is

an enriched narrative of Alarniq's occupation that highlights the emergent yet historically contingent nature of people–place relationships during the Tuniit Period.

7.1 Assessing Variability in the Structure and Setting of Tuniit Campsites at Alarniq

The 2019 survey and excavation data permit new inferences of the spatial setting and structure of Tuniit campsites, suggesting substantial diversity in locational preferences and seasonal land use practices throughout Alarniq's occupational sequence. In this section, I assess archaeological evidence for these small-scale changes, which includes the analysis of five new sites and 68 new Tuniit features. These data reveal a greater diversity in Tuniit locational strategies and occupational activities, including the identification of caching sites, summer camps, and multi-season settlements. There are now 357 Tuniit features identified at Alarniq, including 199 dwellings and a variety of extramural features. An additional 43 potential features were identified through the analysis of remotely piloted aircraft (RPA) visible light and thermal imagery, and RPA-derived digital terrain models (DTMs). The 2019 fieldwork also resulted in the identification of 72 new features that were likely constructed by Early Inuit peoples, including a large inland site (NhHe-27) comprised of surface dwellings and various cache structures. The variation of archaeological features present at the site, and the spatiotemporal patterning of their construction and use, offer a richer picture of Tuniit settlement practices unique to this mainland context. An updated site map is presented in Figure 7.1.

I first provide a description and initial interpretation of sites located inland from the main coastal sequence. I begin with an assessment of Area A (Figure 7.1), which includes the analysis of three new sites — NhHd-25, NhHe-25, and NhHe-26 — as well as the revisited sites of

NhHd-11 and NhHd-19. This is followed by an assessment of Area B (Figure 7.1), which includes the revisited site of NhHd-16 and three features located on nearby terraces. I consider what the distribution of dwellings and extramural features in these areas suggests about Tuniit land use, and examine excavated architecture and artifacts to infer occupational practices and seasonal contexts. My findings indicate that the first Tuniit inhabitants at Alarniq selected naturally formed gravel depressions as a base to construct semi-subterranean sod dwellings (cf. Howse 2017) and elevated gravel terraces near ponds and glacial till to build warm weather dwellings, caches, and possibly graves. While these locational preferences bear similarities to inland sites at Kapuvik, they exhibit greater variability in extramural features (e.g., caches) as well as the size and spatial configuration of campsites and caching places. The variability present within these contexts suggests that Tuniit camp communities in Areas A and B participated in a wide range of socioeconomic activities and returned to residential areas in multiple seasonal contexts. Radiocarbon dates confirm that these activities took place over several centuries, and as such may relate to the changing properties and potentials of Alarniq as a settlement place, especially its transformation from a small island to a large mainland peninsula.

Table 7.1 Summary of Documented Archaeological Features at Alarniq

Feature Type	Number of Features
Semi-Subterranean Dwellings	163
Surface Dwellings	36
Isolated Midpassage	5
Boulder Caches and Cairns (including potential graves)	65
Grave (Confirmed)	1
Middens	47
External Hearths	10
Fox Trap	1
Disturbed Boulder Features	29
Potential Semi-Subterranean Dwellings	16
Potential Cache Pits	15
Potential Boulder Features (Buried or Inundated)	13

Figure 7.1 Updated site map of Alarniq showing the distribution of surveyed sites.

Basemap: ArcticDEM

I then discuss the archaeological features examined within Area C (Figure 7.1). This area is comprised of linearly arranged semi-subterranean sod houses with faunal evidence for intensive marine mammal hunting activities, characteristics that are common among Late Tuniit coastal sites at Alarniq. By employing a combination of pedestrian surveys, RPA surveys, RPA thermal prospection, and excavations, I identify small-scale differences in the size, structure, and placement of dwellings. These differences suggest variation in the season and duration of occupations, as well as in the practices of households. In contrast to Areas A and B, where campsites consist of either dense clusters or evenly spaced dwellings, Area C displays a nested spatial arrangement. Here, most dwellings are organized into small groups (two to four dwellings) that are positioned more closely to one another than they are to other feature clusters at Alarniq. This pattern may suggest different degrees of household affiliation and interaction within a larger camp community. I propose that while individuals in Areas A and B likely established enduring community relationships through their shared use of extramural spaces for activities such as outdoor cooking and caching, those in Area C fostered and maintained social ties through the intergenerational reuse of dwellings, cooperative hunting practices, and shared access to the floe edge within the broader community.

7.1.1 Assessment of Area A

Area A is situated inland from Kangiq beach, approximately 300m southwest of the main coastal site sequence (Figure 7.1). The area is comprised of exposed gravel terraces surrounded by areas of thick vegetation interspersed with ponds, glacial erratics, and boulder till, and was the first area at Alarniq to be exposed post-glaciation, between 3000 and 2500 BP. My fieldwork

identified a wide range of structures and campsites that suggest Area A was occupied in multiple seasons and temporal periods, when different resources and landscape elements were present. Prior to my fieldwork, Area A consisted of two sites, NhHd-11 and NhHd-19, comprised of a mixture of sod houses and boulder surface dwellings, and a wide range of small boulder structures inferred as caches, traps or graves (Howse 2017). Pedestrian and RPA surveys in 2019 resulted in the identification of 12 new archaeological features in these revisited areas. Surveys inland from NhHd-11 and NhHd-19 also resulted in the identification of 41 surface boulder features (e.g., dwellings, caches) located within two new site areas (NhHe-25 and NhHe-26), an additional extramural sod patch feature (NhHd-25), and a potential inundated dwelling (Figure 7.2). Post-field analysis of RPA elevation data and imagery revealed an 18 potential features, most which appear to be gravel pit caches. These findings suggest that Tuniit peoples constructed a wide range of dwelling forms, storage structures, and possibly graves in Area A, indicating a diversity of occupational practices that likely represent centuries of reoccupation activities. The following sections describe these results in greater detail and offer new inferences about local community practices at the end of the Early Tuniit Period (e.g., c. 2700-2500 BP) and during the first centuries of the Late Tuniit Period (c. 2500-2000 BP).

7.1.1.1 NhHd-11 and NhHd-25: Located at 23 – 24.5 MASL, NhHd-11 appears to be one of the first residential areas occupied at Alarniq, with F18, the earliest known dwelling, dating to cal. 2704 — 2427 BP (2σ). Prior to 2019, the site consisted of 31 archaeological features, including 23 large sod patch features described by Howse (2017) as either dwellings or extramural activity areas, six smaller sod patches described as middens or meat pits, and two boulder surface dwellings. Pedestrian surveys in 2019 resulted in the identification of ten new archaeological features, including 8 boulder surface dwellings, an isolated midpassage, and an

Figure 7.2: Map of Area A showing the variation of surveyed features in relation to topography (*left*), and the distribution of feature groupings and structural forms and in relation to simplified landscape elements (*right*).

external hearth. Analysis of RPA imagery revealed an additional 11 potential features, including three small semi-subterranean sod dwellings, seven gravel pit caches, and one boulder cache.

Howse et al. (2019:541) posited that the large sod features at NhHd-11 are possibly the remains of semi-subterranean sod houses that were constructed atop naturally formed depressions, as opposed to inhabitants digging house foundations into the gravel. However, my excavations at NhHd-11 and post-field analysis of the RPA-derived DTM suggests that many of these dwellings have human-made foundations that were cut into natural runnels (F25 and F27 in Figure 7.2). This suggests that while Tuniit inhabitants favoured runnels located between gravel terraces, rather than the terraces themselves, as dwelling locations, they otherwise engaged in comparable building practices to those used to construct semi-subterranean sod dwellings elsewhere at Alarniq.

While sod dwellings at NhHd-11 adhere to Late Tuniit construction practices, the use of runnels appears to have influenced their organization, as most dwellings conform to a north-south orientation that follows the contours of terraces that are perpendicular to the ancient coastline (Figure 7.3). For instance, the DTM of F18 reveals a possible tapered entrance located at the northern end of the dwelling. This corresponds with inferences of the dwelling's structure from excavation data, which included the identification of decayed sod wall remains inferred through soil variations within excavated units, and the distribution patterns of artifacts and internal structures such as a hearth and lamp stand (Figure 7.4, Walker 2020c). DTM analysis of other features indicates that F17 faced south towards F18, while F27 faced north towards F25. Similarly, F11, which I infer as a small semi-subterranean dwelling, appears to face northwest towards F10 (Figure 7.5). This suggests that sod dwellings at NhHd-11 were organized to face

Figure 7.3 Topographic evolution of Areas A and B in relation to archaeological features.

Figure 7.4 Architectural comparison of (A) RPA imagery, (B) RPA-derived digital terrain model, and (C) excavation top plan for NhHd-11:F18.

Figure 7.5 DTM of NhHd-11: F11 depicting possible northwest entrance dwelling.

other dwellings, despite a linear arrangement pattern commonly associated with coast-oriented settlements (see Chapters Five and Six). Households whose entrances faced one another may have shared closer relationships than other households at the camp. For instance, multiple lithic cores were recovered during survey between F20 and F23, and artifacts that fit these cores were found in both dwellings, suggesting the households participated in shared production practices (Walker 2020c: 24–26).

Although sod houses were cold weather structures (IE057; IE295), F18 contains a number of seasonal indicators for warm weather use that may indicate that occupants had either recently returned from inland autumn camps, or alternatively, had exploited cached resources prepared in a previous season. For instance, F18 contained a greater number of caribou remains compared to other dwellings excavated in 2019 (NISP= 26, MNI=2). As Alarniq’s topography

offers little shelter from harsh weather or snow accumulation, it is improbable that it was a grazing ground for tundra-wintering caribou. Rather, caribou were likely hunted further inland near calving grounds in the summer or autumn (IE037; IE329; IE408; Nagy et al. 2011:51). That caribou hunting was a valued practice for inhabitants of F18 is supported by the recovery of an atausik (*cloven-hoof*) lance head (Figure 7.6), an artifact type inferred as the primary caribou hunting weapon used by Tuniit peoples during the “Late Pre-Dorset” and “Early Dorset” periods (c.2800-2000 BP)⁴⁵.

Figure 7.6 Caribou lancehead recovered from NhHd-11: F18

⁵⁷ Meldgaard’s unpublished field notes describe atausik lance heads recovered at 23 MASL at Alarniq, including one (A2310-7) with “x” markings on its lash points, similar to the carvings inferred as shamans’ objects (see Chapter Four, Section 4.1.2.3). Atausik lance heads were also found at 24 MASL at Kapuivik, suggesting they may have been produced either by Early Tuniit peoples, or by Late Tuniit peoples camping inland from the shore (see Chapter Five).

As described in Chapter Four (Section 2.2.2), Alarniq has historically served as an access point between coastal hunting grounds (e.g., Sikituqqijjuq polynya) and trails that lead to caribou hunting grounds and fishing lakes in the interior of Melville Peninsula. Given the location of NhHd-11 inland from the main coastal sequence, as well as radiocarbon dated features ranging from cal. 2705 – 2438 (2σ) to cal. 960 – 920 BP (2σ), it is possible that Area A served as an intermediary residence and caching place for Tuniit peoples travelling between inland camps and coastal settlements, especially after Alarniq fused with the mainland between 2500 and 2000 BP. These broader people-place relationships may be expressed through the construction of the atausik lance head as well — despite its function as a weapon used for inland hunting practices, it is made of ivory and was likely constructed near the coast. The construction of a summer hunting weapon within the context of a winter sod house offers insight into how people were tied to places through memory and practice on different social and spatial scales.

F18 also contained relatively high frequencies of migratory bird remains, especially goose (NISP = 70, MNI = 8), gulls (NISP = 10, MNI = 3), and duck (NISP = 35, MNI = 3), which are indicative of summer or fall subsistence activities. While it is conceivable that the sod house was occupied in late fall when some migratory birds were still locally available, the large number of geese remains is suggestive of hunting during the summer moult. The prevalence of wing and breast bones (81.5%) among the geese remains supports this, as it implies that the birds were butchered outside the dwelling, which would likely occur if they were killed in large numbers. Alternatively, duck bones are equally represented by beaks, legs, wings, and breast bones, suggesting they were hunted individually and butchered within the dwelling. The possibility that moulting geese were hunted on mass in the summer or autumn is further supported by the small cairns at NhHd-11 and at nearby sites (i.e., NhHd-19 and NhHe-25), as

this cache type was used by Early Inuit for storing fish or birds (IE306; IE427; IE433; Friesen 2002). The presence of small boulder dwellings and an external hearth at NhHd-11 also indicate warm weather occupations at NhHd-11, when geese hunting may have taken place (Figure 7.2).

Aside from sod dwellings, there are many small sod patch features at NhHd-11 that are likely the remains of extramural activities capable of altering soil composition and affecting vegetation growth. Test units placed in two of these features (i.e., TP2 and TP7) suggests that they are the remains of animal butchering and tool processing activities. TP2 contains cherts and ivory debitage, a chert biface, two microblades, and the faunal remains of seal, walrus, caribou, and rabbit (Walker 2020c:78). As TP2 is located between two sod houses (F20 and F23) and contains a high degree of artifact and faunal variability, it is likely a small midden. Alternatively, TP7 is not located near dwellings (Figure 7.2) and includes the remains of seal and walrus, as well as one microblade. As the faunal assemblage is dominated by walrus crania fragments and the flipper bones of seals, the sod patch may have been a butchering site from which skeletal elements with high meat value, as well as tusk ivory, were extracted and remaining elements were discarded (Walker 2020c:94, Diab 1998).

In contrast to TP2 and TP 7, the full excavation of a small sod patch 80m west of NhHd-11 (NhHd-25) revealed a probable hide working and ivory tool-making area. As the sod patch is not located near dwellings, it is likely not a midden, and given there are no internal architectural elements within the feature or a discernible boundary, it is unlikely to be a dwelling. However, a wide variety of artifacts were recovered from the sod patch, including chert debitage, ivory debitage, worked ivory, and a harpoon head preform. In addition to the sparse remains of small seal (NISP=12, MNI=1) and walrus (NISP 2, MNI=1), the feature also contained the remains of

at least two foxes, and a considerable number of fragmented bird bones (NISP=7). The presence of fox remains is a strong indicator of fur processing activities, especially since bird bones were often the preferred material for sewing needles (Arnold 1980; Wells 2012). The small amounts of chert debitage are also consistent with tool resharpening rather than more intensive tool manufacture (Walker 2020c:80). Given the proximity of NhHd-25 to fox traps at NhHd-19 (see below), it is possible that the sod patch is the remains of an extramural area where furs were tanned, needles for sewing were prepared, and/or tool-making took place. The recovery of a bone needle preform and three ivory needles at NhHd-11: F18 suggests that this household may have participated in these hideworking practices (Walker 2020c:24).

7.1.1.2 NhHd-19. NhHd-19 is situated in an area with heavy glacial till, on a gravel slope adjacent to a large pond. My assessment suggests that NhHd-19 represents the remains of a palimpsest of extramural activity spaces, showcasing significant changes in socioeconomic practices at Alarniq during the Early Tuniit Period as the area shifted from a coastal beach to paludal context. Prior to fieldwork, Howse (2017:16) had identified 22 features at the site, including a variety of smaller boulder features described as caches, fox traps or graves, and two larger features described as tents or igloos (Howse 2017:16). My surveys identified three new boulder features and a detailed mapping of the site (Figure 7.2). Due to the visual disturbance of the erosion of boulders downslope, discerning the original form of some features was challenging. However, by comparing observations made during pedestrian survey with the DTM and local oral historical information coded in the NVivo database, my analysis presents a clearer understanding of the form and potential use of several features. From this analysis, I interpret features at NhHd-19 as consisting of seven cairns/surface caches, six boulder caches, three fox traps, one boulder chamber structure, and eight disturbed boulder features that are likely

exploited caches. As I describe below, RPA survey of the southwestern portion of NhHd-19 also revealed long rows of boulders in an area where boulder till is most concentrated, which I interpret as human modified features that may be the remains of fishing weirs.

Based on available survey data, I argue that the larger boulder structures at NhHd-19 that were originally interpreted as dwellings are likely caches. For example, while the boulder periphery of F4 may point to the possibility of a dwelling, the nest-like cluster of stones within the feature suggests it is an exploited cache, the larger boulders of which have been dispersed (Figure 7.7). Similar to Qalirusiq, large cairns like F4 may have been storage features for caching larger game animals, possibly during the winter when digging pits presented challenges due to snow cover and ground freeze (IE427, see Chapter Six, Section 6.1.1). This inference is supported by the identification of a polar bear femur near the southeast periphery of the feature.

Figure 7.7 RPA capture of NhHd-19:F4.

Another large structure, F15, may represent a different kind of cache or potentially a grave, rather than a dwelling. This feature is comprised of a rectangular perimeter of large, spaced boulders with an internal boulder wall through its cross section, forming two chambers (Figure 7.8). This feature matches the description of Meldgaard’s “double grave” found at 22 MASL (see Figure 2.5), and resembles intact structures found in that area (Mary-Rousselière 1957). However, as will be further discussed in my assessment of Area B (see section 1.2), excavation of similar features at NhHd-16 suggests that similar chamber structures were constructed for use as caches, possibly for storing hides and equipment rather than meat.

Figure 7.8 RPA capture of NhHd-19: F15, a boulder chamber structure.

Analysis of the DTM indicates that some smaller boulder slab structures identified at NhHd-19 were fox traps. For instance, F9 contains a slanted pit that is too narrow to contain a body

⁵⁸, and no human nor faunal remains were observed near the feature during pedestrian survey (Figure 7.9). Instead, F9 may have functioned in a similar way to the ullisautit (ice door) fox traps constructed by Amitturmiut, in which a fox was baited into a stone pit and trapped from escaping due to a slippery sheet of ice at the slanted entrance (IE180; IE182). The presence of fox traps in this area may correlate with the fox remains found in residential contexts at NhHd-11, and the evidence for tanning activities at NhHd-25. The presence of this kind of fox trap suggests that NhHd-19 was visited in the winter months when the traps were functional.

Figure 7.9 Comparison of orthoimage and DTM for NhHd-19: F9, showing sloped pit inside

⁵⁸ Bundle burials and cremations have not been identified in Tuniit contexts (see Lynnerup 2003), and both would be impractical given the slow decay rates and lack of wood in Arctic environments.

feature indicative of ullisautit style fox trap.

The most common features at NhHd-19 are cairns composed of cobbles and boulders that resemble those found in Area 210 at Kapuivik, which were interpreted as fish caches (see Chapter Five, Section 5.1.1.2). The potential for Alarniq as a fishing site during its earliest occupations is supported by the unique topography of NhHd-19, which was likely characterized by a large intertidal zone between 2800 and 2600 BP. Furthermore, my survey of NhHd-19 identified long rows of boulders within the glacial till, which appear to be anthropogenic in origin, as they are arranged in linear patterns that do not correspond to indicators of past geological processes that would have affected the distribution and accumulation of till, such as erosional patterns and frost cracks (Figure 7.10). Based on their form and positioning near the base of the slope, I interpret these boulder rows as the possible remains of tidal weirs.

Cairn construction near fishing weirs was likely a common practice, as Amitturmiut Knowledge Holders recount how whole fish were cached swiftly in autumn to prevent spoilage (IE433). The absence of boulder outcrops for shade or shelter at Alarniq likely meant that the urgency of caching fish was the primary consideration in determining cache locations. Nevertheless, no fish remains were discovered during the 2019 excavations, nor were fishing tools found in the nearby residential contexts (i.e., NhHd-11). Since fishing activities most likely occurred in the autumn, artifacts related to fishing are more likely be found within boulder dwellings than sod dwellings at NhHd-11, warranting prioritization for future excavation of the site. However, fishing spearheads have been recovered from several other sites at Alarniq, including those located along high terraces. For instance, three fishing harpoons and one fishing spear were retrieved from NhHd-1:F4 in 2017 (Howse 2017:42), an area located at 21.8 MASL where marine emergence had taken place before 2500 BP, supporting that fishing activities

potentially occurred nearby.

Figure 7.10 A) Distribution of Tuniit features in relation to modern topographic variability; B) outline of possible fish weir in relation to roughly estimated shoreline and intertidal zone; C)

southwestern edge of possible weir; D) northeastern portion of possible weir

*Paleotopographic estimate derived from 2500 BP bare earth model, with adjusted sea levels.

** Estimated high tide line is 1.5 MASL above intertidal zone.

NhHd-19 is among the few areas at Alarniq with concentrated glacial till comprised of large boulders, suggesting that the Tuniit people might have been repeatedly drawn to the area to participate in a diversity of seasonal activities that required building materials, as indicated by the wide range of archaeological structures. Autumn fishing activities may have occurred when the area was close to the active coastline, between 2700 and 2500 BP (Figure 7.2, Figure 7.3). Other activities, such as sea mammal cache construction, probably took place at later points in time when isostatic uplift elevated the area and enhanced substrate drainage, rendering the location more suitable for buried caches. Fox traps, on the other hand, could have been built at any time, as both fish and sea mammal caches are capable of attracting foxes, and their exploitation would have brought people back to the site in the winter when fox traps were likely active (IE306; IE473). While excavations and radiocarbon dating are required to determine the nature and temporality of boulder features at NhHd-19, available survey data indicates that the area was repurposed for various economic activities, with cache preparation and exploitation being central activities throughout all periods. These practices would have brought people together *in place* in multiple seasonal contexts, and facilitated enduring community connections through memories, traditions, and cooperative interactions.

7.1.1.3 NhHe-25: A new site, NhHe-25, was identified inland from NhHd-19. Positioned on a raised terrace near ponds and marshes, this site consists of 23 boulder structures. NhHe-25 is the most elevated site at Alarniq, ranging from 24.5 to 25.5 MASL, and was likely the first location in Area A where postglacial land exposure occurred between 3000 and 2500 BP. This suggests that the site may contain some of the earliest constructed features at Alarniq, dating

back to the final centuries of the Early Tuniit Period; the observation of heavy rock tripe lichens on the feature stones supports the early construction of at least some structures.

Features located at NhHe-25 include eight boulder caches, four cairns, four boulder surface dwellings, one external hearth, one chamber structure (F17) that resembles NhHd-19:F15, and five heavily disturbed boulder features that may be either cairns or small dwellings. While some boulder caches resemble those identified at Kapuivik and Qalirusiq, others display larger or more prominent mounds and more varied boulder arrangements. For instance, F1 is covered with a circular cluster of boulders, while F22 consists of two pairs of small boulders, one pink and one white, atop the center of a mound (Figure 7.11). These differences may have helped individuals distinguish their caches from others, or may have communicated information about their contents (IE022; IE433). Alternatively, the features may indicate different sets of activities entirely, such as F22 serving as a pit grave rather than a pit cache (Lynnerup 2003). One knowledge holder in the OHP describes how quartz boulders were sometimes placed atop or near graves in the deep past, to mark them (IE284). Differences in boulder types and frequencies therefore may be a way of distinguishing between potential grave features. This adds a new potential layer to the kinds of relationships that Tuniit peoples developed with Alarniq, demonstrating how quotidian and spiritual life may have intersected through daily practices, and how memory and community were bounded to specific places in the landscape.

The four dwellings at NhHe-25 consist of circular structures with overgrown boulders, arranged in a row in the center of the site. The dwellings' side by side arrangement suggests that they were part of an established camp, rather than transient dwellings from different occupational episodes. Given the sparse boulders of the dwelling peripheries and the presence of an external

hearth, they most likely represent warm weather tents. This interpretation is supported by the high number of boulder caches located at the site, as buried caches were likely prepared in the summer and autumn. Given the similarities between the dwellings and the variation in cache structures, it is possible that the dwellings belong to a particular occupation phase of the site, while some of the caches belong to earlier or later periods, or different seasonal contexts. These caches may have been prepared by those who occupied NhHd-11, or people who reside at other sites at Alarniq, but who passed through NhHe-25 on their way to inland hunting and camping grounds.

Figure 7.11 Comparison of boulder caches at NhHe-25, showing F1 (*left*) and F22 (*right*).

7.1.1.4 NhHe-26: NhHe-26 was also identified during the 2019 survey (Figure 7.2), and is likely the remains of a primarily warm weather residential settlement, one with an organizational structure similar to NhHd-11, potentially indicating the return of its occupants in

multiple seasons. Comparisons with Meldgaard's sketch map of Alarniq (Figure 2.5) indicate that some features at NhHe-26 may have been previously identified. However, no evidence of prior excavations was observed during survey, and no features from this area were described in Meldgaard's reports or recorded in the Nunavut repository. Similar to NhHe-25, this site is comprised of 19 boulder surface features located on a raised ridge (23.5 MASL) bordering a large pond and marshes with pockets of glacial till. Features include six boulder dwellings, two external hearths, 9 boulder caches, a possible equipment cache, and a disturbed boulder feature that is either an exploited cairn or a surface dwelling (Figure 7.2).

While the entrances of most dwellings could not be discerned, F6 appears to face south towards the pond, rather than north towards the relic coastline. This may suggest that dwellings were constructed after the water features had formed, and may point to the warm weather nature of occupations, which were often located near a fresh water source. The fact that dwellings are found next to external hearths also indicates that they were probably warm weather dwellings, given that outdoor cooking likely took place in the summer and autumn. Additionally, as some external hearths were not found near dwellings, it is possible that some boulder features are overgrown. As such, there may be other dwellings present, making the spatial organization of site difficult to discern. Unlike NhHe-25, dwellings at NhHe-26 are not located in a row but rather are interspersed between the caches, which are separated into three small clusters, with two dwellings in each cluster. Given evidence for warm weather occupations and the proximity of NhHe-26 to NhHd-11, it is possible that NhHe-26 was occupied by some of the same households that inhabited sod dwellings at NhHd-11 in the winter⁵⁹. As such, the spatial separation of surface dwellings into pairs could potentially relate to the social affiliations

⁵⁹ A reminder to the reader that sod houses are only occupiable when temperatures are below freezing; their walls leak, flood, and degrade in warmer weather. As such, entirely different structures are needed for summer occupation.

inferred at NhHd-11, where dwelling pairs face shared extramural spaces.

7.1.2 Assessment of Area B.

Area B is located approximately 300m southeast of Area A, on terraces ranging from 21.5 to 19 MASL. Area B is characterized by boulder features situated on raised terraces surrounded by ponds and pockets of boulder till, suggesting it was primarily a warm weather camping area, one that was likely repeatedly visited and where seasonal goods were stored for future use, shaping people-place connections at the site (Figure 7.12). Prior to 2019, Area B consisted of one site, NhHd-16, which was identified by Savelle and Dyke in 2008. The site was comprised of a row of seven boulder features that included five surface dwellings, a boulder cache, and a previously excavated feature (F6) that matched the description of Meldgaard's double grave

⁴ (i.e., a boulder chamber structure) (Savelle and Dyke 2014). Since the features were well-preserved, their structural stones had minimal lichen coverage, and no diagnostic artifacts were visible on the surface, it was unclear whether the site was of Late Tuniit or Early Inuit origin.

The excavation of three features in 2019 (F3, F7, and F7b), and testing of F6, resulted in the recovery of six radiocarbon samples with calibrated dates ranging from 2247 to 1589 BP (2σ), confirming that the site was constructed Late Tuniit peoples. Pedestrian and RPA surveys resulted in the identification of fourteen new features on the main terrace of NhHd-16 (Figure 7.12), including three boulder dwellings, an isolated midpassage, two external hearths, and four caches. Additionally, three new features were discovered on nearby terraces: two boulder surface

⁶⁰ This site was not included in Meldgaard's sketch and his excavation was not reported.

dwelling at 21.5 MASL (F16 and F17 in Figure 7.12) and an isolated midpassage at 18.7 MASL. RPA surveys also detected three potential submerged features, including a dwelling and

Figure 7.12 Map of Area B showing the variation of surveyed features in relation to topography (*left*), and the distribution of feature groupings and structural forms and in relation to simplified landscape elements (*right*).

external hearth in the pond south of the site, and a possible cairn in the pond north of the site.

The majority of features in Area B are indicative of warm weather occupations. For instance, F7 and F8 are found next to external hearths, suggesting outdoor cooking took place. The faunal assemblages of F7 and F7b include the remains of duck (NISP=142, MNI=9), goose (NISP=5, MNI=2), and sandpiper (NISP=2, MNI=1), migratory birds indicative of summer or fall hunting practices. In contrast to NhHd-11: F18, where duck remains were few and elements equally represented, here the faunal assemblage is predominated by wing and breast bones (56%), suggesting ducks were butchered outside the dwelling, possibly in relation to outdoor cooking. The remains of at least two caribou recovered from F7 may indicate that some community members returned to NhHd-16 from inland hunting grounds in the autumn, as faunal elements are limited to ribs and scapula, suggesting that high bearing meat units (i.e., ribs) were transported to the dwelling, possibly with the front limbs still attached. Alternatively, the scapula may have been transported separately to be used as qaluuit (*water scrapers*) to make animal skins more pliable and/or to clean the fur of caribou hides that were transported back to the site (IE238; IE301; KH02).

Although the majority of dwellings are likely warm weather features, they appear to have been organized towards ancient coastlines. For instance, F16 and F17 face east towards the relic shore at 21.5 MASL (Figure 7.3). Likewise, most dwellings at NhHd-16 are linearly arranged and face southeast, suggesting they were constructed to face the sea after the land point that began to emerge around 2500 BP had fully formed, prior to 2000 BP (see Figure 7.3). This possibility is supported by an early radiocarbon date from F7 (e.g., cal. 2109 – 1997 BP [2 σ]), that confirms that F7 was located on a raised terrace relatively close to the active coastline for a

period of its occupancy (Figure 7.3). It is possible that inhabitants of Area B selected residential locations with vantages of the coast to maintain visual access to the coastline for opportunistic hunting, as the pack ice surrounding the nearby Sikutuqqujuq polynya remained stable for seal and walrus hunting in the warmer months (IE056; IE246). The (initial) coastal focus of occupations in Area B is supported by the remains of four small seal⁵, a large seal, and two walrus in F7, as well as the sparse remains of seal and walrus in F3 and F6. However, it is also possible that some dwellings, such as F8 and F9 (which face south), were oriented towards ponds or wetlands as part of later occupations centred on hunting small game (Figure 7.12). The potential focus on small game hunting during some occupational episodes is supported by the high frequency of waterfowl remains in F7 (Walker 2020c:54).

While most dwellings are linearly organized at NhHd-16, there are indicators that interhousehold activities took place in shared extramural spaces. For instance, the placement of the external hearth (F8b) between the entrances of two dwellings (F8 and F9) suggests that it was possibly shared by both households (Figure 7.12). Likewise, the recovery of slate and chert surface debitage between F5, F6, and F7 during survey may suggest that tool-making activities took place outdoors between these features. The artifact assemblage of F7 and F7b also includes large amounts of slate debitage (n = 237) and ivory debitage (n=47), as well as many preformed and finished slate and ivory tools, suggesting that these were majority activities that took place both within and outside of the house (Walker 2020c:50).

NhHd-16 also contains evidence of substantial hideworking, an activity requiring cooperative labor from multiple people and possibly households (Lemoine 2003). The high

⁶¹ The equal representation of vertebrae (n = 66), innominate (n = 10 fragments), and ribs (n = 86) indicates that small seal were transported as whole animals, suggesting the site was located relatively close to the coast when these activities took place, rather than inland and uphill as it during later occupational phases (e.g., 1600 BP).

frequency of fox elements in F7 (NISP=62, MNI=2), with 34% being paw and limb elements, suggests that these low meat-bearing units may have been left on pelts during the initial skinning process, prior to their transportation to the dwelling. The remains of a polar bear in F7, also comprised primarily of paw bones, indicates that the animal was butchered elsewhere and possibly also transported with its paw bones attached to the hide (Walker 2020c:55-56). The presence of two scrapers, three ivory needles, and an ivory awl within F7, as well as an awl in the external hearth (F7b), further supports the prevalence of hideworking practices at the site.

Tools and hides may have been stored for future use, potentially serving as the primary function of the nearby rectangular chamber structures (F3 and F6). Meldgaard (1954b) suggested that the 16 rectangular chamber structures he identified at Alarniq were Tuniit graves, as they resembled Early Inuit graves but were found with Late Dorset (i.e., Late Tuniit) artifacts. However, Meldgaard did not recover human remains from any of these features (Lynnerup et al. 2003:351). Similarly, no human remains or elaborate funerary artifacts were found during the excavation of F3 or testing of F6, making their inference as graves unlikely⁶ (Lynnerup et al. 2003:351, Figure 7.13). Savelle and Dyke (2014) alternatively proposed that NhHd-16: F3 could be a dwelling due to its size and rectangular structure. However, the enclosed perimeter and lack of internal architecture, other than a flagstone-lined floor, suggest it was a storage feature (Figure 7.14). Given the shallow cultural layer of F3 (5-9 cm depth) it is unlikely that the structure served as a meat cache, which were usually buried deep into permafrost (Walker 2020c:42). F3 also lacks a surficial cairn, which is usually found on shallow caches to protect them from scavenging animals (IE436). Thus, it is more probable that F3 was an equipment cache, as these

⁶² Aside from the inferred chamber graves, many “pit graves” were identified by Meldgaard, one which did actually contain human remains (NhHe-14, the “Ochre Grave”). The pit graves are comprised of large mounds with rounded pits and included elaborate ivory carvings, such as the flying bear (see Chapter Four, Figure 4.5).

were often shallowly buried or covered with hides (IE281; IE428; IE469; Stewart et. al. 2000:265).

Figure 7.13 Plan view of F6 (*left*) and DTM visualizing previously excavated area (*right*)

Figure 7.14 Plan view of F3, before excavation (*left*) and with excavated architecture (*right*).

The sparse assemblages of F3 and F6 provide evidence for their possible function as equipment caches. First, the faunal assemblages of both features are dominated by low meat

bearing units: F3 contained a small seal phalanx as well as a walrus maxilla, a tusk fragment, and a walrus tooth, while F6 included a small seal phalanx, large seal vertebra, and 6 unidentified burned bone fragments. The presence of seal phalanges is notable, as the distal bones in the paw are often left attached to hides after they are initially skinned, suggesting that rough hides may have been stored in the features (IE485). Indeed, Early Inuit are known to have cached hides for future use (IE119; IE120; IE455; IE701), and ringed seal hides were the primary material used for tent coverings at summer camps (IE202; IE375). The remaining bones may have also served as valued material resources. The few walrus remains found at F3 are likely associated with ivory processing, and may represent the storage of crania for future tusk extraction. The presence of burned bones in F6 is also noteworthy; while burning may be associated with food refuse, blubber covered pre-burned bones were used by Amitturmiut as charcoal to fuel summer hearths when cassiope was not present. Burned bones from cooking may have been stored at warm weather sites as an emergency fuel source for returning occupants the following year (IE469).

The potential function of rectangular boulder structures as equipment caches not only explains their enclosed architecture and shallow chambers, but also their limited occurrence at multiple sites at Alarniq. For example, only one such structure is found at each NhHd-19 and NhHe-25, and only one intact structure is located on the 22 MASL terrace where Meldgaard's "double grave" was excavated (Lynnerup et al. 2003: Figure 2). Their infrequent presence suggests these structures might have been shared by multiple households within each camp community. As Late Tuniit chamber structures are exclusive to Alarniq, they may be associated with the locale's potential role as a gateway between coastal settlements and interior camps or resource areas. In this respect, NhHd-16 may have served as an outpost camp where people waited for new ice formation in late autumn before travelling to winter settlements like

Qalirusiq, and returned to in the summer to gather materials and prepare for travel to inland camps. This interpretation accounts for the temporal range of dwellings and variability in cache structures, as well as the presence of two potential snow dwellings (represented by isolated midpassages) in Area B (Figure 7.12). In either case, the diverse structures at NhHd-16 reflect a wide range of people-place relationships, incorporating changing seasonal contexts, caching practices, and landscape movements into the persistent use of a small residential space.

7.1.3 Assessment of Area C

Area C is situated on exposed gravel terraces interspersed with pockets of heavy sod, ranging from 10-15 MASL (Figure 7.1). The identification of new dwellings in the area, as well as excavations that suggest inter-household differences in economic practices, indicate significant land use variation despite a continued focus on marine-oriented hunting practices among its occupants. Prior to 2019, Area C was comprised of seven small sites that together included 42 semi-subterranean sod dwellings, four previously excavated sod dwellings (two by Meldgaard [1962], and two by Howse [2017]), 12 middens, and a boulder cache. The 2019 surveys and excavations resulted in the identification of a new site (NhHd-24) comprised of three semi-subterranean sod dwellings, as well as three new semi-subterranean sod dwellings at NhHd-10. An additional 13 potential features were identified through RPA thermal survey and analysis of an RPA-derived DTM, including ten semi-subterranean dwellings, a boulder surface dwelling, and two external hearths. These features are presented in Figure 7.15.

Figure 7.15 Map of Area B showing the variation of surveyed features in relation to topography (*left*), and the distribution of feature groupings and structural forms and in relation to simplified landscape elements (*right*). A) depicts a thermal image of newly documented semi-subterranean dwelling, and B) A digital terrain model of another newly documented semi-subterranean dwelling.

Area C consists predominantly of sod dwellings built along the apex of a coastal bight that formed between 2000 and 1500 BP (Figure 7.16). However, radiocarbon dates suggest some dwellings were reoccupied for several centuries, while others were constructed as part of later occupations, with calibrated radiocarbon dates ranging from 2237 to 573 BP (2σ). Like other areas within the main coastal sequence, camp sites and cache clusters in Area C were previously inferred as winter and spring settlements with a focus on hunting seal and walrus, and increased communal walrus hunting in later periods (Howse et al. 2019, Meldgaard 1962; Savelle and Dyke 2014). The marine focus of Tuniit subsistence activities in Area C is supported by available faunal data from the 2019 excavations. For instance, small seal dominates the faunal assemblages of NhHe-12: F4 and its associated midden, and is well represented within test units from NhHd-21 (Table 7.1 and 7.2). However, walrus is only moderately represented at NhHe-12: F4, making up less than 8% of the total assemblage, with arctic fox and bird remains being more highly represented. This is notable since NhHe-12: F4 is one of the latest occupied features at the site, with dates ranging from cal. 910 – 744 (2σ) to cal. 675-573 BP (2σ), suggesting that intensified walrus hunting was not a consistent component of Late Tuniit occupations in Area C.

Survey data from Area C reveals small-scale variability in dwelling placement and structure, which may indicate different social and seasonal contexts of land use. While previously identified dwellings in Area C are primarily located on raised terraces, my analysis demonstrates that they were also constructed within runnels situated between terraces (Figure 7.17). In contrast to the large, elongated structures constructed within runnels in Area A, which followed the natural contours of the landscape (e.g., NhHd-11:F18), those in Area C are small, circular structures with deep semi-subterranean foundations, similar to those found in Area 204 at Kapuivik (Figure 7.17, see Chapter Five, Section 5.1.2.3). This variability may suggest that

different organizational strategies, perhaps related to intended seasonal uses, informed the placement of dwellings within the later half of the Late Tuniit Period.

Table 7.2 Faunal assemblage of NhHe-12:F4

Species	NISP	% NISP Total (per Test Unit)	MNI
Bird (Unidentified)	58	20.2	1
Duck	15	5.2	3
Gull	1	0.3	1
Arctic Fox	38	13.2	2
Caribou	1	0.3	1
Large Seal	3	1	1
Small Seal	121	42.2	3
Walrus	22	7.7	2
Terrestrial Mammal	3	1	1
Unidentified	24	8.4	
Total	287	100	14

Table 7.3 Faunal assemblages of NhHd-21 Test Units, TP6 (F1) and TP5 (F2).

Test Unit #	Species	NISP	% NISP Total (per Test Unit)	MNI
6	Bird (Unidentified)	18	11.1	1
6	Duck	3	1.9	1
5	Duck	1	5.3	1
6	Arctic Fox	1	0.6	1
5	Large Seal	3	1.9	1
6	Small Seal	27	16.7	1
5	Small seal	2	10.5	1
6	Walrus	4	2.5	1
5	Walrus	5	26.3	1
6	Terrestrial Mammal	2	1.2	1
6	Unidentified	104	64.2	
5	Unidentified	11	57.9	

Figure 7.16 Topographic evolution of Area C in relation to archaeological features.

Figure 7.17 RPA-derived digital terrain model showing semi-subterranean dwellings located in runnels and gravel terraces; new dwellings are outlined, previous dwellings are marked with squares*.
 *due to their shallow foundations, sod dwellings located on terraces are not clearly visualized in the DTM.

Sod dwellings located within runnels in Area C are contrasted with the sod dwellings found nearby on gravel terraces, which tend to be larger, rectangular structures with shallow semi-subterranean foundations. For instance, NhHd-21:F1 (TP6), which is located in a marshy tread at 14 MASL, is 8m² in size with an excavated house floor that reached a depth of 25.5 m below surface, while NhHd-9:F5, which is located on the 11.5 MASL terrace, is 27m² in size with an excavated house floor that reached a depth of 14 cm (Howse 2015:22; Walker 2020c:70). A possible explanation for the structural differences between runnel-based and terrace-based

dwelling is that they represent different kinds of seasonal architecture. Inhabitants of Area C may have selected runnels due to their thick organic surface layers, which likely offered more stable, as well as more insulating, foundations for winter sod dwellings (IE408). However, runnel-based dwellings were also exposed to a higher probability of flooding due to their low drainage capacities and position down slope (IE426; IE442). Consequently, it is plausible that these structures were designed for habitation during the arid phase of the cold season (i.e., late autumn – late winter), as opposed to the spring when brief periods of meltwater were more likely to inundate dwelling floors.

In contrast, dwellings located on gravel terraces may have been intended for use through the spring, as they were resistant to flooding due to their elevation and the higher drainage capacity of their mineral substrates. Additionally, gravel terraces offer a clearer vantage of the floe edge where opportunistic marine hunting would occur—an advantage that may have been less of an influence on the placement of runnel-based houses if they were intended for occupation during the dark period of winter, when visibility was low. The potential different seasonal contexts of sod houses in Area C may also explain the larger size of terrace-based dwellings (Figure 7.18), as spring was a time when people tended to congregate in larger numbers and were more likely to live in multi-family households (IE056; IE134; IE479; Howse et al. 2021, see Chapter Four, Section 4.2.2). Unfortunately, the faunal assemblages of excavated features do not present clear indicators of autumn or spring occupation, and further excavations are needed to determine the seasonal contexts of dwelling construction and use.

The identification of a new boulder dwelling and two potential hearths southeast of NhHe-12 F4 suggests that Area C may have also been periodically occupied in the summer or autumn (Figure 2.19). As discussed in Chapter Five (Section 1.2.3), Amitturmiut would

sometimes construct tent dwellings near the platforms of their sod houses to await the refreeze when it would be possible to rebuild sod walls (IE057; IE295). The presence of the boulder dwelling may represent such an activity, given its proximity to sod houses. As the boulder features were camouflaged by macrolichens and only detectable through RPA thermal survey, it is possible that warm weather structures are underrepresented in coastal contexts at Alarniq, and as such that Late Tuniit peoples may have participated in a wider range of occupational practices than are accounted for by available survey data in Area C. The expansion of RPA thermal surveys should be prioritized as part of future fieldwork to determine the frequency of surface architecture within previously surveyed site areas, especially those with thicker vegetation.

Figure 7.18 Relative size of dwellings in Area C, highlighting those located in runnels.
Basemap: ArcticDEM

Figure 7.19 Orthoimage of new features near NhHe-12 (*left*) and thermal imagery of the same area, showing a) a prospected boulder surface dwelling and b) a sod dwelling (*right*).

The spatial organization of features in Area C exhibit a unique pattern, in which most dwellings are arranged in small linear groups that face the coast (Figure 7.15), but which appear to have been occupied within similar time frames, suggesting they were part of a shared settlement (see Section Two). Some organizational decisions may have been related to the distribution of landscape elements. For instance, the construction of dwellings within runnels was restricted to small areas where soil and vegetation accumulated between terraces likely contributing the spatial discontinuity of dwellings located at similar elevations. However, the proximity of dwellings may have also been socially motivated, serving to foster or maintain social closeness between households during the winter months when extramural communal

activities, like hideworking, were not feasible. This may also explain why dwellings situated within a shared group tend to be of a similar size and architectural form, as well as why tightly placed dwellings include disparate radiocarbon dates that suggest the intergenerational reoccupation of features. Like NhHd-11, where sod houses appear to be organized in pairs (see section 1.1), these spatial practices suggest that winter camp communities were multiscalar, with varied degrees of sociospatial connection between households within larger, linearly organized settlements.

7.2 Persistence and Change in Community Relations at Alarniq

In this section, I present an in-depth temporal analysis of archaeological contexts at Alarniq to develop a richer narrative about continuity and change in place-community relations during the Tuniit Period. My analysis incorporates 71 radiocarbon dates recovered from Tuniit dwellings or unwallied features, supplemented by further examination of the paleotopographic models to refine the earliest age limits (i.e., the age of postglacial land exposure) for each site. By analyzing chronological data, I draw new inferences about the construction, maintenance, differential reuse, and abandonment of residential places at Alarniq, and discuss evidence for the emergence and diversification of Tuniit communities on a local scale. My findings suggest how people and places actively and repeatedly shaped one another. Importantly, the research challenges prime mover models that reduce social and material differences to deterministic forces such as climate change and resource stress.

I first present an updated chronological framework to determine the extent of occupational continuity at Alarniq throughout the Tuniit Period. I provide radiocarbon evidence

that challenges prior interpretations of possible site abandonment from 2400 to 2000 BP, and again from 1500 to 1000 BP (Howse et al. 2019:541). Contrary to these interpretations, the new and recalibrated radiocarbon dates indicate relatively continuous occupations at Alarniq beginning in the terminal Early Tuniit Period until terminal Late Tuniit Period. My assessment also suggests that terminal Late Tuniit occupations in Amittuq persisted several centuries later than previous analyses have suggested, with radiocarbon dates extending local occupations into the fourteenth century CE. These radiocarbon dates offer the clearest evidence for temporal overlap between Late Tuniit and Early Inuit peoples in the region, supporting Amitturmiut testimonies that describe the cohabitation of Tuniit and Early Inuit at Alarniq and other sites in the region (IE246; IE249).

Next, I examine radiocarbon dates within and between feature areas to identify intergenerational site maintenance practices, and to assess inter-campsite contemporaneity. My analysis reveals that many dwellings were either maintained or differentially reused over several centuries, indicating that campsites located on terraces of disparate geological age were regularly occupied within similar time frames (see Howse et al. 2019). Comparisons between these contexts permits inferences about how people established visual-spatial connections and boundaries to create, express, and/or affirm interhousehold and intercamp relations, offering insight into the social and spatial scales at which local communities were formed and diversified over time.

I also assess long-term changes in community organization within the temporal sequence. By comparing radiocarbon data and paleotopographic models with excavated contexts, I draw inferences about residential mobility and community connections within the broader landscape.

My findings highlight the emergence of pronounced differences in the architecture and spatial structure of cold weather settlements beginning around 2000 BP. Material changes within this time frame have previously been explained as adaptive responses to colder temperatures that led to increased sea ice, and, as a result, intensified marine mammal hunting and large semi-sedentary coastal settlements (Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1962; Howse et al. 2021). However, my analysis reveals that a multitude of factors informed local community practices, including shifting topographic features, new land exposure, new inhabitants, and community knowledge and traditions regarding household construction, food security practices (e.g., caching), seasonal movements, and mortuary activities. These findings highlight the mutually productive and relational nature of communities and places during the Tuniit Period.

I also consider how concurrent occupations by Late Tuniit and Early Inuit peoples at Alarniq may have informed the spatial organization of terminal Late Tuniit communities. Inuit residences and caching areas are primarily found in the northern portion of Alarniq. In contrast, terminal Late Tuniit camps are located further south, and exhibit closer proximity to one another than to Inuit camps. This spatial arrangement may suggest deliberate efforts by Tuniit people to distinguish their camp communities through subtle demarcations in residential space, while still maintaining broader social affiliations that separated them from Inuit inhabitants. These spatial practices may have also served to affirm communal control over resource places and hunting grounds, such as the coastal apex in Area C located near the Sikituqqijuq polynya, or caching areas in Area A where abundant building materials (e.g., glacial till) are present. This may explain why areas where Late Tuniit peoples reoccupied houses in the final centuries of the Tuniit Period show the most extensive temporal ranges of intergenerational use documented at Alarniq. These findings indicate that changes in Tuniit community organization involved a myriad of human and

nonhuman spatial relations, and as such are not reducible to prime movers such as climate change or resource stress. The spatiotemporal patterning of local camps highlights the historically situated nature of occupational practices, and the mutually constitutive nature of places and communities during the Tuniit Period.

7.2.1 A New Chronological Framework

The updated radiocarbon sequence includes 27 new radiocarbon dates and 44 previously published dates that broaden the temporal range of Tuniit activities at Alarniq. The dates provide evidence for terminal Early Tuniit occupations and extend the Late Tuniit Period within the region by several centuries (Table 7.3; Figures 7.21 and 7.22). These findings both challenge and expand prior inferences of occupational discontinuity at Alarniq, suggesting that previously inferred periods of site abandonment may be the product of sampling biases and small sample sizes. Finally, the varied elevations of dated features (e.g., later dates on older terraces) challenge the shoreward shifting settlement model presumed to have structured residential organization, and problematizes legacy artifact typologies premised on the assumed temporal correlation between beach ridges and feature age (see also Howse et al. 2019:544).

The earliest dates in the updated radiocarbon sequence come from semi-subterranean dwellings at NhHd-11, with assays yielding calibrated dates of cal. 2705 – 2438 (2 σ) and cal. 2704 – 2427 (2 σ) from F30, and cal. 2704 – 2427 (2 σ) from F18. The OxCal multiplot for terrestrial dates reveals probability peaks predating 2500 BP for these assays, indicating that they likely belong to Early Tuniit occupations (Figure 7.21). Despite the early radiocarbon dates,

Table 7.4 Radiocarbon Assays from Alarniq. Dates Calibrated in OxCal 4.4 using INTCAL20.

Lab Code*	¹⁴ C Age (bp)	Sample Species**	Calibrated or Modelled Age cal. BP 1σ	Calibrated or Modelled Age cal. BP 2σ	Site, Provenience	Orthometric Height (MASL)	Reference
UCIAMS196097	2470 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2699 – 2491	2705 – 2438	NhHd-11: Feature 30, Level 2	24.6	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS196095	2465 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2698 – 2488	2704 – 2427	NhHd-11: Feature 30, Level 2	24.6	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS251105	2465 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2698 – 2488	2704 – 2427	NhHd-11: Feature 18, Level 2	24.9	
UCIAMS251103	2455 ± 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2696 – 2434	2701 – 2366	NhHd-11: Feature 18, Level 2	24.9	
UCIAMS251107	2445 ± 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2685 – 2374	2699 – 2361	NhHd-11: Feature 32, Level 2	24.8	
UCIAMS267473	2440 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2673 – 2371	2693 – 2362	NhHd-11: Feature 32, Level 2	24.8	
P213	3070 ± 129	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2666 – 2456	2714 – 2346	NhHd-1: N/A , Level 2	22-23	Meldgaard 1960b, 1962
UCIAMS251111	2990 ± 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2538 – 2322	2675 – 2223	NhHd-25: Feature 1, Level 2	25.5	
UCIAMS267474	2970 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2508 – 2304	2645 – 2198	NhHd-11: Feature 32, Level 2	24.8	
UCIAMS267475	2965 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2502 – 2298	2633 – 2184	NhHd-11: Feature TP7, Level 1	24.2	
UCIAMS251106	2425 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2487 – 2367	2673 – 2357	NhHd-11: Feature 18, Level 2	24.9	
UCIAMS251104	2405 ± 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2461 – 2357	2607 – 2352	NhHd-11: Feature 18, Level 1	24.9	
P212	2404 ± 137	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2420 – 2358	2465 – 2355	NhHd-1: N/A, Level 2	22-23	Meldgaard 1960b, 1962
UCIAMS196484	2385 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2415 – 2350	2464 – 2347	NhHd-11: Feature 19, Level 2	24.9	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS196093	2380 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2411 – 2348	2463 – 2346	NhHd-11: Feature 19, Level 2	24.9	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS196529	2365 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2363 – 2346	2426 – 2341	NhHd-11: Feature 19, Level 2	24.9	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS267480	2655 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2115 – 1917	2237 – 1801	NhHd-21: Feature 2 (TP5), Level 2	14.8	
UCIAMS251108	2640 ± 20	<i>Ursus maritimus</i>	2102 – 1862	2247 – 1746	NhHd-16: Feature 7, Level 2	21.3	
UCIAMS267479	2090 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	2097 – 2001	2109 – 1997	NhHd-16: Feature 7, Level 2	21.3	
UCIAMS185086	2635 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2091 – 1891	2186 – 1772	NhHd-7: Feature 1, Level 2	19.6	
UCIAMS189007	2630 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2085 – 1885	2176 – 1767	NhHd-7: Feature 1, Surface	19.6	Dyke et al. 2019

Lab Code*	¹⁴ C Age (bp)	Sample Species**	Calibrated or Modelled Age cal. BP 1σ	Calibrated or Modelled Age cal. BP 2σ	Site, Provenience	Orthometric Height (MASL)	Reference
UCIAMS251109	2595 ± 15	<i>Ursus maritimus</i>	2043 – 1805	2157 – 1697	NhHd-16: Feature 7, Level 2	21.3	
UCIAMS189006	2595 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	2038 – 1838	2125 – 1733	NhHd-7: Feature 1, Surface	19.6	Dyke et al. 2019
UCIAMS188998	2030 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1995 – 1943	2037 – 1926	NhHd-3: Feature 9, Level 2	20.96	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS175940	2560 ± 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1992 – 1794	2094 – 1700	NhHd-1: Feature 6, Level 2	23	Dyke et al. 2019
UCIAMS185088	1990 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1979 – 1890	1990 – 1844	NhHd-3: Feature 9, Level 2	20.96	
UCIAMS267477	2515 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1930 – 1735	2029 – 1633	NhHd-16: Feature 3, Level 2	20.3	
UCIAMS175941	2510 ± 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1927 – 1734	2026 – 1627	NhHd-1: Feature 7, Level 2	22.7	Dyke et al. 2019
UCIAMS185087	2495 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1908 – 1719	1997 – 1612	NhHd-3: Feature 9, Level 2	20.96	
UCIAMS267476	2470 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1882 – 1695	1973 – 1589	NhHd-16: Feature 6, Level 2	21.3	
UCIAMS267478	1935 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1875 – 1829	1926 – 1821	NhHd-16: Feature 7, Level 1	21.3	
UCIAMS189008	1925 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1874 – 1825	1921 – 1747	NhHd-7: Feature 1, Level 2	19.6	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS175948	2455 ± 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1874 – 1680	1956 – 1567	NhHd-12: Feature 1, Level 2	20.3	Dyke et al. 2019
UCIAMS196085	1910 ± 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1869 – 1748	1881 – 1742	NhHd-1: Feature 4, Level 2	22.7	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS53029	1910 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1869 – 1750	1874 – 1744	NhHd-1: Feature 6, Surface	23	Savelle and Dyke 2014
UCIAMS267486	2440 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1852 – 1654	1930 – 1550	NhHd-7: Feature 4, Level 2	19.6	
UCIAMS53028	1900 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1830 – 1748	1869 – 1741	NhHd-1: Feature 5, Surface	23	Savelle and Dyke 2014
UCIAMS196089	1875 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1820 – 1743	1827 – 1734	NhHe-11: Feature 13, Level 2	15	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS267485	1865 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1820 – 1736	1824 – 1723	NhHd-7: Feature 4, Level 2	19.6	
UCIAMS185085	1860 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1819 – 1730	1821 – 1720	NhHd-7: Feature 1, Level 2	19.6	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS196086	1855 ± 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1818 – 1719	1822 – 1715	NhHd-1: Feature 4, Level 2	22.7	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS251112	1845 ± 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1785 – 1712	1821 – 1710	NhHd-7: Feature 4, Level 2	19.6	
UCIAMS189900	1845 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1780 – 1713	1820 – 1711	NhHd-3: Feature 9, Level 2	20.96	Howse et al. 2019

Lab Code*	¹⁴ C Age (bp)	Sample Species**	Calibrated or Modelled Age cal. BP 1σ	Calibrated or Modelled Age cal. BP 2σ	Site, Provenience	Orthometric Height (MASL)	Reference
UCIAMS175942	2370 ± 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1755 – 1563	1857 – 1474	NhHd-8: Feature 1, Level 2	18.2	Dyke et al. 2019
UCIAMS53030	1825 ± 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1742 – 1705	1820 – 1632	NhHd-1: Feature 7Surface	22.7	Savelle and Dyke 2014
UCIAMS189005	1825 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1735 – 1710	1785 – 1639	NhHd-7: Feature 1, Level 2	19.6	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS53031	1745 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1698 – 1604	1704 – 1586	NhHd-8: Feature 1, Level 2	18.2	Savelle and Dyke 2014
UCIAMS196094	1710 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1687 – 1550	1692 – 1544	NhHe-11: Feature 13, Level 2	15	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS53034	1705 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1685 – 1550	1692 – 1541	NhHe-14: Feature 1, Level 2	17.9	Savelle and Dyke 2014
K1048	2270 ± 120	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1638 – 1453	1709 – 1366	NhHd-1: N/A, Level 2	19-20	Meldgaard 1960b, 1962
UCIAMS267484	1690 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1587 – 1541	1689 – 1536	NhHd-21: Feature 1 (TP6), Level 2	14.6	
UCIAMS53038	1690 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1587 – 1541	1689 – 1536	NhHd-12: Feature 1, Surface	20.3	Savelle and Dyke 2014
K1047	1970 ± 110	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1313 – 1166	1378 – 1071	NhHd-1: N/A, Level 2	14-15	Meldgaard 1960b, 1962
UCIAMS185083	1715 ± 15	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1064 – 891	1149 – 790	NhHd-9: Feature 5, Level 2	12.2	
UCIAMS189002	1085 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1051 – 956	1055 – 934	NhHd-9: Feature 5, Level 2	12.2	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS189004	1085 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	1051 – 956	1055 – 934	NhHd-9: Feature 5, Level 2	12.2	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS175943	1680 ± 20	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	1036 – 851	1112 – 752	NhHe-11: Feature 4, Level 2	15	Dyke et al. 2019
UCIAMS196090	1000 ± 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	955 – 835	959 – 802	NhHe-16: Feature 5, Level 2	11.7	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS196087	1005 ± 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	955 – 913	959 – 803	NhHe-11: Midden near F13, Level 2	15	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS196092	1035 ± 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	955 – 928	960 – 920	NhHd-11: Feature 22 (TP5), Level 2	24.6	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS196091	965 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	918 – 804	922 – 797	NhHe-16: Feature 5, Level 2	11.7	Howse et al. 2019
UCIAMS267487	955 ± 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	913 – 800	920 – 793	NhHd-24: Feature 1, Level 2	13	
UCIAMS53032	950 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	910 – 800	917 – 793	NhHd-10: Feature 2, Surface	11.3	Savelle and Dyke 2014
UCIAMS251117	945 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	908 – 798	915 – 793	NhHe-24: Feature 11, Level 2	9.5	
UCIAMS251110	945 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	908 – 798	915 – 793	NhHd-21: Feature 1 (TP6), Level 2	14.6	
UCIAMS185084	940 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	906 – 795	912 – 793	NhHd-9: Feature 5, Level 2	12.2	

Lab Code*	¹⁴ C Age (bp)	Sample Species**	Calibrated or Modelled Age cal. BP 1σ	Calibrated or Modelled Age cal. BP 2σ	Site, Provenience	Orthometric Height (MASL)	Reference
UCIAMS251113	915 ± 20	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	904 – 781	910 – 744	NhHe-12: Feature 4, Level 2	14.4	
UCIAMS53033	905 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	899 – 775	904 – 737	NhHe-11: Feature 4, Surface	15	Savelle and Dyke 2014
K1046	1400 ± 100	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	733 – 589	797 – 518	NhHd-1: N/A, Level 2	11-12	Meldgaard 1960b, 1962
UCIAMS251116	700 ± 15	<i>Rangifer tarandus</i>	671 – 657	675 – 573	NhHe-12: Feature 4, Level 2	14.4	
K1045	1330 ± 100	<i>Odobenus rosmarus</i>	664 – 540	730 – 477	NhHd-1: N/A, Level 2	6-7	Meldgaard 1960b, 1962

*“UCAIMS” lab numbers refer to AMS dates. “K” and “P” lab numbers refer to radiometric dates.

** *Odobenus rosmarus* ΔR = 160±50 after Dyke et al. (2019). *Ursus maritimus* modelled on mixed curve (95% marine) based on δ13C values, ΔR = 176±50 after McNeely et al. (2006).

Figure 7.20: OxCal multi-plots of calibrated terrestrial mammal dates.

Figure 7.21: OxCal multi-plots of marine modelled walrus dates. *Delta offset of 160±50 after Dyke et al. (2019).*

Howse (2019:544) has proposed that the presence of a Tyara sliced harpoon head in F30 might signify Late Tuniit construction. However, the application of typologically derived relative chronologies should be approached with caution, given the lack of consistent correlation between the age of features and the age of beach ridges in Amittuq, from which these typologies were developed (Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1962, see Chapter Five, Section 5.2.1). It is noteworthy that Late Tuniit harpoon head types were also recovered from NhHd-11: F18, as were radiocarbon samples that likely do belong to the Late Tuniit occupations (e.g., cal. 2607 – 2352 [2 σ]) (Figure 7.21). Excavation of F18 also revealed artifacts associated with Early Tuniit contexts, such as a large percussion biface reminiscent of one identified at NiHf-1 at Qalirusiq, and an ovate endblade akin to those found in 222: F85 at Kapuivik (Figure 7.23, Kotar 2018; Walker 2020b, see also Meldgaard 1960b:75, 1965:5). This available evidence suggests that F18, and possibly F30, were constructed during the terminal Early Tuniit Period and reoccupied during the initial Late Tuniit Period, similar to camps in Area 222 at Kapuivik. This suggests that intergenerational reoccupation of residential sites was possibly the norm, rather than the exception, within coastal settlement contexts during this time.

The paleotopographic models reinforce the potential for Early Tuniit occupations at Alarniq, indicating that postglacial land exposure in Area A likely occurred between 2900-2700 BP (Figure 7.3). This may suggest that undated features situated along the 24-25.5 MASL terraces also belong to the terminal phase of the Early Tuniit Period. This hypothesis appears particularly relevant for the boulder surface dwellings at NhHe-26, whose similar spatial organization and proximity to NhHd-11 indicate that they may have served as warm-weather residences for the same households (see Section 1.1). To determine the extent of Early Tuniit occupations, as well as the degree of continuity in campsite use between the Early and Late

Tuniit periods, priority should be given in future fieldwork to testing undated features in Area A.

Figure 7.22 A comparison of large chert bifaces from NhHd-11 at Alarniq (*left*) and NiHf-1 at Qalirusiq.

The radiocarbon dates also provide evidence for continuity in Late Tuniit occupations in later time periods. Howse et al. (2019:541) inferred occupational discontinuity at Alarniq due to a chronological gap in the radiocarbon sequence between 2400 and 2000 BP. However, the probability peaks of recalibrated dates on caribou from NhHd-11: F19 (cal. 2426 – 2341 BP [(2 σ)], NhHd-11: F32 (cal. 2645 – 2198 [(2 σ)], and NhHd-1 (cal. 2465 – 2355 BP [(2 σ)] are positively skewed, suggesting they were likely occupied after 2400 BP (Figure 7.21). Similarly, the probability distribution of a new caribou date from NhHd-16: F7 BP (e.g., cal. 2109 – 1997 [(2 σ)] is negatively skewed, suggesting initial occupation of the dwelling occurred prior closer to 2100 BP. A marine modelled date on polar bear from NhHd-16: F7 (cal. 2247 – 1746 [(2 σ)] may also indicate early occupation of the dwelling. These dates are corroborated by the paleotopographic models, which suggest that NhHd-16: F7 could have been constructed as early

as 2500 BP (Figure 7.3).

A comparison of the radiocarbon dates reveals that dwellings dating to 2400-2000 BP are irregularly distributed within the coastal sequence. For instance, the shoreline around 2400 BP was situated near 19 MASL, yet dwellings from this period, such as NhHd-11: F19, are located significantly higher at 25 MASL. Similarly, despite the shoreline's location around 15 MASL at 2000 BP, NhHd-16: F7 is located at 21 MASL (Table 7.3). This pattern suggests that Late Tuniit peoples at Alarniq regularly occupied areas slightly inland from the active coastline. The scarcity of radiocarbon dates spanning 2400-2000 BP may be attributed to sampling biases rather than an actual decline in local occupations. This is because previous excavations have targeted beach terraces whose geological age corresponded to existing gaps in the radiocarbon sequence. However, features from these terraces were primarily constructed in later periods, and it is possible that the occupations belonging to this timeframe are similarly located on earlier formed terraces, potentially interspersed with previously dated features. Expansion of the radiocarbon sequence to include a wider range of residential contexts may help determine the degree of occupational continuity at Alarniq during this time frame.

Howse et al. (2019:541) also observed a chronological gap in the radiocarbon sequence between 1500 to 1000 BP, implying site abandonment during this interval. While there are no terrestrial mammal radiocarbon dates for this period, two marine-modelled dates from NhHd-1 (cal. 1709 – 1366 BP [2σ] and cal. 1378 – 1071 [2σ]) suggest possible occupations within this time frame (Figure 7.22). However, it is worth noting that these dates are derived from normalized radiometric samples, with higher uncertainty ranges than the more recent AMS dates (Meldgaard 1962). Still, given the recovery of these dates from winter sod dwellings, it is

possible that the period from 1500 to 1000 BP was one in which subsistence activities were focused on marine mammal hunting, and as such that terrestrial faunal remains such as caribou are rare within these contexts. The expansion of the radiocarbon sequence to include a greater number of residential contexts from which only marine samples were recovered may help to determine whether the paucity of calibrated dates between 1500 to 1000 BP is the product of local occupational decline or a shift in subsistence practices.

The updated radiocarbon sequence also permits new interpretations of terminal Late Tuniit occupations at Alarniq, including new dates that are significantly younger than those formerly analyzed in the region. Based on the geological age of the coastal terraces where terminal Late Tuniit dwellings are found (i.e., 6-8 MASL), it has long been speculated that the last occupations occurred around 1000 BP (Savelle and Dyke 2014: 255). Prior to my study, the youngest sample from a Late Tuniit context came from NhHe-11: F4 in Area C, which dates to 904 – 737 BP (2σ) (Savelle and Dyke 2014). However, a new caribou sample from NhHe-12: F4 produced a date of cal. 675 – 573 BP⁷ (2σ). Remodelled marine dates from NhHd-1 also suggest terminal Late Tuniit occupations of similar age, including two dates, cal. 797 – 518 BP (2σ) and cal. 730 – 477 BP (2σ), recovered from sod dwellings (Meldgaard 1962). These dates suggest Late Tuniit peoples continued to occupy Alarniq into the fourteenth century.

The new and recalibrated terminal Late Tuniit dates at Alarniq are significant for two reasons. First, they support recently analyzed radiocarbon dates of similar age found at Iqaluktuuq on Victoria Island (Friesen 2019), suggesting that Late Tuniit occupations persisted

⁶³ Early Inuit peoples are believed to have sometimes reoccupied Late Tuniit dwellings or constructed new dwellings at Late Tuniit sites (cf. Meldgaard 1962; Desjardins 2020; Savelle and Dyke 2014). However, neither appears to have occurred at NhHe-12:F4: the dwelling has previously been associated with an earlier date (cal. 910 – 744 BP [2σ]), suggesting it was constructed in a similar time frame to other dwellings in Area C, and its artifact assemblage is typical of Late Tuniit contexts, with no evidence for Early Inuit activities.

into the fourteenth century in multiple regions of the Canadian Arctic. Second, the dates provide the clearest evidence for temporal overlap between Late Tuniit and Early Inuit peoples in Amittuq. While radiocarbon samples have not been recovered from Early Inuit sites at Alarniq, calibrated dates from the nearby site of Pingiqqalik, located 12 km to the south (see Figure 3.2), indicates that Inuit were present in the area by at least cal. 905 – 790 BP [2 σ] (Desjardins 2020). Later dates from Early Inuit contexts at Pingiqqalik (e.g., cal. 664 – 570 BP [2 σ], Kapuivik (cal. 645 – 554 BP [2 σ]), and Qaiqsut (cal. 633 – 552 BP [2 σ]) also suggest chronological overlap with the terminal Late Tuniit dates from Alarniq (Meldgaard 1960b, 1962). This temporal evidence supports local oral histories that describe cohabitation between Amitturmiut ancestors and Tuniit at Alarniq (IE246; IE249), offering new opportunities to consider how interactions between these peoples may have unfolded at the site. Possible evidence for how Tuniit – Inuit relations affected community organization and practices will be further explored in Section 2.3.

7.2.2 Evidence for the Maintenance and Differential Reuse of Residential Space

The updated radiocarbon sequence enables new inferences regarding the intergenerational maintenance and reuse of residential places. The results suggest that most investigated sites at Alarniq, including those in Areas A, B, and C, were repeatedly inhabited throughout the Tuniit Period. This patterning may indicate that intergenerational communities returned to Alarniq throughout the centuries, suggesting persistence in settlement traditions, landscape knowledge, and cultural memory between the terminal Early Tuniit and initial Late Tuniit periods, as well as between the middle and terminal phases of the Late Tuniit Period.

Evidence for reoccupation along the highest coastal terraces of Alarniq challenge prior conceptions of a cultural division between the Early and Late Tuniit periods. The dwellings F18 and F30 at NhHd-11 were likely built during the terminal Early Tuniit Period (i.e., 2800-2500 BP), with F18 associated with radiocarbon dates belonging to the initial Late Tuniit Period, as well. Evidence for the intergenerational maintenance of F18 was also observed in the feature's excavated soil profile. This profile included two distinct cultural layers, separated by interfaces of gravel, that I interpret as dwelling floors from different periods. Scattered pockets of loam identified along the dwelling's periphery could potentially be the remnants of sod walls from separate construction events⁸ (Walker 2020c: 21-30). In contrast, NhHd-11: F19 appears to have been constructed and occupied within a shorter time frame, as the three radiocarbon samples recovered from the dwelling are of similar age, ranging from cal. 2465 to 2341 BP [2 σ] (Howse et al. 2019). This suggests that some dwellings at NhHd-11 were reoccupied over several centuries, while others were constructed as part of later occupational events. This may indicate that a greater number of households occupied the camp during initial Late Tuniit Period.

In 2017, Howse tested samples from a sod patch at NhHd-11 (F22), from which a radiocarbon assay of cal. 960 – 920 BP (2 σ) was recovered (Howse et al. 2019) (Table 7.3). This later date may indicate the presence of terminal Late Tuniit communities at the site. However, none of the other 13 radiocarbon dates from NhHd-11 fall within this time frame (Table 7.3). Considering that F22 seems to be the remains of an extramural activity area rather than a

⁶⁴ It is notable that the caribou samples with the earliest and latest dates with recovered from the eastern periphery of the dwelling, near the bottom of their respective units (Walker2020c:34). However, the unit associated with the earliest date (N502E202) had a maximum depth of 29 cm below surface, while the unit associated with the latest date (N504E202) was only 18cm deep (Figure 7.4). This could suggest that the size and structure of the dwelling during its initial occupational phase differed from its subsequent reconstruction in the Late Tuniit Period, with unit N504E202 existing only within the periphery of the Late Tuniit structure.

dwelling⁹, it is possible that the dated sample belongs to an episode of differential reuse involving nearby cache features rather than the reoccupation of dwellings (see Section 1.1). Notably, about 20 meters northeast of F22, there are seven or more potential gravel caches, resembling those constructed by Amitturmiut to store walrus meat (Figure 7.24, see Desjardin 2020:166). Amitturmiut have historically restricted their construction of gravel caches to areas with sand-free, pebble-like gravel with the ideal substrate depth for burying meat atop the permafrost — conditions often necessitating cache locations away from the shoreline (Desjardins 2017:51, see also IE420; IE431). This selective reuse of NhHd-11 in different periods, as well as the potential reuse of other caching places within Area A (e.g., NhHe-25, NhHe-26, and NhHd-19), could explain why this area displays a greater diversity in dwelling and cache types compared to other feature areas at Alarniq, Kapuivik, and Qalirusiq (see Section 1.1).

It is also possible that the terminal Late Tuniit date at NhHd-11: F18 is intrusive to an earlier extramural feature, and may have been deposited as people travelled between coastal settlements and the interior of Melville Peninsula. The likelihood of Area A having served as a route of pedestrian traffic during the terminal Late Tuniit Period is supported by its intersection with historical Inuit land trails leading to summer camping and hunting grounds (refer to the Trail of Angmaluqtuq in Figure 4.8). Regardless of how the terminal Late Tuniit communities interacted with Area A, the presence of the terminal Late Tuniit radiocarbon sample underscores the complexity of spatial practices and land use at Alarniq, and speaks to the enduring and emergent social connections that Tuniit communities maintained with ancestral places in the landscape.

⁶⁵ Survey of this feature in 2019, and analysis of the RPA-derived DEM following the field season, indicated no discernible semi-subterranean foundation or evidence of internal architectural structures. The test pit excavated by Howse in 2017 revealed no artifacts, but did include faunal remains including caribou and seal, suggesting this feature was a butchering site rather than a dwelling or midden.

Figure 7.23 Comparison of possible Late Tuniit gravel caches at NhHd-11 (*left*) and Historic Inuit gravel caches (*right*).

Radiocarbon dates from Area B similarly indicate reoccupation, with dates on caribou from dwelling NhHd-16: F7, ranging from cal. 2109 – 1997 BP (2σ) to cal. 1926 – 1821 BP (2σ), suggesting that the structure was inhabited during at least two occupational phases. The probability distributions of modelled marine dates from the potential equipment caches at NhHd-16, such as cal. 1973 – 1589 BP (2σ) from F3 and cal. 2029 – 1633 BP (2σ) from F6, are likely contemporary within F7's later occupancy phase (Figure 7.22). This suggests that the caches were actively used when the site was located significantly inland from the shoreline, long after postglacial marine emergence of the area had occurred (c.2500 BP). This pattern may point to Late Tuniit communities' preference for constructing dwellings inland from the active coastline,

possibly for an improved view of the floe edge or to balance access to both the floe edge and inland resource areas, such as building materials (e.g., glacial till) and fresh water (e.g., ponds and lakes). Alternatively, it is possible that some features in Area B, yet to be dated, were inhabited when the camp was coastal, with radiocarbon evidence of later occupations signifying the social maintenance and differential reuse of ancestral spaces. It is notable that radiocarbon evidence for repeated use of boulder surface features in Area B, is not unique, as similar patterns were found at Kapuivik (Chapter Five, Section 2.2). This evidence challenges the perception of boulder surface features (e.g., tents, snow houses, and caches) as transient or single-use structures, indicating that their intergenerational reuse may have been relatively common during the Tuniit Period.

Evidence for the extended reuse of residential areas is consistent throughout the remaining sites in Alarniq's coastal occupation sequence. Several dwellings located between 14.5 and 23 MASL appear to have been occupied within similar time frames (see Howse et al. 2019: 544 for similar findings). For instance, dates on caribou bone from NhHd-21: F1 (14.6 MASL) and NhHd-12: F1 (20.3 MASL) both calibrate to cal. 1689 – 1536 BP (2σ). Similarly, the probability peaks of a caribou sample from NhHe-11: F13 (cal. 1827 – 1734 [2σ]), located at 15 MASL, overlaps with samples from NhHd-7: F4 at 19.6 MASL (cal. 1824 – 1723 BP [2σ]) and NhHd-1: F4 at 22.7 MASL (cal. 1822 – 1715 BP [2σ]) (Figure 7.21). A similar pattern is also recognized for dwellings in Area C, with samples from NhHe-11: F4 at 15 MASL (ca. 904 – 737 BP [2σ]), NhHd-24: F1 at 13 MASL (cal. 920 – 793 BP [2σ]), and NhHe-24: F11 at 9.5 MASL (cal. 915 – 793 BP [2σ]) all suggesting a similar age range. These findings present significant challenges to prior models of a shoreward-shifting settlement pattern, and complicate artifact typologies that were premised on the association between the geological age of beach

ridges and the cultural age of archaeological sites. Instead, the radiocarbon sequence at Alarniq suggests that the long term reoccupation and/or maintenance of Tuniit campsites was the norm rather than the exception, and that the expansion of radiocarbon sequences must be prioritized to clarify the chronological patterning of large, multicomponent archaeological sites in Arctic contexts.

The radiocarbon sequence also reveals dwellings within close proximity to one another that were constructed or inhabited within very different time frames. For instance, F1 and F2 at NhHd-21 are associated with disparate radiocarbon dates. A walrus tooth from F2 produced a date of cal. 2237 – 1801 BP (2σ), which, considering the postglacial marine emergence of the area (refer to Figure 7.16), suggests that the feature was occupied between 2000 – 1801 BP. Two dates on caribou bone of cal. 1689 – 1536 BP (2σ) and cal. 915 – 793 BP (2σ) were recovered from F1, indicating significantly later occupational episodes. Similarly, NhHe-11: F13 is associated with assays on caribou of cal. 1827 – 1734 BP (2σ) and cal. 1692 – 1544 BP (2σ), while features near NhHe-11: F13, including a nearby midden and NhHe-11: F4, date to cal. 959 – 803 BP (2σ) and cal. 904 – 737 BP (2σ), respectively. These examples demonstrate how some dwellings were repeatedly occupied for hundreds of years, while others located within the same camps were likely constructed as part of later occupations, suggesting increases in population or temporal differences in seasonal social aggregations.

Radiocarbon evidence for the repeated use of small sod dwellings such as those at NhHd-9 and NhHd-21 also indicate that the maintenance and reuse of winter dwellings was not limited to large communal features (Table 7.3). This is supported by similar evidence for the repeated occupation of small sod dwellings at Kapuivik in Area 204 during the middle Late Tuniit Period

(e.g., 2000 – 1500 BP, see Chapter Five Section 5.2.1). The reoccupation of sod dwellings at both sites, regardless of their size and location, suggests that the repeated use of dwellings during the Late Tuniit Period was not structured by economic rationalist strategies related to the reduced cost of reoccupying existing infrastructure (cf. Howse et al. 2019: 544). This is supported by the socioeconomic contexts of house construction: a moderately sized semi-subterranean house foundation, as Morgan et al. (2018) describe, could be constructed by a single person in less than a day, and the maintenance of any sod house requires the annual rebuilding of walls and roofs (IE057; IE295). This indicates that Tuniit peoples exerted significant labour in maintaining ancestral dwellings (e.g., reconstructing walls and roofs, clearing annual debris), and continued to occupy these houses even when they were located significantly further from floe edge hunting grounds. This suggests that the reoccupation of sod houses was motivated by social rather than strictly economic factors, possibly serving to maintain and affirm local communities through shared attachments to places, or by fostering affective attachments and memories that shaped community practices in less direct ways.

7.2.3 Mapping Changes in Local Demography and Community Organization

The extensive radiocarbon evidence for the intergenerational reuse of most sites at Alarniq challenges previous interpretations of demographic change that were premised on the correlation between beach ridge age and site age (Meldgaard 1962; Savelle and Dyke 2014; Howse et al. 2019). The findings present new understandings spatiotemporal difference within the occupational sequence that challenge previous models of demographic change during the Tuniit Period, and suggest how community organization at a local scale may have changed over

time. However, some temporal trends can be observed by comparing the location and size of the 37 dwellings for which radiocarbon dates are available (Figure 7.25). In this section, I discuss new interpretations of persistence and change in intra- and inter-community relations at Alarniq, highlighting the relational and multiscale nature of local communities during the Tuniit Period.

My research highlights a variety of social and economic factors that appear to have contributed to the maintenance of multifamily households and larger camps. These include evidence for changing subsistence practices, mortuary practices, and broader landscape relations. My examination centers on the assessment of temporal changes in architecture, the most notable of which is the emergence of exceptionally large ($\geq 40\text{m}^2$) semi-subterranean dwellings that appear to have been constructed and reused during the initial and middle Late Tuniit periods. My findings challenge previous assumptions regarding the temporality of these multi-family houses, which have been typically attributed to the latter half of the Late Tuniit Period (c. 1800-1000 BP). My analysis also suggests long-term changes in community organization, which I argue were product and process of a diversity of landscape relations, including the transition of Alarniq from an island to a mainland peninsula between 2500 and 2000 BP, the increased presence of optimal walrus feeding zones near the coast by 2000 BP, and changing inter-community relations with residential places across the sea ice, such as Pingiqqalik and Kapuivik.

My assessment in this section focuses on three observed patterns. The first involves variation in the spatial setting of campsite locations, and gradual changes in the orientation of dwellings from the terminal Early Tuniit until the terminal Late Tuniit periods. The primary

Figure 7.24 Dwelling size and frequency across Alarniq. Dwelling size classes calculated using Jenks optimization method.

trend is a gradual northward movement of wintering settlements, and the increasing conformity of houses to a coastal orientation. The second pattern involves an observed increase in the construction of small, closely spaced campsites during the terminal Late Tuniit Period (c. 1000-600 BP). However, radiocarbon dates from this time are also found within reoccupied dwellings on the 14 and 15 MASL terraces. I argue that the reoccupation of older dwellings likely represents returning communities with intergenerational ties to Alarniq, while the influx of near shore camps likely represents occupations by new camp communities that previously wintered at other places in the region, such as Kapuivik. I consider why Alarniq may have served as a major aggregation site during the final centuries of the Tuniit Period, including its unique position as a mainland site during a time when a warming climate presumably made sea ice less reliable. I also compare archaeological findings with oral historical accounts that describe the exodus of Tuniit peoples from Amittuq to more southerly regions. This discussion enriches existing archaeological narratives regarding the occupational decline of Tuniit peoples in the eastern Canadian Arctic.

The third pattern involves the spatial organisation of Tuniit and Early Inuit camps at Alarniq during the terminal Late Tuniit Period. Despite the general northward movement of Tuniit camps throughout the occupational sequence, Late Tuniit peoples appear to have deliberately left wide berths between their camps and those of Inuit, which were located even further north, and which are presumably of similar age (c.900 – 600 BP) (Figure 7.1). These practices may have also contributed to the increase in closely spaced terminal Late Tuniit camps, indicating how Tuniit peoples may have demarcated their camps in subtle ways while still maintaining a broader sense of sociospatial affiliation and identity that was separate from Inuit occupants of Alarniq. However, it is notable that some Late Tuniit groups positioned themselves

considerably closer to Early Inuit camps than others, suggesting varied degrees of inter-community interaction and familiarity between the peoples. Based on these observations, I argue that changes in spatial organization during the Late Tuniit Period were not merely by-products of a changing climate or declining resources, but were likely both outcomes and catalysts of a wide range of people-place relations that served to maintain, affirm, and differentiate community membership.

7.2.3.1 The Construction and Abandonment of Multifamily Houses. My analysis presents new insights concerning the temporality and location of large, presumably multi-family sod dwellings. Previous research has suggested that large, multifamily dwellings in the Eastern Arctic were first constructed during the “Middle Dorset” period (c. 2000 – 1500 BP), with even larger dwellings, referred to as longhouses, emerging during the “Late Dorset” period (c.1000 – 600 BP) in places such as Victoria Island, the Boothia Peninsula, and Nunavik (Friesen 2016; Savelle and Dyke 2009). However, as Howse et al. (2021:2) note, few of these structures have been excavated, nor have their presumed ages been confirmed through radiocarbon dating.

While the longhouses present in other regions have not been identified in Amittuq, several large multi-family sod houses ($\geq 40\text{m}^2$) are present at Alarniq (Friesen 2007; Howse et al. 2021; Meldgaard 1962, 1965; Murray 1996; Savelle and Dyke 2009). Large houses associated with radiocarbon dates include NhHd-1: F6, NhHd-8:F1, NhHd-12: F1, which were excavated by Meldgaard (1960b:69), and NhHd-3: F9, which was excavated by Howse (Howse et al. 2021) (Table 7.3). My 2019 fieldwork identified three more multi-family houses at NhHd-11¹⁰, one of which, F18, is associated with four radiocarbon dates. Two more potential dwellings were

⁶⁶ My interpretation of NhHd-11: F18 as a multi-family dwelling is premised on its large size and the presence of multiple internal hearth features (Walker 2020c:20, see Ryan 2003 and Friesen 2007).

identified at NhHd-7 (F8 and F9), which share a similar form to those identified at NhHd-11. While these dwellings are not associated with radiocarbon dates, six dates from nearby houses (NhHd-7:F1 and TP8 near NhHd-7: F4), offer insight into their probable temporality (Figure 7.1).

Radiocarbon analysis demonstrates that multifamily dwellings at Alarniq first emerged by the initial Late Tuniit Period (c. 2700-2500 BP) and persisted during the middle Late Tuniit Period (c. 2000-1500 BP). The earliest of these houses are found at NhHd-11, and were likely constructed during either the terminal Early Tuniit Period or initial Late Tuniit periods (c. 2500-2300 BP) based on the radiocarbon dates recovered from NhHd-11: F18 (Table 7.3). While other large sod dwellings within NhHd-11, such as F13, have not been dated, their structure and spatial organization suggest similar occupational practices as part of a shared camp. While the emergence of multifamily sod houses during the Late Tuniit Period has been inferred as an outcome of increased sedentism and intensive communal walrus hunting, the faunal assemblage of NhHd-11: F18 exhibits a wide diversity of subsistence practices, including an emphasis on birds and small seal, as well as caribou and walrus (Walker 2020c: 36, cf. Howse et al. 2021; Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1962; Ryan 2016). Walrus remains are highly represented by head and hyoid bones (40.7%) suggesting a focus on ivory extraction rather than meat, possibly related to scavenging rather than active hunting. This variation highlights the complex and varied relations between people, animals, and places that contributed to how households came together through communal practices.

Some large, multifamily dwellings at Alarniq are also associated with radiocarbon samples dated to the middle Late Tuniit Period, suggesting their construction was part of a

broader tradition specific to communities at Alarniq. For instance, two large dwellings located at NhHd-7 (F8 and F9) may have been constructed as early as 2300 BP based on the postglacial marine emergence of the area, but radiocarbon dates from nearby smaller dwellings within the same campsite, such as NhHd-7: F1 (cal. 2176 – 1767 BP [2 σ]) and F4 (cal. cal. 1785 – 1639 BP [2 σ]) suggest they may have been constructed or reused within a similar time frame. The largest dwelling excavated at Alarniq, NhHd-12 (120 m²) and is associated with two dates (cal. 1689 – 1536 BP [2 σ] and cal. 1956 – 1567 BP [2 σ]). The second largest dwelling, NhHd-3: F9, measures 87 m², and is associated with four radiocarbon dates, the earliest of which suggests dwelling construction around cal. 2037 – 1926 BP (2 σ), with reoccupation until at least cal. 1820 – 1711 (2 σ). Similarly, NhHd-8: F1, measuring 65 m², produced dates of cal. 1857 – 1474 BP (2 σ) and cal. 1704 – 1586 BP (2 σ).

Howse et al. (2021:12) have suggested that the reoccupation of NhHd-3: F9 and other multifamily houses dated to the middle Late Tuniit Period served to maintain or affirm community social cohesion as part of large-scale cooperative walrus hunting practices. This theory is supported by bathymetric reconstructions of Alarniq, which indicate that the availability of offshore optimal walrus feeding zones were at their maximum c. 2000 BP, with these zones decreasing significant by c. 1500 BP, corresponding to the period when multifamily houses appear to have no longer been reoccupied (Figure 7. 26). However, it is noteworthy that although walrus is well represented within NhHd-3: F9 (NISP = 317, MNI= 3), the assemblage remains dominated by small seal (NISP = 1451, MNI= 20) followed by large seal (NISP = 505,

Figure 7.25 Paleotopography of Alarniq, visualizing optimal walrus feeding zones at bathymetric depths of 15–18 metres below sea level (mbSL) in purple.

MNI= 8)¹¹. This may alternatively suggest that other socioeconomic factors, including a wider range of coastal hunting practices, contributed to changing organizational structures during the middle Tuniit Period.

Evidence for complex mortuary practices during the middle Late Tuniit Period suggest significant changes in community organization and practice. Alarniq is among ten sites in the Eastern Arctic where Tuniit human remains are identified (Lynnerup et al. 2003). Besides the pit grave explored by Meldgaard (1962), four dwelling contexts have contained human remains, (Table 7.4). The interment of individuals within dwellings is suggestive of deep social bonds between people and their homes, positioning these structures as vital entities in changing community relations. Two such contexts, NhHd-3: F9 and NhHd-1: F6, are multifamily houses with radiocarbon dates suggesting abandonment between 1874 and 1711 BP. Another dwelling, NhHd-1: F1, excavated by Meldgaard, might share this age, supported by nearby dwellings NhHd-1: F5 and NhHd-1: F7 with comparable dates of cal. 1869 – 1741 BP (2σ) and cal. 1874 – 1744 BP (2σ), respectively. Similarities in burial practices during the middle Tuniit Period might indicate shared beliefs connecting local camps within a broader community. Moreover, the burial of one person within each house is suggestive of the ritual abandonment of homes, rather than their continued use as mortuary features. This challenges conventional models of Tuniit settlement, suggesting that the abandonment of camps may have been driven by social practices rather than economic strategies.

⁶⁷ When comparing the edible meat index of the minimum number of animals in each category, including those identified only to species (which I give the most conservative index values), seal comprises 57% of the marine mammal assemblage (cf. Table 3, Howse et al. 2019: 10).

Table 7.5 Identified Tuniit Burial Contexts at Alarniq.
**Radiocarbon dates calibrated in IntCal 20*

Provenience	Feature Type	Human Remains	Radiocarbon Dates* cal. BP (2σ)	Reference
NhHd-3: F9	Sod Dwelling (87m ²)	Number of individuals unknown: one cranium fragment, one left tibia fragment, and one left fibula fragment	2037 – 1926 1990 – 1844 1997 – 1612 1820 – 1711	Howse (2017)
NhHd-1: F6	Sod Dwelling (33m ²)	1 adult (likely female)	2094 – 1700 1874 – 1744	Lynnerup et al. (2003)
NhHd-1: F1	Dwelling (original form destroyed)	1 adult (likely female)	—	Lynnerup et al. (2003)
NhHe-9:1	Sod Dwelling (original form destroyed)	1 adult	—	Lynnerup et al. (2003)
NhHe-14: F1	Pit Grave: “Ochre Grave”	1 infant	1692 – 1541	Lynnerup et al. (2003)

7.2.3.2 Temporal Trends in Inter-Community Organization. The new spatiotemporal framework reveals three significant trends in inter-community organization at Alarniq during the Late Tuniit Period that highlight a complex occupational history unique to this settlement place. The first trend concerns the northward relocation of camp communities over time. The oldest Tuniit camps, built between 2700-2100 BP, are situated in the southern part of Alarniq (e.g., Areas A and B), with noticeable diversity in their spatial layouts. Dwellings at NhHd-11 seem to face other dwellings, possibly indicating closer relationships between certain households (see Section 1.1), while dwellings at NhHd-16 are linearly arranged towards the southern coastline, facing Pingiqqalik. In contrast, Tuniit camps whose radiocarbon dates suggest construction between 2100- 1800 BP, including NhHd-1, NhHd-3, and NhHd-7, are located approximately 300m north of Area A, and camps located even further north, such as NhHd-12 and NhHd-8, appear to have been constructed around 1700-1600 BP (Table 7.3). These camps are also linearly arranged and face the eastern coastline. The trend of northward movement continues through the

occupational sequence, with the terminal Late Tuniit camps (c. 1500- 600 BP) located in Area C and nearby sites like NhHe-16 and NhHe-24 positioned on the northern edge of Alarniq (Figure 7.25). This shift is accompanied by a slight change in the orientation of dwellings towards the northeastern coast, facing Kapuivik.

Temporal changes in inter-community organization may indicate shifting socioeconomic practices. An increased focus on winter floe edge hunting around 2000 BP may have influenced the orientation of sod house settlements towards the east-facing coastal bight, where the modern Sikutuqqjuq polynya forms (IE056; IE246). This is potentially supported by an increased presence of optimal walrus feeding zones during this time (see Figure 7.26). Spatial practices at this time also have also been impacted by Alarniq's transformation from an island to a mainland peninsula. These topographic changes may have facilitated the development of a more structured seasonal round between wintering sites at Alarniq and inland resource areas, perhaps resulting in greater food security through practices of seasonal caching (see. Desjardins 2020).

The northeastern orientation of later campsites may have been informed by new relations between wintering sites, which were often oriented within a direct linear array of one another to facilitate navigation over sea ice using wind direction and snow drift patterns (see Chapter Four, Section 4.2.3). Increased land connectivity due to isostatic rebound, as well as more stable sea ice due to shallower sea depths and colder weather, would have increased settlement connectivity and accessibility within the region, and may have resulted in intensified inter-community relationships between 2000 and 1000 BP (see Finkelstein 2016). These changes may have resulted in more regular travel between places such as Kapuivik, making large inter-seasonal aggregations possible, potentially explaining the increase in large communal houses within this

time frame.

The second trend is an observable increase in small campsites in close proximity to one another during the terminal Late Tuniit Period. While dwellings located at 14-15 MASL, such as those in Area C, continued to be occupied throughout the terminal Late Tuniit Period, new camps were also established near the coast at 12-8.5 MASL, with all radiocarbon samples dated to similar time frame of 900-700 BP. Terminal Late Tuniit dates associated with the reoccupation of older dwellings may represent returning communities with intergenerational ties to Alarniq. In contrast, the new camps located closer to the shore may have been constructed by new communities that had previously wintered elsewhere in the region, suggesting an increase in location populations at Alarniq in the final centuries of the Tuniit Period. The potential influx in local populations, as well as a shift in the size and proximity of campsites, may relate to a series of social and environmental changes that have been argued to have precipitated the decline of Tuniit occupations such as climate change, changing sea ice conditions, and resource stress exacerbated by incoming Early Inuit populations (Betts et al. 2015; Maxwell 1985; Ryan 2016; Savelle and Dyke 2014). In this context, Alarniq might have functioned as a crucial aggregation site for Tuniit peoples, given its strategic position near sea mammal hunting grounds and mainland resources. That Tuniit peoples may have gathered in large numbers at Alarniq is corroborated by Amitturmiut oral historical testimonies that describe Tuniit groups as fleeing to the western coast of Foxe Basin, and then travelling south, during their exodus from Amittuq, with the final Tuniit settlement reportedly located on the small island of Ugliit, 20 km south of Alarniq (IE272; IE384 IE472; IE703; KH01; KH04).

The third temporal trend identified in my analysis concerns the spatial organization of

terminal Late Tuniit and Early Inuit camps. As outlined in Section 2.1, while Early Inuit sites have not been dated at Alarniq, Inuit are thought to have arrived in the eastern Canadian Arctic by 1000 BP (Appelt 2003; Maxwell 1985; McGhee 2000). Radiocarbon dates from Pingiqqalik indicate that Inuit were present in the vicinity of Alarniq by at least cal. 905 – 790 BP [2 σ] (Desjardins 2020), while Early Inuit dates from Kapuivik (cal. 645 – 554 BP [2 σ]), and Qaiqsut (cal. 633 – 552 BP [2 σ]) support chronological overlap with the new Late Tuniit dates (e.g., cal. 675 – 573 BP (2 σ), cal. 730 – 477 BP (2 σ). Previously identified sites at Alarniq inferred as belonging to the Early Inuit period (c. 1000-1500 BP) include a large communal house located at 19.5 MASL (NhHe-18), a vaulted grave at 13.5 MASL (NhHe-21), a large cluster of pit caches and middens at 11.5 MASL (NhHe-20), and a row of 17 sod houses and qarmats at 9 MASL (NhHe-19). The 2019 surveys identified three additional sites, including a group of three sod houses at 8 MASL (IE-1), six boulder surface dwellings at 6 MASL (IE-2), and 72 features comprised primarily of boulder caches and cairns at 18-20 MASL (NhHe-27) (Figure 7.1). All Early Inuit sites, with the exception of IE-2, are located in areas where marine emergence occurred prior to 1000 BP, with IE-2 located in an area where land exposure happened shortly after 500 BP.

My analysis suggests that Tuniit and Inuit communities may have maintained distinct identities through their spatial practices. This is evident in how Inuit residences and caching places are spatially restricted to the northern portion of Alarniq, with considerable distances between Inuit and Tuniit sites (Figure 7.1). This contrasts with the shorter distances observed between coeval terminal Late Tuniit camps. The cohabitation of Tuniit and Inuit might have influenced the maintenance and reuse of residential spaces during the terminal Late Tuniit Period. Notably, camps dated prior to 1000 BP were widely dispersed within the central area of

Alarniq, with simultaneous occupational activities taking place between 23 and 14.5 MASL. However, by the terminal Late Tuniit Period, occupational activities, including those in reoccupied dwellings, are restricted to the northern coast on terraces between 15 and 8.5 MASL. This may suggest that Tuniit peoples aggregated in more tightly organized camp clusters, in part, to maintain a broader sense of community affiliation that remained separate of Inuit inhabitants. Given the concentration of terminal Late Tuniit settlements along the coastal bight in Area C, it is possible that changes in spatial practices helped to maintain tenure over productive hunting areas along the floe edge.

Some of Tuniit camps are located within closer to proximity to Early Inuit camps than others. For instance, NhHe-16 is located less than 500m from the large Early Inuit settlement at NhHe-19. NhHe-16 is similarly close by, less than 700m from NhHe-19, with NhHe-16: F5 associated with a radiocarbon date that correspond to the earliest Inuit occupations in the area (e.g., cal. 922 – 797 BP (2 σ)). This may indicate that while some local Tuniit communities avoided Early Inuit peoples (see Park 2016), others associated with them more regularly. This interpretation matches accounts of Tuniit-Inuit cohabitation described in the Igloolik Oral History Archives, which describe the timid and avoidant nature of Tuniit peoples, as well as intimate interactions between Tuniit and Inuit individuals (see Chapter Four, Section 4.1.1). In either case, the spatial differences that emerged during the terminal Late Tuniit Period suggest significant changes in inter-community relations.

7.3 Conclusion

In this chapter I have presented an updated occupational history of Alarniq that challenges previous inferences of social organization and land use, and that positions local Tuniit communities as enduring, emergent, and multiscale social entities. I have discussed archaeological evidence suggesting that community practices at Alarniq were varied and diverse throughout the Tuniit Period, including evidence for changing household and campsite structures, locational strategies, seasonal land use practices, and mortuary practices. My findings suggest that these differences were the product of complex assemblages involving multiscale relations between human and nonhuman actors, such as animals, building materials, ice patterns, and landforms, as well as the norms, memories, and desires of individuals, households, and camps. Through my exploration of diverse settlement contexts, the research suggests that people-place relations served as both records and catalysts of communities, in which the two were mutually constituted through the construction, maintenance, and differential reuse of camps, caching places, and resource areas.

The expanded radiocarbon sequence suggests continuity in occupations at Alarniq for over two millennia, including new evidence for occupations during the terminal Early Tuniit Period, and dates that extend the Late Tuniit Period by several hundred years, suggesting that Tuniit occupations persisted in the region until the fourteenth century. The chronological patterning also indicates that Tuniit peoples repeatedly occupied ancestral camps for centuries. This includes evidence for dwelling maintenance practices during transition periods that typically mark the division of archaeological cultures, such as between the “Late Pre-Dorset” (2800-2500) and “Early Dorset” (2500-2000) periods in Area A, as well as between the “Middle

Dorset” (2000-1500) and “Late Dorset” (1500 – 1000 BP) periods in Area C. These chronological data present challenges to the traditional culture history sequence, as they suggest continuity in community practices within local residential contexts in spite of pronounced technological changes, highlighting that social identities and affiliations extend beyond immediate contexts and rationalist choices (cf. Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1962; Savelle and Dyke 2014).

Despite radiocarbon evidence for the extensive intergenerational reoccupation of campsites, my analysis demonstrates how small-scale diversity in the structure and organization of campsites materialized complex, persisting relationships among local camp groups. Observed material differences indicate that rather than a wintering settlement, a diversity of occupational practices took place at Alarniq, including its probable occupation as an outpost camp within regional travel routes, a seasonal storage place for food and equipment, a grave site, a place of varying subsistence activities (fishing, fox trapping, geese hunting, marine hunting), an autumn camp, and a cold weather residence associated with different socioeconomic contexts and temporal durations. Comparisons with paleotopographic data indicate that the emergence of material differences within the sequence were likely informed by topographic processes that were unique to the area, the most significant of which was likely the transformation of Alarniq from an island into a mainland peninsula. These topographic changes would have presented new opportunities for inter-seasonal residential movements within the landscape, but also for the differential reuse of existing residential spaces in varied seasonal contexts. It appears that it is through a complex assemblage of actors and relations that deep communal connections with Alarniq were fostered over time.

My findings suggest that people came together to form relational communities at local and regional levels during the Tuniit Period, demonstrating the mutable social and spatial scales at which place and landscape were historically articulated. This includes the emergence and maintenance of multi-family houses during the initial and middle Late Tuniit contexts, which suggest intimate connections between certain groups of individuals within large camp communities. Likewise, sod dwellings in Area A appear to be organized so that dwellings faced one another in pairs, indicating different degrees of social affiliation between households within larger camps. A similar nested spatial structure is observed in Area C, where smaller dwellings are arranged in smaller, tightly spaced rows within a broader camp cluster, with contemporaneous radiocarbon dates within the area indicating that smaller dwelling groups were part of larger social aggregations. Comparisons between reoccupied dwellings and the construction of new camps in both Areas A and C suggests that an influx of local populations took place during the initial Late Tuniit and terminal Late Tuniit periods. This may indicate that large scale aggregations correlate with broader changes in inter-community landscape relations within the region. That these aggregations appear to be unique to Alarniq may speak to its unique geographic location on the mainland of Melville Peninsula, perhaps suggesting broader settlement traditions involving movements between interior summer residences and coastal cold weather settlements.

Similar to Kapuivik, my study demonstrates that feature types often considered as single-use or transient in nature were often enduring participants in community relations. This is evidenced through the differential reuse of caching areas in Area A, the intergenerational maintenance of a boulder surface dwelling in Area B, and the construction and potential visitation of graves. These relations may correlate with broader settlement practices involving

seasonal travel to and from inland areas. Alternatively, they may demonstrate how the distribution of particular material resources, such as the boulder till used to build caches and dwellings, shaped spatial activities within local contexts. In either case, the reuse of seemingly transient features suggests that the historical processes that brought people together and maintained enduring camp communities involved a diversity of human and nonhuman interactions within the landscape, and that Arctic archaeologists must attend to small, low-density sites in their investigations of landscape, rather than just large coastal settlements.

Area C also demonstrates greater variability in architecture than previously thought, as it appears that while large rectangular sod houses were constructed on terraces, smaller circular sod houses have gone unidentified within nearby runnels. There does not appear to be a significant correlation between dwelling size and reoccupation practices, suggesting that the labour investment of constructing sod houses was not a primary factor in decisions to maintain or reuse dwellings. Instead, evidence for a diverse range of household and interhousehold practices, such as tool making, seasonal hunting, and mortuary practices, suggests that decisions about reoccupying ancestral homes were socially complex and historically contingent. The potential underrepresentation of warm weather campsites and smaller sod dwellings draw attention to biases present in existing survey data, suggesting that Tuniit campsites may have been more diverse than is currently accounted for, challenging narratives of increased homogeneity in architecture and settlement organization during the Late Tuniit Period (Friesen 2007; Howse et al. 2021; Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1962; Savelle and Dyke 2014)

In the next chapter, I synthesize archaeological and paleotopographic data from Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq to provide a holistic understanding of Amittuq's Tuniit

occupational landscape. This includes a comparison of the similarities and differences observed in the occupational patterning of three study sites, and a consideration of how these local histories come together with oral historical data to form a broader narrative of the archaeological landscape. Through these comparisons, I suggest how humans and nonhumans emerged, broke apart, and came together in local contexts, as well as the broader sociospatial scales at which community bonds and identities were created, maintained, and differentiated through movements and interactions between camps within the region.

Chapter 8

How Persistent Places Came to Matter in Amittuq, Nunavut.

The central problem of this dissertation is the identification and explanation of how local communities and a broader homeland in Amittuq, NU were produced through reciprocal, generative relationships between people and places during the Tuniit Period. I argue that Tuniit communities were relational and more-than-human entities that emerged and changed through placemaking activities of different durations, scales, and intensities. Persistent settlement places were integral to these processes. Rather than serving as static backgrounds for predefined archaeological cultures or socio-evolutionary stage types (Fitzhugh, 1976; Meldgaard 1962; Maxwell 1985; McGhee 1976; Murray 1999) these places were active participants in local camp communities, and as such shaped, and were shaped by, the relational production of human social worlds (Ahenakew 2017; Barad 2003; Cipolla 2019; Deleuze 1992; Harris 2021a; Jevis 2018; Kirby 2013; Price 2008; Qitsualik 2013; Supernant 2022; Tester and Irniq 2008; Whitridge 2004). As product and process of millennia of local community relations, persistent settlement places were, and in many cases remain, affective fields where less tangible elements of the landscape, such as knowledge, emotion, memory, and perceptions of history, connected people with different times and contexts, contributing to the cultivation of a broader sense of social belonging and community in the landscape (Basso 1996; Bauer and Johansen 2023; Brittain 2016; Casey 2016; Deloria 2001; Harris 2014; Harvey 1996; Ingold 2010; Morrison 2016; Pries 2018; Tallbear 2015; Trouillot 1995; Watts 2016; Wildcat 2001).

In the previous chapters, I have shown how Tuniit communities were created,

maintained, and redefined at the social scales of the household and camp through complex and changing relations with the places they inhabited. To identify and explain small-scale variability in Tuniit occupational practices, this investigation analyzed multiple components of the archaeological and historical landscape. These included the assessment of Amitturmiut Inuit oral testimonies to develop new archaeological expectations of Tuniit settlement strategies and inferences of community relations, the employment of predictive GIS models to visualize and interpret postglacial environmental change, and the analysis of Tuniit artifacts and architecture from Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq, documented by multimethod survey, excavation, and radiocarbon sequencing. In this chapter, I compare and discuss this evidence to argue how Tuniit communities, much like historic and present-day Amitturmiut communities, were routinely formed and differentiated at multiple social and spatial scales through a diverse suite of people-place relations ranging from everyday occupational practices to intergenerational settlement traditions (Bennett and Rowley 2004; IE166; IE254; IE256; IE261; IE284; IE338; QIA 2010).

Palaeogeographical analyses indicate that Amittuq was characterized by a heterogenous and constantly shifting biophysical environment during the Tuniit Period. Archaeological patterning suggests how local variability in landscape features and material resources (e.g., building materials) may have conditioned possibilities for movement and settlement, demonstrating the affective roles of these elements in shaping community practices. However, people also appear to have strategically managed and modified local environments in variable ways that suggest local differences in socioeconomic preferences, cultural norms, community knowledge, and traditions. This research documents evidence for the repeated occupation of underrepresented inland areas, including sheltered plateaus, glacial till areas, and lacustrine and paludal contexts. These contexts suggest that people articulated their locational strategies and

socioeconomic practices around specific sets of knowledge about the material affordances of places. Diversity in locational strategies challenge the view of persistent settlement places as inert stages for timeless settlement traditions, especially the economic rationalist idea that Tuniit groups prioritized year-round settlement along outer seacoasts to optimize their access to nearshore marine resources (Maxwell 1985; McGhee 1972; Meldgaard 1962; Appelt et al. 2016; Mary-Rousselière 2002; Savelle and Dyke 2014). The archaeological evidence instead suggests that dynamic and historically contingent relations between people and places repeatedly defined local settlement practices and community movements (Ashmore 2007; Cipolla 2021; Bradley 2000; Bielawski 1988:54; Crellin et al. 2020; Murray 1999:468, cf. Maxwell 1985:154; McGhee 1996:131; Ingold 2000).

Tuniit peoples may have responded to widescale environmental changes, such as bathymetric shifts in nearshore environments, through locally specific food storage practices and seasonal settlement strategies. Extensive marine mammal caching may have been a frequent practice through which resource security was achieved, and may suggest that people planned their seasonal rounds around repeated visits to specific places to prepare and exploit caches. Establishing local resource security would have enabled, and likely encouraged, people to return to persistent settlement places during periods when resources may have been unpredictable, such as during the Roman Climatic Optimum (c. 1750-1550 BP) and Medieval Climatic Anomaly (c. 1000- 600 BP) when marine mammal habitats and sea ice connectivity may have been compromised (Friesen et al. 2020; Szpak et al. 2019). Recently acquired radiocarbon assays support this argument, suggesting that Kapuivik and Alarniq were likely intensively occupied during the Roman Climatic Optimum, and that populations increased at Alarniq within the general timeframe the Medieval Climatic Anomaly. That Tuniit communities repeatedly

occupied coastal places at times when marine resources were unstable is incompatible with views of Tuniit communities as structured by shifting subsistence economies, and is more parsimonious with an understanding of communities as socially and historically constituted assemblages informed by a myriad of priorities, preferences, and relationships (Anderson et al. 2019; Hood 1998; Howse et al. 2019; McGhee 1972; Maxwell 1985:183).

Small-scale variability in architecture and spatial practices suggest that Tuniit household and camp-level social structures were fluid and dynamic. Central to this argument is evidence for major shifts in cold weather settlement contexts during the middle Early Tuniit Period as well as the initial and middle Late Tuniit periods, when communal or multifamily dwellings became more commonplace. At the same time, intra-camp variation in dwelling size and organization across the Tuniit Period suggest that household social dynamics varied internally within local communities. The research highlights the agency of individuals and household groups in defining social relations, and the multiscalar character of community membership within local contexts during the Tuniit Period (Coen et al. 2017; Harris 2014; Price 2008; Tallbear 2015; Yaeger and Canuto 2012).

Differences in the spatial structure of camps suggest that interhousehold relations were variable during both the Early and Late Tuniit periods, and were likely influenced by seasonal practices and local contexts, rather than regionwide shifts in social organization (Bielawski 1988, cf., Harris 2014; Johansen 2008). In warm weather settlement contexts, Tuniit communities prioritized the organization of dwellings around shared extramural spaces where cooking and toolmaking practices were carried out. Alternatively, most cold weather settlements were linearly arranged and faced the floe edge, prioritizing a shared viewshed of communal

hunting areas. These differences draw attention to the potential importance of communal socioeconomic practices in contributing to a collective identity and purpose during the Tuniit Period, and further support the argument for the historically contingent and relational nature of community structures (Friesen 2013; 2022; Howse 2016; IE427; IE499; Whitridge 2014).

Evidence for changing social relations between neighbouring camps further support an argument for relational Tuniit communities, suggesting how the unique material and historic contexts of each settlement place may have shaped the scale and extent of community membership (Ahmed 2005:27; Ashmore and Knapp 1999; Gay 2018; Giddens 1984; Tilley 2016; Yuval-Davis 2004). During the initial and middle Early Tuniit periods, people appear to have prioritized the strategic placement of camps between topographic barriers to establish and affirm social distinctions between local communities (Harvey 1996; Lefebvre 1991; Johansen 2011). Alternatively, Late Tuniit camps tend to be placed in unobstructed, elevated areas to maintain viewsheds between neighbouring communities and the floe edge hunting areas they likely shared (Kosiba and Bauer 2013; Vis 2018; Whitridge 2004). The arrangement of Late Tuniit coastal settlements at Alarniq also suggest efforts to maintain social connections with non-local camps, such as by prioritizing visual and spatial relations with settlements at Kapuivik, which may have been regularly visited by travelling across sea ice (Aporta 2003; IE254; IE260; IE293, Inglis et al. 2022; Nuttal 1992). These differences indicate temporal trends in the intensity of community interaction and social affiliation within Amittuq during the Tuniit Period.

Built spaces appear to not only have shaped the daily relations and social structures of Tuniit communities, but to have participated in the ongoing negotiation of community identities and histories (Bauer and Johansen 2023; Hamilakis 2013; Massumi 2015; Trouillot 1995; Price

2008; Smith 2003). This is evidenced in the ubiquity of recurrent settlement practices geared towards establishing and maintaining connections to ancestral places. Reoccupation practices were relatively common in all periods, and were not restricted to the larger, semi-subterranean dwellings of winter settlements during the Late Tuniit Period, as has been previously suggested (see Dyke et al. 2019; McGhee 1997; Morrison 1999; Habu and Savelle 1994). Instead, evidence for long-term maintenance and reuse practices is found in both cold and warm weather dwelling contexts, as well as storage features and caching areas. The differential reuse of middle Late Tuniit dwellings at Alarniq as human graves is also suggestive of how living communities may have perceived and revised their connections to past people over time. Recurrent placemaking activities demonstrate how reaffirming and/or revising perceived social ties to ancestral places, and presumably, to earlier inhabitants, was likely an important mechanism through which communities were established and maintained during the Tuniit Period (Bauer and Johansen 2023, Hendon 2010; Lyons et al. 2010; Mills 2008; Nuttal 1992; Morrison 2016; Trouillot 1995). This supports the more-than-human character of community membership, and is suggestive of intentional and meaningful sociopolitical strategies used to define a sense of place and community in the landscape.

Continuity in local traditions of reoccupation and reuse suggest that some camp communities were maintained over substantial durations of time. New radiocarbon dates from Kapuivik and Alarniq demonstrate continuity in residential activities at campsites constructed during the terminal Early Tuniit Period (c. 2800 – 2500 BP) by returning occupants in the initial Late Tuniit Period (c. 2500 – 2000 BP). The continuity challenges conceptions of Early and Late Tuniit peoples as chronologically bounded cultures, suggesting that some camp communities endured during the presumed transitional period of 2800 – 2000 BP, in part through the

maintenance of built space. While the transitional period has been characterized as a time of local extinction events, population replacements, and abrupt cultural changes across the eastern Canadian Arctic, this research proposes a narrative of both continuity and change on a local level. In addition, the duration of placemaking events do not necessarily reflect the intensity of their affective relations. Presumably transient contexts, such as caching episodes and summer travel camps, served as important contexts where memory, emotion, temporality, and historicity were expressed, evoked, and repeatedly negotiated through placemaking practice (Basso 1996; Bauer and Johansen 2023; Brittain 2016; Casey 2016; Deloria 2001; Harris 2014; Harvey 1996; Ingold 2010; Morrison 2016; Pries 2018; Tallbear 2015; Trouillot 1995; Watts 2016; Wildcat 2001).

In the remainder of this chapter, I discuss in further detail how the archaeological, oral historical, and palaeogeographical data analyzed in this dissertation coalesce to provide a socially and historically situated understanding of Amittuq's occupational history during the Tuniit Period. I present a preliminary picture of how Tuniit places and communities were mutually formed and differentiated through local relations, and interpret the scale and extent of social interaction and group membership within the regional landscape. In Section One, I consider how differences in Tuniit spatial practices (e.g., location choices, residential mobility, campsite organization) were informed by the unique material conditions of Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq. I argue that the changing availability and accessibility of landscape elements, material resources, and prey species informed the daily practices, movements, and perceptions of people, shaping how people-place relations unfolded on a local level. However, people appear to have strategically utilized the distinct material affordances of places in different ways to establish social affiliations and distinctions. This suggests both continuity and difference in local

preferences, norms, and knowledge, and highlights the shared agency of people and places in defining social worlds. In addition to illustrating the emergent and relational character of Tuniit communities, the research offers a set of spatial and material criteria for identifying Tuniit sites that are beneficial for the design of future survey projects and predictive models aimed at investigating small-scale settlement patterning in Canadian Arctic archaeological contexts.

In Section Two, I examine how the built environment served as a record and catalyst of Tuniit social relations and discuss new inferences of the character and scale of Tuniit communities in the Amittuq region. I outline how people managed and modified their landscapes through the construction of a variety of structures, but also how enduring relations with ancestral settlements, caches, and burial grounds shaped perceptions of history and community, and contributed to the creation, maintenance, and differentiation of household and communal practices, identities, and knowledge systems. I detail how small-scale variability in structures and extramural spaces suggest local differences in intra-camp organizational structures. These differences likely embodied social relations within and between the households who constructed them, but may have also contributed to the ongoing production of communities by conditioning how later inhabitants organized themselves and perceived their connections to past people. While archaeological evidence suggests that community social structures were both locally and seasonally variable, some temporal trends in intra-camp patterning are apparent between settlements. This patterning may indicate that Tuniit peoples responded to environmental and climatic shifts through more collaborative and interconnected settlements, challenging prior models of population fluctuation and emphasizing the agency of people-place relations in shaping and defining social structures and landscapes.

8.1 Diversity and Social Dynamics of Tuniit Land Use

Arctic environments are known for their extreme and unpredictable conditions, but are also prosperous for those with the knowledge and resourcefulness to navigate them.

Archaeological and paleogeographic evidence from Amittuq offer new perspectives on how Tuniit peoples skillfully managed their environments through fluid and emergent community practices. Spatial and temporal variability in local topographies, landcovers, and sea ice informed how people moved and gathered in the landscape. However, the ways local communities engaged with changing material conditions appear to have been shaped as much by community memories, norms, knowledge, perceptions, and traditions as they were by environmental parameters and immediate economic needs. This research suggests how a multitude of human and nonhuman actors conditioned daily practices, longer-term strategies of land use, and broader assemblages of knowledge and meaning, constituting dynamic social communities (Ashmore 2007; Cipolla 2021; Bradley 2000; Crellin et al. 2020; Harris 2014; Harrison-Buck and Hendon 2018; Ingold 2000; Johansen and Bauer 2018; Sørensen 2019; Watts 2016).

In this section, I discuss how local and chronological differences in the availability, accessibility, and connectivity of landscape features and material resources influenced how Tuniit peoples managed their surroundings and cultivated local settlement traditions. Tuniit land use involved a complex suite of flexible and cooperative practices in which decisions about movement, settlement, and resource exploitation were situated within deep knowledge of a dynamic regional environment. I first examine how small-scale variability in local topographies informed the spatial structure of everyday social relations. I suggest that Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq held diverse material resources that conditioned the seasonal contexts and durations of

settlement episodes, and that shaped how locational decisions and specific building and storage practices, historically developed within local contexts. Local diversity in Tuniit settlement practices challenges the econometric idea that Tuniit groups prioritized year-round occupation along outer seacoasts to optimize their access to nearshore marine resources (Maxwell 1985; McGhee 1972; Meldgaard 1962; Appelt et al. 2016; Mary-Rousselière 2002; Savelle and Dyke 2014). Instead, I suggest that Tuniit peoples strategically selected and interacted with landscape elements in varied ways to facilitate a range of social, economic, and political practices, including diverse engagements with inland settings. This resulted in distinct sets of community relations with each settlement place, shaping local occupational histories.

I then examine how geomorphological processes shaped the natural environment and affected residential practices, mobility, and demography. I outline how postglacial rebound transformed the region's topography and how global temperature shifts likely impacted sea level and the development of sea ice, articulating possibilities for travel, hunting, caching, and settlement within the region. Archaeological evidence suggests that these changes impacted the relations and practices of households and camps, but that people responded to these changes in historically situated ways through changing campsite structures, seasonal architecture, and subsistence practices, even within the restricted spatial setting of outer seacoasts. The research challenges previous interpretations of Tuniit population dynamics as being structured by large-scale shifts in environmental conditions by detailing the locally situated character of community structures and the agency of people in managing local resources (see Savelle and Dyke 2014).

Finally, I discuss how Tuniit communities strategically incorporated landscape elements into their organizational practices to create deliberate visual and spatial connections within the

landscape. These connections appear to have played a key role in how neighbouring camps and larger communities were negotiated and affirmed. I examine evidence for how social distinctions were articulated by positioning camps on opposite sides of topographic barriers or orienting them towards opposing directions of the floe edge, which likely limited everyday interactions between local groups. This would not only have helped maintain distinct social structures and identities within local contexts, but may have aided in the cooperative management of floe edge hunting grounds surrounding settlement places (Friesen 2013; 2022; Howse 2016; IE427; IE499; Whitridge 2014). Other camps positioned along hilltops and raised bluffs suggest conscious efforts to maintain visual connections between local groups. Likewise, the spatial and visual alignment of some coeval coastal settlements between Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq may have served to establish or enhance social connections with distant camp communities. The research suggests that local groups were not temporally or spatially static, and instead were repeatedly and actively negotiated through spatial practices informed by complex interactions between people and landscape features.

8.1.1 Regional Diversity in Tuniit Organizational Practices

There is a correlation between topographic heterogeneity and local diversity in Tuniit locational strategies, suggesting that people's perceptions and understandings of landscape features informed settlement decisions. Kapuivik presents the greatest variability in spatial contexts, followed by Alarniq and Qalirusiq. From the time of the earliest documented human occupations in Amittuq around 4500 BP, Kapuivik was comprised of a rugged terrain punctuated by large bedrock outcrops, glacial lakes, and diverse land cover that included glacial till, heavy

mosses, and marshland. Alarniq, while less varied than Kapuivik, presented an array of landscape elements and land cover. Characterized primarily by undulating gravel berms and small coastal ponds, Alarniq also includes inland areas with pockets of glacial till and larger ponds. Qalirusiq, in contrast, is primarily comprised of a large butte covered in frost-shattered limestone, with low-lying mossy plateaus that had likely begun to develop between 3000 and 2500 BP. These topographic differences offered distinct material affordances to Tuniit peoples, and archaeological evidence suggests that camp communities incorporated these elements into their daily practices in varied ways, shaping the form and structure of built spaces and, in turn, the sociospatial relations of households and camps (Bradley 2000; Friesen 2015).

That Tuniit peoples selected and interacted with landscape elements in socially situated ways is evidenced through small-scale diversity in their locational strategies. Prior to my research, Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq were inferred primarily as winter settlements where Tuniit peoples constructed dwellings along outer seacoasts, to maintain their proximity to floe-edge hunting grounds frequented by seal and walrus (Savelle et al. 2009; Desrosiers 2018; Howse et al. 2020). However, evidence for inland occupations found at five newly documented sites, namely NjHa-45 and a new feature cluster in Area 210 at Kapuivik, as well as NhHd-25, NhHe-25, and NhHe-26 at Alarniq, suggests that Tuniit settlement practices were neither focused exclusively on the coast nor were they uniform between localities. Additionally, while inland sites in other regions have often been inferred as the result of a fission-fusion settlement pattern in which Tuniit peoples gathered at coastal settlements in the winter and dispersed into smaller interior camps in the summer (Bielawski 1982, 1988; Maxwell 1985, see Friesen 2022 for exception), variation in cache types and seasonal architecture from Amittuq suggests that inland places were visited in both cold and warm weather contexts, further supporting an argument for

the complex and locally diverse nature of Tuniit settlement strategies. This suggests that inland settlement places were important fields of action in which communities were maintained and differentiated through diverse sets of settlement activities.

An intimate understanding of the material affordances of landscape features likely facilitated site-specific settlement strategies that involved an interplay of logistical decisions, socioeconomic concerns, and community preferences. The newly documented sites share notable similarities in their physiographic settings, such as proximity to material resources, pointing to specific preferences that guided interior settlement practices. For instance, local variation in the size, frequency, and distribution of boulder structures indicate that building material availability factored into location decisions. Given their considerable size and weight, transporting boulders over long distances would have presented significant logistic challenges. This may explain why large boulder features are present in inland areas of Kapuivik and Alarniq where glacial till is concentrated, but are not as spatially constrained at Qalirusiq where limestone scree was widely available. Alternatively, elevated topographic features capable of providing shelter from extreme weather appear to have shaped recurrent winter settlement practices (IE029; IE147; IE163). At Kapuivik, outcrops forming a barricade around NjHa-45 might have shielded snow houses during blizzards, while deep runnels at Alarniq offered protection and insulation for semi-subterranean houses despite exposed coastlines. These examples suggest engagements with the landscape rooted in historical understandings of land use, resulting in repeated sets of occupational practices.

As inland places are not visible from the floe edge, their repeated and seasonally specific use may have been based on community knowledge of their affordances and location. This is

exemplified through the selection of freshwater features for warm weather camps, such as the presence of surface dwellings and caches near the large lake in Area 210 at Kapuivik and those arranged around small ponds at NhHe-26 and NhHd-16 at Alarniq. In addition to providing drinking water and a place to clean meat (IE396; IE433), ponds and lakes may have offered opportunistic hunting opportunities for game birds, as evidenced by cache structures and faunal remains (Bielawski 1988; IE023; IE169; IE249; KH04). Potential evidence for inshore and tidal fishing at Kapuivik and Alarniq, as suggested by the presence of possible weir features, is also significant. While there is often little direct archaeological evidence for this activity, it is remembered by Amitturmiut as a key resource practice of the Tuniit (IE001; IE023; IE169; IE433; IE708; KH02; Friesen 2009, 2022; Peregrine 2001; Robinson 2017; Whitridge 2001). These relationships point to the flexible and context-dependant nature of community spatial structures, and the potential roles of community knowledge and memory in shaping repeated movements and residential activities.

8.1.2 Topographic Transformation and Emergent Spatial Relations

The diverse topographies of Amittuq's settlement places were in a constant state of transformation during the Tuniit Period, largely due to geomorphological processes. This dynamism presented both challenges and opportunities for people, helping to shape possibilities for movement and organizational practices, and contributing to local differences in land use over time (Conolly 2020; Pope et al. 2017; Ross and Friesen 2022). Camp communities responded to topographic changes in different ways, including flexible settlement strategies, resource practices and camp community structures, as well as the active management of places through the

modification of built spaces and caching practices. This variation suggests that Tuniit communities were not passive or reactive entities defined by their environments, but rather were historically and relationally constituted collectives that actively participated in the production of a variegated landscape. The organization of households and camps suggest intimate knowledge of, and attachments to, specific places in the landscape, and highlights how Tuniit communities were locally and chronologically differentiated through situated material relationships rather than just large-scale environmental changes.

Throughout the Tuniit Period, postglacial uplift transformed and expanded landmasses, resulting in the altered spatial connectivity of settlements and resource places in Amittuq. At Kapuivik and Alarniq, increased land exposure is linked with an inferred increase in size and frequency of camps, while at Qalirusiq it is associated with occupational decline. Kapuivik was connected to Qikiqtaaluk (Baffin Island) through a growing chain of islets, which, by 3500 BP, likely facilitated travel between coastal and mainland areas via land-fast ice or pack ice for most of the year. Likewise, Alarniq fused to the mainland by 2500 – 2000 BP enabling travel between the coast and the interior of Melville Peninsula. The accessibility of Kapuivik and Alarniq likely made them reliable year-round coastal hunting locations and inter-seasonal outposts for inland travel, as suggested by the increased frequency and seasonal diversity of campsites and caching places at both sites. In contrast, Qalirusiq was a remote islet encircled by deep waters for much of its occupational history, making it an important seasonal settlement as the nearest land base to open water hunting areas such as the Naggutialuk ice lead⁴⁸, but restricting its accessibility outside of winter (IE054; IE477). However, as new islets emerged between 3500-3000 BP,

⁶⁸ While smaller, nearshore ice leads were likely affected by the formation of shallow sills and ridges, the formation of major polynyas and ice leads are largely dependant on katabatic winds and thermal upwelling, and as such these water features are expected to have formed in similar locations during the Tuniit Period (Prinsenber 1986; IE060; IE330).

occupations at Qalirusiq appear to have declined. This evidence suggests that Kapuivik, Alarniq, and Qalirusiq held unique historic roles within the broader occupational landscape, but that these roles were far from static and instead involved a dynamic interplay of movements and environmental relations.

Postglacial uplift also had a pronounced effect on regional bathymetry, and available archaeological evidence suggests that local communities responded to the widespread changes in nearshore environments in historically situated ways. The most pronounced changes in bathymetry and coastal habitats occurred around 2000 BP, when postglacial uplift significantly expanded nearshore marine shallows, and a climate cooling trend likely resulted in an extended winter hunting season (Friesen et al. 2020; Szpak et al. 2019). As discussed by Murray (1996:98) in the context of Qalirusiq, the emergence of coastal shallows may have provided increased access to nearshore walrus hunting grounds, as depths between 15–18 MASL are prime feeding zones for these animals (see also Fay 1969:113). Radiocarbon dates suggest a significant increase in semi-subterranean dwellings took place within the region during this time, which may relate to increased walrus hunting activities (Howse et al. 2021; Maxwell 1985; Murray 1996).

However, while at Kapuivik and Alarniq these changes are associated with inferences of the repeated use of larger winter settlements, at Qalirusiq they are associated with smaller camps, as well as the emergence of several small sites along nearby bays and peninsulas on Igloodik Island. This may indicate that expanded opportunities for nearshore walrus hunting allowed local communities to prioritize preferred organizational strategies, resulting in local differences within the region. While camp communities dispersed across Igloodik Island during the terminal Early

Inuit and initial Early Tuniit periods, the relative time distance of travel between these camps was minimal due to increased land connectivity. Thus, many were accessible to one another within a few hours of travel on foot, irrespective of the season. The strategic proximity of these camps may suggest the presence of a trans-local community that potentially engaged in regular food sharing, similar to neighbouring camps during the Historic Inuit period (IE029; IE184; IE475; IE505). The patterning underscores how multiple social and spatial scales of community membership may have been articulated through daily interactions within a shifting landscape.

An environmental shift around 1500 BP may also correlate with significant changes in local settlement practices at Alarniq and Kapuivik. Continued postglacial uplift likely resulted in the decreased availability of nearshore hunting zones, as coastal seabeds became too shallow for optimal walrus feeding (Fay 1969; Murray 1996). Similarly, sediment shallowing likely resulted in the formation of new sills and ridges, reducing the regularity of nearshore ice leads (Cofaigh et al. 1999). These environmental shifts correspond with inferred occupational declines between 1500-1000 BP, with the potential exception of Alarniq where two radiocarbon dates from walrus samples fall within this time frame (Howse et al. 2019: 541). It is possible that a decline in land-based settlements relates to a greater number of camp communities moving to ice camps located near newly formed straits. Historically, these are areas where seal breathing hole hunting was known to have been abundant (IE054; IE166). Alarniq may have remained an important land base due to its strategic location near the Sikutuqqijuq Polynya and Ugliit island where walrus hauled out in large numbers during the terminal Late Tuniit and Early Inuit periods (IE054).

The comparison of available archaeological evidence and oral historical information are valuable in reevaluating previous inferences of region-wide population crashes, as they suggest

that occupational declines may be the result of changes in seasonal settlement rounds (e.g., the increased construction of ice camps, which leave no archaeological trace), rather than occupational declines brought on by resource stress (see Savelle and Dyke 2014). In addition, the results suggest that radiocarbon sampling issues may be contributing to temporal gaps in occupational records due to an absence of terrestrial mammal samples associated with temporal contexts of heightened marine mammal hunting. Possible variation in coastal subsistence practices and settlement changes cautions against projecting a local dataset onto regional occupational records without attention to inter-site and inter-regional variability, demonstrating the value of a relational and place-based approach over culture-historical frameworks centered on the construction of type-sites in the Eastern Arctic (Hood 1998; McCoy 2020).

The relationship between archaeological patterning at Kapuivik, Alarniq, and Qalirusiq and evidence for pronounced environmental changes suggest that local groups had their own sets of priorities and norms that shaped their connections to places. Moreover, the evidence challenges the commonly held view that climate change was the primary constraint and defining force of socioeconomic practices and population sizes during the Tuniiit Period (Fitzhugh 1996; Hood 1998; Maxwell 1985; Ryan 2016). While climate change likely had pronounced effects on the bioproductivity of marine life and seasonal sea ice patterns, it is the situated relations between people and changing local topographies that appear to have had a more direct influence on shaping community structures and practices. This underscores the interdependent and mutually constitutive character of people-place relations in defining communities and landscapes.

8.1.3 The Negotiation of Social Boundaries Through Visuospatial Practices

Amitturmiut Knowledge Holders describe the importance of establishing visual lines of sight between camps to foster a sense of community through co-presence and shared experiences in the landscape (IE254; IE260; IE293, Inglis et al. 2022, see Ahmed 2005:27; Tilley 2016; Yuval-Davis 2004:215). Tuniit peoples also appear to have established visuospatial connections by organizing campsites around topographic elements. The utilization of topographic elements to create situated visual geometries — that is, historically contingent configurations of visual relations that shape social realities (see Barad 2014:169) — likely contributed to the perception and experience of social closeness, influencing the way people coexisted in shared spaces. The placement and layout of campsites therefore suggest local and temporal differences in the intensity of social relationships between neighbouring camps and broader communities, highlighting the fluid and multiscale character of community membership (Ashmore and Knapp 1999; Gay 2018; Giddens 1984; Fábrega-Álvarez et al. 2019; Pred 1981; Richards-Rissetto et al. 2014; Smith 2003; Wheatley and Gillings 2000).

Tuniit people appear to have established distinct social structures and identities within local contexts by positioning camps around topographic barriers, which likely limited daily interactions between groups and may have helped in managing shared hunting spots (Harvey 1996; Kosiba and Bauer 2013; Lefebvre 1991; Johansen 2011; Vis 2018; Whitridge 2004). At Kapuivik, in Area 223, small camps were visually distanced from each other through their positioning on opposite sides of outcrop ridges. This arrangement seems to have prioritized visual separation in contemporaneous occupied camps over more practical concerns such as protection from extreme weather, as most campsites were positioned so that dwellings were

exposed to windward coastlines despite their proximity to potential windbreaks. At Qalirusiq, the careful positioning of camps on raised bluffs facing different directions of the floe edge suggest a different visuospatial strategy intended to demarcate local communities. This arrangement may have also helped facilitate the cooperative sharing of hunting areas within a restricted spatial setting, by effectively dividing the floe-edge surrounding the islet.

In other contexts, social affiliations seem to have been maintained by positioning camps on hills and raised terraces to produce wider, shared viewsheds (Gay 2018; Howey and Burg 2021; Robinson et al. 2021; Van Dyke 2016). Radiocarbon dating from all three settlement places demonstrate that camps, especially during the Late Tuniit Period, were often situated on raised terraces or plateaus, significantly above the active shoreline or storm ridge, in areas with a broader viewshed of the coast and floe edge. For instance, Areas 204 and 205 at Kapuivik share a broad vantage of the floe edge surrounding a small peninsula, maintaining visual connection with the nearby settlement of Qaiqsut across the strait. These strategic placements may have offered daily hunting parties an advantage in determining where seals or walruses had congregated, but may have also helped in maintaining cooperative social relationships between campsites, since dispersed camps shared views of communal hunting areas where people may have congregated in large hunting parties.

The strategic positioning of winter camps along coastal terraces may have helped strengthen social affiliations with more distant communities as well, as shared lines of sight across the sea ice may have helped groups maintain connections along sea ice travel routes (Brughmans and Brandes 2017; IE008; Inglis et al. 2022 Smith 2015; Watts 2020). At Alarniq, a seasonal Late Tuniit campsite at NhHd-16 appears to have been initially constructed centuries

after land exposure occurred, in a raised area that had the only clear vantage of the southern floe edge towards Pingiqqalik. Later campsites at Alarniq appear to have utilized the curvature of the coast to separate winter settlements from seasonal camps and caching places to the south, with campsites during the terminal Late Tuniit Period organized to face the northeast, towards Kapuivik. Alternatively, large cairns concentrated on the southern bluff of Qalirusiq may have established widescale visual connections and served as navigational aids, potentially aiding travelling parties in locating caches or burial grounds. The linear alignment of settlements may have facilitated navigation by snowdrifts, allowing travellers to keep a constant array and monitor their direction (IE008). Establishing ease of travel between settlements may have affirmed their perceived closeness through winter travel routes and helping to maintain a sense of community and social connection across Foxe Basin (IE215; IE236).

Variability in visuospatial practices offer new perspectives on social cohesion at local and regional scales throughout the Tuniit Period. In the restricted space of Qalirusiq, Tuniit peoples devised unique ways to delineate camps that were otherwise in very close proximity. This suggests that, despite sharing a relatively small space and likely participating in similar seasonal subsistence practices, local camp communities likely maintained distinct social identities and practices during the Early Tuniit Period. At Kapuivik, where landforms were both diverse and expansive, people engaged in varied spatiotemporal relationships. Similar to Qalirusiq, Early Tuniit camps appear to have demarcated themselves within close spaces, in this case through their organization around topographic barriers. Alternatively, people appear to have fostered more open visual and spatial connections between Late Tuniit camps through the placement of settlements in elevated areas with unobstructed viewsheds. Alarniq's visuospatial organization presents a combination of these strategies, with Late Tuniit camp communities mobilizing

coastline morphologies to generate visual relationships with the floe edge and possibly to establish linear sea ice travel routes with non-local settlement places such as Pingiqqalik and Kapuivik, which were necessary for snow-drift navigation in the winter. These organizational practices demonstrate how Tuniit peoples actively shaped their material surroundings to cultivate multiscale social connections and perceptions, but also how landscape elements historically articulated these processes. This variability is suggestive of the flexible and dynamic nature of communities during the Tuniit Period, and underscores the multiple, nested scales of social identity that were likely fostered and maintained through acts of placemaking.

8.2 Architectures and Built Spaces as Relational Participants

Tuniit peoples managed and modified their occupational landscape through the construction of a wide range of features, the most common of which were dwellings, caches, hearths, fox traps, weirs, and graves. These structures were not merely products of human design or outcomes of immediate environmental needs. Rather, they served as catalysts in the ongoing differentiation of household and community relationships, continually reshaping local social worlds by informing spatial and material practice (Barad 2003; Cipolla 2019; Deloria 2001a; Harris 2021a; Haraway 2017; Johansen 2010; Lefebvre 1991; Shorter 2016; Smith 2003; Watts 2013; Whitridge 2004, 2016). Small-scale variability in the construction, maintenance, use, and abandonment of Tuniit camps and caching places highlight how built spaces held multifaceted and changing roles as part of social landscapes, and were important mechanisms through which community membership was routinely negotiated during the Tuniit Period.

Dwellings and other structures played a critical role in the organization of space within and between Tuniit households. They articulated how people encountered one another through their daily routines and helped to define which activities brought people together and affirm group membership and identity (Basso 1996:45; Casey 1996; Jervis 2022; Overholtzer 2012; TallBear 2015; Ryan 2010). Alternatively, open air spaces were fields of action for larger group activities, helping to shape broader social relations through the repeated sharing of knowledge, food, and material resources (Aldred 2020; Binford 1982; Lightfoot 1998). Internal social dynamics of camps likely varied both locally and chronologically as suggested by internal household structures, differing degrees of spatial connection between neighbouring households, and changes in the frequency and intensity of group practices such as toolmaking and caching. At the same time, continuity in certain practices, such as the consistent form and orientation of warm weather camps structures, possibly indicate wider assemblages of knowledge and practice during the Tuniit Period. The evidence suggests how architecture and people were repeatedly brought together and altered through daily relations that expressed, affirmed, and perhaps challenged the spatial boundaries that defined households and camps.

The location, construction, and layout of existing structures also appear to have contributed to the ongoing production of Tuniit communities by conditioning how later inhabitants organized themselves and perceived their connections to past people. As durable and enduring components of the landscape, built spaces stimulate affective and emotional responses in those who enter embodied engagements with them, shaping perceptions, understandings, and experiences of history, temporality, and memory (Ahmed 2005; Bauer and Johansen 2023; Deloria 2001a; Hamilakis 2013; Massumi 2015; Trouillot 1995; Yuval-Davis 2004; Watts 2016). Through deliberate acts such as the repeated occupation and ritual abandonment of structures,

Tuniit peoples may have affirmed and altered their ties to past people, contributing to a sense belonging and shared heritage that are central to place-based social identity (IE260; IE293; Trott 2005; Sorensen 2015; Supernant 2022; Whitridge 2004). At the same time, built spaces may have entered into new relationships with people as navigational markers and symbols of longstanding community connections to places, evidenced through the differential reuse of ancestral spaces, as well as in their continued roles in the travel routes and stories of Amitturmiut (Aporta 2003; IE194; IE249; IE 434; Nuttal 1992; KH01; KH04). These practices involved repeated engagements with not large semi-subterranean dwellings, as well as seemingly ephemeral features such as caches, emphasizing how Tuniit settlement practices emerged through complex and actively negotiated relations at multiple spatial and temporal scales.

I begin this section with an assessment of the affective roles of caches, which I argue were integral to past peoples' conceptualization of space, memory, and history, serving not only as storage units but as landmarks of collective histories and mediums for social cohesion. This is followed by a comparative analysis of dwelling construction practices centered on diversity within local contexts, as well as evidence for continuity in some structural forms between temporal periods. Through these discussions, I demonstrate how the physical characteristics of dwellings likely expressed and repeatedly articulated Tuniit social structures, suggesting variations in household organization and broader social interactions. This is followed by an assessment of how extramural spaces, which were largely defined by features such as hearths and caches, were product and process of interhousehold organizational structures. In doing so, I explore how these spaces facilitated communal activities and interactions, playing a crucial role in the formation and maintenance of broader social networks and identities. I end the section with a summary of available evidence for the reoccupation of dwellings and campsites in

Amittuq. The research proposes that local communities at Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq returned to specific campsites and caching places for several generations, in some cases for centuries. While prior research suggests that long-term occupational practices were largely restricted to Late Tuniit wintering villages, enduring place-community relations appear to have taken many forms, including the reuse of warm weather camps and caching places, during both the Early and Late Tuniit periods. Observed variability in the maintenance and reuse of constructed spaces may indicate these practices served as a way for people to (re)claim community histories and affirm place-based identities, making them integral to the ongoing production of Tuniit social worlds.

8.2.1 Caching as Medium of Memory, History, and Social Connection

Localized data from Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq suggest that Tuniit caching practices were diverse, as indicated through variation in documented cache types, cache locations, and the timelines of cache construction and reuse in local contexts. Contrary to their depiction as ephemeral or marginal features, caches appear to have played a significant role in how Tuniit peoples sustained long-term social connections with and through places (Friesen and Stewart 2013). Tuniit caches, I argue, were both records and the seeds of complex sociomaterial relations that ranged from immediate resource procurement practices to broader assemblages of knowledge, local tradition, and community connections to place (Hendon 2000; Tilley 2020; Van Dyke 2019; Watkins 2013). Variation in cache structures therefore embody traces of local differences in community practices, structures, and knowledge systems.

The acts of creating and exploiting a cache can be viewed as instances of memory work, historicity, and temporality, in that they involve a series of intentional and historically contingent choices about when, where, and how to engage with places and other people in the landscape (Bennett and Rowley 2004; IE281; IE379; IE427; IE433; IE440). Each decision about where to place a cache, how to prepare its contents, when to return to it, and the distribution of its resources carries a variety of references, impressions, experiences, and understandings of the landscape and people's roles within it. Within this framework, caching emerges as a dynamic way of engaging the past, present, and future simultaneously (Bauer and Johansen 2023; Friesen 2001; Lyons et al. 2010; Mills 2008; Morrison 2016; Walls 2019). Caching places were historically rich contexts that likely evoked emotion, memory, and cooperation, and fostered a strong sense of belonging and shared history that reinforced the interconnectedness of individuals, camps, and broader communities. These engagements suggest that Tuniit caches were not simply the product of economic rationalist decisions, but rather were historically situated and relational entities involved in the recursive production of a social landscape.

Amitturmiut oral history outlines spatial and material conditions necessary for successful meat caching, many which appear to have guided Tuniit practices (Desjardins 2017; IE396; IE432; IE433; IE438). These requirements emphasize the complex and knowledgeable relationships with materials and landforms involved in choosing cache locations, as well as the historical roles of persistent settlement places in shaping local traditions cache construction and use. At Kapuivik and Alarniq, most boulder caches and cairns were constructed from granite and gneiss boulders, which may have informed their location near glacial till areas. At Qalirusiq, Early Tuniit caches were mainly constructed from the abundant limestone scree, while Late Tuniit caches were comprised of scattered glacial till in lowland areas near residences. Protection

from waterlogging would also be considered, as caches were often built in sheltered areas, such as near outcrops, or in elevated areas such as uplifted peneplains or along raised coastal terraces. Ground cover and substrate were equally important variables, and high-drainage mineral substrates, like gravel, were likely prioritized (Desjardins 2017:178). The restricted availability of locations that met these criteria may have structured the movements and practices of local communities. For example, the spatial restriction of glacial till in sheltered, elevated areas may have contributed to the long-term maintenance and reuse of caching places in inland areas, and perhaps played a role in where coastal campsites were strategically situated along shorelines. Spatial limitations may have also prompted the repeated construction or reuse of caches at Qalirusiq, given the small size of the islet for much of its occupational history, leading to repeated engagements with settlements from once-coastal areas.

Variation in the structure and arrangement of boulder caches suggest differences in local community connections with specific places. Boulder caches are the most common storage structures found in Amittuq and are distinguishable from surface cairns by their raised mounds and accumulated vegetation, characteristics resulting from the burial and excavation of meat pits (Kotar 2019; Walker 2020a, 2020b). At Kapuivik, boulder caches are characterized by small mounds marked with one to four large granite or gneiss boulders. Radiocarbon evidence suggest that some locations, such as Area 222, were visited over multiple generations. However, the preserved structures indicate they may have been single-use caches in repeatedly visited caching areas. At Qalirusiq, Early Tuniit boulder caches tend to be larger and marked with piles of smaller cobbles. Evidence for high structural disturbance of most caches could be attributed to more intensive reuse practices, with bigger berms emerging from the repeated excavation of meat pits. Boulder caches from Area A at Alarniq also feature more pronounced mounds in

inland areas, suggesting a similar tradition of repeated structure use. Caches here also display more internal variation, with stone markers arranged in varying frequencies and colour combinations. This may suggest disparate functions, with some caches having been differentially reused as graves, based on their similarity to grave features identified elsewhere at Alarniq (Lynnerup et al. 2003; Meldgaard 1962). This inference is supported by the presence of quartz covering only certain structures, a marker historically associated with mortuary practices (see IE284). However, these differences may also have served as a way to distinguish individual caches within larger groups (IE254), suggesting that they may have been repeatedly reused by the same individuals or households. In either case, their distinction suggests intra-group variation in cache construction and reuse indicative individual or familial-level social differences within broader communities.

While the repeated use of caches and caching locations may have been shaped by the material affordances of local environments, their reuse may also suggest the maintenance or reimagining of community traditions and histories through placemaking practice. Many of these caching places are difficult to reach and are not visible from the outer coast, and as such were likely relocated from memory or knowledge passed down between people, as Inuit do with folk tales that preserve navigational information (IE139; IE167IE187; IE433; KH0; Nuttal 1992). The material properties of caches — that is, that they are primarily marked by durable boulders and intended to be highly visible in the landscape — may have contributed to their historic importance within local contexts. The decision to construct new caches in ancestral locations may potentially reflect efforts to affirm or redefine ancestral ties to places by contributing to the visible record of a place's history. Alternatively, the frequent reuse and modification of existing cache structures, despite the abundance of local building materials, may suggest differences in

local perceptions of communal ties to places, specifically the maintenance of tradition and a particular history, rather than its remaking or continuation. Despite the ephemeral character of their use, caches likely contributed to a lasting and obvious material record of a place's connection with people, and as such have served as important mediums for the negotiation of long-term community identities (Harris 2021a).

Inferences of equipment caches at Kapuivik and Alarniq further demonstrate the varied sociohistorical roles of storage structures and their contributions to the negotiation of community practices and structures. All inferred equipment caches are found in association with warm weather campsites, and radiocarbon dated structures suggest they were constructed between 2000 and 1500 BP. Excavated examples include the rectangular boulder chamber structures at NhHd-16 at Alarniq and the circular boulder structure found in Area 205 at Kapuivik. Common materials found in these structures were ivory, bone, and chert debitage. The infrequent presence of equipment cache features within campsite contexts suggests these structures might have been shared by multiple households within each camp community to store raw materials for tool and craft production. Similar to the inferred intensive use of extramural spaces during this time for tool production, the shared use of equipment caches may further suggest the importance of these activities for reinforcing social ties between households.

The seasonal specificity and temporal restriction of equipment caches might also suggest widespread shifts in residential mobility during the middle Late Tuniit Period. Amitturmiut Inuit stored household items in equipment caches when travelling inland on foot to caribou hunting grounds in the summer, and their emergence in Tuniit contexts may embody similar practices (IE281; IE469). Given Kapuivik's increased accessibility to resource places in the interior of

Qikiqtaaluk via fast ice and Alarniq's land connection to the interior of Melville Peninsula, these settlement places may have served as important outposts during seasonal travel during the middle Tuniit Period. Equipment caches may have been product and process of these broader landscape relations, their construction and use likely informed by seasonal travel and facilitated the maintenance of place-based ecological knowledge (Habu 2018). This possibility stresses the importance of approaching the occupational histories of persistent settlement places not as disconnected occupational contexts, but as part of broader, dynamic assemblages that were continually redefined through local relations between people, materials, and other constituents of the landscape.

8.2.2 Diversity and Continuity in Dwelling Construction

Dwellings were the primary spaces where household social dynamics were negotiated through domestic activities and everyday interactions (Ahmed 2005; Basso 1996:45; Casey 1996; Jervis 2022; Overholtzer 2012; TallBear 2015; Ryan 2010). In Amittuq, Tuniit dwellings held multifaceted social roles, serving not simply as utilitarian shelters but as affective fields that were integral to the formation and expression of identities and relationships. Variability in the size, internal organization, and form of dwellings within and between camps suggests that household social structures were fluid, ranging from individuals or nuclear families to communal/multi-family settings. These differences challenge previous inferences for greater regional uniformity in architectural and organizational practices across the Tuniit Period (Maxwell 1985), suggesting instead that household-level relations were locally and often seasonally specific. Chronological differences also indicate that broad changes in architectural

technologies were likely gradual, challenging architectural typologies that have been used to support interpretations of a sudden and rapid technological transition during the initial Late Tuniit Period (Meldgaard 1960a, 1960b, cf. Ryan 2010). Tuniit architectural practices were likely not predetermined by overarching cultural norms, but were instead context-dependent and actively articulated by engagements between people and materials on a local level. The patterning is suggestive of flexible household structures and the articulation of shared identities at multiple spatial and temporal scales.

Observed variability in the size and internal organization of Tuniit dwellings during the Early and Late Tuniit periods suggests dynamic and fluid organizational structures. The most important differences involve shifts from smaller, nuclear family dwellings to communal or multi-family dwellings. Investigated communal dwellings are dated to the middle Early Tuniit Period at Kapuivik and the initial and middle Late Tuniit periods at Alarniq, and are largely inferred as colder weather structures. Seasonal differences in dwellings may relate to fluid household social structures, wherein larger winter dwellings permitted cooperative practices between multiple families that in the summer would take place within extramural spaces. The patterning may suggest that the construction of communal dwellings were informed by sociopolitical strategies aimed at affirming or enhancing social bonds and collective identities within domestic settings. This inference is supported by the association of larger dwellings with multiple hearths and divided storage areas, which are indicative of the internal separation of family groups (Friesen 2007; Howse et al. 2021). That dwellings of drastically different sizes are both present within the same residential contexts suggests that household organization often was not uniform across the camp community, speaking to multiple scales of social difference and affiliation within local settings.

Variability in dwelling construction practices challenge common architectural types, suggesting instead that architectural changes previously inferred as abrupt and widespread were gradual and locally variable throughout the Tuniit Period. Dwelling forms have been used as temporally diagnostic markers for distinguishing between Pre-Dorset (Early Tuniit) and Dorset (Late Tuniit) archaeological contexts, and are regularly classified within a small number of archaeological types. Elliptical surface dwellings are attributed to the Pre-Dorset culture, and rectangular surface dwellings and semi-subterranean dwellings to the Dorset culture (Meldgaard 1960a, 1960b; Ryan 2010; Savelle and Dyke 2014). A sudden shift in dwelling technologies is often inferred as the product of a rapid, widespread transition from a highly mobile to a semi-sedentary settlement strategy with the onset of the Dorset period. This transition is often framed as evidence of either a cultural replacement due to an incoming migration of new people, or to the *in situ* adaptation of Pre-Dorset peoples to pronounced regional environmental changes within the “core area” of Amittuq (Maxwell 1985; Murray 1999; Prentiss and Lenert 2009; Sutherland 2003; Ryan 2016; cf. Houmard 2018). Both arguments fail to account for the inferred agency of local people in selecting and modifying architectural technologies through the kinds of daily practices and relations discussed above. That dwelling forms emerged through a diverse array of material and historical contexts is suggestive of the flexibility of Tuniit social organization and technologies.

Due to their characterization as highly mobile people, it has largely been assumed that the dwellings of Early Tuniit people are the remains of ephemeral, single-use structures (Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1960b:69). However, significant variability in the size and form of Early Tuniit dwellings suggests they embody different occupational contexts and durations of use. Similar to cache structures, surface dwelling forms vary based on the local availability of building materials

and the seasonal needs of people. Most structures are comprised of boulders, while a lesser number are distinguished by flagstone or gravel perimeters or are without visible boundaries, such as isolated midpassages or box hearths. Rather than holding a single function, boulder surface dwellings appear to represent a variety of seasonal structures, pointing to diverse contexts and durations of use (Claus 2003; Ramsden and Murray 1995; Ryan 2003).

While sparser boulder dwellings may be the remains of tents, as they are most often found in association with external hearths, robust multi-row boulder dwellings may represent more durable cold weather structures intended for longer occupational durations. Based on their similarity to the remains of Inuit qarmats, multi-row boulder structures may have had walls comprised of stacked stones, or composite walls of stone and snow (Fogt 1998). An inferred cold weather seasonal context for these structures is supported by their restricted locational setting. Most multi-row boulder dwellings documented at Qalirusiq and Kapuivik are located along northwestern-facing coastlines, towards Uangnaq, the predominant wind. As such, these durable dwellings may have been intended for turbulent weather conditions associated with strategic locales where camps could be easily relocated from the sea ice due to their alignment with *uqalurait* snow drifts, or alternatively, where pack ice may have dammed nearshore in the autumn or spring due to Uangnaq, resulting in an abundance of floe edge hunting opportunities. Radiocarbon samples on 223-F51 and 223-F39 at Kapuivik suggest that both dwellings were located near the active shoreline when first constructed, and were reoccupied decades or possibly centuries later. This may indicate that multi-row boulder dwellings involved long-term, intergenerational maintenance or reuse practices similar to semi-subterranean dwellings constructed during later periods.

In contrast to the patterning of Early Tuniit surface dwellings, Late Tuniit surface dwellings exhibit less variation in terms of their structure and seasonal contexts. Apart from a few isolated midpassages at Kapuivik and Alarniq, most surface dwellings are small, circular structures with sparse boulder perimeters. For instance, boulder surface dwellings are similar in size and form between NiHf-47 at Qalirusiq, Areas 222 and 205 at Kapuivik, and NhHe-26 and NhHd-16 at Alarniq, despite their different locational settings and associated time frames of use. Based on seasonal indicators of warm weather use, such as external hearths and migratory bird remains, most Late Tuniit surface dwellings appear to be the products of summer or autumn occupations. This correlation supports that Late Tuniit boulder surface dwellings are likely the remains of tent dwellings. Given their architectural and locational similarities to sparser boulder surface dwellings found in Early Tuniit contexts, this may suggest continuity in warm weather architectural practices and settlement strategies within the region. This continuity may suggest broader cultural connections and shared knowledge systems on a regional level that shaped certain sets of occupational practices.

Chronological evidence suggests that the emergence of semi-subterranean dwelling technologies may have occurred earlier than previously thought, challenging the occurrence of a rapid technological shift and pointing instead to the gradual development and incorporation of this technology into community settlement contexts. Radiocarbon dates from Alarniq indicate, for example, that some semi-subterranean dwellings built into runnels at NhHd-11, such as F18 and F32, were initially constructed during the terminal Early Tuniit Period. Moreover, F18 includes additional radiocarbon samples, as well as stratigraphic evidence for multiple building phases, that suggests the dwelling was reconstructed during the initial Late Tuniit Period. These findings suggest an asynchronous and incremental adoption of this architectural technology

across Amittuq. This may indicate that individuals and/or smaller community groups held localized knowledge about construction practices and made autonomous choices about the form and structure of dwellings, further demonstrating the diverse spatial and temporal scales at which social differences unfolded during the Tuniit Period.

8.2.3 Extramural Residential Spaces as Fields of Social Difference

While dwellings were product and process of household social structures, the residential areas located between dwellings were affective fields where broader social connections were negotiated through communal activities (Aldred 2020; Binford 1982; Lightfoot 1998). Reconstructing the practices that people chose to carry out within public settings permits new inferences of the degree of social integration within a camp, as well as the elements of daily life that were central to a shared sense of community. Tuniit people appear to have prioritized organizational structures that facilitated the heightened visibility of activity spaces from dwelling entrances, such as external hearths, caches, and floe edge hunting grounds, which may have shaped daily interactions between households. However, archaeological patterning suggests localized and chronological differences in the specific arrangements of unwallled spaces and intensity of their use, suggesting movement and flow in community engagements rather than inherent boundaries. These differences may embody a politics of belonging, in which decisions about who and what was offered visual or spatial access to shared extramural areas embodied and shaped social relations within the camp community (Ashmore and Knapp 1999; Yuval-Davis 2006; Kosiba and Bauer 2013; Johanson 2008). The patterned variability in the organization and use of extramural spaces offer new perspectives on the flexibility of intra-camp organizational

strategies, and temporal changes in the scale and intensity of camp-wide social integration during the Tuniit Period.

Extramural practices exhibited significant seasonal variation throughout the Tuniit Period, in which most warm weather residential contexts featured clustered layouts while cold weather settlements were arranged linearly along coastal terraces. In some warm weather camps, such as Areas 222 and 205 at Kapuivik, dwellings were arranged in a circular pattern with their entrances facing inwards. Dwelling entrances were interstitial spaces where private household relations intersected with broader communal interactions, and their inward positioning would have produced a central extramural space that was visible and equally accessible to all households. Alternatively, camps in Area A at Alarniq include pairs of dwellings constructed with their entrances towards one another, delineating shared extramural spaces not visible from the entrances of other dwellings. This may suggest the presence of internally focused social groups within a broader camp setting, rather than the more egalitarian organizational structures of camps at Kapuivik. The patterning may indicate that these contexts served a similar social role to construction and use of cold weather communal dwellings, actively shaping daily encounters and serving as material references to the social affiliations of individuals and households within the community.

External hearths were common features in warm weather camps and appear to have been central to the organization of extramural spaces. Historically, external hearths were centers of domestic life within Amitturmiut summer camps, where cooking, oil rendering, tool treatment, and social gatherings were carried out (IE428; IE489). Surveys and excavations of Tuniit external hearths at Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq indicate similarly multifaceted roles, evident

from the presence of animal bones, blubber residue, flint knapping debris, and broken stone and ivory tools. The majority of external hearths were positioned directly outside dwelling entrances, indicating their primary use by individual households. Within the egalitarian arrangement, visible hearths placed within the liminal spaces of dwelling entrances may indicate a deliberate blurring of social boundaries, with neighboring households likely gathering around their own hearths, suggesting a collective rhythm to daily domestic life and a mutual acknowledgment of shared practices and traditions.

Varied patterning in the spatial distribution of toolmaking activities within external spaces, as evidenced by lithic and ivory debitage, suggest periods of intensified communal activities and potentially specialized labour roles within some of warm weather contexts. The greatest frequencies of extramural lithic scatters associated with warm weather camps are found in Areas 205 and 222 at Kapuivik, near the eastern surface dwellings at NhHd-11 at Alarniq, and along the lower terraces of NiHf-1 at Qalirusiq. Available evidence suggests that communal toolmaking activities were most intensive during the terminal Early Tuniit and initial Late Tuniit periods, when these sites were primarily occupied. Communal lithic production activities appear to have taken place primarily around individual hearths as well as within the shared spaces between paired dwelling entrances (Kyle Forsythe, Personal Communication 2023). Alternatively, there is limited evidence for flintknapping and slate work within the central spaces of egalitarian camp structures with the exception of Area 205 at Kapuivik. While artifact distributions suggest that Tuniit people did not restrict particular activities to extramural versus interior spaces, differences in the organization and frequency of extramural practices may suggest that the social structure of camp communities were locally varied, and may also indicate that specialized economic roles within camps occurred as part of warm weather aggregations

during the terminal Early Tuniit and initial Late Tuniit periods.

Available data suggest winter extramural practices were less intensive, largely restricted to hunting, butchering, cache exploitation, and trash disposal, with most other practices taking place within dwellings. The restriction of interhousehold domestic activities may have factored into broader organizational decisions, helping to explain why winter dwellings tend to be linearly arranged towards coastlines rather than designated extramural spaces within camps. Other than the convenience of visually monitoring the floe edge for opportunistic prey, the organization of dwellings towards the floe edge may have anchored households in a shared orientation towards communal hunting areas, which was likely a nexus of daily communal interaction. In doing so, these organizational strategies may have bridged household, camp, and even intercamp relations in similar ways to outdoor cooking and toolmaking practices in warm weather contexts, reaffirming community affiliations through a sense of social cooperation and shared traditions. While winter settlements were generally characterized by a linear organization and restricted extramural activities, NhHd-11 deviates from this pattern, instead mirroring the spatial configurations seen at warm weather camps, such as NhHe-26, in which pairs of dwellings were organized to face one another. This supports inferences for significant changes in community social organization during the terminal Early Tuniit and initial Late Tuniit periods, and suggests that, even when faced with severe weather constraints, organizational decisions were historically contingent and socially situated. This flexibility in local social organization could have been instrumental in reinforcing social affiliations within broader scale communities.

8.2.4 The Long-Term and Repeated Use of Built Space

Tuniit peoples incorporated ancestral structures into their daily lives through their maintenance and repeated use, possibly to establish, affirm, or negotiate community membership. While prior research suggests that long-term occupational practices were limited to Late Tuniit semi-subterranean dwelling contexts, I argue that enduring community relations with ancestral places took many forms, including caching locales and small surface dwellings that are often overlooked as ephemeral, single-use sites. These practices were particularly pronounced at Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq, where limited burial processes, the durability of building materials, and the accumulation of patinas and lichens on architectural stones (signalling their antiquity), served as both archives and agents of tangible community histories. The varied character, frequency, and intensity of intergenerational practices offer new perspectives on how people navigated and revised perceptions of history, temporality, and community memory through local placemaking practice (Bauer and Johansen 2023, Hendon 2010; Lyons et al. 2010; Johansen 2014; Mills 2008; Morrison 2016; Trouillot 1995). In actively and intentionally choosing to reoccupy residential areas, Tuniit people appear to have anchored their contemporary social practices to a deep heritage of people-place relations, cultivating a sense of belonging through which enduring communities were created and maintained. The results demonstrate how the recurrent occupation of places were not the product of timeless settlement traditions, but rather were mechanisms through which people repeatedly articulated how elements of ancestral spaces, and presumably earlier inhabitants, were incorporated into the reimagining of communities.

Tuniit people have often been characterised as highly mobile hunter-gatherers that

behaved in economically rationalist ways (Hood 1998; Maxwell 1985; Savelle and Dyke 2014). This framing presumes that people in Amittuq repeatedly constructed their campsites near outer seacoasts to maintain proximity to nearshore sea mammal hunting spots, thereby neglecting ancestral camps in meaningful ways (Appelt et al. 2016; Darwent et al. 2018; Mary-Rousselière 2002; Savelle and Dyke 2014). Although the long-term occupation of some larger semi-subterranean dwellings are recognized (Dyke et al. 2019:78; McGhee 1997:210; Morrison 1999:140; Habu and Savelle 1994), these exceptions are frequently interpreted through an economic-rationalist lens in which people reduced labour associated with seasonal relocation by reusing old structures (Maxwell 1985; Howse et al. 2019; Savelle et al. 2009). In contrast to this framing, intergenerational practices at Kapuivik and Alarniq appear to have been more frequent in the context of small rather than large semi-subterranean dwellings. This suggests that dwelling reuse was influenced by factors beyond the expected labor involved in maintenance versus construction. The reoccupation of semi-subterranean dwellings may instead have been driven by a variety of deliberate, socially situated considerations that varied between locales and time periods.

A positive relationship between socioeconomic diversity and the frequency of reoccupation practices is illustrated at NhHd-11 at Alarniq. Evidence of reoccupation at this site is primarily from radiocarbon dates associated with a semi-subterranean dwelling, NhHd-11: F18, that suggest its rebuilding or reuse during the terminal Early Tuniit and initial Late Tuniit periods. Furthermore, a radiocarbon sample recovered from an adjacent extramural space, NhHd-11: F22, suggests continued reoccupation of the campsite during the terminal Late Tuniit Period. The reoccupation of NhHd-11 is correlated with repeated yet emergent community practices that took place within the broader surroundings of Area A, including tidal fishing, winter floe edge

hunting, fox trapping, and summer bird hunting. Shifting practices were likely influenced by the changing topography and resource availability of Area A. The nearby site of NhHd-19 offers evidence for weir fishing during the terminal Early Tuniit Period, a time when mudflats dominated the area. Fox traps and cache features at NhHd-19 were likely constructed as the land uplifted and drainage improved in subsequent periods. Additionally, sites NhHe-25 and NhHe-26 contain a mix of boulder caches and cairns which likely contributed to the repeated visitation of Area A.

Following the initial Late Tuniit Period, Area A fused with the mainland of Melville Peninsula. Consequently, NhHd-11 was strategically positioned along one of the most direct routes, later used by Inuit, to access interior caribou hunting grounds. This geographical change might explain the continued interaction of Tuniit peoples with NhHd-11, as evidenced by the terminal Late Tuniit date at F22 (Chapter Seven, Table 7.3). The varied occupational practices that took place in and surrounding NhHd-11 over nearly a millennium suggests that this winter settlement might have held particular resonance for local communities. Its continued reuse amidst fluctuating socioeconomic activities suggests a deepening association of social and historic affiliations embodied through the temporally diverse structures in the surrounding landscape (Bauer and Johansen 2023).

Mortuary practices appear to have also factored into the reoccupation of winter settlements at Alarniq, with four semi-subterranean dwellings containing human burials, indicating the ritualistic abandonment of homes (Lynnerup et al. 2003; Meldgaard 1962). Two of the semi-subterranean dwellings, NhHd-3: F9 and NhHd-1: F6, are each associated with multiple radiocarbon dates, suggesting both were repeatedly occupied over multiple generations prior to a

final occupational phase represented by the burials, occurring within a similar time frame of 1874 – 1711 BP (Table 7.3, Figures 7.21 and 7.22). These dwellings may have been sites of deeply embedded memory and emotional attachment, embodying the social relationships and affinities that informed how later inhabitant understood and engaged with places. The act of burial prevented the ongoing domestic use of the dwellings, and instead transformed them into visible reminders of ancestors. The differential reuse of dwellings as graves indicate that architectural practices were likely integral to household and community identities, and highlights the locally variable and socially dynamic character of community relations.

Radiocarbon evidence suggests that the intergenerational reoccupation of winter settlements may have been relatively common during the Early Tuniit Period, as well. At Kapuivik, dwellings, such as 223: F51 and 223: F39, show signs of being reoccupied after considerable gaps in time. The placement of younger dwellings within older camps is also present in Area 223. For instance, 223: F38 appears to have been constructed during the later occupational phase of 223: F39. At Qalirusiq, some caches and cairns at NiHf-1 are associated with much later dates than the dwellings they are found adjacent to, suggesting that ancestral camps constructed during the initial Early Tuniit Period may have been reoccupied, or otherwise differentially reused as caching places, during the middle Early Tuniit Period. The chronology of Early Tuniit cold weather settlement contexts indicates that the placement and reoccupation of Early Tuniit dwellings and caches were not arbitrary decisions, but instead may suggest deliberate efforts to maintain connections to community histories by including architecture that embodied earlier inhabitants within the residential boundaries of daily camp life.

Perhaps the most significant finding of the research is radiocarbon evidence for the long-

term maintenance and reuse of warm weather sites — that is, sites defined by sparse surface dwellings associated with warm weather seasonal indicators such as external hearths and migratory bird remains. These sites are often inferred as ephemeral, single-use occupational contexts, reflecting the presumed higher residential mobility of summer and fall camps (Bielawski 1988; Coulson and Andreasen 2019; Prentis 2009). In contrast, evidence from Kapuivik suggests that Tuniit peoples repeatedly occupied warm weather camps, with the clearest evidence associated with Late Tuniit activities. This includes radiocarbon evidence for the construction or reuse of a surface dwelling (F82), boulder cache (F82b), and external hearth (F83) dated to the initial Late Tuniit Period, within a cluster of surface dwellings and caches that otherwise date to the terminal Early Tuniit Period. Radiocarbon assays for reoccupation is also present within middle Late Tuniit contexts, including dates suggesting multiple occupational phases within two boulder surface dwellings, NhHd-16: F7 at Alarniq and 205: F05 at Kapuivik, each which is adjacent to an inferred equipment cache of similar age.

Given the similarities in reoccupied contexts, it appears that the preparation and exploitation of caches were important practices tied to the maintenance and reuse of summer and autumn camps. As discussed in Section 2.1, caches involved diverse cooperative activities, such as resource procurement, construction, and exploitation, which would have brought people together in different seasons and for varied durations of time within these residential contexts. Caching practices also involved assemblages of situated knowledge and social memory related to the proper selection of cache locations, food preparation, and the relocation of caches. As such, caching practices were likely integral to the daily and seasonal rhythms of local communities, strengthening communal bonds and attachments to specific places. When groups returned to these camps, they were not just returning to a physical location, but to a repository of shared

memories, experiences, and ancestral connections. In repeatedly choosing to occupy a warm weather camp, people reaffirmed their connections not just to the land, but also to each other and to their shared past, despite the shorter duration and generally smaller size of these gatherings. This act of return required trust and cooperation among community members, and may have ensured that caches were respected and shared equitably.

The maintenance and reuse of Tuniit camps has important chronological implications for Eastern Arctic research. First, the reoccupation of the semi-subterranean dwelling at NhHd-11(F18) and the campsite in Area 222 during the terminal Early Tuniit and initial Late Tuniit periods challenges the prevalent cultural-historical model, as it suggests local continuity in camp communities at Kapuivik and Alarniq within the time frame when the Pre-Dorset (Early Tuniit) archaeological culture is inferred to have been rapidly replaced by the Dorset (Late Tuniit) archaeological culture, either by cultural diffusion or environmental adaptation (c. 2800-2500 BP) (Maxwell 1985; Savelle and Dyke). Second, that people frequently reoccupied ancestral dwellings and camps in diverse seasonal contexts complicates the use of beach ridge sequencing as a relative dating method, as it demonstrates that the cultural age of dwellings and geological age of beach ridge formations do not always correspond. This has important implications for the chronological typologies that were initially constructed from these sequences and used to infer sociomaterial changes during the Tuniit periods (Meldgaard 1962; Taylor 1968; Maxwell 1985), as well as interpretations of local and regional demography that were premised on the changing frequency of dwellings within beach ridge sequences (Savelle and Dyke 2014).

Evidence for the long-term and repeated use of built spaces at Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq suggests that material changes were gradual and varied locally during the Tuniit Period,

and that people actively managed their communities and landscapes through a wide range of spatial and temporal practices. Despite changing topographies, local ecologies, climates, and likely regional demographics, Tuniit peoples often continued to reoccupy settlement places, often going to great lengths to ensure their ability to successfully maintain ancestral settlements. In cold weather contexts, these practices included significant changes in resource procurement practices, and the differential reuse of dwelling structures as caches and graves. In the context of warm weather camps, maintenance practices centered on ensuring resource security through the construction and reuse of caches. These findings indicate that complex, dynamic social communities emerged through diverse placemaking activities, and that transient contexts were affective fields where enduring community relations were cultivated.

8.3 Conclusions

This research has argued for the mutually constitutive nature of place and community in the eastern Canadian Arctic. I reconceptualize Tuniit settlement places not merely as reflections of reductive archaeological cultures, but as vibrant, dynamic entities that actively participated in the production of human social worlds. The evidence presented herein also highlights how Tuniit peoples actively shaped settlement places, resulting in the recursive and relational constitution of past communities (Ahenakew 2017; Barad 2003; Basso 1996; Cipolla 2019; Deloria 2001; Harris 2014; Ingold 2010; Massumi 2015; Price 2008; Qitsualik 2013; Smith 2003; Supernant 2022; Tallbear 2015; Watts 2016; Whitridge 2004). Through the incorporation of Amitturmiut place stories and knowledge of the landscape, paleotopographic data, and archaeological traces of Tuniit settlement practices, this research underscores the value of including different ways of

knowing and being with places when reconstructing occupational histories. In the next and final chapter, I consider what has emerged differently in my narrative of Amittuq's occupational past by taking a historically situated and place-based approach to the Tuniit archaeological landscape. In doing so, I demonstrate the value of a place-based framework for developing more historically contingent and socially situated narratives of Arctic communities and landscapes.

Chapter 9

Conclusion

Inuit describe the Canadian Arctic as *nalunaqtuq* (*uncanny, ineffable*) to convey how the land is always changing, so that there is no end to what can be learned and taught through it (Qitsualik-Tinsley 2013:24). Inuit see their identities, knowledge, and histories as inseparable from the land, and as such their communities can be understood as fluid and more-than-human (Aporta 2003; IE215; IE236; IE261; Dawson et al. 2022; Nuttal 1992; Price 2008; Qitsualik 2013, Robinson 2022; Tester and Irniq 2008, Whitridge 2004, 2016). The central problem of this dissertation has been the identification and explanation of how ancient communities in Amittuq (*Northern Foxe Basin*), NU may have emerged and changed through similarly interdependent and mutually productive relationships between people and the places during the Tuniit Period (c. 4500 – 600 BP). I have argued that Tuniit communities were created and redefined across multiple social, spatial, and chronological scales through daily occupational practices, longer-term strategies of land use, and broader assemblages of movement, memory, knowledge, and history that were repeatedly articulated through encounters with persistent settlement places (Ashmore 2007; Cipolla 2021; Bradley 2000; Crellin et al. 2020; Harris 2014; Harrison-Buck and Hendon 2018; Ingold 2000; Johansen 2010; Sørensen 2019; Watts 2016). The result is an archaeological narrative in which the relationships between people and places were co-constitutive of a historically contingent, fluid, and emergent occupational landscape — one whose vestiges continue to materialize and acquire meaning as valued components of the Amitturmiut homeland and Inuit cultural heritage (Aporta 2003, Pauktuutit 2006; QIA 2010; Watts 2016).

Previous archaeological narratives conceptualized a macro-scale Arctic settlement system in which Tuniit groups in Amittuq primarily occupied outer seacoasts to maintain close proximity to abundant nearshore marine resources that were unique to this “core area” of economic prosperity and cultural development (Fitzhugh 1997; Maxwell 1985; McGhee 1972; Meldgaard 1962; Savelle and Dyke 2014; Taylor 1968). These narratives frame repeatedly occupied coastal settlements as “stairways of history” (see Howse 2019:533, Odgaard 2015), in which changes in material culture are chronologically mapped between sites located on consecutive beach terraces, based on the geological age of their formation. This framing portrays Tuniit peoples as bounded archaeological cultures or socio-evolutionary stage types structured by large-scale external forces such as cultural diffusion and environmental change, and reduces persistent settlement places to static backgrounds upon which these bounded entities were repeatedly inscribed (Appelt et al. 2016; Fitzhugh 1976; Hardenberg 2013; Mary-Rousselière 2002; Maxwell 1985; Murray 1999). As a result, key aspects of Tuniit communities, including small-scale diversity in their social structures and the relational nature of their formation, have remained outside the scope of archaeological observation, investigation, and analysis (see Kotar 2022 for exception). In presenting persistent settlement places as static archives of archaeological cultures, “core area” narratives have tended to neglect their roles as sites of living history. This has produced a divide between Tuniit and Inuit that contradicts local oral histories of intercultural interaction and shared connections to places (Birch et al. 2022:2). In distancing contemporary communities from their archaeological heritage, this approach has marginalized Inuit knowledge and limited opportunities for meaningful collaboration with local communities within Tuniit archaeological research (Hood 1998, 2002, see Atalay 2016; Birch 2022; Schnieder and Heyes 2020; Supernant 2022; Watts 2016).

The research presented in this dissertation aimed to construct a relational and historically situated narrative of Tuniit occupational history by reinterpreting past communities through the places they inhabited, rather than imposing predefined models of culture, environment, and history onto these places. The approach is premised on archaeological studies that emphasize the relational character of places as fields of action where human social structures are repeatedly defined through thought and practice, and that treat the different social and spatial scales of landscape production holistically (Ashmore and Knapp 2000; Basso 1996; Anschuetz et al. 2001; Ingold, 1993; Johansen 2010; Tilley, 1994; Smith 2003). Rather than isolating stratified social scales onto fixed space, this framing permitted the decoupling of scale from fixed endpoints such as the type-site and culture area (e.g., the “core area”), and attended instead to how intersecting scales of spatial relations contributed to the production of communities within a dynamic and emergent landscape.

I combined this relational landscape approach with an Indigenous and posthuman feminist framework that more readily accounts for the agency of both humans and non-humans in continually shaping communities and their historic realities (Akiwenzie-Damm et al. 2019; Barad 2003; Cipolla et al 2021; Crellin 2020; Crellin and Harris 2020; Colwell-Chanthaphonh and Ferguson 2007; Deleuze and Guattari 1987; Deloria 1992, 2001b; Harris 2021a; TallBear 2015; Tester and Irniq 2008; Watts 2013, 2016). I argue that the human-centric, Western spatial ontologies that often underlie econometric or phenomenological approaches to archaeological landscapes are insufficient for addressing people-place relations in the Canadian Arctic where people do not (and likely did not) adhere to these cultural logics.

Inuit are inextricably linked to Nuna (*the land*) and recognize Nuna’s agency in shaping

reality (IE215; IE236; IE261; Dawson et al. 2022; Nuttal 1992; Price 2008; Qitsualik 2008, 2013; Tester and Irniq 2008, Whitridge 2004). As Rachel Qitsualik-Tinsley (2008:15) explains, Inuit exercise a sense of sovereignty free of possessiveness, due to an “incomplete knowing” of the land and its ability to change what is knowable (see also Heyes and Dowsley 2018; Price 2008; Kushwaha 2013). This epistemology resonates with Anishnaabe – Kanien’kehá:ka scholar Vanessa Watt’s (2016:34) theorization of place and thought as mutually constituted, and Karen Barad’s (2003; 2007) agential realism in which social and scientific knowledge production are framed as inherently inseparable and material. Building from these frameworks, I have argued that Tuniit places were not meaningless spaces until they were made meaningful by people through practices, norms, or ideals (Marshall and Alberta 2014: 25). Instead, they emerged through the same historical relations in which humans and nonhumans acquired shared belonging and connection as social collectives, resulting in new sets of relations and, and as such, new potentials for what could materialize and become meaningful as part of the occupational landscape (Basso 1996; Casey 1996; Deloria 2001a:16; TallBear 2015; Haraway 2017; Harris 2014; Lefebvre 1991:64; Massumi 2015; Pries 2018:5; Watts 2013:22).

Framing places simultaneously as records and catalysts of communities highlights how the identity and agency of people, landforms, architecture, and other entities emerges through the specific historical contexts in which they acquire form and meaning with others *in place* (sensu Tallbear 2015, see Barad and Gandorfer 2021:49). Within my study, this has meant that archaeological knowledge production should be also treated as an emergent and relational process tied to the places under investigation (Amundsen-Meyer 2023; Johnson 2012; Joyce 2021: 96; Price 2008; Tagalik et al. 2023; Watts 2016). Every interaction with data, be it in the form of artifacts, legacy data, or oral history, is an act of difference in that it imposes a specific

point of view upon the material and spatial elements under observation, or what Karen Barad calls “agential cuts” (2007:185). Agential cuts are the primary apparatus of both social and scientific knowledge production as they determine what can be seen, imagined, felt, and discussed, critically informing the relations and practices made possible through research (Barad 2007:148, Deleuze 1992:159). Inuit also advocate for a relational approach to knowledge production by emphasising place-based learning and the principle of *Saimaqatigiingniq* (*reconciliation/balance between equals*), which promotes the theoretical leveling and integration of Inuit and non-Inuit knowledge and practice (QIA 2010; Price 2008; Qitsualik 2008, 2013; Tagalik et al. 2023). These concepts guided my approach to analysis, in particular the attention to productive frictions that emerged by bringing different forms of historical evidence (e.g., archaeological, oral-historical, paleogeographic) into open-ended dialogues that move past ideal types common to Arctic archaeological research (Barad 2003; Bennett 2020:118; Garrouette & Westcott 2013; Haraway 2016:39-40; Harris 2018:87; Rosiek and Snyder 2020; Tuhiwai Smith 2012:34)

Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq, I have argued, are product and process of millennia of community relations, involving not only Tuniit peoples, but Early, Historic, and contemporary Inuit peoples. Amitturmiut oral histories have materialized through encounters with Nuna and stand as an important knowledge source for rethinking how persistent settlement places might have shaped, and been shaped by, encounters with people in earlier periods. Following Watt’s (2016:11) recommendations for collaborative Indigenous research, I employed oral stories not as representations or metaphors, but as agents tied to materially locatable places capable of reshaping knowledge, perception, and interaction with archaeological materials and places (see Barad 2007; Haraway 1997). The study facilitated a range of collaborative efforts that highlight

the epistemological value of Amitturmiut oral traditions in constructing more responsible research designs aligned with community interests, and in building historically contingent interpretations of Tuniit landscapes. Central to the analysis were semi-structured interviews conducted with local Knowledge Holders in Igloolik, NU, and archival research on Inuit oral testimonies transcribed by the Igloolik Oral History Project (OHP). These sources express detailed descriptions of spatial practices not commonly recognized in regional ethnographic and archaeological research, and new insights into how repeated encounters with Tuniit archaeological remains have shaped Inuit memory, perceptions of history, and social attachments to places. Descriptions of Tuniit and Early Inuit settlement practices also facilitated the identification of archaeological features that have been overlooked in Tuniit contexts, such as equipment caches and fishing weirs, offering new perspectives on local community practices. Other collaborative initiatives included regular consultations with local authorities, such as the Igloolik Hunters and Trappers Association, and the running of an archaeology youth camp and field school program in Igloolik, NU. These capacity building efforts were reciprocally beneficial, as they helped to integrate different ways of engaging with archaeological data, and kept subject positions visible and open to critical intervention throughout the research.

To better understand the dynamic character of Amittuq's environments, my investigation involved the palaeogeographical analysis of persistent settlement places. The palaeogeographical component included the construction and analysis of predictive GIS models that visualized the topographic and bathymetric transformation of the region in 500-year time slices, to interpret the potential relationships between paleoenvironmental changes and Tuniit spatial practices. These models were combined with spatialized oral historical data to analyze differences in local ecological settings, such as changes in freshwater systems and near shore marine habitats over

time. The models contributed to the development of new inferences about how Tuniit people engaged with one another within a constantly shifting environment, and the affective capacities of non-humans, such as landforms, in shaping movements, perceptions, and practices.

The archaeological analytical component centered on the analysis of Tuniit architecture and artifacts gathered from Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq through remotely piloted aircraft (RPA) visible light and thermography surveys, pedestrian survey, excavations, and radiocarbon sequencing. Incorporating archaeological expectations derived from oral historical and palaeogeographical analyses into my judgemental survey sampling strategy facilitated the identification of locational contexts where underrepresented seasonal activities (e.g., inland caching and fishing) appear to have taken place. Conducting judgmental remotely piloted and pedestrian surveys in targeted inland settings resulted in the identification of seven newly documented archaeological sites, contributing to a richer narrative of Tuniit movement and locational strategies within the regional landscape, that challenge prior models of a shoreward-shifting regional settlement strategy (Meldgaard 1962; Howse et al. 2017; Rowley 2003; Savelle et al 2009). The analysis of inland areas and coastal settlements facilitated new inferences about the organization of domestic and communal spaces, suggesting how humans and nonhumans came together as social collectives through everyday relations across a significant span of time (ca. 4000 – 600 BP).

The research suggests that Kapuivik, Qalirusiq, and Alarniq were not isolated or disconnected occupational contexts, nor records of predictable and uniform regional histories. Observed variability in location choices, architecture, organizational structures, site maintenance practices, and seasonal land use suggest that Tuniit communities engaged in relations and practices that were unique to the material and historical contexts of each settlement place (IE290; IE498; Price 2008; Watts 2020:124-125). At the same time, local relations were embedded within broader

community assemblages of knowledge, practice, movement, and connection within the region, as suggested by material evidence for similarities in building, storage, and mortuary practices, the visual and spatial alignment of settlements, and the long-term and recurrent use of structures and spaces. Available evidence characterizes the active role of Tuniit peoples in strategically managing their communities through historically contingent and socially meaningful engagements with persistent places, and the affective capacities of landforms, materials, and architecture in shaping human perceptions, experiences, and actions (Ahmed 2005; Basso 1996; Eastman 2020 [1911]; Harris 2014; Massumi 2015; Nuttall 1992:77-80; Price 2008; Tallbear 2015; Watts 2013).

This dynamic and multiscale perspective on Tuniit communities challenges cultural-historical models that reduce the identity of past peoples to monolithic cultural entities (Hood 1998, see Birch et al. 2022). Instead, this research highlights how community memberships were plural and repeatedly differentiated across multiple social scales, as well as how local communities appear to have persisted across time spans traditionally associated with separate archaeological cultures and their chronological periods, such as evidence for continuity in the maintenance of campsites between the Early Tuniit (Pre-Dorset) and Late Tuniit (Dorset) periods (Birch 2022; Holland-Lulewicz 2021; Kotar 2022; Lightfoot 1995). The work also challenges socio-evolutionary models that frame large-scale environmental forces as the primary catalysts of social action and cultural change, suggesting instead how local relations between human and nonhumans contributed to how people made sense of their worlds, and the ongoing negotiation of community structures and practices (Fitzhugh 1997; Mary-Rousselière 2002; Nagy 1996; Savelle and Dyke 2014; Taylor 1968). In doing so, the study builds on the recent work of Kotar (2022) in further demonstrating that established ideal types regularly employed in Arctic archaeology (i.e., archaeological cultures) are not a required foundation for contemporary

research in the eastern Canadian Arctic (see Johansen 2003; Johansen and Bauer in press).

This dissertation demonstrates the benefits of relational, place-based framework for the study of past communities. By addressing how places, and not just people, actively participated in the production of social and material differences, the research offers an avenue through which archaeologists can begin to move past frameworks that treat Arctic landscapes as representations of a singular past, and instead develop historically situated narratives that more fully explore what it means to be human in an emergent, more-than-human world. In approaching Tuniit sites as Inuit cultural heritage, the framework employed here challenges how Arctic archaeology has historically engaged with, and built narratives of, Indigenous lands and communities. Instead, it works towards deconstructing settler-colonial frameworks by reorienting interpretive authority towards Indigenous epistemologies to construct richer interpretations of Tuniit landscapes that respect, and better represent, the historic realities of local communities. In the remainder of this chapter, I review the strengths and limitations of the study and delineate avenues for future archaeological research. I then offer some closing remarks on the broader significance of the study to anthropology as a discipline.

9.1 Strengths and Limitations of the Present Study and Future Research Directions

9.1.1 Multimethod Surveys and the Expansion of Spatial Sampling

One of the strengths of this study has been the development of an applied multimethod survey approach involving RPA and pedestrian survey techniques and the refinement of archaeological expectations about site locations based on the analysis of Inuit oral history. The

analysis demonstrates that the combined approach is effective for overcoming some of the logistical limitations of Arctic research, identifying a greater range of site types, and constructing richer inferences of Tuniit settlement strategies, movements, and recurrent practices. Previous surveys in Amittuq have been largely restricted to coastal areas where marine emergence occurred during the Tuniit Period — namely, beach terraces below 50 MASL. This has been due, in part, to the presumption that Tuniit peoples adhered to a shoreward-shifting settlement strategy (Meldgaard 1962; Howse et al. 2017; Rowley 2003; Savelle et al 2009). Remote Arctic fieldwork also poses significant logistic limitations related to sustainable crew size, in-field transportation, field season duration, and financial restrictions like equipment transportation costs that have influenced sampling strategies and research locations (Duffy et al. 2018). These concerns have contributed to a focus in Tuniit archaeological research on more accessible coastal areas (Walker 2020a:2).

Conducting judgmental remotely piloted aircraft (RPA) and pedestrian surveys in targeted settings, informed by new location expectations from Amitturmiut oral history, resulted in the identification of seven newly documented inland sites. The work highlights the potential of incorporating local landscape knowledge into archaeological research designs for addressing the potential spatial biases of archaeological research. The presence of inland Tuniit sites also challenges the conception of coastal settlement places as stages for essentializing behaviours or traditions by highlighting small-scale diversity in Tuniit settlement practices.

The surveys also demonstrate the efficacy of visible light RPA technologies for identifying subtle and uneven archaeological deposits that may otherwise go undetected due to differences in surface conditions and feature visibility in arctic contexts. Alternatively, infrared

thermal surveys were effective at detecting subsurface boulder features. The surveys suggest that feature inundation and burial are relatively common in Amittuq, and that the likelihood of these post-depositional processes increase further inland due to deeper soils and the complexities of freshwater systems. The detection of new architectural features in coastal areas suggest that lichen coverage on feature stones and background disturbances like glacial till may regularly camouflage sites and contribute to sampling biases, emphasizing the benefits of a multimethod survey approach. The research indicates that combined RPA techniques are an effective method for the initial testing of arctic archaeological contexts and can be effective for visualizing and comparing architectural structures, contributing to more synthetic studies of camp structure differences.

Although the survey techniques I have employed offer a solution to some of the time and labour constraints that tend to restrict data collection in the Canadian Arctic, systematic pedestrian surveys and test pitting would have greatly benefitted the interpretive goals of the study. Future efforts to include intensive systematic survey of smaller areas will provide enhanced insights into the frequency and structure of low-density occupation areas, and help to determine the extent of feature burial within inland archaeological contexts. Systematic surveys will also be essential for further evaluating the efficacy of RPA technologies across different environmental and archaeological contexts, to better determine the scope of their utility. In particular, the combination of RPA thermography experiments with the systematic survey of inland contexts with deeper soils and thicker ground cover may be beneficial in enhancing current understandings of the capacities and limitations of subsurface RPA detection methods for Arctic research.

While evidence for inland occupational practices is important, existing interpretations are based on a small sample of new sites, meaning that the frequency and temporality of the construction and use of inland settlement places remain largely unknown on a regional level. The expansion of inland surveys will be critical for explaining how household and camp-level relations may have been regularly negotiated through interior practices, and for interpreting the scale and extent of broader community movements and connections within the regional landscape. There are several inland Tuniit sites described in Amitturmiut oral history that have yet to be surveyed by archaeologists, such as Uaalinaq on the eastern coast of Foxe Basin and Angmaluqtuq within the interior of Melville Peninsula, which are promising targets for future survey. Preliminary GIS analysis of satellite imagery indicate that undocumented archaeological structures are likely present in these areas. The investigation of these particular sites will offer research potential for the integration of oral history and archaeological analyses, as well as for the possible study of Tuniit – Early Inuit interactions during the terminal Late Tuniit Period (Friesen 2022).

9.1.2 Chronology-Building and Challenges to Previous Temporalizing Logics

This study has introduced an improved method of temporal analysis for coastal Arctic contexts that combines expanded radiocarbon sequences with geological temporal markers to refine site chronologies. This proves to be particularly beneficial for the chronological analysis of settlement places where past peoples relied heavily on marine subsistence resources. While Dyke et al. (2019) have developed a local marine reservoir correction ($\Delta R = 160 \pm 50$) for improved accuracy in the modelling of walrus samples, the probability ranges of these calibrated

dates still cover an extensive range of 200 to 400 years (2σ). Utilizing postglacial marine emergence rates to set temporal boundaries on the early limit of these dates provides a strategy for reducing the probability ranges of modelled walrus dates, enabling the estimation of smaller scale temporal differences that enhance interpretations of site maintenance and reoccupation. These data were critical for interpreting the repeated use of dwellings and extramural spaces during the terminal Early Tuniit and initial Late Tuniit periods, presenting the clearest evidence for continuity in local community relations between time frames traditionally attributed to separate periodized archaeological cultures within the region.

The refined chronologies produced through this research have important implications for the use of beach ridge chronologies in Canadian Arctic archaeological research, as they suggest that the age of coastal dwellings frequently do not correspond with the geological age of the coastal terraces on which they are located. The temporal variability of coastal contexts challenges models of sudden and abrupt technological change in Tuniit architecture and artifacts that were founded on the assumed contemporaneity of Tuniit sites and beach ridges (Maxwell 1985; Meldgaard 1962; Taylor 1968; Rowley 2003). In particular, they suggest that some archaeological forms considered to be diagnostic of an archaeological culture or time period, such as Late Tuniit (Dorset) semi-subterranean dwellings, are associated with both Early and Late Tuniit occupational contexts. This suggests that technological changes were often gradual and locally specific, highlighting potential social differences between camp communities within the region.

The refined chronologies also permitted comprehensive inferences about the relationship between topographic change and occupational practices. Through the production of predictive

GIS models, I have shown how topographic changes likely shaped local and regional community movements and land use. These changes continually altered the seasonal accessibility of land and ice routes, the location of freshwater sources, and the distribution of the feeding, breeding, and basking grounds of sea mammals. The study identifies several areas where marine emergence first occurred in the northern Foxe Basin, offering predicted targets for the location of early sites, which will be of benefit to future archaeological survey projects. By interpolating the models with oral historical and archaeological data through GIS applications, my project underscores the utility of paleogeographical analyses for building multifaceted interpretations of socially and historically situated occupational landscapes.

While the current study has offered new perspectives on local occupational histories, radiocarbon sequences for Amittuq remain relatively sparse, and the extent of campsite reoccupations remain unknown. Due to the logistic limitations of my fieldwork, most newly documented inland sites were not sampled for radiocarbon dating material, and the dating of these areas will be critical in future work to better understand continuity and change within interior settlement contexts. The expansion of radiocarbon dates at Qalirusiq will also be critical, as current chronologies are largely based on surface samples and legacy dates. The expansion of radiocarbon dates along the uppermost terraces of Qalirusiq may help in further determining if the islet was peopled prior to 4500 BP, as suggested by the early limits of some calibrated dates. This will be important in developing inferences of trans-local community relations during the initial Early Tuniit Period.

Another priority will be the expansion of radiocarbon sequences to identify sites within the temporal range of 1500 – 1000 BP, which may be underrepresented in coastal contexts due to

an absence of terrestrial mammal samples. The recovery of two walrus samples that date within this time frame suggest that sampling issues may be partially responsible for chronological gaps in existing occupational sequences. Given these possible sampling issues, the expansion of walrus radiocarbon dating sequences in contexts where terrestrial samples are absent will be central in future investigations of possible occupational declines during the middle Late Tuniit Period. Ongoing work on refining the regional marine reservoir correction for ringed seal may also contribute to this important project of chronological revision (James Savelle, personal communication 2023).

9.2 Concluding Remarks

Archaeologists are storytellers of the past, and how these stories are told has a profound effect on how human social worlds are perceived and understood (Bennett 2012:232; Garrouette & Westcott 2013; Haraway 2016:39-40; Joyce 2008; Rosiek and Snyder 2020). This dissertation has taken an initial step towards a place-based approach to the study of Tuniit social worlds. Through the development of a relational narrative of Amittuq's occupational landscape, the work confronts ahistorical, essentialist, and deterministic conceptions of culture that have perpetuated exclusionary narratives of not only Arctic societies, but Indigenous societies worldwide. The research highlights the relational, multifaceted, and deeply social character of people-place relations, and their substantial role in the making and remaking of community and history. Instead of confining archaeological observations to established ideal types regularly employed in Arctic archaeology (e.g., archaeological cultures), this study has explored a reimagining of who and what counts as an agent of knowledge in archaeological research, including land and stories

(Deloria 1992; Price 2008; Qitsualik 2008; Tallbear 2015; Watts 2016). I argue that approaching persistent places as mediums of knowledge and living history constitutes an important step towards the continued collaborative integration of Inuit knowledge and research interests within Arctic archaeological research, as it offers a conceptual framework for critically engaging with the inseparability of past and present places in Inuit Nunangat.

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